

EUCAIM's Hyper-Ontology

language [en](#)

Latest version:

<https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#>

Previous version:

[1.4 \(September 2025\)](#)

Revision:

2.0

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EuCanImage

FORTH

GUMed

INCISIVE

ProCancer-I

Publisher:

LIMICS

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Format [JSON LD](#)

Format [RDF/XML](#)

Format [N Triples](#)

Format [TTL](#)

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Ontology Specification Draft

Objective

In the [EUCAIM EC-Co-funded project](#), we employ an **ontology integration** approach toward semantic interoperability among heterogeneous cancer image data models and distributed big cancer data repositories. Our aim is to ensure the interoperability of cancer data at different levels as a consolidated framework that aggregates health data from multiple heterogeneous sources and integrates them into a common semantic meta-model called **Hyper-Ontology**. This work covers four main projects from the [AI4HI](#) network: [ProCancer-I](#), [INCISIVE](#), [CHAIMELEON](#), and [EuCanImage](#), and new datasets from the onboarding process.

Hyper-Ontology's Specifications

The Hyper-Ontology is a [FAIR](#)-compliant, well-founded layered and modular domain and domain-application ontology that defines the essentials of **oncology** and **medical imaging**. It is developed using a hybrid iterative semantically and formally well-founded approach composed of two main strategies: bottom-up (based on the domain-specific knowledge provided by [AI4HI](#)) and top-down (based on the [mCODE](#) specifications). The Hyper-Ontology version 2.0 covers 22 cancer types, including **prostate, breast, colon, liver, rectum, lung, colorectal, brain, pancreas, thyroid, sarcoma, ovary, and kidney**. It supports various EUCAIM components, such as the ETL, EUCAIM CDM and HealthDCAT-AP, and image segmentation/annotation.

Classes	3992	Object property	180	Data property	60
Synonyms	3491	exactMatch	2277	Query criteria	731
OMOP Mapped concepts	3128	FHIR Mapped concepts	352	DICOM Mapped concepts	14
SNOMEDCT	2286	ICD-O-3	241	RadLex	350
LOINC	236	NAACCR	131	ICD-10	41
UCUM	30	RxNorm	42	Race	7
Cancer types and subtypes	277	Imaging modalities	53	Topography	242
Histology/Morphology	144	Comorbidities	42	Tumor Marker Test	35

Hyper-Ontology's Structure

Five main modules are defined in the hyper-ontology:

1. **Clinical&Biological Module**: includes cancer types and subtypes, histology/morphology, body part, tumor grade/stage, procedure (surgical/therapeutic), family history, medication, tumor marker tests, lab test results, genomics, etc.
2. **Imaging Module**: includes imaging procedures and modalities (e.g., MR, CT, WSI), tumor assessment (e.g., PI-RADS and BI-RADS), manufacturers, imaging descriptors (e.g., enhancement pattern, tissue composition, mass density, mass shape), imaging criteria (e.g., VASARI criteria).
3. **Common Module**: defines staging/grading values and other qualifier values such as unit of measure, time patterns, family degrees, absence and presence findings.
4. **Specific Module**: defined to support specific metadata (EUCAIM DCAT Application Profile) and syntactic mapping with OMOP and FHIR.
5. **Generic Module**: defines generic categories, supporting the semantic integration with the EUCAIM CDM.

Cross-reference for EUCAIM's Hyper-Ontology classes, object properties and data properties back to [ToC](#)

This section provides details for each class and property defined by EUCAIM's Hyper-Ontology.

Classes

- ["+](#)
- ["++](#)
- ["+++"](#)
- ["++++"](#)
- [+2](#)
- [0](#)
- [0](#)
- [1](#)
- [1 cigarette per day](#)
- [1+](#)
- [1/3-2/3](#)
- [16 to 25 cigarettes per day \(about 1 pack\)](#)
- [17-hydroxycorticosteroid measurement](#)
- [18q chromosome deletion \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [1A](#)
- [1B](#)
- [2](#)
- [2 to 5 cigarettes per day](#)
- [2+](#)
- [26 to 35 cigarettes per day \(about 1 1/2 packs\)](#)
- [3](#)
- [3+](#)
- [3D CRT three dimensional conformal radiation therapy](#)
- [3DHISTECH](#)
- [6 to 15 cigarettes per day \(about 1/2 pack\)](#)
- [<](#)
- [<1/3](#)
- [=](#)
- [>](#)
- [>2/3](#)
- [Abdomen](#)
- [Abdomen and Pelvis](#)
- [Abdomen excision](#)
- [Abdomen proper](#)
- [Abdominal abscess](#)
- [Abdominal cavity injury](#)
- [Abdominal mass](#)
- [Abdominal organ finding](#)
- [Abdominal visceral abscess](#)
- [Abdominopelvic cross-sectional segment](#)
- [Abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)
- [Abdominoperineal pull-through procedure](#)
- [Abdominoperineal resection](#)
- [Abemaciclib](#)
- [Abnormal](#)
- [Abnormal finding on evaluation procedure](#)
- [Abnormal sexual function](#)
- [Abscess](#)
- [Abscess of digestive system](#)
- [Abscess of liver](#)
- [Absence findings](#)
- [Absent](#)
- [Acinar cell carcinoma](#)
- [Acinar cell carcinoma](#)
- [Acinar cell carcinoma of prostate gland](#)
- [Acinar cell neoplasm](#)
- [Acinar cell neoplasms](#)
- [Acoustic feature of mass](#)
- [Action](#)
- [Active](#)
- [Active Surveillance](#)
- [Active Surveillance](#)

- [Active surveillance of prostate cancer](#)
- [Activity](#)
- [ADAC](#)
- [ADC map](#)
- [ADC value](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma of cervix](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma of large intestine](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma of liver](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma of pelvis](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma of uterus](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma with mixed subtypes](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation of prostate gland](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma, NOS](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of ascending colon](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of cecum](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of colon, NOS](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of descending colon](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of hepatic flexure of colon](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of lung, NOS](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of rectum, NOS](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of sigmoid colon](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of splenic flexure of colon](#)
- [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of transverse colon](#)
- [Adenoma](#)
- [Adenoma AND/OR adenocarcinoma](#)
- [Adenoma of liver](#)
- [Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#)
- [Adenomatous polyposis coli](#)
- [Adenosquamous carcinoma](#)
- [Adenosquamous carcinoma of ascending colon](#)
- [Adenosquamous carcinoma of cecum](#)
- [Adenosquamous carcinoma of colon, NOS](#)
- [Adenosquamous carcinoma of descending colon](#)
- [Adenosquamous carcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon](#)
- [Adenosquamous carcinoma of prostate gland](#)
- [Adenosquamous carcinoma of rectum, NOS](#)
- [Adenosquamous carcinoma of sigmoid colon](#)
- [Adenosquamous carcinoma of splenic flexure of colon](#)
- [Adenosquamous carcinoma of transverse colon](#)
- [Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#)
- [Adjectival modifier](#)
- [Adjuvant - intent](#)
- [Administration of hormone](#)
- [Administration of medication](#)
- [Administrative statuses](#)
- [Adnexal and skin appendage neoplasms](#)
- [Adrenal gland](#)
- [Adverse Event](#)
- [African](#)
- [Age](#)
- [Age AND/OR growth period](#)
- [Age at diagnosis](#)
- [Age at onset of clinical finding](#)
- [Age at smoking cessation](#)
- [Agfa](#)
- [Aggressive](#)
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- [AJCC/UICC 8th Ta Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC 8th Tis Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC 8th Tis\(DCIS\) Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC 8th Tis\(LAMN\) Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC 8th Tis\(Paget\) Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC 8th TX Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical M0 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical M1 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical M1a Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical M1b Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical M1c Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical MX Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical N0 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical N1 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical NX Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical T2 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical T2a Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical T2b Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical T2c Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical T3 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical T3a Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical T3b Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical T4 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC clinical TX Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC finding](#)
- [AJCC/UICC M0 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC M1 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC M1a Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC M1b Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC M1c Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC MX Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC N0 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC N1 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC NX Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological N0 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological N1 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological NX Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological T1 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological T1a Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological T1b Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological T1c Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological T2 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological T2a Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological T2b Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological T2c Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological T3 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological T3a Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological T3b Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological T4 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC pathological TX Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC T1 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC T1a Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC T1b Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC T1c Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC T2 Category.](#)
- [AJCC/UICC T2a Category.](#)

- [AJCC/UICC T2b Category](#)
- [AJCC/UICC T2c Category](#)
- [AJCC/UICC T3 Category](#)
- [AJCC/UICC T3a Category](#)
- [AJCC/UICC T3b Category](#)
- [AJCC/UICC T4 Category](#)
- [AJCC/UICC TX Category](#)
- [Alanine aminotransferase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Alanine aminotransferase|Catalytic Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Albumin measurement](#)
- [Albumin measurement, urine, quantitative](#)
- [Albumin/Protein.total in 24 hour Urine by Electrophoresis](#)
- [Albumin/Protein.total|Mass Fraction|Urine](#)
- [Alcohol abuse](#)
- [Alcohol dependence](#)
- [Alcohol drinker status](#)
- [Alcohol drinker status value](#)
- [Alcohol use pattern](#)
- [Alcohol use pattern value](#)
- [Alcoholic liver damage](#)
- [Alive](#)
- [ALK gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [Alkaline phosphatase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Alkaline phosphatase measurement](#)
- [Alkaline phosphatase|Catalytic Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Alkylating agent](#)
- [All times past](#)
- [Almost entirely fat](#)
- [Alphanumeric](#)
- [ALT - blood measurement](#)
- [Altered bowel function](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical grade allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical M category allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer grade GX](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological grade allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1a \(qualifier value\)](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1b \(qualifier value\)](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1c \(qualifier value\)](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer yp grade allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)
- [American Joint Committee on Cancer, Cancer Staging Manual, 8th edition neoplasm staging system](#)
- [American society of anesthesiologists morbidity state](#)
- [American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification](#)
- [American Urological Association staging system for prostate cancer](#)
- [Anal region structure](#)
- [Anal structure](#)
- [Anastomosis of intestine](#)
- [Anastomosis of intestine to anus](#)
- [Anastomosis of intestine, large-to-anus](#)
- [Anastrozole](#)
- [Anatomic location of neoplasm](#)
- [Anatomic pathology procedure](#)
- [Anatomic Site](#)
- [Anatomical Plane](#)
- [Anatomical structure](#)
- [Androgen deprivation therapy](#)
- [Androgen level](#)
- [Anechoic](#)
- [Anemia](#)
- [Angiography](#)
- [Angiosarcoma](#)

- [Angiosarcoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Angiosarcoma of liver](#)
- [Angular margin](#)
- [Annotated Dataset](#)
- [Annotation Status](#)
- [Annotation Type](#)
- [Annotation/Segmentation](#)
- [Annotator Specialty](#)
- [Anorectal disorder](#)
- [Anorectal structure](#)
- [Answer or Value Set](#)
- [Anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)
- [Anterior resection of rectum](#)
- [Anthracycline](#)
- [Anti-thyroid antibody measurement](#)
- [Antibody measurement](#)
- [Antineoplastic agent](#)
- [Antineoplastic Agents](#)
- [ANTINEOPLASTIC AND IMMUNOMODULATING AGENTS](#)
- [Antineoplastic antibiotic](#)
- [Antineoplastic chemoimmunotherapy](#)
- [Aorta](#)
- [Apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)
- [Apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Apical transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Apocrine adenocarcinoma](#)
- [Apocrine adenocarcinoma of breast, NOS](#)
- [Arab](#)
- [Architectural distortion of breast](#)
- [Area striata structure](#)
- [Areola structure](#)
- [Arm](#)
- [Arterial phase](#)
- [Arterial Spin Labeling \(ASL\)](#)
- [ASA physical status class 1](#)
- [ASA physical status class 2](#)
- [ASA physical status class 3](#)
- [ASA physical status class 4](#)
- [ASA physical status class 5](#)
- [ASA physical status class 6](#)
- [ASA1 \(no disturbance\)](#)
- [ASA2 \(mild/moderate\)](#)
- [ASA3 \(severe\)](#)
- [ASA4 \(life threatening\)](#)
- [ASA5 \(moribund\)](#)
- [Ascending colon](#)
- [Ascending colon structure](#)
- [Asian](#)
- [Asian Indian](#)
- [Aspartate aminotransferase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Aspartate aminotransferase measurement](#)
- [Aspartate aminotransferase\[Catalytic Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Aspiration of breast](#)
- [Assessment](#)
- [Assessment scales](#)
- [Asymmetric enhancement](#)
- [Asymptomatic](#)
- [Atezolizumab](#)
- [ATM \(ATM serine/threonine kinase\) gene variant](#)
- [ATRX \(ATRX chromatin remodeler\) gene variant measurement](#)
- [ATRX gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [Attenuation characteristic](#)
- [Attenuation correction method](#)
- [Attribute](#)
- [Auricular region structure](#)
- [Authorisation to access, view and process in-situ the datasets](#)
- [Authorisation to download the datasets](#)
- [Authorisation to remotely process the datasets without the ability to access and visualise data, even remotely](#)
- [Autoantibody measurement](#)
- [Autoimmune disease](#)
- [Autoimmune hepatitis](#)

- [Autoimmune liver disease](#)
- [Automatic](#)
- [Autosomal dominant hereditary disorder](#)
- [Autosomal hereditary disorder](#)
- [Axial](#)
- [Axial scan mode](#)
- [Axial skeleton structure](#)
- [Axillary lymph node group](#)
- [Axillary lymph node structure](#)
- [Background parenchymal enhancement pattern](#)
- [Basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)
- [Basal cell adenocarcinoma](#)
- [Basal cell adenocarcinoma of prostate gland](#)
- [Basal cell neoplasm \(morphology\)](#)
- [Basal ganglia](#)
- [Basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Basal transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Basal-like 1](#)
- [Basal-like 2](#)
- [Base of prostate](#)
- [Baseline](#)
- [Behavior descriptors](#)
- [Behavior finding](#)
- [Behavior observable](#)
- [Benign](#)
- [Benign adenomatous neoplasm](#)
- [Benign adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Benign adenomatous neoplasm - category](#)
- [Benign epithelial neoplasm](#)
- [Benign neoplasm of liver](#)
- [Benign neoplastic disease](#)
- [Benign prostatic hyperplasia](#)
- [Benign tumor of digestive organ](#)
- [Bevacizumab](#)
- [BI-RADS 0](#)
- [BI-RADS 1](#)
- [BI-RADS 2](#)
- [BI-RADS 3](#)
- [BI-RADS 4](#)
- [BI-RADS 4A](#)
- [BI-RADS 4B](#)
- [BI-RADS 4C](#)
- [BI-RADS 5](#)
- [BI-RADS 6](#)
- [BI-RADS assessment](#)
- [BI-RADS N/A](#)
- [Bilateral](#)
- [Biliary tract structure](#)
- [Binary](#)
- [Biological Therapy](#)
- [Biomedical device](#)
- [Biopsy](#)
- [Biopsy finding](#)
- [Biopsy of abdomen using ultrasound guidance](#)
- [Biopsy of breast](#)
- [Biopsy of lymph node](#)
- [Biopsy of lymphatic structure](#)
- [Biopsy of male genital system](#)
- [Biopsy of prostate](#)
- [Biopsy of thorax](#)
- [Biopsy of trunk](#)
- [Biopsy result abnormal](#)
- [Biopsy result normal](#)
- [Black or African American](#)
- [Bladder](#)
- [Bladder control - finding](#)
- [Bladder finding](#)
- [Bleeding](#)
- [Block dissection of pelvic lymph nodes](#)
- [Blood calcium measurement](#)
- [Blood cell count outside reference range](#)

- [Blood in urine](#)
- [Blood leukocyte number below reference range](#)
- [Blood relative](#)
- [Blood urate measurement](#)
- [Blood urea measurement](#)
- [Body measurement finding](#)
- [Body organ structure](#)
- [Body part structure](#)
- [Body region structure](#)
- [Body structure](#)
- [Body substance specimen](#)
- [Body system structure](#)
- [Body tissue structure](#)
- [Bone and/or joint structure of cranium](#)
- [Bone marrow disorder](#)
- [Bone marrow structure](#)
- [Bone structure](#)
- [Bone structure of femur](#)
- [Bone structure of head](#)
- [Boolean value](#)
- [Boost radiation therapy](#)
- [Bounding box](#)
- [Bowel finding](#)
- [Bowels: fully continent](#)
- [Brachytherapy](#)
- [Brachytherapy of breast](#)
- [Brachytherapy, High Dose rate \(HDR\)](#)
- [BRAF \(B-Raf proto-oncogene, serine/threonine kinase\) gene variant measurement](#)
- [BRAF gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [Brain](#)
- [Brain and spinal cord structure](#)
- [Brain Deep White Matter Structure](#)
- [Brain Lesion Site](#)
- [Brain natriuretic peptide measurement](#)
- [Brain part](#)
- [Brain region](#)
- [Brain stem](#)
- [Brain tissue structure](#)
- [Brain, NOS](#)
- [brain-dead patient, organ donor](#)
- [Brain@Gross total resection of lobe of brain \(lobectomy\)](#)
- [Brain@Subtotal resection of tumor, lesion or mass in brain](#)
- [BRCA1 \(BRCA1 DNA repair associated\) gene variant measurement](#)
- [BRCA1 gene mutation detected](#)
- [BRCA1 gene mutation negative](#)
- [BRCA1 gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [BRCA1 mutation carrier detection test](#)
- [BRCA1+BRCA2 gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [BRCA2 \(BRCA2 DNA repair associated\) gene variant](#)
- [BRCA2 gene mutation negative](#)
- [BRCA2 gene mutation positive](#)
- [BRCA2 mutation carrier detection test](#)
- [Breast](#)
- [Breast cancer genetic marker of susceptibility detected](#)
- [Breast cancer genetic marker of susceptibility not detected](#)
- [Breast Carcinoma by Gene Expression Profile](#)
- [Breast changes](#)
- [Breast composition](#)
- [Breast Conservation Treatment](#)
- [Breast fed](#)
- [Breast finding](#)
- [Breast function](#)
- [Breast lump](#)
- [Breast part](#)
- [Breast procedure](#)
- [Breast signs and symptoms](#)
- [Breast structure](#)
- [Breast, NOS](#)
- [Breastfeeding \(mother\)](#)
- [Bronchial structure](#)
- [Bronchus and lung](#)

- [Brother](#)
- [C reactive protein \[Mass/volume\] in Blood by High sensitivity method](#)
- [C-reactive protein measurement](#)
- [Calcification disorder](#)
- [Calcifications](#)
- [Calcifications in a mass](#)
- [Calcifications outside of a mass](#)
- [Calcium \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Calcium measurement](#)
- [Calcium|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Calcium|Moment in time|Blood|40.078 g/mole](#)
- [Calvarial Remodeling](#)
- [Calvarial Remodeling value](#)
- [Cancer Ag 15-3](#)
- [Cancer Ag 15-3 \[Units/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cancer Ag 15-3 | Serum or Plasma | Chemistry - non-challenge](#)
- [Cancer Ag 15-3|Arbitrary Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cancer Ag 19-9 \[Units/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cancer antigen 15-3 measurement](#)
- [Cancer antigen 19-9 measurement](#)
- [Cancer Condition Type](#)
- [Cancer disease progression](#)
- [Cancer Patient](#)
- [Cancer staging](#)
- [Canon](#)
- [Capecitabine](#)
- [Carbamazepine Injection](#)
- [Carbohydrate measurement](#)
- [Carboplatin](#)
- [Carcinoembryonic Ag \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Carcinoembryonic Ag|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Carcinoembryonic Ag|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Carcinoembryonic antigen level](#)
- [Carcinoembryonic antigen measurement](#)
- [Carcinoma](#)
- [Carcinoma in situ](#)
- [Carcinoma in situ \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Carcinoma in situ of breast](#)
- [Carcinoma in situ of male genital organ](#)
- [Carcinoma in situ of prostate](#)
- [Carcinoma of breast](#)
- [Carcinoma of cervix](#)
- [Carcinoma of colon](#)
- [Carcinoma of genital organ](#)
- [Carcinoma of pancreas](#)
- [Carcinoma of prostate](#)
- [Carcinoma of uterus](#)
- [Carcinoma of vagina](#)
- [Carcinoma of vulva](#)
- [Carcinoma with osteoclast-like giant cells](#)
- [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS](#)
- [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of ascending colon](#)
- [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of cecum](#)
- [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of colon, NOS](#)
- [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of descending colon](#)
- [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of hepatic flexure of colon](#)
- [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of rectum, NOS](#)
- [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of sigmoid colon](#)
- [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of splenic flexure of colon](#)
- [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of transverse colon](#)
- [Cardinal number](#)
- [Care regime](#)
- [Case-control](#)
- [Category](#)
- [Cavity](#)
- [CDH1 \(cadherin 1\) gene variant](#)
- [Cecum](#)
- [Cecum structure](#)
- [Cells.estrogen receptor/100 cells in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)
- [Cells.Ki-67 nuclear Ag/100 cells in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)
- [Cells.progesterone receptor/100 cells in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)

- [centimeter](#)
- [Central nervous system part](#)
- [Central nervous system tumor morphology](#)
- [Central portion of breast](#)
- [Central zone necrosis](#)
- [Central zone of left half prostate](#)
- [Central zone of prostate](#)
- [Central zone of right half prostate](#)
- [Cerebellar nucleus](#)
- [Cerebellar part](#)
- [Cerebellar peduncle](#)
- [Cerebellar white matter structure](#)
- [Cerebellum](#)
- [Cerebral cortex part](#)
- [Cerebral hemisphere part](#)
- [Cerebral hemisphere structure](#)
- [Cerebral hemisphere white matter part](#)
- [Cerebral lobe structure](#)
- [Cerebral meninges](#)
- [Cerebral white matter structure](#)
- [Cerebrum](#)
- [Cervical spine](#)
- [Cervix uteri](#)
- [Change patterns](#)
- [Change values](#)
- [CHEK2 \(checkpoint kinase 2\).gene variant](#)
- [Chemistry](#)
- [Chemotherapy](#)
- [Chemotherapy cycle](#)
- [Chemotherapy protective agent](#)
- [Chemotherapy Regimen](#)
- [Chest](#)
- [Chest and abdomen](#)
- [Chest imaging](#)
- [Chest injury](#)
- [Chest pain](#)
- [Chest, abdomen, and pelvis](#)
- [Child](#)
- [Child-Pugh score](#)
- [Child-Pugh score class A](#)
- [Child-Pugh score class B](#)
- [Child-Pugh score class C](#)
- [Chinese](#)
- [Cholangiocarcinoma](#)
- [Cholangitis](#)
- [Cholesterol \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cholesterol in HDL \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cholesterol in LDL \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cholesterol measurement](#)
- [Cholesterol.in HDL|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cholesterol.in HDL|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cholesterol.in LDL|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cholesterol.in LDL|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cholesterol|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cholesterol|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma|386.664 g/mole](#)
- [Chromosome region 6q22 rearrangements in Tissue by FISH](#)
- [Chronic digestive system disorder](#)
- [Chronic disease](#)
- [Chronic disease monitoring](#)
- [Chronic hepatitis](#)
- [Chronic inflammatory disorder](#)
- [Chronic liver disease](#)
- [Cigarette smoker](#)
- [Cigarettes pack-years smoked during life](#)
- [Circumferential \(Radial\) Margin Involved by Tumor](#)
- [Circumferential \(Radial\) Margin Uninvolved by Tumor](#)
- [Circumscribed margin](#)
- [Cirrhosis of liver](#)
- [Classification system](#)
- [Clinical & Biological Module](#)
- [Clinical equipment and/or device](#)

- [Clinical finding](#)
- [Clinical history/examination observable](#)
- [Clinical specialty](#)
- [Clinical Test Result](#)
- [Clip](#)
- [cM category](#)
- [cM0](#)
- [cM1](#)
- [cM1a](#)
- [cM1b](#)
- [cM1c](#)
- [cN category](#)
- [cN0](#)
- [cN0i+](#)
- [cN0i-](#)
- [cN0m+](#)
- [cN0m-](#)
- [cN1](#)
- [cN1a](#)
- [cN1b](#)
- [cN1c](#)
- [cN1mi](#)
- [cN2](#)
- [cN2a](#)
- [cN2b](#)
- [cN3](#)
- [cN3a](#)
- [cN3b](#)
- [cN3c](#)
- [cNX](#)
- [Co-morbid conditions](#)
- [Cohort](#)
- [Collection method](#)
- [Colon](#)
- [Colon and rectum](#)
- [Colon part](#)
- [Colon structure](#)
- [Colon, NOS](#)
- [Colonic lesion](#)
- [Colonoscopy Video Recording](#)
- [Combined chemotherapy and radiation therapy](#)
- [combined modalities](#)
- [Combined posterior acoustic pattern](#)
- [Combined site](#)
- [Common Module](#)
- [Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 1](#)
- [Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 2](#)
- [Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 3](#)
- [Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 4](#)
- [Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 5](#)
- [Complete](#)
- [Complete excision](#)
- [Complete Resection](#)
- [Complete response](#)
- [Complete response \(CR\)](#)
- [Completeness](#)
- [Complex cystic and solid echogenicity](#)
- [Complex epithelial neoplasm](#)
- [Computed radiography](#)
- [Computed tomography](#)
- [Computed tomography](#)
- [Computed Tomography Dose Index Volume](#)
- [Computerized Tomography \(CT Scan\) of Chest, Abdomen and Pelvis](#)
- [Condition clinical status](#)
- [Condition clinical status value](#)
- [Condition stability status](#)
- [Conformal radiotherapy](#)
- [Conformal radiotherapy](#)
- [Congenital disease](#)
- [Congenital hamartoma](#)
- [Congenital melanosis](#)

- [Connective, subcutaneous and other soft tissues](#)
- [Connective, Subcutaneous and other soft tissues of lower limb and hip](#)
- [Connective, Subcutaneous and other soft tissues of upper limb and shoulder](#)
- [Construction](#)
- [Construction of anastomosis](#)
- [Contact Date](#)
- [Context values](#)
- [Continent of urine](#)
- [Contouring](#)
- [Contrast agent](#)
- [Control group](#)
- [Conventional tomography](#)
- [Core needle biopsy](#)
- [Core needle biopsy of breast](#)
- [Core needle biopsy of prostate](#)
- [Corpus callosum](#)
- [Correspondence](#)
- [Cortical Involvement](#)
- [Cortical Involvement value](#)
- [Cortisol \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cortisol measurement](#)
- [Cortisol|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Cortisol|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma|362.466 g/mole](#)
- [Cough](#)
- [Couinaud hepatic segment II](#)
- [Couinaud hepatic segment III](#)
- [Couinaud hepatic segment IV](#)
- [Couinaud hepatic segment V](#)
- [Couinaud hepatic segment VI](#)
- [Couinaud hepatic segment VII](#)
- [Couinaud hepatic segment VIII](#)
- [Couinaud liver segment](#)
- [Counseling](#)
- [Creatinine \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Creatinine \[Mass/volume\] in Urine](#)
- [Creatinine measurement](#)
- [Creatinine measurement, urine](#)
- [Creatinine|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Any Urine specimen](#)
- [Creatinine|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Creatinine|Mass Concentration|Urine](#)
- [Creatinine|Moment in time|Blood|113.12 g/mole](#)
- [Creatinine|Moment in time|Urine|113.12 g/mole](#)
- [Cribriform tumor pattern](#)
- [Cross-sectional abdomen](#)
- [Cross-sectional attenuation correction method](#)
- [Cross-sectional pelvis](#)
- [cross-sectional procedure attribute](#)
- [Cross-sectional thorax](#)
- [CT attenuation correction](#)
- [cT category](#)
- [CT Imaging Acquisition Protocol Element CTDI VOL](#)
- [CT of breast](#)
- [CT of chest](#)
- [CT of thorax with contrast](#)
- [CT procedure attribute](#)
- [CT scan mode](#)
- [cT0](#)
- [cT1](#)
- [cT1a](#)
- [cT1b](#)
- [cT1c](#)
- [cT1mi](#)
- [cT2](#)
- [cT2a](#)
- [cT2b](#)
- [cT2c](#)
- [cT3](#)
- [cT3a](#)
- [cT3b](#)
- [cT4](#)
- [cT4a](#)

- [cT4b](#)
- [cT4c](#)
- [cT4d](#)
- [cTis](#)
- [cTisDCIs](#)
- [cTisPaget](#)
- [cTX](#)
- [cubic centimeter](#)
- [cubic millimeter](#)
- [Curative therapy](#)
- [Current](#)
- [Current drinker](#)
- [Current drinker of alcohol](#)
- [Current non-drinker of alcohol](#)
- [Current or past](#)
- [Current or specified](#)
- [Cyclophosphamide](#)
- [Cyst](#)
- [Cyst of abdomen](#)
- [Cyst of liver](#)
- [Cystadenoma](#)
- [Cystadenoma of liver](#)
- [Cystadenoma, NOS](#)
- [Cystic](#)
- [Cystic, mucinous and serous neoplasms](#)
- [Cystic, mucinous AND/OR serous neoplasm](#)
- [Cysts](#)
- [Cysts value](#)
- [Cytologic test](#)
- [Cytopenia](#)
- [Cytotoxic antibiotic](#)
- [Damage](#)
- [Data Value](#)
- [Dataset Access Condition](#)
- [Dataset Type](#)
- [Date](#)
- [Date of death](#)
- [Date of Diagnosis](#)
- [Date of Last Contact](#)
- [Daughter](#)
- [day](#)
- [DCIS \(Ductal carcinoma in situ\) of breast](#)
- [Dead](#)
- [Deep White Matter Invasion](#)
- [Degenerative disorder](#)
- [Degree findings](#)
- [Degrees of severity](#)
- [Delayed phase](#)
- [Delivered radiation dose](#)
- [Demographic history detail](#)
- [Density descriptor](#)
- [Deposit](#)
- [Derived](#)
- [Derived Unit of International System of Units](#)
- [Descending colon](#)
- [Descending colon structure](#)
- [Descriptor](#)
- [Destructive procedure](#)
- [Destructive procedure by anatomic site](#)
- [device](#)
- [Diagnosis](#)
- [Diagnostic Imaging](#)
- [Diagnostic intent](#)
- [Diagnostic/Screening Processes or Results](#)
- [Diencephalon part](#)
- [Difficulty breathing](#)
- [Difficulty initiating bladder emptying](#)
- [Difficulty passing urine](#)
- [Diffuse hemorrhage](#)
- [Diffuse intrinsic pontine glioma](#)
- [Diffuse non-Hodgkin's lymphoma](#)

- [Diffuse tumor configuration](#)
- [Diffusion Characteristics](#)
- [Diffusion Characteristics value](#)
- [Diffusion MRI](#)
- [Diffusion Spectrum Imaging](#)
- [Diffusion tensor imaging](#)
- [Diffusion weighted](#)
- [Diffusion weighted imaging](#)
- [Digestive organ structure](#)
- [Digestive system finding](#)
- [Digestive system hereditary disorder](#)
- [Digestive tract part](#)
- [Digestive tract structure](#)
- [Digital examination](#)
- [Digital examination of rectum](#)
- [Digital Microscopy](#)
- [Digital Radiography](#)
- [Digitized hematoxylin-eosin \(HE\) slides](#)
- [Discoloration of skin](#)
- [Discoloration of skin of breast](#)
- [Disease](#)
- [Disease caused by parasite](#)
- [Disease Clinical Qualifier](#)
- [Disease due to Taeniidae](#)
- [Disease Grade Qualifier](#)
- [Disease morphology qualifier](#)
- [Disease of liver](#)
- [Disease phases](#)
- [Disease qualifier](#)
- [Disease-specific](#)
- [Disorder caused by alcohol](#)
- [Disorder due to infection](#)
- [Disorder of abdomen](#)
- [Disorder of abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)
- [Disorder of body cavity](#)
- [Disorder of body system](#)
- [Disorder of breast](#)
- [Disorder of cellular component of blood](#)
- [Disorder of colon](#)
- [Disorder of digestive organ](#)
- [Disorder of digestive system](#)
- [Disorder of digestive tract](#)
- [Disorder of endocrine system](#)
- [Disorder of female genital organs](#)
- [Disorder of female reproductive system](#)
- [Disorder of fetus and/or newborn](#)
- [Disorder of gastrointestinal tract](#)
- [Disorder of hematopoietic structure](#)
- [Disorder of immune function](#)
- [Disorder of integument](#)
- [Disorder of intestine](#)
- [Disorder of kidney and/or ureter](#)
- [Disorder of large intestine](#)
- [Disorder of lipoprotein AND/OR lipid metabolism](#)
- [Disorder of lower gastrointestinal tract](#)
- [Disorder of lower respiratory system](#)
- [Disorder of lung](#)
- [Disorder of male genital organ](#)
- [Disorder of male reproductive system](#)
- [Disorder of nervous system](#)
- [Disorder of pelvic region of trunk](#)
- [Disorder of pelvis](#)
- [Disorder of pigmentation](#)
- [Disorder of pleura and pleural cavity](#)
- [Disorder of prostate](#)
- [Disorder of rectum](#)
- [Disorder of respiratory system](#)
- [Disorder of retroperitoneum](#)
- [Disorder of skin](#)
- [Disorder of skin and/or subcutaneous tissue](#)
- [Disorder of skin pigmentation](#)

- [Disorder of soft tissue](#)
- [Disorder of the urinary system](#)
- [Disorder of thoracic segment of trunk](#)
- [Disorder of thorax](#)
- [Disorder of thyroid gland](#)
- [Disorder of trunk](#)
- [Disorder of uterus](#)
- [Disorder of vagina](#)
- [Dissection of lymph node](#)
- [Distant Metastasis \(NOS\)](#)
- [Distant metastasis present](#)
- [Distributions](#)
- [DNA mismatch repair protein Msh3 \[Presence\] in Cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)
- [Docetaxel](#)
- [Docetaxel Injection](#)
- [Domain: Condition](#)
- [Domain: Drug](#)
- [Domain: Meas Value](#)
- [Domain: Measurement](#)
- [Domain: Observation](#)
- [Domain: Person](#)
- [Domain: Procedure](#)
- [Domain: Spec Anatomic Site](#)
- [Domain: Specimen](#)
- [Domain: Unit](#)
- [Don't know/refused](#)
- [dose area product](#)
- [Doxorubicin](#)
- [Doxorubicin liposomal](#)
- [Drug measurement](#)
- [Drug observable](#)
- [Drug or medicament](#)
- [Drug therapy](#)
- [Drug therapy observable](#)
- [Drug-induced](#)
- [Drug-induced disorder of liver](#)
- [Drug-induced gastrointestinal disturbance](#)
- [Drug-induced lesion](#)
- [Drug-induced pneumonitis](#)
- [Drug-related disorder](#)
- [Dual-energy CT](#)
- [DUCT CARCINOMA/ Invasive carcinoma of no special type](#)
- [Duct changes](#)
- [Duct ectasia](#)
- [Ductal and lobular neoplasms](#)
- [Ductal carcinoma in situ, solid type](#)
- [Ductal carcinoma in situ, solid type of breast, NOS](#)
- [Ductal, lobular AND/OR medullary neoplasm](#)
- [Durvalumab](#)
- [Dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging](#)
- [Dynamic nuclear imaging acquisition](#)
- [Dyslipidemia](#)
- [Dysplasia](#)
- [Dysplastic nodule](#)
- [Dyspnea](#)
- [Dysuria](#)
- [E - Extrahepatic marker](#)
- [Ear](#)
- [Ear, nose and throat structure](#)
- [Early arterial phase](#)
- [Early venous phase](#)
- [Ease of respiration - finding](#)
- [Echinococcosis](#)
- [Echinococcosis of liver](#)
- [Echo planar](#)
- [Echo time](#)
- [Echogenicity characteristic](#)
- [ECOG performance status](#)
- [ECOG performance status - grade 0](#)
- [ECOG performance status - grade 1](#)
- [ECOG performance status - grade 2](#)

- [ECOG performance status - grade 3](#)
- [ECOG performance status - grade 4](#)
- [ECOG performance status - grade 5](#)
- [ECOG performance status finding](#)
- [ECOG Performance Status score](#)
- [Edema](#)
- [Edema](#)
- [Edema Volume](#)
- [Edition of American Joint Commission on Cancer, Cancer Staging Manual used for TNM staging](#)
- [Effective dose](#)
- [EGFR gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [Electrons](#)
- [Eloquent Brain](#)
- [Eloquent Brain Areas](#)
- [Elscint](#)
- [Embryonal neuroepithelial tumor](#)
- [Emphysema](#)
- [Encapsulated papillary carcinoma](#)
- [Endocrine gland structure](#)
- [ENDOCRINE THERAPY](#)
- [endoluminal coil](#)
- [endorectal coil](#)
- [Endoscopic operation](#)
- [Endoscopic procedure](#)
- [Endoscopy](#)
- [Energy and stamina finding](#)
- [Enhancement pattern](#)
- [enhancement phase](#)
- [Enhancement Quality](#)
- [Enhancement Quality value](#)
- [Enhancing](#)
- [Enhancing margin](#)
- [Enhancing margin value](#)
- [Enhancing tumor](#)
- [Enhancing tumor Crosses Midline](#)
- [Enhancing tumor Crosses Midline value](#)
- [Enhancing Tumor Volume](#)
- [Enterectomy with anastomosis](#)
- [Entire](#)
- [Entire body region](#)
- [Entire breast](#)
- [Entire Broca's area](#)
- [Entire cerebral cingulum](#)
- [Entire colon](#)
- [Entire face and neck](#)
- [Entire limb](#)
- [Entire ovary](#)
- [Entire thyroid gland](#)
- [Entire uterus](#)
- [Entire vulva](#)
- [Enzyme level - finding](#)
- [Enzyme measurement](#)
- [enzyme unit per liter](#)
- [enzyme unit per milliliter](#)
- [Ependymal Extension](#)
- [Ependymal Extension value](#)
- [Epirubicin](#)
- [Episode](#)
- [Epithelial neoplasm](#)
- [Epithelial neoplasms, NOS](#)
- [Epithelioid glioblastoma](#)
- [ER negative](#)
- [ER positive](#)
- [ERBB2 gene duplication \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by FISH](#)
- [ERBB2 Gene Mutation measurement](#)
- [ERBB2 gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [ERBB2 Gene Variant measurement \(HER2\)](#)
- [Eribulin](#)
- [Esaote](#)
- [Esophagus](#)
- [Estrogen receptor Ag \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)

- [Ethnic group](#)
- [Ethnicity](#)
- [European](#)
- [EuroSpine Morbidity state](#)
- [Evaluation finding](#)
- [Evaluation of gastrointestinal tract](#)
- [Evaluation of test results](#)
- [Evaluation of urine specimen](#)
- [Evaluation procedure](#)
- [Event](#)
- [Evidence Type](#)
- [Ex-drinker](#)
- [Ex-smoker](#)
- [Exam](#)
- [Examination by method](#)
- [Examination of abdomen](#)
- [Excision](#)
- [Excision of abdominal lymph node](#)
- [Excision of axillary lymph node](#)
- [Excision of axillary lymph nodes group](#)
- [Excision of brain](#)
- [Excision of breast](#)
- [Excision of breast tissue](#)
- [Excision of colon](#)
- [Excision of group of lymph nodes](#)
- [Excision of head structure](#)
- [Excision of intestinal structure](#)
- [Excision of lesion of breast](#)
- [Excision of lesion of large intestine](#)
- [Excision of lesion of rectum](#)
- [Excision of lesion of rectum by transanal approach](#)
- [Excision of liver](#)
- [Excision of lung or bronchus](#)
- [Excision of lymph node](#)
- [Excision of malignant lesion of trunk](#)
- [Excision of malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Excision of malignant tumor of rectum by transanal approach](#)
- [Excision of mass](#)
- [Excision of mass of breast](#)
- [Excision of mass of pelvic region](#)
- [Excision of neoplasm](#)
- [Excision of pelvic lymph node](#)
- [Excision of pelvis](#)
- [Excision of polyp of large intestine](#)
- [Excision of rectum by transanal approach](#)
- [Excision of regional lymph nodes](#)
- [Exemestane](#)
- [Expression Negative](#)
- [Expression Positive](#)
- [Extensiveness](#)
- [Extent of Resection](#)
- [Extents](#)
- [External beam radiation therapy procedure](#)
- [External beam radiation therapy using electrons](#)
- [External beam radiation therapy using photons](#)
- [External radiation therapy using superficial radiation](#)
- [Extramural vein invasion](#)
- [Extramural vein invasion \[Presence\] in Colorectal cancer specimen by Light microscopy](#)
- [Extramural vein invasion | Colorectal cancer specimen | Pathology](#)
- [Extraprostatic Extension \(EPE\)](#)
- [Extraprostatic extension of tumor present](#)
- [Extreme fibroglandular tissue](#)
- [Extremely dense](#)
- [Extremity](#)
- [Extremity part](#)
- [Eye region structure](#)
- [Face](#)
- [Face and/or neck structure](#)
- [Facilitated](#)
- [Facilitated diffusion](#)
- [Fairly heavy drinker](#)

- [False](#)
- [Family history of breast cancer](#)
- [Family history of cancer](#)
- [Family history of clinical finding](#)
- [Family history of disorder](#)
- [Family history of endocrine disorders](#)
- [Family history of female genital tract disorder](#)
- [Family history of malignant neoplasm of breast at under age 50 in second degree relative](#)
- [Family history of malignant neoplasm of breast diagnosed before 45 years of age](#)
- [Family history of malignant neoplasm of breast in first degree relative](#)
- [Family history of malignant neoplasm of genital structure](#)
- [Family history of malignant neoplasm of ovary](#)
- [Family history of malignant neoplasm of ovary in first degree relative](#)
- [Family history of malignant neoplasm of ovary in second degree relative](#)
- [Family history of neoplasm](#)
- [Family history of neoplasm of breast](#)
- [Family history of prostate cancer](#)
- [Family history unknown](#)
- [Family history with explicit context](#)
- [Father](#)
- [Fatigue](#)
- [Fatty](#)
- [Feet first orientation](#)
- [FEMALE](#)
- [Female](#)
- [Female \(finding\)](#)
- [Female genital organ structure](#)
- [Female genital tract functions](#)
- [Female genital tract structure](#)
- [Female genitalia finding](#)
- [Female reproductive finding](#)
- [FH: Breast disease](#)
- [FH: Genitourinary disease](#)
- [FH: neoplasm of female genital organ](#)
- [FH: neoplasm of male genital organ](#)
- [FH: neoplasm of ovary](#)
- [FHIR](#)
- [Fibroepithelial neoplasms](#)
- [Fibrolamellar hepatocellular carcinoma](#)
- [Fibromatous neoplasms](#)
- [Fibrosis of lung](#)
- [FIGO grade 1](#)
- [FIGO grade 2](#)
- [FIGO grade 3](#)
- [FIGO ovarian tumor staging system](#)
- [FIGO Stage 0](#)
- [FIGO Stage 1](#)
- [FIGO Stage 2](#)
- [FIGO Stage 3](#)
- [FIGO Stage 4](#)
- [FIGO staging system of gynecological malignancy](#)
- [FIGO Vaginal tumor staging system](#)
- [Final](#)
- [Finding context value](#)
- [Finding of abdomen](#)
- [Finding of abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)
- [Finding of American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification](#)
- [Finding of blood, lymphatics and immune system](#)
- [Finding of bowel action](#)
- [Finding of bowel continence](#)
- [Finding of change compared to previous radiologic examination](#)
- [Finding of change compared to previous radiologic examination finding](#)
- [Finding of colon](#)
- [Finding of color of skin](#)
- [Finding of defecation](#)
- [Finding of frequency of urination](#)
- [Finding of grade](#)
- [Finding of Hepatitis B status](#)
- [Finding of Hepatitis C status](#)
- [Finding of histologic grading differentiation AND/OR behavior](#)
- [Finding of immune status](#)

- [Finding of large intestine](#)
- [Finding of lesion](#)
- [Finding of pattern of urination](#)
- [Finding of pelvic region of trunk](#)
- [Finding of pelvis](#)
- [Finding of region of thorax](#)
- [Finding of respiration](#)
- [Finding of sexual function](#)
- [Finding of substance level](#)
- [Finding of thickness of skin](#)
- [Finding of tobacco use and exposure](#)
- [Finding of trunk structure](#)
- [Finding of upper trunk](#)
- [Finding of urinary bladder emptying](#)
- [Finding of urinary tract proper](#)
- [Finding of urinary tract proper](#)
- [Finding related to ability to pass urine](#)
- [Finding related to biological sex](#)
- [Finding related to menstrual cycle](#)
- [Finding relating to alcohol drinking behavior](#)
- [Finding status values](#)
- [Finding suspected or known present](#)
- [Finding value](#)
- [Finding with explicit context](#)
- [Fine needle aspiration biopsy of prostate](#)
- [Fine needle aspiration of breast](#)
- [Fine needle biopsy](#)
- [First degree](#)
- [First degree blood relative](#)
- [First line treatment](#)
- [FLAIR](#)
- [Flow of urine - finding](#)
- [Flowsheet - laboratory](#)
- [floxuridine](#)
- [Fluid disorder](#)
- [Fluid disturbance](#)
- [Fluid sample albumin measurement](#)
- [Fluorescence imaging](#)
- [Fluoroscopy](#)
- [Fluorouracil](#)
- [Focal](#)
- [focal damage](#)
- [Focal nodular hyperplasia of liver](#)
- [FOLFIRI](#)
- [FOLFIRINOX](#)
- [FOLFOX](#)
- [Follicular adenocarcinoma](#)
- [Follicular carcinoma, NOS](#)
- [Follow-up](#)
- [Follow-up Examination After Treatment for Malignant Neoplasm](#)
- [Follow-up status](#)
- [Foot](#)
- [Formations](#)
- [Fotemustine](#)
- [Free prostate specific antigen level](#)
- [Free:total PSA ratio](#)
- [French Federation of Cancer Centers Sarcoma Group \(FNCLCC\) grading system](#)
- [Frequencies](#)
- [Frequency interval](#)
- [Frontal brain region](#)
- [Frontal lobe](#)
- [Eujifilm](#)
- [Fulvestrant](#)
- [Function](#)
- [Functional finding](#)
- [Functional finding of gastrointestinal tract](#)
- [Functional magnetic resonance imaging](#)
- [g e n1000029](#)
- [G1 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G1](#)
- [G1: Well differentiated](#)
- [G2 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G2](#)

- [G2: Moderately differentiated](#)
- [G3 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G3](#)
- [G3: Poorly differentiated](#)
- [G4 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G4](#)
- [G4: Undifferentiated](#)
- [G5 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G5](#)
- [Gallbladder](#)
- [Gamma glutamyl transferase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Gamma glutamyl transferase measurement](#)
- [Gas retention](#)
- [Gastrointestinal anastomosis procedure](#)
- [Gastrointestinal and digestive anastomosis](#)
- [Gastrointestinal and digestive injury](#)
- [Gastrointestinal obstruction](#)
- [Gastrointestinal tract finding](#)
- [Gastrointestinal tract structure](#)
- [Gemcitabine](#)
- [Gender](#)
- [Gene deletion](#)
- [Gene mutation](#)
- [Gene rearrangement](#)
- [General adjectival modifier](#)
- [General body state finding](#)
- [General clinical stage for disease AND/OR neoplasm](#)
- [General clinical state](#)
- [General clinical state finding](#)
- [General Electric](#)
- [General finding of observation of patient](#)
- [General pathology](#)
- [General physical performance status](#)
- [General problem AND/OR complaint](#)
- [Generic anatomical site tumor invasion status](#)
- [Generic Category](#)
- [Generic Module](#)
- [Generic tumor staging descriptor](#)
- [Genetic disease](#)
- [Genetic finding](#)
- [Genetic finding detected](#)
- [Genetic finding not detected](#)
- [Genetic test](#)
- [Genital finding](#)
- [Genitourinary sample](#)
- [Giant cell glioblastoma](#)
- [Giant cell glioblastoma of brain](#)
- [Glandular zone of prostate](#)
- [Gleason finding](#)
- [Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer](#)
- [Gleason grade group 1](#)
- [Gleason grade group 2](#)
- [Gleason grade group 3](#)
- [Gleason grade group 4](#)
- [Gleason grade group 5](#)
- [Gleason grade score 10 out of 10](#)
- [Gleason grade score 2 out of 10](#)
- [Gleason grade score 3 out of 10](#)
- [Gleason grade score 4 out of 10](#)
- [Gleason grade score 5 out of 10](#)
- [Gleason grade score 6 out of 10](#)
- [Gleason grade score 7 out of 10](#)
- [Gleason grade score 8 out of 10](#)
- [Gleason grade score 9 out of 10](#)
- [Gleason grading system for prostatic cancer](#)
- [Gleason pattern](#)
- [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 1](#)
- [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 2](#)
- [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 3](#)
- [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 4](#)
- [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 5](#)
- [Gleason score](#)
- [Gleason scoring system for malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)
- [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 1](#)

- [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 2](#)
- [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 3](#)
- [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 4](#)
- [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 5](#)
- [Glioblastoma](#)
- [Glioblastoma multiforme](#)
- [Glioblastoma multiforme of brain](#)
- [Glioblastoma multiforme of central nervous system](#)
- [Glioblastoma, NOS, of nervous system, NOS](#)
- [Glioma](#)
- [Glioma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Gliomatosis cerebri](#)
- [Gliomatosis cerebri](#)
- [Gliosarcoma](#)
- [Globulin measurement](#)
- [Glucose \[Mass/volume\] in Venous blood](#)
- [Glucose measurement](#)
- [Glucose measurement, blood](#)
- [Glucose measurement, quantitative](#)
- [Glucose|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Glucose|Moment in time|Blood venous|180.156 g/mole](#)
- [Glycoproteins measurement](#)
- [Gonadotropin releasing hormone analogues](#)
- [Grade 1 on a scale of 0 to 5](#)
- [Grade 1 tumor](#)
- [Grade 2 on a scale of 0 to 5](#)
- [Grade 2 tumor](#)
- [Grade 3 on a scale of 0 to 5](#)
- [Grade 3 tumor](#)
- [Grade 4 on a scale of 0 to 5](#)
- [Grade 4 tumor](#)
- [Grade 5 on a scale of 0 to 5](#)
- [Grade cannot be assessed \(GX\); Unknown](#)
- [Grade group 1 \(Gleason score 3 + 3 = 6\)](#)
- [Grade group 2 \(Gleason score 3 + 4 = 7\)](#)
- [Grade group 3 \(Gleason score 4 + 3 = 7\)](#)
- [Grade group 4 \(Gleason score 3 + 5 = 8\)](#)
- [Grade group 4 \(Gleason score 4 + 4 = 8\)](#)
- [Grade group 4 \(Gleason score 5 + 3 = 8\)](#)
- [Grade group 5 \(Gleason score 4 + 5 = 9\)](#)
- [Grade group 5 \(Gleason score 5 + 4 = 9\)](#)
- [Grade group 5 \(Gleason score 5 + 5 = 10\)](#)
- [Grade Pathological](#)
- [Grades](#)
- [Gradient echo](#)
- [gram per deciliter](#)
- [Granulocyte colony-stimulating factor](#)
- [Gravida](#)
- [Gross examination and sampling of tissue specimen](#)
- [Gross Total Resection](#)
- [Gross total resection of lobe of brain \(lobectomy\).|\(Tumor involves more than half of lobe\)](#)
- [Growth alteration](#)
- [GSTP1 gene+APC gene methylation \[Presence\] in Tissue by Molecular genetics method](#)
- [GX: Histologic grade cannot be assessed](#)
- [Gy](#)
- [H+](#)
- [Haemorrhage Volume](#)
- [Hamartoma](#)
- [Hamartoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Hamartoma of intestine](#)
- [Hamartomatous polyp](#)
- [Head](#)
- [Head and neck](#)
- [Head first orientation](#)
- [Head part](#)
- [Health Status Assessment](#)
- [Health-related behavior](#)
- [Health-related behavior finding](#)
- [Healthcare professional](#)
- [Healthy patient](#)
- [Heart](#)

- [Heart and/or pericardium structure](#)
- [Heart, mediastinum, and pleura](#)
- [Heavy cigarette smoker \(20-39 cigarettes per day\)](#)
- [Heavy drinker](#)
- [Hemangioma](#)
- [Hematocrit \[Volume Fraction\] of Blood](#)
- [Hematopoietic neoplasm](#)
- [Hematoxylin and eosin stain method](#)
- [Hematoxylin stain method](#)
- [Hemoglobin \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Hemoglobin A1c/Hemoglobin.total in Blood by HPLC](#)
- [Hemoglobin A1c/Hemoglobin.total|Mass Fraction|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Hemoglobin below reference range](#)
- [Hemoglobin level outside reference range](#)
- [Hemoglobin|Moment in time|Blood](#)
- [Hemoptysis](#)
- [Hemorrhage](#)
- [Hemorrhage volume](#)
- [Hemorrhage volume value](#)
- [Hemorrhagic tumor](#)
- [Hepatic cystadenoma](#)
- [Hepatic fibrosis](#)
- [Hepatic flexure](#)
- [Hepatic flexure of colon](#)
- [Hepatocellular carcinoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Hepatocellular carcinoma, fibrolamellar](#)
- [HER2](#)
- [HER2 \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)
- [HER2 Ag \[Presence\] in Tissue by Immune stain](#)
- [HER2 negative](#)
- [HER2 positive](#)
- [HER2 positive \(enriched\)/HR positive \(luminal\)](#)
- [HER2 positive\(enriched\)/HR negative \(non-luminal\)](#)
- [HER2 | Breast cancer specimen | Pathology](#)
- [HER2 | Tissue and Smears | Pathology](#)
- [Hereditary cancer-predisposing syndrome](#)
- [Hereditary disease](#)
- [Hereditary disorder of nervous system](#)
- [Hereditary disorder of the integument](#)
- [Heterogeneous fibroglandular tissue](#)
- [Heterogeneously dense](#)
- [Heterogenously echogenic](#)
- [High](#)
- [High ADC value](#)
- [High density](#)
- [High density lipoprotein cholesterol measurement](#)
- [High dose rate brachytherapy](#)
- [High grade glioma](#)
- [High histologic grade](#)
- [High risk](#)
- [High Risk Acute Leukemia](#)
- [High risk of recurrence, prostate cancer](#)
- [Hip joint](#)
- [Hip region structure](#)
- [Hispanic](#)
- [Hispanic or Latino](#)
- [Histologic](#)
- [Histologic Behavior and Type](#)
- [Histologic feature of neoplasm](#)
- [Histologic grade of neoplasm](#)
- [Histologic grade of primary malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Histologic grade of primary malignant neoplasm of prostate by International Society of Urological Pathology technique](#)
- [Histologic grades](#)
- [Histologic grading differentiation AND/OR behavior](#)
- [Histologic test](#)
- [Histologic type of malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Histologic type of primary malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Histological grades](#)
- [Histological grading systems](#)
- [Histology/Morphology](#)
- [Histopathology](#)

- [Histopathology finding](#)
- [Histopathology Result](#)
- [Histopathology test](#)
- [History of cancer metastatic to bone](#)
- [History of cancer metastatic to brain](#)
- [History of cancer metastatic to liver](#)
- [History of cancer metastatic to lung](#)
- [History of cancer metastatic to lymph nodes](#)
- [History of clinical finding in subject](#)
- [History of disseminated malignant neoplasm](#)
- [History of metastatic cancer](#)
- [Hitachi](#)
- [Hologic](#)
- [Homogeneously dense](#)
- [Hormone](#)
- [HORMONE ANTAGONISTS AND RELATED AGENTS](#)
- [Hormone measurement](#)
- [Hormone receptor negative neoplasm](#)
- [Hormone receptor positive tumor](#)
- [Hormone refractory prostate cancer](#)
- [Hormone replacement therapy](#)
- [Hormone sensitive prostate cancer](#)
- [Hormone therapy](#)
- [HORMONES AND RELATED AGENTS](#)
- [Human Specimen](#)
- [Husband](#)
- [Hyperechoic](#)
- [Hypermethylated](#)
- [Hyperpigmentation of skin](#)
- [Hyperplasia of prostate](#)
- [Hyperthermia Treatment](#)
- [Hypoechoic](#)
- [Hypofractionated radiation therapy](#)
- [Hypofractionated stereotactic radiotherapy using megavoltage radiation](#)
- [Hypofractionated whole breast radiation therapy](#)
- [Hypothalamic or pituitary hormone](#)
- [Hypothalamic releasing factor](#)
- [Hypothalamus](#)
- [I](#)
- [I](#)
- [I.M.S](#)
- [ICDO3Morphology](#)
- [ICDO3Topography](#)
- [ICDO3Tumor](#)
- [IDH1 \(isocitrate dehydrogenase \(NADP\(+\)\) 1\).gene variant measurement](#)
- [IDH1 and IDH2 genes targeted mutation analysis in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method](#)
- [IDH1 gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [IDH2 \(isocitrate dehydrogenase \(NADP\(+\)\) 2\).gene variant measurement](#)
- [IGRT \(image-guided radiation therapy\)](#)
- [II](#)
- [II](#)
- [IIA](#)
- [IIA](#)
- [IIB](#)
- [IIB](#)
- [IIC](#)
- [IIC](#)
- [III](#)
- [III](#)
- [IIIA](#)
- [IIIA](#)
- [IIIB](#)
- [IIIB](#)
- [IIIC](#)
- [IIIC](#)
- [Image](#)
- [Image acquisition mode](#)
- [Image Acquisition Date](#)
- [Image Coordinate System](#)
- [Image Date](#)
- [Image processing attribute](#)

- [Image Series](#)
- [Image Study](#)
- [Imaging](#)
- [Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)
- [Imaging by body site](#)
- [Imaging Criteria](#)
- [Imaging finding](#)
- [Imaging guidance](#)
- [Imaging guided biopsy](#)
- [Imaging modality](#)
- [Imaging Module](#)
- [Imaging observable](#)
- [Imaging observation](#)
- [Imaging observation descriptor](#)
- [Imaging of abdomen](#)
- [Imaging of brain](#)
- [Imaging of breast](#)
- [Imaging of central nervous system](#)
- [Imaging of genitourinary system](#)
- [Imaging of pelvis](#)
- [Imaging procedure descriptor](#)
- [Imaging procedure property](#)
- [Imaging result abnormal](#)
- [Imaging result normal](#)
- [Imaging sequence](#)
- [Imaging technician](#)
- [Imaging without IV contrast](#)
- [Immediate family member](#)
- [Immune system excision](#)
- [Immune system surgical procedure](#)
- [Immunologic agent](#)
- [Immunological therapy](#)
- [Immunomodulatory](#)
- [Immunotherapeutic agent](#)
- [Immunotherapy for cancer](#)
- [Impaired urinary system function](#)
- [Improved](#)
- [In situ neoplasm \(morphology\)](#)
- [Inactive](#)
- [Inadequate](#)
- [Incomplete emptying of urinary bladder](#)
- [Incontinence](#)
- [Incontinence of feces](#)
- [Increased](#)
- [Increased frequency of urination](#)
- [Indeterminate](#)
- [Indistinct margin](#)
- [Infant feeding method - finding](#)
- [Infection control management](#)
- [Infection of liver caused by parasite](#)
- [Infiltrating carcinoma with ductal and lobular features](#)
- [Infiltrating duct and lobular carcinoma](#)
- [Infiltrating duct and lobular carcinoma of breast, NOS](#)
- [Infiltrating duct carcinoma](#)
- [Infiltrating duct carcinoma of breast](#)
- [Infiltrating duct carcinoma of prostate](#)
- [Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS](#)
- [Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS, of breast, NOS](#)
- [Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#)
- [Infiltrating duct mixed with other types of carcinoma](#)
- [Infiltrating lobular carcinoma of breast](#)
- [Inflammation of specific body organs](#)
- [Inflammatory disease of liver](#)
- [Inflammatory disorder of lower respiratory tract](#)
- [Inflammatory morphology](#)
- [Infratentorial brain part](#)
- [Infratentorial brain structure](#)
- [Injury of abdomen](#)
- [Injury of breast](#)
- [Inspection](#)
- [Insula and opercula structure](#)

- [Insular carcinoma](#)
- [Insular structure](#)
- [Insulin \[Units/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Insulin measurement](#)
- [Insulin-like growth factor-I receptor Ag \[Presence\] in Tissue by Immune stain](#)
- [Intensity modulated external beam neutron radiation therapy](#)
- [Intensity modulated intracavitary brachytherapy](#)
- [Intensity modulated radiation therapy](#)
- [Intensity modulated radiation therapy](#)
- [Intensity of stain of estrogen receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)
- [Intensity of stain of progesterone receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)
- [Intents](#)
- [Intergroup Rhabdomyosarcoma Study Group Clinical Staging and Grouping System](#)
- [Intermediate](#)
- [Intermediate histologic grade](#)
- [Intermediate Risk](#)
- [Intermediate risk of recurrence, prostate cancer](#)
- [Intermediate weighted](#)
- [Internal capsule](#)
- [internally inserted coil](#)
- [International Society of Pathology histologic grade group](#)
- [International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 1](#)
- [International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 2](#)
- [International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 3](#)
- [International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 4](#)
- [International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 5](#)
- [International Society of Urological Pathology prostate cancer staging system](#)
- [international unit per milliliter](#)
- [Interoperability level](#)
- [Interpretation of findings](#)
- [Intervals of weeks and months](#)
- [Interventional radiology](#)
- [Intestinal obstruction](#)
- [Intestinal polyposis syndrome](#)
- [Intestinal structure](#)
- [Intra-abdominal collection](#)
- [Intra-abdominal digestive structure](#)
- [Intra-abdominal proper structure](#)
- [Intra-abdominal urinary structure](#)
- [Intra-abdominopelvic structure](#)
- [Intra-pelvic structure of true pelvis](#)
- [Intraabdominal bile collection](#)
- [Intracavitary brachytherapy](#)
- [Intracranial structure](#)
- [Intraductal calcifications](#)
- [Intraductal carcinoma and lobular carcinoma in situ](#)
- [Intraductal carcinoma, noninfiltrating, NOS](#)
- [Intraductal carcinoma, noninfiltrating, NOS, of prostate gland](#)
- [Intraluminal brachytherapy](#)
- [Intraoperative Rad Rx \(IORT\)](#)
- [Intravascular brachytherapy](#)
- [Invasion into the Seminal vesicle](#)
- [Invasive](#)
- [Invasive carcinoma of breast](#)
- [Invasive carcinoma of breast with extensive intraductal component](#)
- [Invasive carcinoma of breast without extensive intraductal component](#)
- [Invasive ductal carcinoma with an extensive intraductal component](#)
- [IOERT - intraoperative electron radiotherapy](#)
- [IPATASERTIB](#)
- [Ipilimumab](#)
- [irinotecan](#)
- [Iron deficiency anemia](#)
- [Irregular](#)
- [Irregular mass](#)
- [Isoechoic](#)
- [IV](#)
- [IV](#)
- [IVA](#)
- [IVA](#)
- [IVB](#)
- [IVB](#)

- [IVC](#)
- [Joint structure of lower extremity](#)
- [Joint structure of pelvic girdle](#)
- [Karnofsky Performance Scale \(KPS\) 0](#)
- [Karnofsky performance status](#)
- [KERMA area product](#)
- [Kidney](#)
- [Kidney disease](#)
- [Kidney finding](#)
- [Kidney structure](#)
- [Knee](#)
- [Known](#)
- [Known absent](#)
- [Known present](#)
- [KPS 10](#)
- [KPS 100](#)
- [KPS 20](#)
- [KPS 30](#)
- [KPS 40](#)
- [KPS 50](#)
- [KPS 60](#)
- [KPS 70](#)
- [KPS 80](#)
- [KPS 90](#)
- [KRAS \(KRAS proto-oncogene, GTPase\) gene variant measurement](#)
- [KRAS gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal Laboratory](#)
- [Laboratory](#)
- [Laboratory data interpretation](#)
- [Laboratory procedure](#)
- [Laboratory procedure categorized by method](#)
- [Laboratory procedure performed](#)
- [Laboratory procedures -general](#)
- [Laboratory test](#)
- [Laboratory Test Result](#)
- [Lactate dehydrogenase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Red Blood Cells](#)
- [Lactate dehydrogenase measurement](#)
- [Laparoscopic procedure](#)
- [Laparoscopic Procedures on the Prostate](#)
- [Laparoscopic prostatectomy](#)
- [Laparoscopic radical prostatectomy](#)
- [Laparoscopy, surgical prostatectomy, retropubic radical, including nerve sparing, includes robotic assistance, when performed](#)
- [Lapatinib](#)
- [Large cell carcinoma, NOS](#)
- [Large cell carcinoma, NOS, of lung, NOS](#)
- [Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma](#)
- [Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma](#)
- [Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma of prostate gland](#)
- [Large intestine excision](#)
- [Large intestine part](#)
- [Late arterial phase](#)
- [Late venous phase](#)
- [Laterality](#)
- [Latino](#)
- [LCIS \(lobular carcinoma in situ\) of breast](#)
- [Left](#)
- [Left anterior apical part of transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Left anterior apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Left anterior basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Left anterior basal transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Left anterior middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Left anterior middle transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Left apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)
- [Left apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Left apical transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Left basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)
- [Left basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Left basal transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Left breast structure](#)
- [Left colectomy](#)
- [Left colon structure](#)
- [Left lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)

- [Left middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)
- [Left middle transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Left posterior apical part of transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Left posterior basal transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Left posterior middle transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Left posterolateral apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Left posterolateral basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Left posterolateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Left posteromedial apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Left posteromedial middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Left thorax structure](#)
- [Length dimension of neoplasm](#)
- [Length of lymph node in excised specimen](#)
- [Lentiginosis](#)
- [Lentigo](#)
- [Lesion](#)
- [Lesion observable](#)
- [Lesion of liver](#)
- [Lesion of lung](#)
- [Lesion of prostate](#)
- [Lesion of rectum](#)
- [Lesion of uterus](#)
- [Lesion Site](#)
- [Lesion size](#)
- [Lesion size, additional dimension](#)
- [Lesion size, greatest dimension](#)
- [Less than one cigarette per day](#)
- [Letrozole](#)
- [leucovorin](#)
- [Leukemia Finding](#)
- [Leukocytes \[#\]/volume\] in Stem cell product](#)
- [Leukopenia](#)
- [Level 1 axillary clearance of lymph nodes](#)
- [Level 2 axillary clearance of lymph nodes](#)
- [Level 3 axillary clearance of lymph nodes](#)
- [LI-RADS 1](#)
- [LI-RADS 2](#)
- [LI-RADS 3](#)
- [LI-RADS 4](#)
- [LI-RADS 5](#)
- [LI-RADS assessment](#)
- [LI-RADS M](#)
- [LI-RADS Treated](#)
- [Lifetime non-drinker](#)
- [Lifetime non-drinker of alcohol](#)
- [Light cigarette smoker \(1-9 cigarettes per day\)](#)
- [Light drinker](#)
- [Light microscopy](#)
- [Likert scale](#)
- [Limited](#)
- [Lipids measurement](#)
- [Liver](#)
- [Liver and intrahepatic bile ducts](#)
- [Liver and/or biliary structure](#)
- [Liver cell carcinoma](#)
- [Liver damage](#)
- [Liver disorder due to infection](#)
- [Liver finding](#)
- [Liver lobe part](#)
- [Liver mass](#)
- [Liver part](#)
- [Liver regeneration](#)
- [Liver segment](#)
- [Liver structure](#)
- [Liver tumor morphology](#)
- [Lobe of liver](#)
- [Lobectomy](#)
- [Lobectomy of brain](#)
- [Lobular](#)
- [Lobular carcinoma](#)
- [Lobular carcinoma in situ \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)

- [Lobular carcinoma in situ, NOS](#)
- [Lobular carcinoma in situ, NOS, of breast, NOS](#)
- [Lobular carcinoma in situ, pleomorphic of breast, NOS](#)
- [Lobular carcinoma, NOS](#)
- [Lobular carcinoma, NOS, of breast, NOS](#)
- [Local](#)
- [Local excision](#)
- [Localized](#)
- [Longitudinal](#)
- [Longitudinal](#)
- [Low](#)
- [Low ADC value](#)
- [Low anterior resection of rectum](#)
- [Low density lipoprotein cholesterol measurement](#)
- [Low dose](#)
- [Low dose rate brachytherapy](#)
- [Low histologic grade](#)
- [Low risk](#)
- [Low risk of recurrence, prostate cancer](#)
- [Low-Dose Computed Tomography](#)
- [Lower body part structure](#)
- [Lower bowel structures](#)
- [Lower extremity part](#)
- [Lower gastrointestinal procedure](#)
- [Lower respiratory tract observable](#)
- [Lower respiratory tract specimen](#)
- [Lower respiratory tract structure](#)
- [Lower-inner quadrant of breast](#)
- [Lower-outer quadrant of breast](#)
- [Lumbar spine](#)
- [Lumbosacral region of spine structure](#)
- [Lumbosacral spine](#)
- [Luminal A](#)
- [Luminal androgen receptor](#)
- [Luminal B](#)
- [Luminal B- HER2 negative](#)
- [Luminal B- HER2 positive](#)
- [Lumpectomy of breast](#)
- [Lung excision](#)
- [Lung finding](#)
- [Lung involvement stages](#)
- [Lung mass](#)
- [Lung observable](#)
- [Lung part](#)
- [Lung stage L1](#)
- [Lung stage L2](#)
- [Lung stage L3](#)
- [Lung structure](#)
- [Lung volume](#)
- [Lung volume AND/OR capacity](#)
- [Lung, NOS](#)
- [Lymph node observable](#)
- [Lymph node station of involved lymph nodes](#)
- [Lymph node structure of limb](#)
- [Lymph Nodes with Metastasis](#)
- [Lymphatic \(small vessel\) tumor invasion finding](#)
- [Lymphatic small vessel invasion by tumor absent](#)
- [Lymphatic small vessel invasion by tumor present](#)
- [Lymphatic system excision](#)
- [Lymphoid neoplasm](#)
- [Lymphovascular invasion](#)
- [Lymphovascular invasion extent](#)
- [Lymphovascular invasion extent in Cancer specimen Qualitative](#)
- [Lymphovascular invasion extent | Cancer specimen | Pathology](#)
- [Lynch syndrome](#)
- [M - Metastatic marker](#)
- [M category](#)
- [Macrocalcifications](#)
- [Magnetic resonance angiography](#)
- [Magnetic resonance imaging](#)
- [Magnetic resonance imaging](#)

- [Magnetic resonance imaging guidance](#)
- [Magnetic resonance imaging of breast for screening for malignant neoplasm procedure](#)
- [Magnetic resonance spectroscopy](#)
- [Magnetic resonance venography](#)
- [MALE](#)
- [Male](#)
- [Male \(finding\)](#)
- [Male genital organ structure](#)
- [Male genital sample](#)
- [Malignant](#)
- [Malignant adenomatous neoplasm](#)
- [Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Malignant basal cell tumor](#)
- [Malignant colorectal neoplasm](#)
- [Malignant epithelial neoplasm](#)
- [Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Malignant glioma](#)
- [Malignant glioma of brain](#)
- [Malignant glioma of brainstem](#)
- [Malignant glioma of central nervous system](#)
- [Malignant hematopoietic neoplasm](#)
- [Malignant lymphoma](#)
- [Malignant lymphoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Malignant lymphoma of liver](#)
- [Malignant lymphoma, non-Hodgkin, NOS](#)
- [Malignant lymphoma, non-Hodgkin, NOS, of unknown primary site](#)
- [Malignant lymphoma, NOS](#)
- [Malignant lymphomas, NOS or diffuse](#)
- [Malignant meningeal neoplasm](#)
- [Malignant meningioma of meninges of brain](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of abdomen](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of anorectum](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of areola](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of bladder](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of bone](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of brain](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of brainstem](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of breast](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of bronchus and lung](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of central nervous system](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of cerebral meninges](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of cervix uteri](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of colon](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of colon and/or rectum](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of digestive system](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of female breast](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of gallbladder](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of gastrointestinal tract](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of genital structure](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of genitourinary organ](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of intraabdominal organ](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of liver](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of lower respiratory tract](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of nervous system](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of nipple](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of oesophagus](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of other connective and soft tissue](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of ovary](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of pancreas](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of rectum](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of respiratory system](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of skeletal system](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of soft tissue](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of stomach](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of thorax](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of thyroid gland](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of uterus](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of vagina](#)
- [Malignant neoplasm of vulva](#)

- [Malignant neoplasm: Nipple and areola](#)
- [Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs](#)
- [Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract](#)
- [Malignant neoplastic disease](#)
- [Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm](#)
- [Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm, epithelial](#)
- [Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm, neural](#)
- [Malignant neuroendocrine tumor](#)
- [Malignant peripheral nerve sheath tumor, NOS](#)
- [Malignant phyllodes tumor](#)
- [Malignant squamous cell neoplasm](#)
- [Malignant tumor of ascending colon](#)
- [Malignant tumor of axilla](#)
- [Malignant tumor of bronchus](#)
- [Malignant tumor of cecum](#)
- [Malignant tumor of descending colon](#)
- [Malignant tumor of digestive organ](#)
- [Malignant tumor of female genital organ](#)
- [Malignant tumor of head and neck](#)
- [Malignant tumor of hepatic flexure](#)
- [Malignant tumor of intestine](#)
- [Malignant tumor of kidney](#)
- [Malignant tumor of large intestine](#)
- [Malignant tumor of lung](#)
- [Malignant tumor of lymphoid hemopoietic and related tissue](#)
- [Malignant tumor of male genital organ](#)
- [Malignant tumor of meninges](#)
- [Malignant tumor of neck](#)
- [Malignant tumor of pelvis](#)
- [Malignant tumor of sigmoid colon](#)
- [Malignant tumor of splenic flexure](#)
- [Malignant tumor of upper limb](#)
- [Malignant tumor staging](#)
- [Mammary duct ectasia](#)
- [Mammographic architectural distortion of breast finding](#)
- [Mammographic breast composition finding \(finding\)](#)
- [Mammographic breast tissue appearance](#)
- [Mammography](#)
- [Mammography](#)
- [Mammography assessment \(Category 0\) - Need additional imaging evaluation](#)
- [Mammography assessment \(Category 1\) - Negative](#)
- [Mammography assessment \(Category 2\) - Benign finding](#)
- [Mammography assessment \(Category 3\) - Probably benign finding, short interval follow-up](#)
- [Mammography assessment \(Category 4\) - Suspicious abnormality, biopsy should be considered](#)
- [Mammography assessment \(Category 4A\) - low suspicion of malignancy](#)
- [Mammography assessment \(Category 4B\) - moderate suspicion of malignancy](#)
- [Mammography assessment \(Category 4C\) - high suspicion of malignancy](#)
- [Mammography assessment \(Category 5\) - Highly suggestive of malignancy](#)
- [Mammography assessment \(Category 6\) - known biopsy, proven malignancy](#)
- [Mammography assessment finding](#)
- [Mammography finding](#)
- [Mammography normal](#)
- [Mammography reference location](#)
- [Management of drug regimen](#)
- [Manual](#)
- [Manufacturer](#)
- [Marconi](#)
- [Margin](#)
- [Marked](#)
- [Markers for liver tumor staging](#)
- [Mask](#)
- [Mass](#)
- [Mass of body structure](#)
- [Mass of colon](#)
- [Mass of digestive structure](#)
- [Mass of female genital structure](#)
- [Mass of respiratory structure](#)
- [Mass of thoracic structure](#)
- [Mass of uterus](#)
- [Mass-Molar conversion](#)
- [Mathematical sign](#)

- [Maximal](#)
- [Measure of pregnancy](#)
- [Measurement](#)
- [Measurement finding](#)
- [Measurement finding outside reference range](#)
- [Measurement finding within reference range](#)
- [Measurement of level of drug in blood](#)
- [Measurement of level of substance in blood](#)
- [Measurement of liver enzyme](#)
- [Measurement of substance](#)
- [Measurement of substance in specimen](#)
- [Mechanical abnormality](#)
- [Mechanical disorder](#)
- [Mechanical lesion](#)
- [Mechanisms](#)
- [Mediastinum](#)
- [Medical Assessment](#)
- [Medical Oncologist](#)
- [Medical practitioner](#)
- [Medical therapy](#)
- [Medication](#)
- [Medication Review](#)
- [Mediso](#)
- [Melan-A and Ki67 Ag.\[Identifier\] in Tissue by Immune stain](#)
- [Melanocyte stimulating hormone releasing factor](#)
- [Melanosis](#)
- [Meninges](#)
- [Meninges part](#)
- [Meninges structure](#)
- [Meninges, NOS](#)
- [Meningioma, malignant](#)
- [Menopausal flushing](#)
- [Menopausal symptom](#)
- [Menopause finding](#)
- [Menopause, function](#)
- [Menstruation absent](#)
- [Menstruation finding](#)
- [Mental state, behavior / psychosocial function observable](#)
- [Mental state, behavior and/or psychosocial function finding](#)
- [Mesenchymal stem-like](#)
- [Mesenchymal-like](#)
- [Mesh](#)
- [MET gene mutations found.\[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [Metabolic disease](#)
- [Metabolic finding](#)
- [Metastasis](#)
- [Metastasis to adrenal gland](#)
- [Metastasis to bone](#)
- [Metastasis to brain](#)
- [Metastasis to central nervous system](#)
- [Metastasis to digestive organ](#)
- [Metastasis to digestive organs](#)
- [Metastasis to endocrine gland](#)
- [Metastasis to intrathoracic organs](#)
- [Metastasis to kidney](#)
- [Metastasis to Liver](#)
- [Metastasis to lung](#)
- [Metastasis to nervous system](#)
- [Metastasis to pleura](#)
- [Metastasis to retroperitoneum](#)
- [Metastasis to the Muscle](#)
- [Metastasis to the Viscera](#)
- [Metastatic](#)
- [Metastatic malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Methotrexate](#)
- [Methylated](#)
- [mg/kg](#)
- [mg/m2](#)
- [MGMT \(O-6-methylguanine-DNA methyltransferase\) gene variant measurement](#)
- [MGMT gene methylation \[Presence\] in Tissue by Molecular genetics method](#)
- [mGy](#)

- [Microcalcifications](#)
- [Microlobulated](#)
- [Microlobulated margin](#)
- [Microsatellite markers exhibiting instability/Microsatellite instability markers assessed in Cancer specimen](#)
- [Microsatellite stability measurement](#)
- [Microscopic specimen observation](#)
- [Microscopy](#)
- [Microscopy \(procedure\)](#)
- [Microsurgery - action](#)
- [Micturition finding](#)
- [Middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)
- [Middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Middle region of prostate](#)
- [Middle transition zone of prostate](#)
- [MiE](#)
- [Mild](#)
- [Mild systemic disease](#)
- [Miller and Payne Classification](#)
- [milli-international unit per liter](#)
- [milli-international unit per liter](#)
- [milligram](#)
- [milligram per 24 hours](#)
- [milligram per deciliter](#)
- [milliliter](#)
- [millimeter](#)
- [millimole per liter](#)
- [millisecond](#)
- [milliunit per liter](#)
- [Minimal](#)
- [Missing Value Reason](#)
- [Mixed](#)
- [Mixed ductal and lobular carcinoma in situ of breast](#)
- [Mixed ductal and lobular carcinoma of breast](#)
- [Mixed neuroendocrine non-neuroendocrine neoplasm](#)
- [MKI67 \(marker of proliferation Ki-67\).gene variant measurement](#)
- [MKI67 Negative](#)
- [MKI67 Positive](#)
- [Modality descriptor](#)
- [Modality Radiation treatment](#)
- [Modality radiation value](#)
- [Modality-related characteristic](#)
- [Moderate](#)
- [Moderate alcohol use](#)
- [Moderate cigarette smoker \(10-19 cigarettes per day\)](#)
- [Moderate drinker](#)
- [Modified radical mastectomy](#)
- [Modified Ryan Scheme for Tumor Regression](#)
- [Modifier mainly for procedure](#)
- [Molecular genetic test](#)
- [Molecular imaging](#)
- [Molecular pathology](#)
- [Monitoring of patient](#)
- [Monitoring of patient with cancer](#)
- [Monitoring procedure](#)
- [month](#)
- [More than 35 cigarettes per day \(about 2 packs or more\)](#)
- [moribund patient who is not expected to survive](#)
- [Morphologic descriptor](#)
- [Morphologic Finding](#)
- [Morphologically abnormal structure](#)
- [Morphologically altered structure](#)
- [Mother](#)
- [Motor area](#)
- [Motor cortex](#)
- [MR Echo Type](#)
- [MR fluoroscopy](#)
- [MR imaging coil](#)
- [MR preparation or modification technique](#)
- [MR procedure attribute](#)
- [MRI guided biopsy](#)
- [MRI guided biopsy of prostate](#)

- [MRI of brain](#)
- [MRI of brain with arterial spin labeling](#)
- [MRI of breast](#)
- [MRI of breast for screening](#)
- [MRI of breast for screening for malignant neoplasm](#)
- [MRI of chest](#)
- [MRI of pelvis](#)
- [MRI of prostate](#)
- [MRI scan abnormal](#)
- [MRI scan normal](#)
- [MRI-US fusion guided prostate biopsy](#)
- [mSv](#)
- [Mucinous adenocarcinoma](#)
- [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of ascending colon](#)
- [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of breast, NOS](#)
- [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of cecum](#)
- [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of colon, NOS](#)
- [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of descending colon](#)
- [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon](#)
- [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of rectum, NOS](#)
- [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of sigmoid colon](#)
- [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of splenic flexure of colon](#)
- [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of transverse colon](#)
- [Multicentric](#)
- [Multifocal](#)
- [Multifocal or Multicentric](#)
- [Multifocal or Multicentric value](#)
- [Multiparametric magnetic resonance imaging](#)
- [Multiparametric MRI of prostate](#)
- [Musculoskeletal structure of sacral spine](#)
- [Musculoskeletal structure of spine](#)
- [Mutated](#)
- [Mutated/c.1-124C>T](#)
- [Mutated/c.1-146C>T](#)
- [MYH-associated polyposis](#)
- [Myxofibrosarcoma](#)
- [N category](#)
- [N/A](#)
- [Nab paclitaxel](#)
- [nanogram per deciliter](#)
- [nanogram per milliliter](#)
- [nanomole per liter](#)
- [National Cancer Institute common terminology criteria for adverse event grade finding](#)
- [National Public Health Classification data](#)
- [Natriuretic peptide B \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Natriuretic peptide.B|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Nature of procedure values](#)
- [Natures](#)
- [NBN \(nibrin\) gene variant](#)
- [nCET tumor Crosses Midline](#)
- [nCET tumor Crosses Midline value](#)
- [Neck](#)
- [Neck and chest](#)
- [Neck, chest and abdomen](#)
- [Necrosis](#)
- [Necrosis Volume](#)
- [Necrotic tumor](#)
- [Needle aspiration of breast](#)
- [Needle biopsy](#)
- [Needle biopsy of prostate](#)
- [Needle biopsy specimen tumor quantitation](#)
- [Negative](#)
- [Negative descriptors](#)
- [Negative screening](#)
- [Negative Test Result](#)
- [Neo-adjuvant - intent](#)
- [Neoadjuvant antineoplastic therapy](#)
- [Neoadjuvant chemotherapy](#)
- [Neoadjuvant Therapy response value](#)
- [Neoplasm](#)
- [Neoplasm and/or hamartoma](#)

- [Neoplasm and/or hamartoma \(morphologic abnormality\).](#)
- [Neoplasm by body site](#)
- [Neoplasm observable](#)
- [Neoplasm of axilla](#)
- [Neoplasm of axillary lymph nodes](#)
- [Neoplasm of bone](#)
- [Neoplasm of breast](#)
- [Neoplasm of colon](#)
- [Neoplasm of digestive organ](#)
- [Neoplasm of digestive system](#)
- [Neoplasm of endocrine gland](#)
- [Neoplasm of endocrine system](#)
- [Neoplasm of extremity](#)
- [Neoplasm of female breast](#)
- [Neoplasm of female genital organ](#)
- [Neoplasm of gastrointestinal tract](#)
- [Neoplasm of head and neck](#)
- [Neoplasm of integumentary system](#)
- [Neoplasm of intestinal tract](#)
- [Neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)
- [Neoplasm of intrathoracic organs](#)
- [Neoplasm of kidney](#)
- [Neoplasm of large intestine](#)
- [Neoplasm of liver](#)
- [Neoplasm of lower respiratory tract](#)
- [Neoplasm of lung](#)
- [Neoplasm of male genital organ](#)
- [Neoplasm of nervous system](#)
- [Neoplasm of ovary](#)
- [Neoplasm of pelvis](#)
- [Neoplasm of prostate](#)
- [Neoplasm of rectum](#)
- [Neoplasm of respiratory tract](#)
- [Neoplasm of shoulder](#)
- [Neoplasm of skeletal system](#)
- [Neoplasm of skin](#)
- [Neoplasm of thorax](#)
- [Neoplasm of thyroid gland](#)
- [Neoplasm of trunk](#)
- [Neoplasm of upper limb](#)
- [Neoplasm of uterus](#)
- [Neoplasm of vagina](#)
- [Neoplasm, benign](#)
- [Neoplasm, malignant](#)
- [Neoplasm, malignant of ascending colon](#)
- [Neoplasm, malignant of breast, NOS](#)
- [Neoplasm, malignant of cecum](#)
- [Neoplasm, malignant of colon, NOS](#)
- [Neoplasm, malignant of descending colon](#)
- [Neoplasm, malignant of hepatic flexure of colon](#)
- [Neoplasm, malignant of prostate gland](#)
- [Neoplasm, malignant of rectum, NOS](#)
- [Neoplasm, malignant of sigmoid colon](#)
- [Neoplasm, malignant of splenic flexure of colon](#)
- [Neoplasm, malignant of transverse colon](#)
- [Neoplasm, metastatic](#)
- [Neoplasms, NOS](#)
- [Neoplastic disease](#)
- [Nerve sheath tumors](#)
- [Nervous system tumor morphology.](#)
- [Neuroblastoma](#)
- [Neuroblastoma \(morphologic abnormality\).](#)
- [Neurocutaneous syndrome](#)
- [Neuroendocrine carcinoma](#)
- [Neuroendocrine Carcinoma, NOS](#)
- [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of ascending colon](#)
- [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of cecum](#)
- [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of colon, NOS](#)
- [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of descending colon](#)
- [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of hepatic flexure of colon](#)
- [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of rectum, NOS](#)

- [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of sigmoid colon](#)
- [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of splenic flexure of colon](#)
- [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of transverse colon](#)
- [Neuroendocrine neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Neuroendocrine neoplasm, malignant](#)
- [Neuroendocrine tumor](#)
- [Neuroendocrine tumor grade 1](#)
- [Neuroendocrine tumor, NOS](#)
- [Neuroendocrine tumor, NOS, of prostate gland](#)
- [Neutron capture therapy](#)
- [Never](#)
- [NFI Gene Mutation](#)
- [Nipple discharge symptom](#)
- [Nipple finding](#)
- [Nipple structure](#)
- [Nivolumab](#)
- [No](#)
- [No ADC images](#)
- [No anti-cancer treatment - watchful waiting](#)
- [No contrast enhancement](#)
- [No contrast injected](#)
- [No eloquent brain](#)
- [No evidence of disease](#)
- [No family history of clinical finding](#)
- [No family history of malignancy](#)
- [No family history of ovarian cancer](#)
- [No FH: breast carcinoma](#)
- [No FLAIR images](#)
- [No nCET](#)
- [No nipple discharge](#)
- [No posterior acoustic features](#)
- [No response \(NR\)](#)
- [No vascular invasion by tumor](#)
- [Nodes removed](#)
- [Nodular](#)
- [Nodule](#)
- [Nodule of lung](#)
- [Non - drinker](#)
- [Non Binary](#)
- [Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease](#)
- [Non-circumscribed margin](#)
- [Non-coronary systemic artery structure](#)
- [Non-curative therapy](#)
- [Non-enhancing margin](#)
- [Non-enhancing margin value](#)
- [Non-enhancing tumor](#)
- [Non-Enhancing Tumor Volume](#)
- [Non-Hodgkin lymphoma](#)
- [Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma \(clinical\)](#)
- [Non-infiltrating intraductal carcinoma](#)
- [Non-small cell carcinoma](#)
- [Non-small cell carcinoma of lung, NOS](#)
- [Non-smoker](#)
- [Non-solid](#)
- [Non-surgical biopsy](#)
- [Non-surgical breast biopsy](#)
- [Non-surgical chest biopsy](#)
- [None](#)
- [Nonenhancing](#)
- [Normal](#)
- [Normal sexual function](#)
- [Normality findings](#)
- [Not applicable: Neoadjuvant therapy not given](#)
- [Not assessable/applicable](#)
- [Not assessed](#)
- [Not available](#)
- [Not detected](#)
- [Not Hispanic or Latino](#)
- [Not identified](#)
- [Not methylated](#)
- [Not mutated](#)

- [Not parallel](#)
- [Not performed](#)
- [Not pregnant](#)
- [Nothing](#)
- [Nottingham Grade 1](#)
- [Nottingham Grade 2](#)
- [Nottingham Grade 3](#)
- [Nottingham grade of primary malignant neoplasm of breast](#)
- [Nottingham histologic grading system](#)
- [NRAS Gene Mutation measurement](#)
- [Nuclear imaging acquisition](#)
- [Nuclear medicine](#)
- [Nuclear medicine imaging](#)
- [Nuclear medicine imaging procedure](#)
- [Number](#)
- [Number of births at term](#)
- [Number of cigarettes per day](#)
- [Number of lymph nodes containing metastatic neoplasm in excised specimen](#)
- [Number of lymph nodes examined by microscopy in excised specimen](#)
- [Number of regional lymph nodes containing metastatic neoplasm in excised specimen](#)
- [Number of tumor nodules](#)
- [Numeric grade](#)
- [Numeric grade on a scale 0 to 5](#)
- [Nutritional anemia](#)
- [Nutritional deficiency associated condition](#)
- [Observable entity](#)
- [Observation Category](#)
- [Obstetric history](#)
- [Occasional drinker](#)
- [Occipital lobe](#)
- [Occipital region](#)
- [Oligodendroglioma](#)
- [OMOP](#)
- [On the number of days you reported you smoked cigarettes during the past 30 days, how many cigarettes did you smoke per day, on average \[PhenX\]](#)
- [Oncotype DX breast recurrence score](#)
- [Only-Image](#)
- [Open prostatectomy](#)
- [Operation on abdominal region](#)
- [Operation on breast](#)
- [Operation on colon](#)
- [Operation on lower respiratory tract](#)
- [Operation on lung](#)
- [Operation on lymph node](#)
- [Operation on male genital system](#)
- [Operation on pelvic region of trunk](#)
- [Operation on prostate](#)
- [Operation on rectum](#)
- [Operation on respiratory tract](#)
- [Operation on sigmoid](#)
- [Operations by approach](#)
- [Operative procedure on pelvis](#)
- [Optic canal](#)
- [Orbit structure](#)
- [Organ within abdominopelvic cavity](#)
- [Orientation descriptor](#)
- [Original Dataset](#)
- [Origins](#)
- [Other Anatomic Concept](#)
- [Other carcinoma in situ of breast](#)
- [Other Hispanic/Latino/Spanish](#)
- [Other hormone antagonists and related agents](#)
- [Other modality \(DICOM\)](#)
- [Others](#)
- [Oval](#)
- [Oval mass](#)
- [Ovarian part](#)
- [Ovary](#)
- [Ovary](#)
- [Overlapping lesion of breast](#)
- [oxaliplatin](#)

- [Oxyphilic adenocarcinoma](#)
- [P - Portal vein marker](#)
- [P53 protein Ag.\[Presence\] in Tissue by Immune stain](#)
- [Paclitaxel](#)
- [Pain in male pelvis](#)
- [Pain in pelvis](#)
- [Pain of breast](#)
- [Painful ejaculation](#)
- [PALB2 \(partner and localizer of BRCA2\) gene variant](#)
- [PALB2 gene targeted mutation analysis in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method](#)
- [Palbociclib](#)
- [Palliative intent](#)
- [Palpation](#)
- [Palpation of abdomen](#)
- [Pancreas](#)
- [Papillary adenocarcinoma](#)
- [Papillary adenocarcinoma, NOS](#)
- [Papillary carcinoma](#)
- [Papillary carcinoma, follicular variant](#)
- [Papillary carcinoma, NOS](#)
- [Papillary carcinoma, NOS, of breast, NOS](#)
- [Papillary thyroid carcinoma](#)
- [Parallel](#)
- [Parent](#)
- [Parietal lobe](#)
- [Parietal region](#)
- [Partial](#)
- [Partial excision of large intestine](#)
- [Partial lobectomy of brain](#)
- [Partial mastectomy](#)
- [Partial Methylated](#)
- [Partial resection of colon](#)
- [Partial resection of lobe of brain|\(Tumor involves more than half of lobe\)](#)
- [Partial response](#)
- [Partial response \(PR\)](#)
- [Partially solid](#)
- [Past](#)
- [Past - specified](#)
- [Pathogeneses](#)
- [Pathology](#)
- [Pathology \(qualifier value\)](#)
- [Pathology examination findings present](#)
- [Pathology protocols - general](#)
- [Pathology Result](#)
- [Pathophysiologic finding](#)
- [Patient](#)
- [Patient age](#)
- [Patient condition finding](#)
- [Patient condition undetermined](#)
- [Patient Orientation](#)
- [Patient Position](#)
- [Patient status finding](#)
- [Patient with Cancer](#)
- [Patient with lesion not being a malignant tumor](#)
- [Patient's condition improved](#)
- [Patient's condition stable](#)
- [Patient's condition worsened](#)
- [Patient-based](#)
- [PD-L1 by clone 22C3 \[Presence\] in Tissue by Immune stain](#)
- [PD-L1 by Immune stain measurement](#)
- [Pectoral region structure](#)
- [Pelvic alimentary structure](#)
- [Pelvic echography](#)
- [Pelvic lymphadenectomy](#)
- [Pelvic mass](#)
- [Pelvic organ finding](#)
- [Pelvis](#)
- [Pelvis and lower extremities](#)
- [Pembrolizumab](#)
- [Pending](#)
- [per microliter](#)

- [per nanoliter](#)
- [percent](#)
- [Percent of cell nuclei positive for proliferation marker protein Ki-67 in primary malignant neoplasm by immunohistochemistry](#)
- [Percent of cell nuclei positive for proliferation marker protein Ki-67 in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)
- [Performance measure status](#)
- [Performance Status Assessment](#)
- [Performance Status Assessment Answer Finding](#)
- [Performance Status Assessment Answer Value](#)
- [Performance status qualifier](#)
- [Perfusion Magnetic Resonance Imaging](#)
- [Perfusion-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging](#)
- [Perimenopausal state](#)
- [Perineal prostatectomy](#)
- [Perineal structure](#)
- [Perineural Invasion](#)
- [Perineural invasion \[Presence\] in Cancer specimen](#)
- [Perineural invasion by tumor absent](#)
- [Perineural invasion by tumor present](#)
- [Perineural invasion finding](#)
- [Perineural invasion | Cancer specimen | Pathology](#)
- [Peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Person](#)
- [Person in family of subject](#)
- [Person in the family](#)
- [Person in the healthcare environment](#)
- [Pertuzumab](#)
- [PET-CT](#)
- [PET-MR](#)
- [Peutz-Jeghers polyp](#)
- [Peutz-Jeghers syndrome](#)
- [Pharmaceutical / biologic product](#)
- [Pharmacological assessment](#)
- [Philips](#)
- [Photon Counting Computed Tomography](#)
- [Phyllodes tumor, malignant](#)
- [Phyllodes tumor, malignant of breast, NOS](#)
- [Physical](#)
- [Physical examination](#)
- [Physical Examination](#)
- [Physical object](#)
- [Physical status qualifier](#)
- [Physician](#)
- [Physician who performed a surgical procedure was not a surgeon \(i.e., radiation oncologist, diagnostic radiologist, or general practitioner\)](#)
- [PI-RADS 1](#)
- [PI-RADS 1 - Very low \(Lesion\)](#)
- [PI-RADS 2](#)
- [PI-RADS 2 - Low \(Lesion\)](#)
- [PI-RADS 3](#)
- [PI-RADS 3 - Intermediate \(Lesion\)](#)
- [PI-RADS 4](#)
- [PI-RADS 4 - High \(Lesion\)](#)
- [PI-RADS 5](#)
- [PI-RADS 5 - Very high \(Lesion\)](#)
- [PI-RADS assessment](#)
- [PI-RADS Lesion Assessment Category](#)
- [PI-RADS Overall Assessment Category](#)
- [PI-RADS X](#)
- [PI-RADS X - Inadequate or absent \(Lesion\)](#)
- [Pial Invasion](#)
- [Pial Invasion value](#)
- [Picker International](#)
- [picogram per milliliter](#)
- [PIK3CA gene \[VCF\] in Cancer specimen by Sequencing](#)
- [PIK3CA gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [Pixel](#)
- [Plain radiography](#)
- [Plain X-ray imaging - action](#)
- [Planar nuclear medicine imaging](#)
- [Platelets \[# /volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Platelets|Number Concentration \(count/vol\)|Moment in time|Blood](#)
- [Pleural effusion](#)

- [pM category](#)
- [pM0](#)
- [pM1](#)
- [pM1a](#)
- [pM1b](#)
- [pM1c](#)
- [pM1d](#)
- [pN category](#)
- [pN0](#)
- [pN0\(i+\)](#)
- [pN0\(i-\)](#)
- [pN0m+](#)
- [pN0m-](#)
- [pN1](#)
- [pN1a](#)
- [pN1b](#)
- [pN2](#)
- [pN3](#)
- [pN3a](#)
- [pN3b](#)
- [pN3c](#)
- [Pneumonitis](#)
- [pNX](#)
- [Polyp](#)
- [Polyp of intestine](#)
- [Poor stream of urine](#)
- [Poorly defined](#)
- [Population](#)
- [Positive](#)
- [Positive integer](#)
- [Positive Laboratory Test Result](#)
- [Positron emission tomography](#)
- [Positron emission tomography](#)
- [Positron emission tomography of whole body](#)
- [Positron emission tomography of whole body using choline C-11](#)
- [Postarterial phase](#)
- [Posterior acoustic enhancement](#)
- [Posterior acoustic feature](#)
- [Posterior acoustic shadowing](#)
- [Postmenopausal state](#)
- [Postmenopause - Menopause present](#)
- [Postoperative chemotherapy](#)
- [Potassium \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Potassium measurement](#)
- [Potassium|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Potassium|Moment in time|Blood|39.098 g/mole](#)
- [PR negative](#)
- [PR positive](#)
- [Pre-operative chemotherapy](#)
- [Prefer not to answer](#)
- [Pregnancy observable](#)
- [Pregnancy status](#)
- [Pregnancy status value](#)
- [Pregnancy, childbirth / puerperium observable](#)
- [Pregnant](#)
- [Premenopausal state](#)
- [Premenopause - Menopause absent](#)
- [Presence findings](#)
- [Presence of direct invasion by malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Presence of direct invasion by neoplasm](#)
- [Presence of direct invasion by primary malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Presence of direct invasion by primary malignant neoplasm to lymphatic vessel and/or small blood vessel](#)
- [Presence of estrogen receptor in neoplasm](#)
- [Presence of estrogen receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)
- [Presence of metastatic discontinuous spread of malignant neoplasm of colon to pericolic tissue](#)
- [Presence of metastatic discontinuous spread of primary malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Presence of progesterone receptor in neoplasm](#)
- [Presence of progesterone receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)
- [Present](#)
- [Preventive intent](#)
- [Previous](#)

- [Primary](#)
- [Primary adenocarcinoma of ascending colon](#)
- [Primary adenocarcinoma of colon](#)
- [Primary adenocarcinoma of digestive organ](#)
- [Primary adenocarcinoma of pelvis](#)
- [Primary Cancer Condition](#)
- [Primary Gleason pattern](#)
- [Primary Gleason Pattern 1](#)
- [Primary Gleason Pattern 2](#)
- [Primary Gleason Pattern 3](#)
- [Primary Gleason Pattern 4](#)
- [Primary Gleason Pattern 5](#)
- [Primary malignant meningioma of meninges of brain](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of abdomen](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of ascending colon](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of brain](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of breast](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of breast with axillary lymph node invasion](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of cecum](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of colon](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of descending colon](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of esophagus](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of female breast](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of gallbladder](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of hepatic flexure of colon](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of intestinal tract](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of intrathoracic organs](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of kidney](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of large intestine](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of liver](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of lung](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of male genital organ](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of nervous system](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of ovary](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of pelvis](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of rectum](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of respiratory tract](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of sigmoid colon](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of splenic flexure of colon](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of stomach](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of transverse colon](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of trunk](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of urinary bladder](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of uterine cervix](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of uterus](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of vagina](#)
- [Primary malignant neoplasm of vulva](#)
- [Primary mucinous carcinoma of digestive organ](#)
- [Primary pattern unknown, secondary pattern unknown](#)
- [Primary sclerosing cholangitis](#)
- [Primary tumor size](#)
- [problematic](#)
- [Procedure](#)
- [Procedure](#)
- [Procedure by intent](#)
- [Procedure by method](#)
- [Procedure carried out on subject](#)
- [Procedure Category](#)
- [Procedure on abdomen](#)
- [Procedure on colon](#)
- [Procedure on genitourinary system](#)
- [Procedure on large intestine](#)
- [Procedure on lung](#)
- [Procedure on lymph node](#)
- [Procedure on lymphoid organ](#)
- [Procedure on male genital organ](#)
- [Procedure on male genital system](#)
- [Procedure on organ](#)

- [Procedure on pelvic region of trunk](#)
- [Procedure on pelvis](#)
- [Procedure on prostate](#)
- [Procedure on rectum](#)
- [Procedure on sigmoid colon](#)
- [Procedure on thorax](#)
- [Procedure on tissue specimen](#)
- [Procedure on trunk](#)
- [Procedure with a procedure focus](#)
- [Procedure with explicit context](#)
- [Processed Dataset](#)
- [Proctectomy and anastomosis of colon to anus](#)
- [Progesterone receptor Ag.\[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)
- [Progression](#)
- [Progressive disease](#)
- [Projection radiography](#)
- [Proliferation](#)
- [Proliferative mass](#)
- [Proportion Enhancing](#)
- [Proportion Enhancing value](#)
- [Proportion nCET](#)
- [Proportion nCET value](#)
- [Proportion Necrosis](#)
- [Proportion Necrosis value](#)
- [Proportion of Edema](#)
- [Proportion of Edema value](#)
- [Prostate](#)
- [Prostate and vas deferens structures](#)
- [Prostate cancer risk of recurrence not determined or neither low, intermediate nor high](#)
- [Prostate finding](#)
- [Prostate gland](#)
- [Prostate mass](#)
- [Prostate part](#)
- [Prostate specific Ag.\[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Prostate specific Ag|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Prostate specific Ag|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Prostate specific antigen measurement](#)
- [Prostate specific antigen normal](#)
- [Prostatectomy](#)
- [Prostatic and/or seminal vesicle structures](#)
- [Protein level - finding](#)
- [Protein measurement](#)
- [Proton-density](#)
- [Protons](#)
- [Provider-specific procedure](#)
- [pT category](#)
- [pT0](#)
- [pT1](#)
- [pT1a](#)
- [pT1b](#)
- [pT2](#)
- [pT2a](#)
- [pT2b](#)
- [pT2c](#)
- [pT3](#)
- [pT3a](#)
- [pT3b](#)
- [pT4](#)
- [pT4a](#)
- [pT4b](#)
- [PTEN Gene Mutation](#)
- [pTis](#)
- [pTX](#)
- [Pulmonary structure including vessels and lymphoid tissue](#)
- [PW](#)
- [PZ+TZ](#)
- [Qualifier](#)
- [Qualifier for certainty of diagnosis](#)
- [Qualitative distribution of primary malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Race](#)
- [Radiation dose](#)

- [radiation exposure measure](#)
- [Radiation Therapy \(Procedure\)](#)
- [Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System \(Procedure\)](#)
- [Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Beam Radiation @ Prostate Display label: Beam Radiation of Prostate](#)
- [Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Brachytherapy @ Prostate](#)
- [Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Brachytherapy @ Prostate @ High Dose Rate \(HDR\) \(Display label: Brachytherapy of Prostate - High Dose Rate\)](#)
- [Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Brachytherapy @ Prostate @ Low Dose Rate \(LDR\) \(Display label: Brachytherapy of Prostate - Low Dose Rate\)](#)
- [Radiation therapy care](#)
- [Radiation therapy course of treatment](#)
- [Radiation therapy procedure or service](#)
- [Radiation Therapy, Male Reproductive System, Beam Radiation](#)
- [Radiation Therapy, Male Reproductive System, Brachytherapy](#)
- [Radical excision](#)
- [Radical mastectomy](#)
- [Radical Perineal prostatectomy](#)
- [Radical prostatectomy](#)
- [Radical Retropubic prostatectomy](#)
- [Radiochemotherapy via intravenous route](#)
- [Radiofluoroscopy](#)
- [Radiographic imaging - action](#)
- [Radiographic imaging procedure](#)
- [Radiographic lesion margin characteristics](#)
- [Radiographic lesion shape finding](#)
- [Radiographic procedure of chest](#)
- [radiography procedure attribute](#)
- [Radioisotope study of musculoskeletal system](#)
- [Radiologic finding](#)
- [Radiologic guidance procedure](#)
- [Radiologist](#)
- [Radiology result normal](#)
- [Radionuclide imaging - action](#)
- [Radionuclide therapy](#)
- [Radiotherapy](#)
- [Radiotherapy - intraoperative control](#)
- [Radiotherapy to breast](#)
- [Radiotherapy to thorax](#)
- [Ranked categories](#)
- [Ratio value](#)
- [Re-excision of breast for clearance of tumor margins](#)
- [Reason for no specific anti-cancer treatment](#)
- [Reasons for treatment](#)
- [RECIST finding](#)
- [RECIST: complete response](#)
- [RECIST: partial response](#)
- [RECIST: progressive disease](#)
- [RECIST: stable disease](#)
- [Rectal examination](#)
- [Rectal mass](#)
- [Rectal polypectomy](#)
- [Rectum](#)
- [Rectum finding](#)
- [Rectum structure](#)
- [Rectum, NOS](#)
- [Recurrence](#)
- [Recurrent](#)
- [Recurrent tumor](#)
- [Red blood cell count below reference range](#)
- [Reexcision](#)
- [Regimes and therapies](#)
- [Region of cerebral cortex](#)
- [Region of colon](#)
- [Region of frontal cortex](#)
- [Region of large intestine](#)
- [Region of prostate](#)
- [Region of temporal cortex](#)
- [Regional lymph node metastasis present](#)
- [Regional lymph node structure](#)
- [Regional lymph nodes examined \[#\] Specimen](#)
- [Regular frequency](#)

- [Relapse](#)
- [Relapse](#)
- [Relative](#)
- [Relative sites](#)
- [Remission](#)
- [Remission](#)
- [Removal](#)
- [Removal - action](#)
- [Removal of entire genital organ](#)
- [Reoperation](#)
- [Resection](#)
- [Resection Margin Involved by tumor](#)
- [Resection Margin Uninvolved by tumor](#)
- [Resection of polyp](#)
- [Resection of rectum](#)
- [Residual cancer burden class](#)
- [Residual Cancer Burden Class 0](#)
- [Residual Cancer Burden Class 1](#)
- [Residual Cancer Burden Class 2](#)
- [Residual Cancer Burden Class 3](#)
- [Resolved](#)
- [ResourceType: Condition](#)
- [ResourceType: Diagnostic Report](#)
- [ResourceType: Measurement](#)
- [ResourceType: Medication](#)
- [ResourceType: Medication Administration](#)
- [ResourceType: Observation](#)
- [ResourceType: Patient](#)
- [ResourceType: Procedure](#)
- [Respiratory finding](#)
- [Respiratory function finding](#)
- [Respiratory observable](#)
- [Response to cancer treatment](#)
- [Response to treatment](#)
- [Restricted](#)
- [Restricted diffusion](#)
- [RET gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [Retention](#)
- [Retraction of nipple](#)
- [Retraction of skin of breast](#)
- [Retroperitoneal compartment structure](#)
- [Retropubic prostatectomy](#)
- [Ribociclib](#)
- [Right](#)
- [Right anterior apical part of transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Right anterior apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Right anterior basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Right anterior basal transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Right anterior middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Right anterior middle transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Right apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)
- [Right apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Right apical transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Right basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)
- [Right basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Right basal transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Right breast structure](#)
- [Right colectomy](#)
- [Right colon structure](#)
- [Right lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Right middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)
- [Right middle transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Right posterior apical part of transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Right posterior basal transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Right posterior middle transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Right posterolateral apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Right posterolateral basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Right posterolateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Right posteromedial apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Right posteromedial middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)
- [Right thorax structure](#)

- [Risk Assessment](#)
- [Risk assessment value](#)
- [Risky alcohol consumption](#)
- [Robot assisted laparoscopic radical prostatectomy](#)
- [Robotic assisted surgery](#)
- [Round](#)
- [Round mass](#)
- [Rounded](#)
- [Sacituzumab govitecan](#)
- [Sacrum](#)
- [Sampling - action \(qualifier value\)](#)
- [Sampling of tissue specimen](#)
- [Sarcoma](#)
- [Sarcoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Sarcoma of liver](#)
- [Satellites](#)
- [Satellites value](#)
- [Scalding pain on urination](#)
- [Scalp and/or neck structure](#)
- [Scattered fibroglandular tissue](#)
- [Scintigraphy](#)
- [Sclerosing cholangitis](#)
- [Screening](#)
- [Screening for cancer](#)
- [Screening for disorder](#)
- [Screening for malignant neoplasm of breast](#)
- [Screening for neoplasm](#)
- [Screening procedure](#)
- [Second degree](#)
- [Second degree blood relative](#)
- [Second line treatment](#)
- [Secondary](#)
- [Secondary Cancer Condition](#)
- [Secondary Gleason pattern](#)
- [Secondary Gleason Pattern 1](#)
- [Secondary Gleason Pattern 2](#)
- [Secondary Gleason Pattern 3](#)
- [Secondary Gleason Pattern 4](#)
- [Secondary Gleason Pattern 5](#)
- [Secondary malignant neoplasm of axilla](#)
- [Secondary malignant neoplasm of axillary lymph nodes](#)
- [Secondary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)
- [Secondary malignant neoplasm of liver](#)
- [Secondary malignant neoplasm of trunk](#)
- [Secondary malignant neoplasm of viscera](#)
- [SEG](#)
- [Segmentation Method](#)
- [Semiautomatic](#)
- [Seminal vesicle invasion by tumor present](#)
- [Seminal Vesicles](#)
- [Sentinel lymph node biopsy](#)
- [Serum testosterone measurement](#)
- [Severe](#)
- [Severe systemic disease](#)
- [Severe systemic disease that is a threat to life](#)
- [Severities](#)
- [Sex assigned at birth](#)
- [Sexual function](#)
- [Sexual function painful](#)
- [Shimadzu](#)
- [Shoulder](#)
- [Sibling](#)
- [Side](#)
- [Side of Lesion Center](#)
- [Siemens](#)
- [Sigmoid colectomy](#)
- [Sigmoid colon](#)
- [Sigmoid colon structure](#)
- [Signet ring cell carcinoma](#)
- [Signet ring cell carcinoma of ascending colon](#)
- [Signet ring cell carcinoma of cecum](#)

- [Signet ring cell carcinoma of colon, NOS](#)
- [Signet ring cell carcinoma of descending colon](#)
- [Signet ring cell carcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon](#)
- [Signet ring cell carcinoma of rectum, NOS](#)
- [Signet ring cell carcinoma of sigmoid colon](#)
- [Signet ring cell carcinoma of splenic flexure of colon](#)
- [Signet ring cell carcinoma of transverse colon](#)
- [Similar ADC value](#)
- [Simple mastectomy](#)
- [Single photon emission computed tomography](#)
- [Single photon emission computed tomography with computed tomography](#)
- [Single photon imaging](#)
- [Sister](#)
- [Situation with explicit context](#)
- [Size additional dimension in Tumor](#)
- [Size maximum dimension in Tumor](#)
- [Skeletal system structure](#)
- [Skin AND/OR mucosa finding](#)
- [Skin finding](#)
- [Skin observable](#)
- [Skin retraction](#)
- [Skin structure](#)
- [Skin thickening of breast](#)
- [Skull](#)
- [Skull foramen](#)
- [Slice Thickness](#)
- [Slide Microscopy](#)
- [Small cell carcinoma](#)
- [Small cell carcinoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Small cell carcinoma of prostate](#)
- [Small cell carcinoma, NOS](#)
- [Small cell carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#)
- [Small intestine](#)
- [Smoker](#)
- [Smoking - history](#)
- [Smoking status](#)
- [Smoking status value](#)
- [Smoking-related terms](#)
- [Social / personal history observable](#)
- [Social History](#)
- [Sodium \[Moles/volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Sodium|Substance Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Soft tissue](#)
- [Soft tissue tumor AND/OR sarcoma](#)
- [Solid](#)
- [Solid papillary carcinoma in situ](#)
- [Son](#)
- [Spatial and relational concepts](#)
- [Spatial enhancement pattern](#)
- [Special atomic mapping values](#)
- [Special disorder atoms](#)
- [Specialized physician](#)
- [Specific Module](#)
- [Specified time](#)
- [Specimen](#)
- [Specimen from anus and/or rectum](#)
- [Specimen from breast](#)
- [Specimen from colon](#)
- [Specimen from digestive system](#)
- [Specimen from gastrointestinal tract](#)
- [Specimen from genital system](#)
- [Specimen from large intestine](#)
- [Specimen from left breast](#)
- [Specimen from lower gastrointestinal tract](#)
- [Specimen from lung](#)
- [Specimen from prostate](#)
- [Specimen from rectum](#)
- [Specimen from respiratory system](#)
- [Specimen from right breast](#)
- [Specimen from trunk](#)
- [SPECT-CT](#)

- [Spiculated](#)
- [Spiculated margin](#)
- [Spin echo](#)
- [Spin labeling](#)
- [Spinal meninges](#)
- [Spine](#)
- [Splenic flexure](#)
- [Splenic flexure of colon](#)
- [Spontaneous](#)
- [Spouse](#)
- [Squamous cell carcinoma](#)
- [Squamous cell carcinoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)
- [Squamous cell carcinoma of male genital](#)
- [Squamous cell carcinoma of prostate](#)
- [Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS](#)
- [Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS, of lung, NOS](#)
- [Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#)
- [Squamous cell neoplasm](#)
- [Squamous cell neoplasms](#)
- [Stable](#)
- [Stable disease](#)
- [Stage 0](#)
- [Stage 1](#)
- [Stage 2](#)
- [Stage 3](#)
- [Stage 4](#)
- [Staging and scales](#)
- [Staining method](#)
- [Standard Risk Acute Leukemia](#)
- [Standing position](#)
- [Start time](#)
- [Static nuclear imaging acquisition](#)
- [Status of regression of tumor](#)
- [steatosis of liver](#)
- [Stereotactic radiation therapy using megavoltage radiation](#)
- [Stereotactic radiotherapy](#)
- [Steroid measurement](#)
- [Stimulated Thyroglobulin antibody measurement](#)
- [Stimulated Thyroglobulin measurement](#)
- [STK11 \(serine/threonine kinase 11\), gene variant](#)
- [Stomach](#)
- [Stop time](#)
- [Strength of stream of urine - finding](#)
- [Structure of abdomen proper](#)
- [Structure of abdominopelvic organ](#)
- [Structure of abdominopelvic viscus](#)
- [Structure of ankle and/or foot](#)
- [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)
- [Structure of apex of prostate](#)
- [Structure of body conduit](#)
- [Structure of bone organ](#)
- [Structure of brain meninges](#)
- [Structure of breast and/or endocrine system](#)
- [Structure of Broca's area](#)
- [Structure of Brodmann areas 17 \(striate cortex\), 18 \(parastriate cortex\) and 19 \(peristriate cortex\) of the occipital lobe](#)
- [Structure of caudate lobe of liver](#)
- [Structure of cecum and/or colon and/or rectum](#)
- [Structure of central nervous system](#)
- [Structure of cerebral association fiber](#)
- [Structure of cerebral cingulum](#)
- [Structure of cerebral cortex](#)
- [Structure of compartment of abdomen](#)
- [Structure of cortex of frontal lobe](#)
- [Structure of cortex of occipital lobe](#)
- [Structure of cortex of parietal lobe](#)
- [Structure of cortex of temporal lobe](#)
- [Structure of diencephalon](#)
- [Structure of digestive system](#)
- [Structure of endocrine system](#)
- [Structure of female genital system in pelvic cavity](#)
- [Structure of female internal genital organ](#)

- [Structure of femur](#)
- [Structure of free lower limb](#)
- [Structure of free upper limb](#)
- [Structure of frontal pole](#)
- [Structure of genitourinary system](#)
- [Structure of great blood vessel \(organ\)](#)
- [Structure of half of body lateral to midsagittal plane](#)
- [Structure of half of brain lateral to midsagittal plane](#)
- [Structure of half of thorax lateral to midsagittal plane](#)
- [Structure of half of trunk lateral to midsagittal plane](#)
- [Structure of joint region](#)
- [Structure of joint region of lower limb](#)
- [Structure of large artery](#)
- [Structure of large intestine](#)
- [Structure of lateral half of abdomen lateral to midsagittal plane](#)
- [Structure of left colic flexure](#)
- [Structure of left half of body](#)
- [Structure of left half of prostate](#)
- [Structure of left ovary](#)
- [Structure of lesser wing of sphenoid bone](#)
- [Structure of lobe of brain](#)
- [Structure of lobe of lung](#)
- [Structure of long bone of lower limb](#)
- [Structure of lower lobe of left lung](#)
- [Structure of lower lobe of lung](#)
- [Structure of lower lobe of right lung](#)
- [Structure of lung and/or mediastinum](#)
- [Structure of lymph node](#)
- [Structure of lymph node of left axilla](#)
- [Structure of lymph node of right axilla](#)
- [Structure of lymphatic system](#)
- [Structure of lymphatic system of axilla](#)
- [Structure of lymphatic system of upper limb](#)
- [Structure of mammary region](#)
- [Structure of middle lobe of lung](#)
- [Structure of middle lobe of right lung](#)
- [Structure of musculoskeletal system](#)
- [Structure of musculoskeletal system of cervical spine](#)
- [Structure of musculoskeletal system of lumbar spine](#)
- [Structure of musculoskeletal system of thoracic spine](#)
- [Structure of nervous system](#)
- [Structure of nervous tissue of brain](#)
- [Structure of orbital region](#)
- [Structure of organ in respiratory system](#)
- [Structure of organ within abdomen proper cavity](#)
- [Structure of organ within cavity of true pelvis](#)
- [Structure of pelvic segment of trunk](#)
- [Structure of pelvic viscus](#)
- [Structure of peripheral auditory system](#)
- [Structure of posterior arch of pelvic ring](#)
- [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#)
- [Structure of pulmopleural compartment](#)
- [Structure of right colic flexure](#)
- [Structure of right half of pelvis](#)
- [Structure of right half of prostate](#)
- [Structure of right lateral lobe of prostate](#)
- [Structure of right ovary](#)
- [Structure of shoulder and/or upper arm](#)
- [Structure of shoulder girdle region](#)
- [Structure of skin and/or mucous membrane](#)
- [Structure of skin and/or surface epithelium](#)
- [Structure of soft tissues of left upper extremity](#)
- [Structure of soft tissues of right upper extremity](#)
- [Structure of spheroidal joint](#)
- [Structure of subdivision of abdominopelvic compartment](#)
- [Structure of subdivision of nervous system](#)
- [Structure of subregion of head](#)
- [Structure of subregion of trunk](#)
- [Structure of surface region of upper back](#)
- [Structure of thoracic cavity and/or content](#)
- [Structure of thoracic viscus](#)

- [Structure of upper back](#)
- [Structure of upper lobe of left lung](#)
- [Structure of upper lobe of lung](#)
- [Structure of upper lobe of right lung](#)
- [Structure of upper urinary system](#)
- [Structure of urinary organ](#)
- [Structure of vertebral column and/or spinal cord](#)
- [Structure of vertebral region of cervical part of back](#)
- [Structure of vertebral region of lumbar part of back](#)
- [Structure of vertebral region of thoracic part of back](#)
- [Structure of viscus](#)
- [Structure of white matter of brain](#)
- [Subcutaneous mastectomy](#)
- [Subdivision of intra-abdominopelvic structure](#)
- [Subject under discussion with suspicious findings](#)
- [Subjects of information](#)
- [Substance observable](#)
- [Substance use behavior](#)
- [Subtotal prostatectomy](#)
- [Subtotal Resection](#)
- [Subtotal resection of tumor, lesion, or mass of brain\(Less than half of lobe involved with tumor\)|Specimen sent to pathology](#)
- [Supine](#)
- [Supratentorial brain](#)
- [Supratentorial brain part](#)
- [Surgery](#)
- [Surgical action](#)
- [Surgical circumferential margin finding](#)
- [Surgical circumferential margin involved by malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Surgical circumferential margin uninvolved by malignant neoplasm](#)
- [Surgical clip](#)
- [Surgical margin finding](#)
- [Surgical margin involved by tumor](#)
- [Surgical margin uninvolved by tumor](#)
- [Surgical procedure](#)
- [Surgical procedure on thorax](#)
- [Surgical Procedures on the Male Genital System](#)
- [Surgical Procedures on the Prostate](#)
- [Surgical removal](#)
- [Surgical repair](#)
- [Surgical Resection](#)
- [Surgical resection status](#)
- [Surveillance](#)
- [Survey](#)
- [Survival time](#)
- [Surviving free of recurrence of neoplastic disease](#)
- [Suspicious](#)
- [Swelling of breast](#)
- [Symmetric enhancement](#)
- [Symmetrical](#)
- [Symptom](#)
- [Symptomatic](#)
- [Symptomatic](#)
- [Systematic Prostate Biopsy](#)
- [Systemic artery of trunk](#)
- [T category](#)
- [T1 weighted](#)
- [T1-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging](#)
- [T1-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging with Contrast](#)
- [T1/FLAIR Ratio](#)
- [T1/FLAIR Ratio value](#)
- [T1<<FLAIR](#)
- [T1<FLAIR](#)
- [T1W-CE](#)
- [T1~FLAIR](#)
- [T2 weighted](#)
- [T2* weighted](#)
- [T2/T1 weighted](#)
- [Tamoxifen](#)
- [Targeted medication therapy review](#)
- [Targeted Prostate Biopsy](#)
- [Targeted Therapy](#)

- [Targetoid](#)
- [TD identified, number unknown](#)
- [TDM1](#)
- [Technique radiation value](#)
- [Temozolomide](#)
- [Temporal brain region](#)
- [Temporal context value](#)
- [Temporal lobe](#)
- [Temporal Qualifier](#)
- [TERT \(telomerase reverse transcriptase\) gene variant measurement](#)
- [TERT gene promotor region targeted mutation analysis in Tissue by Molecular genetics method](#)
- [Testosterone measurement](#)
- [TGFBR1 gene+TGFBR2 gene targeted mutation analysis in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method](#)
- [Thalamus](#)
- [Therapeutic](#)
- [Therapeutic procedure](#)
- [Therapy](#)
- [Thermotherapy](#)
- [Thick](#)
- [Thick skin](#)
- [Thickening of skin](#)
- [Thickness of enhancing margin](#)
- [Thickness of enhancing margin value](#)
- [Thickness of skin](#)
- [Thin skin](#)
- [Third line treatment](#)
- [Thoracic segment of trunk](#)
- [Thoracic spine](#)
- [Thorax excision](#)
- [Three dimensional conformal radiotherapy](#)
- [Three dimensional external beam radiation therapy](#)
- [Thyroglobulin \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Thyroglobulin Ab \[Units/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Thyroglobulin Ab|Arbitrary Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Thyroglobulin antibody measurement](#)
- [Thyroglobulin measurement](#)
- [Thyroid](#)
- [Thyroid and/or parathyroid structures](#)
- [Thyroid part](#)
- [Thyroid stimulating hormone measurement](#)
- [Thyroid stimulating immunoglobulins \[Units/volume\] in Serum](#)
- [Thyrotropin \[Units/volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Thyrotropin|Arbitrary Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Tier 1](#)
- [Tier 1A+](#)
- [Tier 1C+](#)
- [Tier 2](#)
- [Tier 2A+](#)
- [Tier 2C+](#)
- [Tier 3](#)
- [Tier 3A+](#)
- [Tier 3C+](#)
- [Time patterns](#)
- [Timepoint](#)
- [Tissue composition](#)
- [Tissue Contrast](#)
- [Tissue specimen](#)
- [Tissue specimen from colon](#)
- [Tissue specimen from gastrointestinal tract](#)
- [Tissue specimen from genital system](#)
- [Tissue specimen from large intestine](#)
- [Tissue specimen from prostate](#)
- [TNM category](#)
- [TNM classification of malignant tumor after operation](#)
- [TNM Clin M](#)
- [TNM Clin N](#)
- [TNM Clin Stage Group](#)
- [TNM Clin T](#)
- [TNM Path M](#)
- [TNM Path N](#)
- [TNM Path Stage Group](#)

- [TNM Path T](#)
- [TNM stage grouping](#)
- [TNM tumor staging classifications](#)
- [Tobacco smoking behavior - finding](#)
- [Tobacco use and exposure](#)
- [Tobacco user](#)
- [Tomographic imaging](#)
- [Tomographic imaging - action](#)
- [Tomographic imaging, plain radiologic - action](#)
- [Tomography](#)
- [Tomotherapy](#)
- [Topographical modifier](#)
- [Topography unknown](#)
- [Toshiba](#)
- [Total colectomy](#)
- [Total lobectomy of brain](#)
- [Total pneumonectomy](#)
- [Total prostate specific antigen level](#)
- [Total radiation dose delivered](#)
- [Total Tumor Volume](#)
- [TP53 \(tumor protein p53\) gene variant measurement](#)
- [TP53 Gene Mutation](#)
- [TP53 gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)
- [Trabecular adenocarcinoma](#)
- [Transgender](#)
- [Transition zone of prostate](#)
- [Transitional cell carcinoma](#)
- [Transitional cell carcinoma, NOS](#)
- [Transitional cell carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#)
- [Transitional cell neoplasm](#)
- [Transitional cell papillomas and carcinomas](#)
- [Transperineal needle biopsy of prostate](#)
- [Transrectal needle biopsy of prostate](#)
- [Transverse colectomy](#)
- [Transverse colon](#)
- [Transverse colon structure](#)
- [Trastuzumab](#)
- [Trastuzumab deruxtecan](#)
- [Treatment](#)
- [Treatment](#)
- [Treatment changed](#)
- [Treatment response value](#)
- [Triglyceride \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Triglycerides measurement](#)
- [Triglyceride|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Triglyceride|Moment in time|Blood](#)
- [Triple-negative breast cancer](#)
- [Trivial cigarette smoker \(0-1 cigarettes per day\)](#)
- [True](#)
- [Trunk excision](#)
- [Trunk structure](#)
- [Tubular adenocarcinoma](#)
- [Tubular adenocarcinoma of breast, NOS](#)
- [Tucatinib](#)
- [Tumor antigen measurement](#)
- [Tumor border configuration](#)
- [Tumor budding](#)
- [Tumor calcification](#)
- [Tumor configuration](#)
- [Tumor configuration](#)
- [Tumor configuration \(finding\)](#)
- [Tumor configuration observable entity](#)
- [Tumor Examination](#)
- [Tumor extension finding](#)
- [Tumor finding](#)
- [Tumor focality](#)
- [Tumor grade](#)
- [Tumor histopathological grade status values](#)
- [Tumor internal vascularity](#)
- [Tumor invasion finding](#)
- [Tumor invasion of perineural tissue absent \(prostate\)](#)

- [Tumor invasion of perineural tissue present \(prostate\)](#)
- [Tumor Location](#)
- [Tumor marker measurement](#)
- [Tumor measureable](#)
- [Tumor Morphology](#)
- [Tumor Observation](#)
- [Tumor of respiratory system](#)
- [Tumor Progression](#)
- [Tumor quantitation](#)
- [Tumor Regression Grade](#)
- [Tumor Regression Grade 0|Complete response: No viable cancer cells|No residual tumor](#)
- [Tumor Regression Grade 1|Moderate response: Single cells or small groups of cancer cells](#)
- [Tumor Regression Grade 2|Minimal response: Residual cancer outgrown by fibrosis](#)
- [Tumor Regression Grade 3|Poor response: Minimal or no tumor kill; extensive residual cancer](#)
- [Tumor Regression Score 0](#)
- [Tumor Regression Score 1](#)
- [Tumor Regression Score 2](#)
- [Tumor Regression Score 3](#)
- [Tumor Size Method](#)
- [Tumor stage finding](#)
- [Tumor staging](#)
- [Tumor vascularity](#)
- [Tumor vascularity absent](#)
- [Tumor volume](#)
- [Tumour marker levels](#)
- [Two dimensional external beam radiation therapy](#)
- [TZ+CZ](#)
- [UIH](#)
- [Ultra high dose rate radiotherapy](#)
- [Ultrasonic guidance procedure](#)
- [Ultrasonographic observable](#)
- [Ultrasonography of abdomen](#)
- [Ultrasonography of breast](#)
- [Ultrasonography of thorax](#)
- [Ultrasound](#)
- [Ultrasound](#)
- [Ultrasound guided biopsy](#)
- [Ultrasound scan finding](#)
- [Unable to determine](#)
- [Unapproved attribute](#)
- [Undetermined](#)
- [Unifocal](#)
- [Unilateral](#)
- [Unit of measure](#)
- [Unit of radiation dose](#)
- [Unit of radiotherapy](#)
- [Unit of time](#)
- [Unknown](#)
- [Unknown or no information|Not documented in patient record](#)
- [Unknown or no information|Not documented in patient record](#)
- [Unspecified](#)
- [Upper body part structure](#)
- [Upper body structure](#)
- [Upper extremity part](#)
- [Upper limb lymph node structure](#)
- [Upper-inner quadrant of breast](#)
- [Upper-outer quadrant of breast](#)
- [Upright position](#)
- [Urate \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Urate|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Urea \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)
- [Urea|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)
- [Urea|Moment in time|Blood|60.056 g/mole](#)
- [Uric acid measurement](#)
- [Urinary incontinence](#)
- [Urinary system finding](#)
- [Urinary tract](#)
- [Urinary tract pain](#)
- [Urine albumin measurement](#)
- [Urine finding](#)
- [Urine protein measurement](#)

- [Urine protein test](#)
- [Urine stream interrupted](#)
- [Urine substance measurement](#)
- [Urogenital finding](#)
- [US male genital system](#)
- [US scan and biopsy of pelvis](#)
- [US scan and biopsy of prostate](#)
- [US scan of genitourinary system](#)
- [US scan of prostate](#)
- [US-guided systematic biopsy](#)
- [Uses contraception](#)
- [Uses hormonal contraception](#)
- [Uterus](#)
- [Uterus and fallopian tubes](#)
- [Uterus part](#)
- [Uterus, NOS](#)
- [Uterus, NOS](#)
- [V - Hepatic vein marker](#)
- [Vacuum assisted biopsy of lesion of breast](#)
- [Vagina](#)
- [Vagina, NOS](#)
- [Vaginal lesion](#)
- [Vaginal mass](#)
- [Value](#)
- [VASARI Criteria](#)
- [VASARI Criteria value](#)
- [Vascular invasion by tumor present](#)
- [Venography](#)
- [Venous \(large vessel\) extramural invasion by tumor present](#)
- [Venous \(large vessel\) intramural invasion by tumor present](#)
- [Venous \(large vessel\) invasion by tumor present](#)
- [Ventricle, NOS](#)
- [Very heavy cigarette smoker \(more or equal to 40 cigarettes per day\)](#)
- [Very heavy drinker](#)
- [Very high](#)
- [Very low](#)
- [Vessels in rim of tumor](#)
- [Video imaging](#)
- [Video imaging - action](#)
- [Vinorelbine](#)
- [Viscus structure finding](#)
- [Vital Signs](#)
- [Volumetric Imaging Criteria](#)
- [Volumetric modulated arc therapy](#)
- [Volumetric modulated arc therapy](#)
- [Voxel](#)
- [Vulva](#)
- [Vulval part](#)
- [Wedge-shaped](#)
- [week](#)
- [Weight change finding](#)
- [Weight finding](#)
- [Weight loss](#)
- [Weight trend finding](#)
- [Well defined](#)
- [Wernicke's area](#)
- [White](#)
- [White blood cell disorder](#)
- [WHO CNS tumor grading system](#)
- [WHO grade for central nervous system tumor](#)
- [Whole body bone imaging](#)
- [Whole Slide Imaging](#)
- [Wife](#)
- [Worsened](#)
- [X-ray guided biopsy](#)
- [year](#)
- [Yes](#)
- [ypN0](#)
- [ypN1](#)
- [ypN1a](#)
- [ypN1b](#)

- [ypN1c](#)
- [ypN1mi](#)
- [ypN2](#)
- [ypN2a](#)
- [ypN2b](#)
- [ypN3](#)
- [ypN3a](#)
- [ypN3b](#)
- [ypN3c](#)
- [ypT0](#)
- [ypT1](#)
- [ypT1a](#)
- [ypT1b](#)
- [ypT1c](#)
- [ypT1mi](#)
- [ypT2](#)
- [ypT3](#)
- [ypT4](#)
- [ypT4a](#)
- [ypT4b](#)
- [ypT4c](#)
- [ypT4d](#)
- [ypTis](#)
- [ypTis\(DCIS\)](#)
- [ypTis\(Paget\)](#)
- [ypTx](#)
- [Zonal necrosis](#)

"+"^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001944>

has super-classes

[Present](#)^c

"++"^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002396>

has super-classes

[Present](#)^c

"+++"^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002399>

has super-classes

[Present](#)^c

"++++"^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002403>

has super-classes

[Present](#)^c

+2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001870>

Deprecated

has super-classes

[Data Value](#)^c

0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000045>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)^c

0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002257>

has super-classes

[Data Value](#)^c, [Number](#)^c

1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002448>

has super-classes

[Number](#)^c, [Positive integer](#)^c

1 cigarette per day^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001159>

has super-classes

[Number of cigarettes per day](#)^c

1+^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001877>

has super-classes

[Data Value](#)^c

1/3-2/3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001391>

has super-classes

[Proportion Enhancing value](#)^c, [Proportion Necrosis value](#)^c, [Proportion nCET value](#)^c, [Proportion of Edema value](#)^c, [Ratio value](#)^c

16 to 25 cigarettes per day (about 1 pack)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001155>

has super-classes

[Number of cigarettes per day](#)^c

17-hydroxycorticosteroid measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050516>

has super-classes

[Hormone measurement](#)^c, [Steroid measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cortisol measurement](#)^c

18q chromosome deletion [Identifier] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052091>

has super-classes

[Gene deletion](#)^c

1A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000049>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)^c

1B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000048>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)^c

2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002438>

has super-classes

[Number](#)^c, [Positive integer](#)^c

2 to 5 cigarettes per day^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001158>

has super-classes

[Number of cigarettes per day](#)^c

2+^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001879>

has super-classes

[Data Value](#)^c

26 to 35 cigarettes per day (about 1 1/2 packs)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001151>

has super-classes

[Number of cigarettes per day](#)^c

3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002459>

has super-classes

[Number](#)^c, [Positive integer](#)^c

3+^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001882>

has super-classes

[Data Value](#)^c

3D CRT three dimensional conformal radiation therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1028468>

has super-classes

[Conformal radiotherapy](#)^c

3DHISTECH^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000065>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

6 to 15 cigarettes per day (about 1/2 pack)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001156>

has super-classes

[Number of cigarettes per day](#)^c

<^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002529>

has super-classes

[Mathematical sign](#)^c

<1/3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001390>

has super-classes

[Proportion Enhancing value](#)^c, [Proportion Necrosis value](#)^c, [Proportion nCET value](#)^c, [Proportion of Edema value](#)^c, [Ratio value](#)^c

=^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002513>

has super-classes

[Mathematical sign](#)^c

>^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002546>

has super-classes

[Mathematical sign](#)^c

>2/3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001392>

has super-classes

[Proportion Enhancing value](#)^c, [Proportion Necrosis value](#)^c, [Proportion nCET value](#)^c, [Proportion of Edema value](#)^c, [Ratio value](#)^c

Abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000173>

Subdivision of trunk proper which is demarcated from the thorax internally by the inferior surface of the sternocostal part of the diaphragm and externally by the costal margin, from the back of abdomen by the external surface of the posterior abdominal wall, from the perineum by the superior surface of the urogenital diaphragm and from the lower limbs by the inguinal folds; together with the thorax, and perineum, it constitutes the trunk proper. Examples: There is only one abdomen. [FMA]

has super-classes

[Abdomen and Pelvis](#)^c, [Abdominopelvic cross-sectional segment](#)^c, [Abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)^c, [Chest, abdomen, and pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdomen proper](#)^c, [Intra-abdominopelvic structure](#)^c, [Pelvis](#)^c, [Structure of abdomen proper](#)^c, [Structure of compartment of abdomen](#)^c

Abdomen and Pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000211>

has super-classes

[Chest, abdomen, and pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdomen](#)^c, [Pelvis](#)^c

Abdomen excision^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000242>

has super-classes

[Operation on abdominal region](#)^c, [Trunk excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of abdominal lymph node](#)^c, [Excision of intestinal structure](#)^c, [Excision of liver](#)^c, [Prostatectomy](#)^c

Abdomen proper^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000249>

has super-classes

[Abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intra-abdominal proper structure](#)^c

Abdominal abscess^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1042193>

has super-classes

[Disorder of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdominal visceral abscess](#)^c

Abdominal cavity injury^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1041257>

has super-classes

[Injury of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Liver damage](#)^c

Abdominal mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000282>

has super-classes

[Finding of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cyst of abdomen](#)^c, [Hamartoma of intestine](#)^c, [Liver mass](#)^c, [Mass of colon](#)^c, [Mass of uterus](#)^c, [Polyp of intestine](#)^c, [Prostate mass](#)^c, [Rectal mass](#)^c

Abdominal organ finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000305>

has super-classes

[Finding of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdominal visceral abscess](#)^c, [Bowel finding](#)^c, [Kidney finding](#)^c, [Liver finding](#)^c, [Neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c, [Pelvic organ finding](#)^c

Abdominal visceral abscess^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1042085>

has super-classes

[Abdominal abscess](#)^c, [Abdominal organ finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abscess of liver](#)^c

Abdominopelvic cross-sectional segment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000094>

This cross-sectional segment is bounded superiorly by a virtual horizontal plane at the level of the junction between T8 and T9 (and thus also includes part of the thoracic volume below this level); and inferiorly it extends to the perineum, including the volume of the true and false pelvic cavities and part but not necessarily the entire external genitalia. The volume includes the entire transverse thickness of the body over the longitudinal extent between the superior (upper) and inferior (lower) boundaries including the skin and subcutaneous tissue. The segment relates to the cross-sectional or projectional volume as perceived by transmissive or emissive imaging. [SNOMEDCT]

has super-classes

[Structure of subregion of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdomen](#)^c, [Cross-sectional abdomen](#)^c

Abdominopelvic segment of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000252>

This segment relates to the volume of the trunk that is bounded by and includes: superiorly thoracic diaphragm and inferiorly the perineum and external genitalia. The volume includes the entire transverse thickness of the body over the longitudinal extent between these upper (superior) and lower (inferior) boundaries including the overlying muscles, skin and subcutaneous tissue. The segment includes the abdominopelvic cavity, contents and wall including the posterior lumbar region, the volume of the true and false pelvic cavities including the bony pelvis and pelvic wall, the entire perineum and external genitalia including skin and subcutaneous tissue. [SNOMEDCT]

has super-classes

[Chest, abdomen, and pelvis](#)^c, [Lower body part structure](#)^c, [Structure of subregion of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdomen](#)^c, [Cross-sectional pelvis](#)^c, [Structure of pelvic segment of trunk](#)^c

Abdominoperineal pull-through procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056755>

has super-classes

[Anastomosis of intestine, large-to-anus](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Proctectomy and anastomosis of colon to anus](#)^c

Abdominoperineal resection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060424>

has super-classes

[Operations by approach](#)^c, [Resection of rectum](#)^c

Abemaciclib^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036270>

An orally available cyclin-dependent kinase (CDK) inhibitor that targets the CDK4 (cyclin D1) and CDK6 (cyclin D3) cell cycle pathway, with potential antineoplastic activity. Abemaciclib specifically inhibits CDK4 and 6, thereby inhibiting retinoblastoma (Rb) protein phosphorylation in early G1. Inhibition of Rb phosphorylation prevents CDK-mediated G1-S phase transition, thereby arresting the cell cycle in the G1 phase, suppressing DNA synthesis and inhibiting cancer cell growth. Overexpression of the serine/threonine kinases CDK4/6, as seen in certain types of cancer, causes cell cycle deregulation. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Abnormal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000056>

has super-classes

[Normality findings](#)^c

Abnormal finding on evaluation procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003797>

has super-classes

[Evaluation finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy result abnormal](#)^c, [Imaging result abnormal](#)^c

Abnormal sexual function^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024222>

has super-classes

[Finding of sexual function](#)^c

Abscess^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036517>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abscess of digestive system](#)^c

Abscess of digestive system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036538>

has super-classes

[Abscess](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abscess of liver](#)^c

Abscess of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046390>

has super-classes

[Abdominal visceral abscess](#)^c, [Abscess of digestive system](#)^c, [Disease of liver](#)^c, [Liver mass](#)^c

Absence findings^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001079>

has super-classes

[Finding value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Absent](#)^c, [N/A](#)^c, [Negative](#)^c, [No](#)^c, [No ADC images](#)^c, [No FLAIR images](#)^c, [No contrast enhancement](#)^c, [No contrast injected](#)^c, [No eloquent brain](#)^c, [No evidence of disease](#)^c, [No nCET](#)^c, [None](#)^c, [Not assessable/applicable](#)^c, [Not assessed](#)^c, [Not available](#)^c, [Not detected](#)^c, [Not methylated](#)^c, [Not mutated](#)^c, [Nothing](#)^c

is disjoint with

[Presence findings](#)^c

Absent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001886>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c, [Calvarial Remodeling value](#)^c, [Cortical Involvement value](#)^c, [Cysts value](#)^c, [Ependymal Extension value](#)^c, [Pial Invasion value](#)^c, [Satellites value](#)^c

Acinar cell carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049490>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Acinar cell carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049570>

has super-classes

[Acinar cell neoplasms](#)^c

Acinar cell carcinoma of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021457>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Acinar cell neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049109>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm](#)^c

Acinar cell neoplasms^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049531>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Acinar cell carcinoma](#)^c

Acoustic feature of mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035461>

has super-classes

[Ultrasonographic observable](#)^c

Action^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001054>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Removal - action](#)^c, [Surgical action](#)^c

Active^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001177>

has super-classes

[Condition clinical status value](#)^c, [General adjectival modifier](#)^c

Active Surveillance^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1028588>

has super-classes

[Surveillance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Active surveillance of prostate cancer](#)^c

Active Surveillance^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000009>

has super-classes

[Episode](#)^c

Active surveillance of prostate cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1028587>

has super-classes

[Active Surveillance](#)^c, [Monitoring of patient with cancer](#)^c

Activity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000017>

has super-classes

[Observation Category](#)^c

ADAC^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000052>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

ADC map^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016700>

[PI-RADS] A measure of the degree of motion of water molecules in tissues. It is determined by calculating the signal loss in data obtained with different b-values and is expressed in units of mm²/sec or μm²/sec. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Imaging sequence](#)^c

ADC value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005444>

has super-classes

[Diffusion weighted imaging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[High ADC value](#)^c, [Low ADC value](#)^c, [Similar ADC value](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma of cervix^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003321>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of cervix uteri](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma of large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052245>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of large intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary adenocarcinoma of colon](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038137>

has super-classes

[Malignant adenomatous neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of liver](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Liver cell carcinoma](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma of pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007487>

has super-classes

[Malignant adenomatous neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma of uterus](#)^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of pelvis](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma of uterus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003318>

has super-classes

[Adenocarcinoma of pelvis](#)^c, [Carcinoma of uterus](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma with mixed subtypes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045788>

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049460>

has super-classes

[Complex epithelial neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021492>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine tumor](#)^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of pelvis](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047138>

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of ascending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061042>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of cecum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060937>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of cecum](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of colon, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062317>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of descending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061735>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of hepatic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061183>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of lung, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062977>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033194>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of rectum, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062662>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of sigmoid colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062008>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of splenic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061573>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of transverse colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061360>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Adenoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052301>

has super-classes

[Benign adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Adenomatous polyposis coli](#) ^c

Adenoma AND/OR adenocarcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049158>

has super-classes

[Epithelial neoplasm](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Benign adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c, [Benign adenomatous neoplasm - category](#) ^c, [Liver tumor morphology](#) ^c,
[Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c

Adenoma of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036427>

has super-classes

[Benign adenomatous neoplasm](#) ^c, [Benign neoplasm of liver](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Cystadenoma of liver](#) ^c, [Hepatic cystadenoma](#) ^c

Adenomas and adenocarcinomas^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045781>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma with mixed subtypes](#) ^c, [Adenocarcinoma, NOS](#) ^c, [Basal cell adenocarcinoma](#) ^c, [Ductal carcinoma in situ, solid type](#) ^c,
[Follicular carcinoma, NOS](#) ^c, [Mixed neuroendocrine non-neuroendocrine neoplasm](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine Carcinoma, NOS](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine tumor, NOS](#) ^c,
[Oxyphilic adenocarcinoma](#) ^c, [Papillary adenocarcinoma, NOS](#) ^c, [Papillary carcinoma, follicular variant](#) ^c, [Trabecular adenocarcinoma](#) ^c, [Tubular adenocarcinoma](#) ^c

Adenomatous polyposis coli^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059056>

has super-classes

[Adenoma](#) ^c, [Benign adenomatous neoplasm - category](#) ^c, [Polyp](#) ^c

Adenosquamous carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049457>

has super-classes

[Complex epithelial neoplasm](#) ^c, [Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c

Adenosquamous carcinoma of ascending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061022>

has super-classes

[Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#) ^c, [ICDO3Tumor](#) ^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of ascending colon](#) ^c

Adenosquamous carcinoma of cecum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060923>

has super-classes

[Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#) ^c, [ICDO3Tumor](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of cecum](#) ^c

Adenosquamous carcinoma of colon, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062263>

has super-classes

[Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#)^c, [ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of colon](#)^c

Adenosquamous carcinoma of descending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059749>

has super-classes

[Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#)^c, [ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Adenosquamous carcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059091>

has super-classes

[Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#)^c, [ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of ascending colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of hepatic flexure of colon](#)^c

Adenosquamous carcinoma of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021525>

has super-classes

[Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#)^c, [ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of pelvis](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma of prostate](#)^c

Adenosquamous carcinoma of rectum, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059787>

has super-classes

[Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#)^c, [ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of pelvis](#)^c

Adenosquamous carcinoma of sigmoid colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061960>

has super-classes

[Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#)^c, [ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of sigmoid colon](#)^c

Adenosquamous carcinoma of splenic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059151>

has super-classes

[Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#)^c, [ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c

Adenosquamous carcinoma of transverse colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061328>

has super-classes

[Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#)^c, [ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of transverse colon](#)^c

Adenosquamous cell carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016677>

has super-classes

[Malignant adenomatous neoplasm](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenosquamous carcinoma of ascending colon](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of cecum](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of colon, NOS](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of descending colon](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of rectum, NOS](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of transverse colon](#)^c

Adjectival modifier^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000024>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[General adjectival modifier](#)^c, [High risk](#)^c, [Low risk](#)^c, [Physical](#)^c, [Previous](#)^c, [Resolved](#)^c, [Topographical modifier](#)^c

Adjuvant - intent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002471>

has super-classes

[Therapeutic](#)^c

Administration of hormone^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034319>

has super-classes

[Administration of medication](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hormone therapy](#)^c

Administration of medication^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034187>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c, [Treatment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Administration of hormone](#)^c, [Chemotherapy](#)^c, [Drug therapy](#)^c

is in range of

[hasEpisodeEventRelatedEntity](#)^{op}

Administrative statuses^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000363>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Follow-up status](#)^c, [Performance measure status](#)^c, [Reasons for treatment](#)^c

Adnexal and skin appendage neoplasms^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063562>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Apocrine adenocarcinoma](#)^c

Adrenal gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000084>

A flattened, roughly triangular body resting upon the upper end of each kidney; it is one of the ductless glands furnishing internal secretions (epinephrine and norepinephrine from the medulla and steroid hormones from the cortex). [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Endocrine gland structure](#)^c, [Retroperitoneal compartment structure](#)^c, [Structure of lateral half of abdomen lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c,
[Structure of organ within abdomen proper cavity](#)^c

Adverse Event^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000013>

has super-classes

[Event](#)^c

African^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001046>

has super-classes

[Ethnicity](#)^c, [Race](#)^c

Age^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002041>

has super-classes

[Descriptor](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Patient age](#)^c

Age AND/OR growth period^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000126>

has super-classes

[Common Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Age at diagnosis](#)^c, [Age at onset of clinical finding](#)^c

Age at diagnosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000131>

has super-classes

[Age AND/OR growth period](#)^c

is in range of

[hasAgeAtDiagnosis](#)^{op}

Age at onset of clinical finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000128>

has super-classes

[Age AND/OR growth period](#)^c

Age at smoking cessation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050967>

has super-classes

[Tobacco use and exposure](#)^c

Agfa^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000051>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Aggressive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000157>

Describes a tumor or condition that develops, grows, or spreads rapidly. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Disease Clinical Qualifier^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021462>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M0 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 7th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M0 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015453>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 7th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021468>

is equivalent to

[TNM Clin M^c](#) and ([hasAnswer^{op}](#) exactly 1 [cM1a^c](#))

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M1a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021475>

is equivalent to

[TNM Clin M^c](#) and ([hasAnswer^{op}](#) exactly 1 [cM1b^c](#))

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021483>

is equivalent to

[TNM Clin M^c](#) and ([hasAnswer^{op}](#) exactly 1 [cM1c^c](#))

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical MX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021502>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th MX Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical MX Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical N0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021513>

is equivalent to

[TNM Clin N^c](#) and ([hasAnswer^{op}](#) exactly 1 [cN0^c](#))

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical N0 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical N1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021538>

is equivalent to

[TNM Clin N](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [cN1](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th N1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical N1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical NX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021552>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th NX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical NX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015455>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical T2 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021567>

is equivalent to

[TNM Clin T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [cT2a](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical T2a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021583>

is equivalent to

[TNM Clin T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [cT2b](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical T2b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021618>

is equivalent to

[TNM Clin T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [cT2c](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical T2c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015458>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical T3 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021637>

is equivalent to

[TNM Clin T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [cT3a](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T3a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical T3a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021678>

is equivalent to

[TNM Clin T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [cT3b](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T3b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical T3b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021700>

is equivalent to

[TNM Clin T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [cT4](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical T4 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th clinical TX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021723>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th TX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical TX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th edition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000417>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th M1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th MX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th N1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th NX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th T4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th TX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical N1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological N1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T4 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th M0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015462>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC M0 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M0 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th M1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000437>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC M1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th M1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th M1c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th M1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016727>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC M1a Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological M1a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th M1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016778>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC M1b Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th M1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016830>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC M1c Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th MX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015467>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC MX Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical MX Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th N0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015473>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC N0 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical N0 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological N0 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th N1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015480>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical N1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological N1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th NX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015488>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC NX Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical NX Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological NX Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological M1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034108>

is equivalent to

[TNM Path M](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [pM1a](#)^c)
has super-classes
[AJCC/UICC 7th M1a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological N0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021747>

is equivalent to

[TNM Path N](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [pN0](#)^c)
has super-classes
[AJCC/UICC 7th N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological N0 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological N1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021772>

is equivalent to

[TNM Path N](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [pN1](#)^c)
has super-classes
[AJCC/UICC 7th N1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological N1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological NX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021798>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th NX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological NX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015497>

is equivalent to

[TNM Path T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [pT1](#)^c)
has super-classes
[AJCC/UICC 7th T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T1 Category](#)^c
has sub-classes
[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021600>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T1a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021657>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T1b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021825>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T1c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T1c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015507>

is equivalent to

[TNM Path T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [pT2](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T2 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021853>

is equivalent to

[TNM Path T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [pT2a](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T2a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021882>

is equivalent to

[TNM Path T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [pT2b](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T2b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021912>

is equivalent to

[TNM Path T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [pT2c](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T2c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015518>

is equivalent to

[TNM Path T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [pT3](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T3 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021943>

is equivalent to

[TNM Path T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [pT3a](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T3a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T3a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021975>

is equivalent to

[TNM Path T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [pT3b](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T3b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T3b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022008>

is equivalent to

[TNM Path T](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} exactly 1 [pT4](#)^c)

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T4 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th pathological TX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022042>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th TX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological TX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th T1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000458>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC T1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th T1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th T1c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th T1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015530>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC T1a Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th T1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015543>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC T1b Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th T1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015557>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC T1c Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th T2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000480>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC T2 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th T2b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th T2c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2 Category](#)^c,
[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th T2a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015572>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC T2a Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th T2b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015588>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC T2b Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th T2c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015605>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC T2c Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th T3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000503>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC T3 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T3a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th T3b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th T3a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015623>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC T3a Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th T3b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015642>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC T3b Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th T4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015662>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC T4 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T4 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 7th TX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015683>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC TX Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical TX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 7th pathological TX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064417>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical M0 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M0\(i+\) Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M0(i+) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1077153>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M0\(i+\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M0 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063977>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical M1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1d Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1071413>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1071047>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1071168>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1071290>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1d Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical MX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1073798>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th MX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063997>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical N0 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0\(i+\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0\(mol+\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0a Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0(i+) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1071788>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0\(i+\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0(mol+) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1071915>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0\(mol+\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1071662>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1071537>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063842>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1mi Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1067703>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1a\(sn\) Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1a(sn) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1101188>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1067882>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1115147>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1114827>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1114190>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1114508>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1067615>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1mi Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1067792>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1mi Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063907>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2mi Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1069673>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1069458>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1069352>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2mi Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1069565>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2mi Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063923>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1069892>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N3a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1070003>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N3b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1069782>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N3c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064193>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical NX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1072967>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th NX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065617>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 0a](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 0is](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 0a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1093922>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0a](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 0](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 0is^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1094168>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0is](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 0](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065440>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1A](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1C](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1E](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1s](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1091753>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1A1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1A2](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1A3](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1A1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1103690>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1A2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1103973>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1A3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1104257>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1091990>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1B^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1B1^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1B2^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1B1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1104542>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1B^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1B2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1104828>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1B^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1092467>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1C^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1E^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1092228>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1E^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1s^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1091517>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1s^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064868>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2A^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2B^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2C^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2E^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1084290>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2A^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2A1^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2A2^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2A1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1116762>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2A2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1117088>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1083687>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1083887>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2C](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2E^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1084088>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2E](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064222>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3A](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3C](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3D](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1074962>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3A](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3A1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3A2](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3A1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1111682>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3A2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1111373>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1074665>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3B^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1074813>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3C^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3C1^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3C2^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3C1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1107743>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3C^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3C2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1107447>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3C^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3D^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1075112>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3D^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064777>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4A^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4B^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4C^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1082123>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4A^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4A1^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4A2^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4A1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1107152>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4A^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4A2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1106858>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1082508>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1082315>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4C](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065557>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063940>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1d Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1mi Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1070457>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1a1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1a2 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1a1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1110758>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1a2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1111065>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1070115>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1b1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1b2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1b3 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1b1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1099833>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1b2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1099298>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1b3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1099565>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1070573>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1c1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1c2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1c3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1c1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1113242>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1c2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1113557>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1c3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1113873>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1070342>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1mi Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1070228>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1mi Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064315>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2d Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1075877>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2a1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2a2 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2a1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1112928>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2a2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1112615>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1075722>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1075568>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1075415>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065218>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3e Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1088763>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1088987>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1088097>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1088318>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3e Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1088540>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3e Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064733>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T4 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4e Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1081553>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1081365>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1081178>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1081742>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4e Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1081932>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4e Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Ta Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065113>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Ta Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063892>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Tis Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis\(DCIS\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis\(LAMN\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis\(Paget\) Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis(DCIS) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1069247>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Tis\(DCIS\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis(LAMN) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1069040>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Tis\(LAMN\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis(Paget) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1069143>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Tis\(Paget\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th clinical TX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1091048>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th TX Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000418>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th M1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th MX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th N1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th N2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th N3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th N4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th NX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th TX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Ta Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Tis Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 0](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Ta Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 0](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Ta Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th M0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063788>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M0\(i+\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M0 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th M0(i+) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065678>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M0 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M0\(i+\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M0\(i+\) Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th M1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063815>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th M1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th M1c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th M1d Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th M1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066868>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th M1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1067027>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th M1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1067108>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th M1d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066947>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1d Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1d Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th MX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064138>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical MX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological MX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th N0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064453>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0\(i+\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th N0\(mol+\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th N0a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th N0b Category](#)^c,
[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th N0(i+) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1077317>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0\(i+\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0\(i+\) Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th N0(mol+) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1077648>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0\(mol+\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0\(mol+\) Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th N0a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1077815>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th N0b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1077482>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063865>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th N1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th N1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th N1mi Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1068638>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1a\(sn\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N1a(sn) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1116437>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1068443>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1b1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th N1b2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th N1b3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th N1b4 Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N1b1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1102290>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N1b2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1101462>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N1b3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1101737>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N1b4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1102013>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1068540>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N1mi Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1068347>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1mi Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1mi Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065327>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th N2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th N2c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th N2mi Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N2a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1090352>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N2b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1090815>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N2c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1090583>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th N2mi Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1090122>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N2mi Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2mi Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th N3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064063>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N3a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th N3b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th N3c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3 Category](#)^c,
[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th N3a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1072433>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N3 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th N3b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1072698>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N3 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th N3c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1072565>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N3 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N3c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th N4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063802>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N4 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N4 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th NX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064087>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical NX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological NX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064252>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M0\(i+\) Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M0(i+) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1075263>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M0\(i+\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M0 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064567>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1c Category](#)^c,
[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1d Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1079718>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1079540>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1079363>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1079187>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th M1d Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological M1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological MX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1073657>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th MX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065272>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological N0 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0\(i+\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0\(mol+\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0a Category](#)^c,
[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0(i+) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1089665>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0\(i+\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0(mol+) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1089438>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0\(mol+\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1089212>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1089893>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N0b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063853>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1c Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1mi Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1068252>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1a\(sn\) Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1a(sn) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1118402>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1067973>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b3 Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1096172>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1096683>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1096940>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1096427>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1068065>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1mi Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1068158>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N1mi Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063793>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2c Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2mi Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066202>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066065>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065998>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2mi Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066133>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N2mi Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N2 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064963>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1085942>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N3a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1085732>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N3b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1085523>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N3c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064648>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th N4 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological NX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1072832>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th NX Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064490>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 0a](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 0is](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 0a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1078152>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0a](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 0](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 0is^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1077983>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0is](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 0](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064528>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1A](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1B](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1C](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1E](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1s](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1078322>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1A1](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1A2](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1A3](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1A1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1097198>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1A](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1A2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1097717>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1A](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1A3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1097457>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1A](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1078665>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1B](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1B1](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1B2](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1B1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1103127>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1B^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1B2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1103408>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1B^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1079012>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1C^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1E^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1078493>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1E^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1s^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1078838>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1s^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065012>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2A^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2B^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2C^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2E^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1086792>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2A^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2A1^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2A2^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2A1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1109238>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2A^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2A2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1108937>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1086153>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1086578>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2C](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2E^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1086365>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2E](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064348>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3A](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3C](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3D](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1076033>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3A](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3A1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3A2](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3A1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1100372>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3A2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1100102>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1076348>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1076190>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3C](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3C1](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3C2](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3C1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1100643>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3C](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3C2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1100915>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3C](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3D^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1076507>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3D](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063878>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4A](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4B](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4C](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1068737>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4A](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4A1](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4A2](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4A1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1102847>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4A](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4A2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1102568>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4A](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1068837>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4B](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1068938>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4C](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064283>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T0 Category](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064822>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1 Category](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T1 Category](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1a Category](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1b Category](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1c Category](#) ^c,
[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1d Category](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1mi Category](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1082897>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1a Category](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1 Category](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1a1 Category](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1a2 Category](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1a1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1095918>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1a Category](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1a2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1095665>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1a Category](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1082702>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1b Category](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1 Category](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1b1 Category](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1b2 Category](#) ^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1b3 Category](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1b1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1094415>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1b Category](#) ^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1b2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1094912>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1b3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1094663>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1083488>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1c1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1c2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1c3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1c1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1118072>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1c2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1117743>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1c3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1117415>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1083093>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1mi Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1083290>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1mi Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063790>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2d Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065740>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2a1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2a2 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2a1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1097978>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2a2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1098240>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065932>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065867>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065803>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2d Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064165>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological T3 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3d Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3e Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1074227>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1074083>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1073940>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1074372>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3e Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1074518>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3e Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065062>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T4 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4c Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4e Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1087658>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1087007>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1087877>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1087440>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4e Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1087223>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4e Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Ta Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063832>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Ta Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063958>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Tis Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis\(DCIS\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis\(LAMN\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis\(Paget\) Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis(DCIS) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1070927>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Tis\(DCIS\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis(LAMN) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1070690>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Tis\(LAMN\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis(Paget) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1070808>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Tis\(Paget\) Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th pathological TX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1091282>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th TX Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064690>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#), [Stage.0^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage.0a^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage.0is^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage.0^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage.0^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1080992>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 0a](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 0a](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0is^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1080807>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 0is](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 0is](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064607>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c, [Stage 1](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1C](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1E](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1s](#)^c,
[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1079897>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A2](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A3](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1A](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1099032>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1098767>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1098503>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1080258>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1B1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1B2](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1B](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1B1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1106273>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1B^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1B2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1106565>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1B^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1080077>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1C^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1C^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1E^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1080623>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1E^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1E^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1s^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1080440>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 1s^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 1s^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064112>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#), [Stage 2^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2A^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2B^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2C^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2E^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1073103>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2A1^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2A2^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2A^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2A^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2A1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1105403>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2A2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1105115>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1073378>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2B](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1073240>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2C](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2C](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2E^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1073517>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 2E](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 2E](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063808>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c, [Stage 3](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3A](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3C](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3D](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066562>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3A1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3A2](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3A](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3A1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1095162>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3A2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1095413>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066713>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3B](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066790>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3C1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3C2](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3C](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3C](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3C1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1109843>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3C](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3C2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1109540>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3C](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3D^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066637>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 3D](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 3D](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064040>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c, [Stage 4](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4A](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4C](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1072172>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4A1](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4A2](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4A](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4A1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1112303>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4A2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1111992>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4A](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1072302>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4B](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4B](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1072043>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Stage 4C](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Stage 4C](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065165>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T0 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065498>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T1c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T1d Category](#)^c,
[AJCC/UICC 8th T1mi Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1092948>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1a1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T1a2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T1a1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1105982>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T1a2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1105692>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1093433>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1b1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th T1b2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th T1b3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T1b1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1116113>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T1b2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1115790>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T1b3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1115468>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1093190>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1c1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th T1c2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th T1c3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T1c1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1108637>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T1c2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1108040>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T1c3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1108338>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T1d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1092707>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1d Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1d Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T1mi Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1093677>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T1mi Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1mi Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063797>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T2b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T2c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T2d Category](#)^c,
[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T2a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066488>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2a1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th T2a2 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T2a1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1110147>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T2a2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1110452>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T2b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066415>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th T2c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066343>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T2d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1066272>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2d Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063823>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th T3b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th T3c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th T3d Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC 8th T3e Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T3a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1067357>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T3b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1067273>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T3c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1067190>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T3d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1067528>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3d Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T3e Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1067442>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3e Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3e Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064915>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th T4b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th T4c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th T4d Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC 8th T4e Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T4a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1084697>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T4b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1085108>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T4c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1084493>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T4d Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1085315>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4d Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4d Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th T4e Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1084902>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th T4 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4e Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4e Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC 8th Ta Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064018>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Ta Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Ta Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Tis Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1064382>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Tis\(DCIS\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Tis\(LAMN\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th Tis\(Paget\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Tis(DCIS) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1076828>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Tis Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis\(DCIS\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis\(DCIS\) Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Tis(LAMN) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1076667>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Tis Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis\(LAMN\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis\(LAMN\) Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th Tis(Paget) Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1076990>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Tis Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical Tis\(Paget\) Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological Tis\(Paget\) Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC 8th TX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1065383>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th edition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th clinical TX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological TX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC clinical M0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016883>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC M0 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M0 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC clinical M1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000857>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC M1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical M1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical M1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016937>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC M1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical M1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016992>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC M1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical M1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017048>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC M1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical M1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical MX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017105>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC MX Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical MX Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical N0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017163>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC N0 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical N0 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N0 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical N1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017222>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical N1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical N1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical NX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017282>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC NX Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical NX Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical T2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001130>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T2c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical T2a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017343>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical T2b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017405>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical T2c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017468>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T2c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T2c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical T3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001355>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T3a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T3b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical T3a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017532>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T3a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical T3b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017597>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T3b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T3b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical T4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017663>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T4 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical T4 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th clinical T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC clinical TX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017730>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC TX Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th clinical TX Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000398>

has super-classes

[Cancer staging^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th edition^c](#), [AJCC/UICC M0 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC M1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC MX Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC N0 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC N1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC NX Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC T1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC T2 Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC T3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC T4 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC TX Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC M0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000527>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M0 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M0 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC M1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000822>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC M1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC M1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC M1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical M1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC M1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000893>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC M1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M1a Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical M1a Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC M1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002642>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC M1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M1b Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical M1b Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC M1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000930>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC M1 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th M1c Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical M1c Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC MX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000552>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th MX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical MX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC N0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000578>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological N0 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC N1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000605>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th N1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical N1 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological N1 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC NX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000633>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th NX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC clinical NX Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC pathological NX Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC pathological N0 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017798>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC N0 Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological N0 Category](#)^c, [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N0 Category](#)^c

AJCC/UICC pathological N1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017867>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC N1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological N1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological N1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological NX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1017937>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC NX Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological NX Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological T1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000968>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T1a Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC pathological T1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological T1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015705>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological T1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015728>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological T1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015752>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological T2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001173>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T2a Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC pathological T2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T2c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological T2a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015777>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological T2b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015803>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological T2c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015830>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T2c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T2c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological T3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001403>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T3a Category^c](#),
[AJCC/UICC pathological T3b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological T3a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015858>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T3a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological T3b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015887>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T3b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T3b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological T4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018008>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T4 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological T4 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC 8th pathological T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC pathological TX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018080>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC TX Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th pathological TX Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC T1 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000662>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T1 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC T1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC T1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC T1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T1 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC T1a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001007>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T1a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T1a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC T1b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001047>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T1b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T1b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC T1c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001088>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T1 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T1c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T1c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC T2 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000692>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC T2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC T2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC T2c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T2 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T2 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC T2a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001217>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T2a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T2a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC T2b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001262>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T2b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T2b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC T2c Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001308>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T2 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T2c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T2c Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T2c Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC T3 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000723>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC T3a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC T3b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T3 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T3 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC T3a Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001452>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T3a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T3a Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T3a Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC T3b Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001502>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC T3 Category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T3b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T3b Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T3b Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC T4 Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000755>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th T4 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical T4 Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological T4 Category^c](#)

AJCC/UICC TX Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000788>

has super-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 7th TX Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC clinical TX Category^c](#), [AJCC/UICC pathological TX Category^c](#)

Alanine aminotransferase [Enzymatic activity/volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033782>

has super-classes

[ALT - blood measurement](#)^c, [Alanine aminotransferase|Catalytic Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Chemistry](#)^c

Alanine aminotransferase|Catalytic Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049784>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alanine aminotransferase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Albumin measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050460>

has super-classes

[Protein measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Fluid sample albumin measurement](#)^c

Albumin measurement, urine, quantitative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050589>

has super-classes

[Urine albumin measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Albumin/Protein.total in 24 hour Urine by Electrophoresis](#)^c

Albumin/Protein.total in 24 hour Urine by Electrophoresis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034070>

has super-classes

[Albumin measurement, urine, quantitative](#)^c, [Albumin/Protein.total|Mass Fraction|Urine](#)^c, [Chemistry](#)^c

Albumin/Protein.total|Mass Fraction|Urine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050344>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Albumin/Protein.total in 24 hour Urine by Electrophoresis](#)^c

Alcohol abuse^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001147>

has super-classes

[Alcohol use pattern value](#)^c

Alcohol dependence^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001144>

has super-classes

[Alcohol use pattern value](#)^c

Alcohol drinker status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004527>

has super-classes

[Substance use behavior](#)^c

Alcohol drinker status value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001132>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Current](#)^c, [Never](#)^c, [Prefer not to answer](#)^c, [Previous](#)^c

Alcohol use pattern^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004526>

has super-classes

[Substance use behavior](#)^c

Alcohol use pattern value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001141>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alcohol abuse](#)^c, [Alcohol dependence](#)^c, [Current drinker of alcohol](#)^c, [Current non-drinker of alcohol](#)^c, [Moderate alcohol use](#)^c, [Risky alcohol consumption](#)^c

Alcoholic liver damage^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047530>

has super-classes

[Disorder caused by alcohol](#)^c, [Drug-induced disorder of liver](#)^c, [Drug-induced lesion](#)^c, [Liver damage](#)^c

Alive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024297>

has super-classes

[General clinical state finding](#)^c

ALK gene mutations found [Identifier] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051959>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

Alkaline phosphatase [Enzymatic activity/volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033839>

has super-classes

[Alkaline phosphatase measurement](#)^c, [Alkaline phosphatase|Catalytic Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Chemistry](#)^c

Alkaline phosphatase measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050776>

has super-classes

[Measurement of liver enzyme](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alkaline phosphatase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Alkaline phosphatase|Catalytic Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049786>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alkaline phosphatase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Alkylating agent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036307>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cyclophosphamide](#)^c, [Fotemustine](#)^c, [Temozolomide](#)^c

All times past^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001069>

has super-classes

[Past - specified](#)^c

Almost entirely fat^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016685>

has super-classes

[Tissue composition](#)^c

Alphanumeric^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002258>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Mathematical sign](#)^c

ALT - blood measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050607>

has super-classes

[Measurement of level of substance in blood](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alanine aminotransferase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Altered bowel function^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050831>

has super-classes

[Finding of bowel action](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000183>

has super-classes

[Finding value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical M category allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical grade allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological grade allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer yp grade allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

is in range of

[hasStageValue](#)^{op}

American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical grade allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001746>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer grade GX](#)^c, [G1 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G1](#)^c, [G2 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G2](#)^c, [G3 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G3](#)^c, [G4 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G4](#)^c, [G5 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G5](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical M category allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000186>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[cM0](#)^c, [cM1](#)^c, [cM1a](#)^c, [cM1b](#)^c, [cM1c](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000190>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[cN0](#)^c, [cN0i+](#)^c, [cN0i-](#)^c, [cN0m+](#)^c, [cN0m-](#)^c, [cN1](#)^c, [cN1a](#)^c, [cN1b](#)^c, [cN1c](#)^c, [cN1mi](#)^c, [cN2](#)^c, [cN2a](#)^c, [cN2b](#)^c, [cN3](#)^c, [cN3a](#)^c, [cN3b](#)^c, [cN3c](#)^c, [cNX](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000195>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[0](#)^c, [IA](#)^c, [IB](#)^c, [I](#)^c, [II](#)^c, [IIA](#)^c, [IIB](#)^c, [IIC](#)^c, [III](#)^c, [IIIA](#)^c, [IIIB](#)^c, [IIIC](#)^c, [IV](#)^c, [IVA](#)^c, [IVB](#)^c, [IVC](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000201>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[cT0](#)^c, [cT1](#)^c, [cT1a](#)^c, [cT1b](#)^c, [cT1c](#)^c, [cT1mi](#)^c, [cT2](#)^c, [cT2a](#)^c, [cT2b](#)^c, [cT2c](#)^c, [cT3](#)^c, [cT3a](#)^c, [cT3b](#)^c, [cT4](#)^c, [cT4a](#)^c, [cT4b](#)^c, [cT4c](#)^c, [cT4d](#)^c, [cTX](#)^c, [cTis](#)^c, [cTisDCIs](#)^c, [cTisPaget](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer grade GX^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001891>

is equivalent to

[Grade cannot be assessed \(GX\); Unknown](#)^c

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical grade allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological grade allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer yp grade allowable value](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological grade allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001741>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer grade GX](#)^c, [G1 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G1](#)^c, [G2 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G2](#)^c, [G3 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G3](#)^c, [G4 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G4](#)^c, [G5 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G5](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000208>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1a \(qualifier value\)](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1b \(qualifier value\)](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1c \(qualifier value\)](#)^c, [pM0](#)^c, [pM1](#)^c, [pM1a](#)^c, [pM1b](#)^c, [pM1c](#)^c, [pM1d](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000216>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[pN0](#)^c, [pN0\(+\)](#)^c, [pN0\(i-\)](#)^c, [pN0m+](#)^c, [pN0m-](#)^c, [pN1](#)^c, [pN1a](#)^c, [pN1b](#)^c, [pN2](#)^c, [pN3](#)^c, [pN3a](#)^c, [pN3b](#)^c, [pN3c](#)^c, [pNX](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000225>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[I](#)^c, [II](#)^c, [IIA](#)^c, [IIB](#)^c, [IIC](#)^c, [III](#)^c, [IIIA](#)^c, [IIIB](#)^c, [IIIC](#)^c, [IV](#)^c, [IVA](#)^c, [IVB](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000235>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[pT0](#)^c, [pT1](#)^c, [pT1a](#)^c, [pT1b](#)^c, [pT2](#)^c, [pT2a](#)^c, [pT2b](#)^c, [pT2c](#)^c, [pT3](#)^c, [pT3a](#)^c, [pT3b](#)^c, [pT4](#)^c, [pT4a](#)^c, [pT4b](#)^c, [pTX](#)^c, [pTis](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001184>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1a (qualifier value)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001199>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1b (qualifier value)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001215>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1c (qualifier value)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001232>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer yp grade allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001743>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer grade GX](#)^c, [G1 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G1](#)^c, [G2 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G2](#)^c, [G3 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G3](#)^c, [G4 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G4](#)^c, [G5 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G5](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001052>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ypN0](#)^c, [ypN1](#)^c, [ypN1a](#)^c, [ypN1b](#)^c, [ypN1c](#)^c, [ypN1mi](#)^c, [ypN2](#)^c, [ypN2a](#)^c, [ypN2b](#)^c, [ypN3](#)^c, [ypN3a](#)^c, [ypN3b](#)^c, [ypN3c](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001605>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ypT0](#)^c, [ypT1](#)^c, [ypT1a](#)^c, [ypT1b](#)^c, [ypT1c](#)^c, [ypT1mi](#)^c, [ypT2](#)^c, [ypT3](#)^c, [ypT4](#)^c, [ypT4a](#)^c, [ypT4b](#)^c, [ypT4c](#)^c, [ypT4d](#)^c, [ypTis](#)^c, [ypTis\(DCIS\)](#)^c, [ypTis\(Paget\)](#)^c, [ypTx](#)^c

American Joint Committee on Cancer, Cancer Staging Manual, 8th edition neoplasm staging system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044309>

has super-classes

[Tumor staging](#)^c

American society of anesthesiologists morbidity state^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047416>

has super-classes

[Performance Status Assessment](#)^c

American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047414>

is equivalent to

[American society of anesthesiologists morbidity state](#)^c

has super-classes

[Performance Status Assessment](#)^c

American Urological Association staging system for prostate cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044305>

has super-classes

[Tumor staging](#)^c

Anal region structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063618>

has super-classes

[Perineal structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anal structure](#)^c

Anal structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063622>

has super-classes

[Anal region structure](#)^c

Anastomosis of intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056721>

has super-classes

[Gastrointestinal anastomosis procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anastomosis of intestine to anus](#)^c, [Enterectomy with anastomosis](#)^c

Anastomosis of intestine to anus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056736>

has super-classes

[Anastomosis of intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anastomosis of intestine, large-to-anus](#)^c

Anastomosis of intestine, large-to-anus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056745>

has super-classes

[Anastomosis of intestine to anus](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdominoperineal pull-through procedure](#)^c

Anastrozole^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036111>

A nonsteroidal inhibitor of estrogen synthesis that resembles paclitaxel in chemical structure. As a third-generation aromatase inhibitor, anastrozole selectively binds to and reversibly inhibits aromatase, a cytochrome P-450 enzyme complex found in many tissues including those of the premenopausal ovary, liver, and breast; aromatase catalyzes the aromatization of androstenedione and testosterone into estrone and estradiol, the final step in estrogen biosynthesis. In estrogen-dependent breast cancers, anastrozole may inhibit tumor growth. (NCI04)

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Anatomic location of neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049756>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

Anatomic pathology procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034164>

has super-classes

[Evidence Type](#)^c, [Laboratory procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Histopathology test](#)^c, [Procedure on tissue specimen](#)^c

Anatomic Site^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063491>

Named locations of or within the body. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Other Anatomic Concept](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lesion Site](#)^c

Anatomical Plane^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016614>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

Anatomical structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000055>

has super-classes

[Body structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Body organ structure](#)^c, [Body region structure](#)^c, [Body system structure](#)^c, [Body tissue structure](#)^c, [Other Anatomic Concept](#)^c

Androgen deprivation therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022437>

has super-classes

[Hormone therapy](#)^c

Androgen level^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1006897>

has super-classes

[Hormone measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Testosterone measurement](#)^c

Anechoic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016626>

BI-RADS US: Without internal echoes [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Echogenicity characteristic](#)^c

Anemia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051685>

has super-classes

[Disorder of cellular component of blood](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Nutritional anemia](#)^c

Angiography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016774>

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Venography](#)^c

Angiosarcoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1042302>

has super-classes

[Sarcoma](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Angiosarcoma of liver](#)^c

Angiosarcoma (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049511>

has super-classes

[Sarcoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Angiosarcoma of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046706>

A malignant vascular neoplasm arising from the liver. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Angiosarcoma](#)^c, [Sarcoma of liver](#)^c

Angular margin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005423>

BI-RADS US: Some or all of the margin has sharp corners, often forming acute angles. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Non-circumscribed margin](#)^c

Annotated Dataset^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000019>

has super-classes

[Dataset Type](#)^c

Annotation Status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001211>

has super-classes

[Annotation/Segmentation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Final](#)^c, [Pending](#)^c

is in range of

[hasAnnotationStatus](#)^{op}

Annotation Type^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001202>

has super-classes

[Annotation/Segmentation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bounding box](#)^c, [Contouring](#)^c, [Mask](#)^c, [Mesh](#)^c

is in range of

[hasAnnotationType](#)^{op}

Annotation/Segmentation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001210>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Annotation Status](#)^c, [Annotation Type](#)^c, [Annotator Specialty](#)^c, [Image Coordinate System](#)^c, [Imaging sequence](#)^c, [Segmentation Method](#)^c

Annotator Specialty^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001203>

has super-classes

[Annotation/Segmentation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Imaging technician](#)^c, [Medical Oncologist](#)^c, [Radiologist](#)^c

is in range of

[hasAnnotatorSpecialty](#)^{op}

Anorectal disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051682>

has super-classes

[Disorder of gastrointestinal tract](#)^c, [Disorder of pelvic region of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of anorectum](#)^c

Anorectal structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000219>

has super-classes

[Pelvic alimentary structure](#)^c, [Structure of pelvic segment of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Rectum structure](#)^c

Answer or Value Set^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001187>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alcohol drinker status value](#)^c, [Alcohol use pattern value](#)^c, [Cancer Condition Type](#)^c, [Condition clinical status value](#)^c, [Condition stability status](#)^c, [Modality radiation value](#)^c, [Neoadjuvant Therapy response value](#)^c, [Number of cigarettes per day](#)^c, [Performance Status Assessment Answer Value](#)^c, [Pregnancy status value](#)^c, [Risk assessment value](#)^c, [Smoking status value](#)^c, [Surgical resection status](#)^c, [Technique radiation value](#)^c, [Treatment response value](#)^c, [VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

Anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000227>

has super-classes

[Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c

Anterior resection of rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058078>

has super-classes

[Operations by approach](#)^c, [Resection of rectum](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Low anterior resection of rectum](#)^c

Anthracycline^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035833>

has super-classes

[Cytotoxic antibiotic](#)^c

Anti-thyroid antibody measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050463>

has super-classes

[Autoantibody measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Thyroglobulin antibody measurement](#)^c

Antibody measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050461>

has super-classes

[Protein measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Autoantibody measurement](#)^c

Antineoplastic agent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035058>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anastrozole](#)^c, [Antineoplastic antibiotic](#)^c, [Atezolizumab](#)^c, [Bevacizumab](#)^c, [Capecitabine](#)^c, [Carboplatin](#)^c, [Cyclophosphamide](#)^c, [Docetaxel](#)^c, [Doxorubicin](#)^c, [Durvalumab](#)^c, [Epirubicin](#)^c, [Eribulin](#)^c, [Exemestane](#)^c, [Fluorouracil](#)^c, [Gemcitabine](#)^c, [Ipilimumab](#)^c, [Lapatinib](#)^c, [Letrozole](#)^c, [Methotrexate](#)^c, [Nab paclitaxel](#)^c, [Nivolumab](#)^c, [Paclitaxel](#)^c, [Pembrolizumab](#)^c, [Pertuzumab](#)^c, [Ribociclib](#)^c, [Trastuzumab](#)^c, [Tucatinib](#)^c, [Vinorelbine](#)^c, [irinotecan](#)^c, [oxaliplatin](#)^c

Antineoplastic Agents^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034115>

has super-classes

[ANTINEOPLASTIC AND IMMUNOMODULATING AGENTS](#)^c

has sub-classes

[IPATASERTIB](#)^c

ANTINEOPLASTIC AND IMMUNOMODULATING AGENTS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001553>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Antineoplastic Agents](#)^c, [ENDOCRINE THERAPY](#)^c

Antineoplastic antibiotic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035839>

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cytotoxic antibiotic](#)^c

Antineoplastic chemoimmunotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035100>

has super-classes

[Immunotherapy for cancer](#)^c

Aorta^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000143>

The main trunk of the systemic arteries. [MeSH]

has super-classes

[Non-coronary systemic artery structure](#)^c, [Structure of great blood vessel \(organ\)](#)^c, [Structure of large artery](#)^c, [Systemic artery of trunk](#)^c

Apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000187>

has super-classes

[Structure of apex of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Right apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c

Apical peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000017>

has super-classes

[Structure of apex of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c

Apical transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000246>

has super-classes

[Structure of apex of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left apical transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right apical transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Apocrine adenocarcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063570>

has super-classes

[Adnexal and skin appendage neoplasms](#)^c, [Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Apocrine adenocarcinoma of breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060833>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Arab^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001070>

has super-classes

[Ethnicity](#)^c, [Race](#)^c

Architectural distortion of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016360>

has super-classes

[Mammographic breast tissue appearance](#)^c

Area striata structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000416>

has super-classes

[Structure of Brodmann areas 17 \(striate cortex\), 18 \(parastriate cortex\) and 19 \(peristriate cortex\) of the occipital lobe](#)^c

Areola structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063635>

has super-classes

[Breast part](#)^c

Arm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000220>

The portion of the upper extremity between the shoulder and the elbow. For clinical purposes this term is also used to refer to the whole superior limb. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Entire limb](#)^c, [Extremity](#)^c, [Structure of free upper limb](#)^c, [Structure of shoulder and/or upper arm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Upper extremity part](#)^c

Arterial phase^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016761>

has super-classes

[enhancement phase](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Early arterial phase](#)^c, [Late arterial phase](#)^c

Arterial Spin Labeling (ASL)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016661>

has super-classes

[Spin labeling](#)^c

ASA physical status class 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052872>

has super-classes

[Finding of American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification](#)^c

ASA physical status class 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052871>

has super-classes

[Finding of American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification](#)^c

ASA physical status class 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052870>

has super-classes

[Finding of American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification](#)^c

ASA physical status class 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052869>

has super-classes

[Finding of American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification](#)^c

ASA physical status class 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052868>

has super-classes

[Finding of American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification](#)^c

ASA physical status class 6^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052867>

has super-classes

[Finding of American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification](#)^c

ASA1 (no disturbance)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001197>

has super-classes

[EuroSpine Morbidity state](#)^c

ASA2 (mild/moderate)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001196>

has super-classes

[EuroSpine Morbidity state](#)^c

ASA3 (severe)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001195>

has super-classes

[EuroSpine Morbidity state](#)^c

ASA4 (life threatening)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001194>

has super-classes

[EuroSpine Morbidity state](#)^c

ASA5 (moribund)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001193>

has super-classes

[EuroSpine Morbidity state](#)^c

Ascending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063736>

has super-classes

[Colon](#)^c

Ascending colon structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063371>

is equivalent to

[Ascending colon](#)^c

has super-classes

[Right colon structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of right colic flexure](#)^c

Asian^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001320>

has super-classes

[Race](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Asian Indian](#)^c, [Chinese](#)^c

Asian Indian^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001076>

has super-classes

[Asian](#)^c, [Ethnicity](#)^c

Aspartate aminotransferase [Enzymatic activity/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033755>

has super-classes

[Aspartate aminotransferase measurement](#)^c, [Aspartate aminotransferase|Catalytic Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c,
[Chemistry](#)^c

Aspartate aminotransferase measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033729>

has super-classes

[Measurement of liver enzyme](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Aspartate aminotransferase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Aspartate aminotransferase|Catalytic Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049789>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Aspartate aminotransferase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Aspiration of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058470>

has super-classes

[Breast procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Needle aspiration of breast](#)^c

Assessment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005456>

has super-classes

[Imaging observation](#)^c, [Risk Assessment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[BI-RADS assessment](#)^c, [LI-RADS assessment](#)^c, [PI-RADS assessment](#)^c

is in domain of

[ImagingAssessmentMethodFor](#)^{op}

Assessment scales^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037297>

has super-classes

[Staging and scales](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Likert scale](#)^c, [Oncotype DX breast recurrence score](#)^c, [Performance Status Assessment](#)^c

Asymmetric enhancement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005494>

BI-RADS MRI: more enhancement in one breast than in the other [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Spatial enhancement pattern](#)^c

Asymptomatic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000100>

Without clinical signs or indications that raise the possibility of a particular disorder or dysfunction. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Disease qualifier](#)^c

Atezolizumab^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036213>

A humanized, Fc optimized, monoclonal antibody directed against the protein ligand PD-L1 (programmed cell death-1 ligand 1; CD274), with potential immune checkpoint inhibitory and antineoplastic activities. Atezolizumab binds to PD-L1, blocking its binding to and activation of its receptor programmed death 1 (PD-1; PDCD1) expressed on activated T-cells, which may enhance the T-cell-mediated immune response to neoplasms and reverse T-cell inactivation. In addition, by binding to PD-L1, atezolizumab also prevents binding of this ligand to B7.1 (CD80) expressed on activated T cells, which further enhances the T-cell-mediated immune response. PD-L1 is overexpressed on many human cancer cell types and on various tumor-infiltrating immune cells. PD-L1 binding to PD-1 on T-cells suppresses the immune system and results in increased immune evasion. PD-1, a transmembrane protein, is a negative regulator of the immune system that limits the expansion and survival of CD8+ T cells. The Fc region of atezolizumab is modified in such a way that it does not induce either antibody-dependent cytotoxicity (ADCC) or complement-dependent cytotoxicity (CDC). [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

ATM (ATM serine/threonine kinase) gene variant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063244>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

ATRX (ATRX chromatin remodeler) gene variant measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051954>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

ATRX gene mutations found [Identifier] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051949>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

Attenuation characteristic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016620>

has super-classes

[Modality-related characteristic](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Posterior acoustic feature](#)^c

Attenuation correction method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016770>

has super-classes

[Image processing attribute](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cross-sectional attenuation correction method](#)^c

Attribute^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002646>

has super-classes

[Common Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Unapproved attribute](#)^c

Auricular region structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000125>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Ear](#) ^c

Authorisation to access, view and process in-situ the datasets^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000023>

has super-classes

[Dataset Access Condition](#) ^c

Authorisation to download the datasets^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000024>

has super-classes

[Dataset Access Condition](#) ^c

Authorisation to remotely process the datasets without the ability to access and visualise data, even remotely^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000022>

has super-classes

[Dataset Access Condition](#) ^c

Autoantibody measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050462>

has super-classes

[Antibody measurement](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Anti-thyroid antibody measurement](#) ^c

Autoimmune disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039962>

has super-classes

[Disease](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Autoimmune liver disease](#) ^c

Autoimmune hepatitis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047776>

Hepatitis caused by autoantibodies. Drugs, infections, and toxins may trigger the production of the autoantibodies against the liver parenchyma. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Autoimmune liver disease](#) ^c, [Inflammatory disease of liver](#) ^c

Autoimmune liver disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037388>

has super-classes

[Autoimmune disease](#) ^c, [Disease of liver](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Autoimmune hepatitis](#) ^c

Automatic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000008>

Values for segmentation method (ProCancer-I, Prostate gland segmentation UC)
Operating with minimal human intervention; independent of external control. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Modifier mainly for procedure](#)^c, [Segmentation Method](#)^c

Autosomal dominant hereditary disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052290>

has super-classes

[Autosomal hereditary disorder](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lynch syndrome](#)^c, [Peutz-Jeghers syndrome](#)^c

Autosomal hereditary disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052280>

has super-classes

[Hereditary disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Autosomal dominant hereditary disorder](#)^c

Axial^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000018>

Situated on or along or in the direction of an axis. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Topographical modifier](#)^c

Axial scan mode^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000146>

has super-classes

[CT scan mode](#)^c

Axial skeleton structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000108>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Spine](#)^c

Axillary lymph node group^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063640>

has super-classes

[Axillary lymph node structure](#)^c

Axillary lymph node structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000158>

Axillary lymph nodes are often visible on mammograms. Normal nodes are smaller than 2 cm and contain hyperechoic fatty hilar areas. Larger nodes may be normal when a very thin cortical rim is seen around the hilar fat. Enlarged round lymph nodes or those with small or no fatty hilar areas are abnormal, although there is no specific feature or finding to distinguish a nodal metastasis from a benign reactive node. Presence of fat in the nodal hilus does not exclude metastatic involvement; replacement of the node by tumor may be a gradual process best detected by interval change. In a

patient with breast cancer, a cortical bulge or cortical area of increased echogenicity may suggest tumor involvement. A normal lymph node can be up to 2 cm in longest dimension. Larger lymph nodes, 3 cm or longer, with very thin cortical rims and most of the node consisting of fat, are also normal. Large rounded nodes lymph nodes, 3 cm or longer, with very thin cortical rims and most of the node consisting of fat, are also normal. Large rounded nodes with a paucity of hilar fat or none at all, should be evaluated further and correlated clinically. [RADLEX]

has super-classes

[Structure of lymphatic system of axilla](#)^c, [Upper limb lymph node structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Axillary lymph node group](#)^c, [Structure of lymph node of left axilla](#)^c, [Structure of lymph node of right axilla](#)^c

Background parenchymal enhancement pattern^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005500>

has super-classes

[Enhancement pattern](#)^c

Basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000157>

has super-classes

[Anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Base of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Right basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c

Basal cell adenocarcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049464>

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#)^c, [Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Malignant basal cell tumor](#)^c

Basal cell adenocarcinoma of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022482>

has super-classes

[ICD03Tumor](#)^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of pelvis](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Basal cell neoplasm (morphology)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049428>

has super-classes

[Cystic, mucinous AND/OR serous neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant basal cell tumor](#)^c

Basal ganglia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000375>

has super-classes

[Brain Lesion Site](#)^c, [Cerebral hemisphere part](#)^c

Basal peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000131>

has super-classes

[Base of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c

Basal transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000071>

has super-classes

[Base of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Basal-like 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046262>

has super-classes

[Triple-negative breast cancer](#)^c

Basal-like 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046261>

has super-classes

[Triple-negative breast cancer](#)^c

Base of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000037>

has super-classes

[Region of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Baseline^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001948>

has super-classes

[Timepoint](#)^c

Behavior descriptors^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002285>

has super-classes

[Descriptor](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Facilitated](#)^c, [Restricted](#)^c, [Symptomatic](#)^c

Behavior finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056151>

has super-classes

[Mental state, behavior and/or psychosocial function finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Health-related behavior finding](#)^c

Behavior observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050922>

has super-classes

[Mental state, behavior / psychosocial function observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Health-related behavior](#)^c

Benign^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000059>

Image annotation label (INCISIVE, Annotation Definitions and guidelines)

For neoplasms, a non-infiltrating and non-metastasizing neoplastic process that is characterized by the absence of morphologic features associated with malignancy (e.g., severe atypia, nuclear pleomorphism, tumor cell necrosis, and abnormal mitoses). For other conditions, a process that is mild in nature and not dangerous to health. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Disease morphology qualifier](#)^c, [General adjectival modifier](#)^c

Benign adenomatous neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040867>

has super-classes

[Benign neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenoma of liver](#)^c

Benign adenomatous neoplasm (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049403>

has super-classes

[Adenoma AND/OR adenocarcinoma](#)^c, [Benign epithelial neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenoma](#)^c, [Cystadenoma](#)^c

Benign adenomatous neoplasm - category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052256>

has super-classes

[Adenoma AND/OR adenocarcinoma](#)^c, [Benign epithelial neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenomatous polyposis coli](#)^c

Benign epithelial neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049148>

has super-classes

[Epithelial neoplasm](#)^c, [Neoplasm, benign](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Benign adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Benign adenomatous neoplasm - category](#)^c

is disjoint with

[Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Benign neoplasm of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036398>

has super-classes

[Benign tumor of digestive organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of liver](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenoma of liver](#)^c

is disjoint with

[Malignant neoplasm of liver](#)^c

Benign neoplastic disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040678>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Benign adenomatous neoplasm](#)^c, [Benign tumor of digestive organ](#)^c, [Hemangioma](#)^c

is disjoint with

[Malignant neoplastic disease](#)^c

Benign prostatic hyperplasia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024373>

has super-classes

[Hyperplasia of prostate](#)^c

Benign tumor of digestive organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040772>

has super-classes

[Benign neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Benign neoplasm of liver](#)^c

Bevacizumab^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035837>

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

BI-RADS 0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005470>

Incomplete--Need Additional Imaging Evaluation and/or Prior Mammograms for Comparison. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[BI-RADS assessment](#)^c

BI-RADS 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005469>

has super-classes

[BI-RADS assessment](#)^c

BI-RADS 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005468>

Benign Finding(s). [RadLex]

has super-classes

[BI-RADS assessment](#)^c

BI-RADS 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005466>

Probably Benign. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[BI-RADS assessment](#)^c

BI-RADS 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005465>

Suspicious. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[BI-RADS assessment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[BI-RADS 4A](#)^c, [BI-RADS 4B](#)^c, [BI-RADS 4C](#)^c

BI-RADS 4A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005460>

low suspicion for malignancy. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[BI-RADS 4](#)^c

BI-RADS 4B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005472>

moderate suspicion of malignancy. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[BI-RADS 4](#)^c

BI-RADS 4C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005471>

high suspicion for malignancy. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[BI-RADS 4](#)^c

BI-RADS 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005464>

Highly Suggestive of Malignancy. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[BI-RADS assessment](#)^c

BI-RADS 6^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005463>

Management: surgical excision when clinically appropriate. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[BI-RADS assessment](#)^c

BI-RADS assessment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005459>

has super-classes

[Assessment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[BI-RADS 0](#)^c, [BI-RADS 1](#)^c, [BI-RADS 2](#)^c, [BI-RADS 3](#)^c, [BI-RADS 4](#)^c, [BI-RADS 5](#)^c, [BI-RADS 6](#)^c, [BI-RADS N/A](#)^c

BI-RADS N/A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005461>

has super-classes

[BI-RADS assessment](#)^c

Bilateral^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016659>

has super-classes

[Laterality](#)^c

Biliary tract structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000184>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gallbladder](#)^c

Binary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000023>

Consisting of two (e.g., units, components, elements, terms, possibilities) or based on two. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[General adjectival modifier](#)^c

Biological Therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1014763>

has super-classes

[Therapeutic procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Immunological therapy](#)^c

Biomedical device^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000109>

has super-classes

[Clinical equipment and/or device](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Clip](#)^c

Biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001712>

has super-classes

[Removal](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy of lymphatic structure](#)^c, [Biopsy of trunk](#)^c, [Imaging guided biopsy](#)^c, [Needle biopsy](#)^c, [Non-surgical biopsy](#)^c

Biopsy finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018153>

has super-classes

[Evaluation finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy result abnormal](#)^c, [Biopsy result normal](#)^c

Biopsy of abdomen using ultrasound guidance^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016119>

has super-classes

[Ultrasonography of abdomen](#)^c, [Ultrasound guided biopsy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI-US fusion guided prostate biopsy](#)^c

Biopsy of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056766>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of thorax](#)^c, [Breast procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Core needle biopsy of breast](#)^c, [Non-surgical breast biopsy](#)^c, [Vacuum assisted biopsy of lesion of breast](#)^c

Biopsy of lymph node^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001717>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of lymphatic structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Sentinel lymph node biopsy](#)^c

Biopsy of lymphatic structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001716>

has super-classes

[Biopsy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy of lymph node](#)^c

Biopsy of male genital system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001880>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of trunk](#)^c, [Procedure on male genital system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy of prostate](#)^c

Biopsy of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001938>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of male genital system](#)^c, [Procedure on prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI guided biopsy of prostate](#)^c, [Needle biopsy of prostate](#)^c, [US scan and biopsy of prostate](#)^c

Biopsy of thorax^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056791>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy of breast](#)^c, [Non-surgical chest biopsy](#)^c

Biopsy of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001767>

has super-classes

[Biopsy](#)^c, [Procedure on trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy of male genital system](#)^c, [Biopsy of thorax](#)^c, [US scan and biopsy of pelvis](#)^c

Biopsy result abnormal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1028707>

has super-classes

[Abnormal finding on evaluation procedure](#)^c, [Biopsy finding](#)^c

Biopsy result normal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1028828>

has super-classes

[Biopsy finding](#)^c

Black or African American^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001321>

has super-classes

[Race](#)^c

Bladder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000301>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography](#)^c, [Structure of urinary organ](#)^c

Bladder control - finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018227>

has super-classes

[Functional finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Continent of urine](#)^c, [Urinary incontinence](#)^c

Bladder finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018302>

has super-classes

[Pelvic organ finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Continent of urine](#)^c, [Urinary incontinence](#)^c

Bleeding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051861>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hemoptysis](#)^c

Block dissection of pelvic lymph nodes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018378>

has super-classes

[Excision of pelvic lymph node](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Pelvic lymphadenectomy](#)^c

Blood calcium measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050641>

has super-classes

[Calcium measurement](#)^c, [Measurement of level of substance in blood](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Calcium \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Blood cell count outside reference range^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051827>

has super-classes

[Measurement finding outside reference range](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cytopenia](#)^c

Blood in urine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000350>

has super-classes

[Urine finding](#)^c

Blood leukocyte number below reference range^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036512>

has super-classes

[Cytopenia](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Leukopenia](#)^c

Blood relative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001048>

has super-classes

[Relative](#)^c

has sub-classes

[First degree blood relative](#)^c, [Second degree blood relative](#)^c

Blood urate measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050631>

has super-classes

[Measurement of level of substance in blood](#)^c, [Uric acid measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Urate \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Blood urea measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050601>

has super-classes

[Measurement of level of substance in blood](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Urea \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Body measurement finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050779>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Weight finding](#)^c

Body organ structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000214>

An anatomical structure that consists of the maximal set of organ parts so connected to one another that together they constitute a self-contained unit of macroscopic anatomy, distinct both morphologically and functionally from other such units. Together with other organs, an organ constitutes an organ system or a body part. An organ is divisible into organ parts but not organs (examples: femur, biceps, liver, heart, aorta, sciatic nerve, ovary). [SNOMEDCT]

has super-classes

[Anatomical structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brain Deep White Matter Structure](#)^c, [Breast structure](#)^c, [Digestive organ structure](#)^c, [Structure of abdominopelvic organ](#)^c, [Structure of bone organ](#)^c, [Structure of viscus](#)^c

Body part structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000212>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Extremity](#)^c, [Intra-abdominopelvic structure](#)^c, [Structure of vertebral region of cervical part of back](#)^c, [Structure of vertebral region of lumbar part of back](#)^c, [Structure of vertebral region of thoracic part of back](#)^c, [Trunk structure](#)^c, [Upper body structure](#)^c

Body region structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000116>

Curation of this category is in progress

has super-classes

[Anatomical structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Auricular region structure](#)^c, [Axial skeleton structure](#)^c, [Biliary tract structure](#)^c, [Body part structure](#)^c, [Bone and/or joint structure of cranium](#)^c, [Bone structure of head](#)^c, [Brain and spinal cord structure](#)^c, [Chest, abdomen, and pelvis](#)^c, [Combined site](#)^c, [Ear, nose and throat structure](#)^c, [Eloquent Brain Areas](#)^c, [Entire body region](#)^c, [Entire limb](#)^c, [Eye region structure](#)^c, [Face and/or neck structure](#)^c, [Female genital organ structure](#)^c, [Female genital tract structure](#)^c, [Heart and/or pericardium structure](#)^c, [Heart, mediastinum, and pleura](#)^c, [Hip region structure](#)^c, [Intra-abdominal urinary structure](#)^c, [Intracranial structure](#)^c, [Joint structure of lower extremity](#)^c, [Joint structure of pelvic girdle](#)^c, [Liver and intrahepatic bile ducts](#)^c, [Lower body part structure](#)^c, [Lower respiratory tract structure](#)^c, [Lumbosacral region of spine structure](#)^c, [Male genital organ structure](#)^c, [Musculoskeletal structure of sacral spine](#)^c, [Musculoskeletal structure of spine](#)^c, [Neck, chest and abdomen](#)^c, [Non-coronary systemic artery structure](#)^c, [Prostate and vas deferens structures](#)^c, [Prostatic and/or seminal vesicle structures](#)^c, [Pulmonary structure including vessels and lymphoid tissue](#)^c, [Retroperitoneal compartment structure](#)^c, [Scalp and/or neck structure](#)^c, [Skull foramen](#)^c, [Structure of ankle and/or foot](#)^c, [Structure of body conduit](#)^c, [Structure of endocrine system](#)^c, [Structure of female genital system in pelvic cavity](#)^c, [Structure of female internal genital organ](#)^c, [Structure of free lower limb](#)^c, [Structure of free upper limb](#)^c, [Structure of great blood vessel \(organ\)](#)^c, [Structure of half of body lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c, [Structure of joint region](#)^c, [Structure of joint region of lower limb](#)^c, [Structure of large artery](#)^c, [Structure of lateral half of abdomen lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c, [Structure of lesser wing of sphenoid bone](#)^c, [Structure of organ in respiratory system](#)^c, [Structure of organ within cavity of true pelvis](#)^c, [Structure of pelvic viscus](#)^c, [Structure of peripheral auditory system](#)^c, [Structure of posterior arch of pelvic ring](#)^c, [Structure of pulmopleural compartment](#)^c, [Structure of shoulder and/or upper arm](#)^c, [Structure of shoulder girdle region](#)^c, [Structure of spheroidal joint](#)^c, [Structure of thoracic cavity and/or content](#)^c, [Structure of thoracic viscus](#)^c, [Structure of upper urinary system](#)^c, [Structure of urinary organ](#)^c, [Structure of vertebral column and/or spinal cord](#)^c, [Systemic artery of trunk](#)^c

Body structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000024>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anatomical structure](#)^c, [ICDO3Topography](#)^c, [Morphologically altered structure](#)^c, [Topography unknown](#)^c

is in range of

[Has direct site](#)^{op}, [HasDirectProcedureSite](#)^{op}, [hasAnnotationLabel](#)^{op}, [hasBodySite](#)^{op}, [hasImageBodyPart](#)^{op}, [hasLocation](#)^{op}, [hasSegmentLabel](#)^{op}

Body substance specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002118>

has super-classes

[Human Specimen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Tissue specimen](#)^c

Body system structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000146>

has super-classes

[Anatomical structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of breast and/or endocrine system](#)^c, [Structure of digestive system](#)^c, [Structure of genitourinary system](#)^c, [Structure of lung and/or mediastinum](#)^c, [Structure of lymphatic system](#)^c, [Structure of musculoskeletal system](#)^c, [Structure of musculoskeletal system of cervical spine](#)^c, [Structure of musculoskeletal system of lumbar spine](#)^c, [Structure of musculoskeletal system of thoracic spine](#)^c, [Structure of nervous system](#)^c, [Structure of skin and/or mucous membrane](#)^c, [Structure of skin and/or surface epithelium](#)^c

Body tissue structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP100040607>

has super-classes

[Anatomical structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Soft tissue](#)^c

Bone and/or joint structure of cranium^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000138>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Skull](#)^c

Bone marrow disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059866>

has super-classes

[Disorder of hematopoietic structure](#)^c

Bone marrow structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063269>

has super-classes

[Structure of bone organ](#)^c

Bone structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063497>

has super-classes

[Skeletal system structure](#)^c, [Structure of bone organ](#)^c

Bone structure of femur^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000198>

has super-classes

[Structure of femur](#)^c

Bone structure of head^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000078>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Skull](#)^c

Boolean value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000034>

has super-classes

[General adjectival modifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[False](#)^c, [True](#)^c

is in range of

[has deceased](#)^{op}

Boost radiation therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016741>

has super-classes

[Radiotherapy](#)^c

Bounding box^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000118>

Annotation type (INCISIVE, Annotation Definitions and guidelines)

has super-classes

[Annotation Type](#)^c

Bowel finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000318>

has super-classes

[Abdominal organ finding](#)^c, [Gastrointestinal tract finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of intestine](#)^c, [Finding of large intestine](#)^c

Bowels: fully continent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024450>

has super-classes

[Finding of bowel continence](#)^c, [Finding of large intestine](#)^c

Brachytherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058845>

has super-classes

[Radionuclide therapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brachytherapy of breast](#)^c, [High dose rate brachytherapy](#)^c, [Intracavitary brachytherapy](#)^c, [Intravascular brachytherapy](#)^c, [Low dose rate brachytherapy](#)^c

Brachytherapy of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060736>

has super-classes

[Brachytherapy](#)^c

Brachytherapy, High Dose rate (HDR)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001179>

has super-classes

[Modality radiation value](#)^c

BRAF (B-Raf proto-oncogene, serine/threonine kinase) gene variant measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063262>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[BRAF gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c

BRAF gene mutations found [Identifier] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051926>

has super-classes

[BRAF \(B-Raf proto-oncogene, serine/threonine kinase\) gene variant measurement](#)^c

Brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000051>

An organ composed of grey and white matter containing billions of neurons that is the center for intelligence and reasoning. It is protected by the bony cranium. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Brain and spinal cord structure](#)^c, [ICDO3Topography](#)^c, [Intracranial structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brain part](#)^c, [Brain stem](#)^c, [Brain, NOS](#)^c, [Cerebrum](#)^c, [Frontal lobe](#)^c, [Occipital lobe](#)^c, [Parietal lobe](#)^c, [Temporal lobe](#)^c, [Ventricle, NOS](#)^c

Brain and spinal cord structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000001>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brain](#)^c

Brain Deep White Matter Structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000441>

has super-classes

[Body organ structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brain stem](#)^c, [Corpus callosum](#)^c, [Internal capsule](#)^c

Brain Lesion Site^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063493>

has super-classes

[Lesion Site](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Basal ganglia](#)^c, [Brain stem](#)^c, [Cerebellum](#)^c, [Corpus callosum](#)^c, [Frontal lobe](#)^c, [Insular structure](#)^c, [Occipital lobe](#)^c, [Parietal lobe](#)^c, [Temporal lobe](#)^c, [Thalamus](#)^c

Brain natriuretic peptide measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050722>

has super-classes

[Hormone measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Natriuretic peptide B \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Brain part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000359>

has super-classes

[Brain](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brain region](#)^c, [Brain tissue structure](#)^c

Brain region^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000360>

has super-classes

[Brain part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Frontal brain region](#)^c, [Infratentorial brain structure](#)^c, [Occipital region](#)^c, [Parietal region](#)^c, [Structure of half of brain lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c, [Supratentorial brain](#)^c, [Temporal brain region](#)^c

Brain stem^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000061>

Three sections, the midbrain, pons and medulla oblongata, that are located at the base of the brain. The brain stem regulates the central nervous system, and is vital as a conduit for motor and sensory innervations. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Brain](#)^c, [Brain Deep White Matter Structure](#)^c, [Brain Lesion Site](#)^c, [Eloquent Brain Areas](#)^c

Brain tissue structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000358>

has super-classes

[Brain part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of nervous tissue of brain](#)^c

Brain, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000324>

has super-classes

[Brain](#)^c

brain-dead patient, organ donor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000028>

has super-classes

[Physical status qualifier](#)^c

Brain@Gross total resection of lobe of brain (lobectomy)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004592>

has super-classes

[Gross Total Resection](#)^c

Brain@Subtotal resection of tumor, lesion or mass in brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004590>

has super-classes

[Subtotal Resection](#)^c

BRCA1 (BRCA1 DNA repair associated) gene variant measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063181>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[BRCA1 gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c

BRCA1 gene mutation detected^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035265>

has super-classes

[Breast cancer genetic marker of susceptibility detected](#)^c

BRCA1 gene mutation negative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035286>

has super-classes

[Breast cancer genetic marker of susceptibility not detected](#)^c

BRCA1 gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046138>

A molecular genetics procedure that detects gene variants of BRCA1 in a blood or tissue specimen. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[BRCA1 \(BRCA1 DNA repair associated\) gene variant measurement](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

BRCA1 mutation carrier detection test^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035226>

is equivalent to

[BRCA1 \(BRCA1 DNA repair associated\) gene variant measurement](#)^c

has super-classes

[Molecular genetic test](#)^c

BRCA1+BRCA2 gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045865>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

BRCA2 (BRCA2 DNA repair associated) gene variant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063184>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

BRCA2 gene mutation negative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035331>

has super-classes

[Breast cancer genetic marker of susceptibility not detected](#)^c

BRCA2 gene mutation positive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035308>

has super-classes

[Breast cancer genetic marker of susceptibility detected](#)^c

BRCA2 mutation carrier detection test^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035245>

is equivalent to

[BRCA2 \(BRCA2 DNA repair associated\) gene variant](#)^c

has super-classes

[Molecular genetic test](#)^c

Breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063727>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast, NOS](#)^c, [Central portion of breast](#)^c, [Lower-inner quadrant of breast](#)^c, [Lower-outer quadrant of breast](#)^c, [Overlapping lesion of breast](#)^c, [Upper-inner quadrant of breast](#)^c, [Upper-outer quadrant of breast](#)^c

Breast cancer genetic marker of susceptibility detected^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034574>

has super-classes

[Genetic finding detected](#)^c

has sub-classes

[BRCA1 gene mutation detected](#)^c, [BRCA2 gene mutation positive](#)^c

Breast cancer genetic marker of susceptibility not detected^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034637>

has super-classes

[Genetic finding not detected](#)^c

has sub-classes

[BRCA1 gene mutation negative](#)^c, [BRCA2 gene mutation negative](#)^c

Breast Carcinoma by Gene Expression Profile^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007979>

has super-classes

[Carcinoma of breast](#)^c

has sub-classes

[HER2 negative](#)^c, [HER2 positive](#)^c, [Luminal A](#)^c, [Luminal B](#)^c

Breast changes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059064>

has super-classes

[Breast finding](#)^c

Breast composition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052158>

has super-classes

[Mammography finding](#)^c

Breast Conservation Treatment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034673>

Breast conservation treatment is defined as excision of the primary tumor and adjacent breast tissue, followed by radiation therapy. This procedure is also referred to as lumpectomy, segmental mastectomy, or partial mastectomy. (from Consensus Statements: Treatment of Early-stage Breast Cancer, 1990) [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Operation on breast](#)^c

Breast fed^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048461>

has super-classes

[Infant feeding method - finding](#)^c

Breast finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037127>

has super-classes

[Finding of region of thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast changes](#)^c, [Breast lump](#)^c, [Breast signs and symptoms](#)^c, [Disorder of breast](#)^c, [Nipple finding](#)^c, [Retraction of skin of breast](#)^c, [Skin thickening of breast](#)^c, [Swelling of breast](#)^c

Breast function^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043689>

has super-classes

[Function](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breastfeeding \(mother\)](#)^c

Breast lump^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037126>

has super-classes

[Breast finding](#)^c

Breast part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063633>

has super-classes

[Breast structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Areola structure](#)^c, [Nipple structure](#)^c

Breast procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034670>

has super-classes

[Procedure on organ](#)^c, [Procedure on thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Aspiration of breast](#)^c, [Biopsy of breast](#)^c, [Operation on breast](#)^c

Breast signs and symptoms^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047840>

has super-classes

[Breast finding](#)^c

Breast structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000136>

One of two hemispheric projections of variable size situated in the subcutaneous layer over the pectoralis major muscle on either side of the chest. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[Breast, NOS](#)^c

has super-classes

[Body organ structure](#)^c, [Pectoral region structure](#)^c, [Structure of breast and/or endocrine system](#)^c, [Structure of half of thorax lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c, [Structure of mammary region](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast part](#)^c, [Entire breast](#)^c, [Left breast structure](#)^c, [Right breast structure](#)^c

Breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000270>

has super-classes

[Breast](#)^c

Breastfeeding (mother)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043690>

has super-classes

[Breast function](#)^c

Bronchial structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000405>

has super-classes

[Structure of thoracic cavity and/or content](#)^c

Bronchus and lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000192>

A sample that contains lung and bronchial tissues. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Combined site](#)^c, [ICDO3Topography](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung, NOS](#)^c

Brother^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001029>

has super-classes

[Sibling](#)^c

C reactive protein [Mass/volume] in Blood by High sensitivity method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033965>

has super-classes

[C-reactive protein measurement](#)^c, [Chemistry](#)^c

C-reactive protein measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050652>

has super-classes

[Globulin measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[C reactive protein \[Mass/volume\] in Blood by High sensitivity method](#)^c

Calcification disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000107>

has super-classes

[Deposit](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Calcifications](#)^c, [Macrocalcifications](#)^c, [Microcalcifications](#)^c

Calcifications^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000102>

[BI-RADS]: Mammo: As an associated feature, this may be used in conjunction with one or more other findings to describe calcifications within or immediately adjacent to the finding(s) (see descriptors or calcifications, section B of BI-RADS). [RADLEX]

has super-classes

[Calcification disorder](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Calcifications in a mass](#)^c, [Calcifications outside of a mass](#)^c, [Intraductal calcifications](#)^c

Calcifications in a mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000106>

has super-classes

[Calcifications](#)^c

Calcifications outside of a mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000104>

[BI-RADS] US: Calcifications situated in fat or fibroglandular tissue are less conspicuous than when present within a mass. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Calcifications](#)^c

Calcium [Mass/volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033540>

has super-classes

[Blood calcium measurement](#)^c, [Calcium|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Calcium|Moment in time|Blood|40.078 g/mole](#)^c, [Chemistry](#)^c

Calcium measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050541>

has super-classes

[Measurement of substance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Blood calcium measurement](#)^c

Calcium|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049793>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Calcium \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Calcium|Moment in time|Blood|40.078 g/mole^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049993>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Calcium \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Calvarial Remodeling^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016711>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Calvarial Remodeling value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016711>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Absent](#)^c, [Present](#)^c

Cancer Ag 15-3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040963>

has super-classes

[Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cancer Ag 15-3 | Serum or Plasma | Chemistry - non-challenge](#)^c

Cancer Ag 15-3 [Units/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045838>

A quantitative procedure that measures the concentration (units/volume) of cancer antigen 15-3 in a serum or plasma specimen. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Cancer Ag 15-3 | Serum or Plasma | Chemistry - non-challenge](#)^c, [Cancer Ag 15-3 | Arbitrary Concentration | Moment in time | Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cancer antigen 15-3 measurement](#)^c

Cancer Ag 15-3 | Serum or Plasma | Chemistry - non-challenge^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1041060>

has super-classes

[Cancer Ag 15-3](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cancer Ag 15-3 \[Units/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Cancer Ag 15-3 | Arbitrary Concentration | Moment in time | Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038387>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cancer Ag 15-3 \[Units/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Cancer Ag 19-9 [Units/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052034>

has super-classes

[Cancer antigen 19-9 measurement](#)^c, [Chemistry](#)^c

Cancer antigen 15-3 measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039793>

has super-classes

[Glycoproteins measurement](#)^c, [Tumor antigen measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cancer Ag 15-3 \[Units/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Cancer antigen 19-9 measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052017>

has super-classes

[Tumor antigen measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cancer Ag 19-9 \[Units/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Cancer Condition Type^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001133>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary](#)^c, [Secondary](#)^c

is in range of

[hasCancerConditionType](#)^{op}

Cancer disease progression^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004582>

has super-classes

[Measurement](#)^c

is in domain of

[hasEvidenceType](#)^{op}

Cancer Patient^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001051>

has super-classes

[Patient](#)^c

is in domain of

[Suffers from](#)^{op}, [diagnosedWith](#)^{op}, [hasTreatment](#)^{op}

is in range of

[hasAssociatedPatient](#)^{op}

Cancer staging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044563>

has super-classes

[Tumor staging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC finding](#)^c, [Generic anatomical site tumor invasion status](#)^c, [Generic tumor staging descriptor](#)^c, [Stage 0](#)^c, [Stage 1](#)^c, [Stage 2](#)^c, [Stage 3](#)^c, [Stage 4](#)^c

Canon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000050>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Capecitabine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035836>

A fluoropyrimidine carbamate belonging to the class of antineoplastic agents called antimetabolites. As a prodrug, capecitabine is selectively activated by tumor cells to its cytotoxic moiety, 5-fluorouracil (5-FU); subsequently, 5-FU is metabolized to two active metabolites, 5-fluoro-2-deoxyuridine monophosphate (FdUMP) and 5-fluorouridine triphosphate (FUTP) by both tumor cells and normal cells. FdUMP inhibits DNA synthesis and cell division by reducing normal thymidine production, while FUTP inhibits RNA and protein synthesis by competing with uridine triphosphate for incorporation into the RNA strand. (NCI04)

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c, [Immunologic agent](#)^c

Carbamazepine Injection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033130>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Carbohydrate measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050471>

has super-classes

[Measurement of substance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glucose measurement](#)^c

Carboplatin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035863>

A second-generation platinum compound with a broad spectrum of antineoplastic properties. Carboplatin contains a platinum atom complexed with two ammonia groups and a cyclobutane-dicarboxyl residue. This agent is activated intracellularly to form reactive platinum complexes that bind to nucleophilic groups such as GC-rich sites in DNA, thereby inducing intrastrand and interstrand DNA cross-links, as well as DNA-protein cross-links. These carboplatin-induced DNA and protein effects result in apoptosis and cell growth inhibition. This agent possesses tumoricidal activity similar to that of its parent compound, cisplatin, but is more stable and less toxic. (NCI04)

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Carcinoembryonic Ag [Mass/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045880>

A quantitative procedure that measures the concentration (mass/volume) of carcinoembryonic antigen in a serum or plasma specimen. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Carcinoembryonic Ag\[Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Carcinoembryonic Ag|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Carcinoembryonic antigen measurement](#)^c

Carcinoembryonic Ag[Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038452>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoembryonic Ag.\[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Carcinoembryonic Ag|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036497>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoembryonic Ag.\[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Carcinoembryonic antigen level^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060222>

has super-classes

[Tumour marker levels](#)^c

Carcinoembryonic antigen measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039547>

has super-classes

[Protein measurement](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoembryonic Ag.\[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049524>

has super-classes

[Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Carcinoma in situ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002243>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma in situ of breast](#)^c, [Carcinoma in situ of male genital organ](#)^c

Carcinoma in situ (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049499>

has super-classes

[Epithelial neoplasm](#)^c, [In situ neoplasm \(morphology\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Encapsulated papillary carcinoma](#)^c, [Lobular carcinoma in situ \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Non-infiltrating intraductal carcinoma](#)^c

Carcinoma in situ of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002305>

has super-classes

[Carcinoma in situ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of breast](#)^c

has sub-classes

[DCIS \(Ductal carcinoma in situ\) of breast](#)^c, [LCIS \(lobular carcinoma in situ\) of breast](#)^c, [Other carcinoma in situ of breast](#)^c

Carcinoma in situ of male genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002307>

has super-classes

[Carcinoma in situ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of male genital organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma in situ of prostate](#)^c

Carcinoma in situ of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015917>

has super-classes

[Carcinoma in situ of male genital organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intraductal carcinoma, noninfiltrating, NOS, of prostate gland](#)^c

Carcinoma of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000169>

A carcinoma arising from the breast, most commonly the terminal ductal-lobular unit. It is the most common malignant tumor in females. Risk factors include country of birth, family history, menstrual and reproductive history, fibrocystic disease and epithelial hyperplasia, exogenous estrogens, contraceptive agents, and ionizing radiation. The vast majority of breast carcinomas are adenocarcinomas (ductal or lobular). Breast carcinoma spreads by direct invasion, by the lymphatic route, and by the blood vessel route. The most common site of lymph node involvement is the axilla. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[Malignant neoplasm of breast](#)^c and ([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Breast](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant epithelial neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of breast](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast Carcinoma by Gene Expression Profile](#)^c, [HER2 negative](#)^c, [HER2 positive](#)^c, [Infiltrating duct carcinoma of breast](#)^c, [Infiltrating lobular carcinoma of breast](#)^c, [Invasive carcinoma of breast](#)^c, [Mixed ductal and lobular carcinoma of breast](#)^c

Carcinoma of cervix^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003320>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of cervix uteri](#)^c

Carcinoma of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000174>

A malignant epithelial neoplasm that arises from the colon and invades through the muscularis mucosa into the submucosa. The vast majority are adenocarcinomas. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Malignant epithelial neoplasm^c](#), [Malignant neoplasm of colon^c](#)

Carcinoma of genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000178>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of genital structure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma of prostate^c](#)

Carcinoma of pancreas^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000085>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of pancreas^c](#)

Carcinoma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000179>

One of the most common malignant tumors afflicting men. The majority of carcinomas arise in the peripheral zone and a minority occur in the central or the transitional zone of the prostate gland. Grossly, prostatic carcinomas appear as ill-defined yellow areas of discoloration in the prostate gland lobes. Adenocarcinomas represent the overwhelming majority of prostatic carcinomas. Prostatic-specific antigen (PSA) serum test is widely used as a screening test for the early detection of prostatic carcinoma. Treatment options include radical prostatectomy, radiation therapy, androgen ablation and cryotherapy. Watchful waiting or surveillance alone is an option for older patients with low-grade or low-stage disease. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Carcinoma of genital organ^c](#), [Malignant neoplasm of prostate^c](#)

Carcinoma of uterus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003322>

has super-classes

[Malignant epithelial neoplasm^c](#), [Malignant neoplasm of uterus^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma of uterus^c](#)

Carcinoma of vagina^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003325>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of vagina^c](#)

Carcinoma of vulva^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003327>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of vulva^c](#)

Carcinoma with osteoclast-like giant cells^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049182>

has super-classes

[Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c

Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063537>

has super-classes

[Epithelial neoplasms, NOS](#) ^c

Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of ascending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061108>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#) ^c, [Malignant epithelial neoplasm](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of ascending colon](#) ^c

Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of cecum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059452>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of cecum](#) ^c

Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of colon, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062485>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#) ^c, [Malignant epithelial neoplasm](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of colon](#) ^c

Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of descending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061867>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#) ^c, [Malignant epithelial neoplasm](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of descending colon](#) ^c

Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of hepatic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061267>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#) ^c

Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of rectum, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062848>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#) ^c, [Malignant epithelial neoplasm](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of rectum](#) ^c

Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of sigmoid colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059101>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of sigmoid colon](#) ^c

Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of splenic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061612>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of splenic flexure of colon](#) ^c

Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of transverse colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061462>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor^c](#), [Primary malignant neoplasm of transverse colon^c](#)

Cardinal number^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002335>

has super-classes

[Number^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Positive integer^c](#)

Care regime^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034299>

has super-classes

[Regimes and therapies^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Radiation therapy care^c](#)

Case-control^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000005>

has super-classes

[Collection method^c](#)

Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000012>

has super-classes

[Generic Module^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Generic Category^c](#), [Observation Category^c](#), [Procedure Category^c](#)

Cavity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051040>

has super-classes

[Mechanical lesion^c](#)

CDH1 (cadherin 1) gene variant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063206>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation^c](#)

Cecum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063731>

has super-classes

[Colon^c](#)

Cecum structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063321>

is equivalent to

[Cecum](#)^c

has super-classes

[Structure of cecum and/or colon and/or rectum](#)^c

Cells.estrone receptor/100 cells in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045931>

A quantitative immune staining procedure that measures the percentage of cells expressing estrogen receptor per the total number of cells in a breast cancer specimen. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

Cells.Ki-67 nuclear Ag/100 cells in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045913>

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

Cells.progesterone receptor/100 cells in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046195>

A quantitative immune staining procedure that measures the percentage of cells expressing progesterone receptor per the total number of cells in a breast cancer specimen. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

centimeter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001954>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

Central nervous system part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063275>

has super-classes

[Structure of central nervous system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Meninges structure](#)^c

Central nervous system tumor morphology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049105>

has super-classes

[Nervous system tumor morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glioma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Central portion of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000284>

has super-classes

[Breast](#)^c

Central zone necrosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051032>

has super-classes

[Zonal necrosis](#) ^c

Central zone of left half prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000225>

The portion of the central zone of the prostate that is located to the anatomical left of center. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Central zone of prostate](#) ^c

Central zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000168>

PI-RADS: The central zone is the region of the prostate surrounding the ejaculatory ducts posterior and superior, from the base of the prostate to the verumontanum. Its lateral border fuses with the proximal peripheral zone border at the prostate base. It has the shape of an inverted cone with its base oriented towards the base of the gland. It contains about 20% of the glandular tissue. It contains more stroma than glandular tissue. The term “central gland” refers to the central zone and the transition zone combined. The use of this term is discouraged. If the central zone is not seen as a distinct regional part, then a finding in this region should be localized to the transition zone. [RADLEX]

has super-classes

[Glandular zone of prostate](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Central zone of left half prostate](#) ^c, [Central zone of right half prostate](#) ^c

Central zone of right half prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000254>

The portion of the central zone of the prostate that is located to the anatomical right of center. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Central zone of prostate](#) ^c

Cerebellar nucleus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000399>

has super-classes

[Cerebellar part](#) ^c, [Eloquent Brain Areas](#) ^c

Cerebellar part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000374>

has super-classes

[Cerebellum](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Cerebellar nucleus](#) ^c, [Cerebellar peduncle](#) ^c

Cerebellar peduncle^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000398>

has super-classes

[Cerebellar part](#) ^c, [Eloquent Brain Areas](#) ^c

Cerebellar white matter structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000355>

has super-classes

[Structure of white matter of brain](#) ^c

Cerebellum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000373>

has super-classes

[Brain Lesion Site](#)^c, [Infratentorial brain part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cerebellar part](#)^c

Cerebral cortex part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000382>

has super-classes

[Structure of cerebral cortex](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Region of cerebral cortex](#)^c

Cerebral hemisphere part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000369>

has super-classes

[Cerebral hemisphere structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Basal ganglia](#)^c, [Cerebral white matter structure](#)^c, [Insula and opercula structure](#)^c

Cerebral hemisphere structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000368>

has super-classes

[Cerebrum](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cerebral hemisphere part](#)^c, [Structure of cerebral cortex](#)^c

Cerebral hemisphere white matter part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000379>

has super-classes

[Cerebral white matter structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Internal capsule](#)^c, [Structure of cerebral association fiber](#)^c

Cerebral lobe structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000363>

has super-classes

[Structure of lobe of brain](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Insular structure](#)^c, [Occipital lobe](#)^c

Cerebral meninges^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000305>

is equivalent to

[Structure of brain meninges](#)^c

has super-classes

[Meninges](#)^c

Cerebral white matter structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000377>

has super-classes

[Cerebral hemisphere part](#)^c, [Structure of white matter of brain](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cerebral hemisphere white matter part](#)^c, [Corpus callosum](#)^c

Cerebrum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000367>

has super-classes

[Brain](#)^c, [Supratentorial brain part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cerebral hemisphere structure](#)^c, [Structure of diencephalon](#)^c

Cervical spine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000240>

The set of vertebrae immediately caudal to the skull. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Spine](#)^c, [Structure of musculoskeletal system of cervical spine](#)^c, [Structure of vertebral region of cervical part of back](#)^c

Cervix uteri^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000290>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography](#)^c

Change patterns^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002077>

has super-classes

[Change values](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Stable](#)^c

Change values^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002076>

has super-classes

[Finding status values](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Change patterns](#)^c

CHEK2 (checkpoint kinase 2) gene variant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063223>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

Chemistry^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050450>

has super-classes

[Laboratory procedure](#)^c, [Measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alanine aminotransferase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Blood](#)^c, [Albumin/Protein.total in 24 hour Urine by Electrophoresis](#)^c, [Alkaline phosphatase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Blood](#)^c, [Aspartate aminotransferase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [C reactive protein \[Mass/volume\] in Blood by High sensitivity method](#)^c, [Calcium \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c, [Cancer Ag 19-9 \[Units/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cholesterol \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cholesterol in HDL \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cholesterol in LDL \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cortisol \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Creatinine \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c, [Creatinine \[Mass/volume\] in Urine](#)^c, [Gamma glutamyl transferase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Glucose \[Mass/volume\] in Venous blood](#)^c, [Hemoglobin A1c/Hemoglobin.total in Blood by HPLC](#)^c, [Insulin \[Units/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Lactate dehydrogenase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Red Blood Cells](#)^c, [Natriuretic peptide B \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c, [Potassium \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c, [Prostate specific Ag \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Sodium \[Moles/volume\] in Blood](#)^c, [Thyroglobulin \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Thyroid stimulating immunoglobulins \[Units/volume\] in Serum](#)^c, [Thyrotropin \[Units/volume\] in Blood](#)^c, [Triglyceride \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c, [Urate \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c, [Urea \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Chemotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024528>

has super-classes

[Administration of medication](#)^c, [Therapeutic procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chemotherapy cycle](#)^c, [Combined chemotherapy and radiation therapy](#)^c, [Neoadjuvant chemotherapy](#)^c, [Postoperative chemotherapy](#)^c, [Pre-operative chemotherapy](#)^c

Chemotherapy cycle^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035191>

has super-classes

[Chemotherapy](#)^c

Chemotherapy protective agent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063651>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

has sub-classes

[leucovorin](#)^c

Chemotherapy Regimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034214>

has super-classes

[Drug therapy](#)^c

Chest^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000067>

Subdivision of trunk proper, which is demarcated from the neck by the plane of the superior thoracic aperture and from the abdomen internally by the inferior surface of the diaphragm and externally by the costal margin and associated with the thoracic vertebral column and ribcage and from the back of the thorax by the external surface of the posterolateral part of the rib cage, the anterior surface of the thoracic vertebral column and the posterior axillary lines; together with the abdomen and the perineum, it constitutes the trunk proper. [FMA]

has super-classes

[Chest and abdomen](#)^c, [Neck and chest](#)^c, [Thoracic segment of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Mediastinum](#)^c, [Pectoral region structure](#)^c, [Structure of half of thorax lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c, [Structure of mammary region](#)^c

Chest and abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000183>

has super-classes

[Chest, abdomen, and pelvis](#)^c, [Neck, chest and abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chest](#)^c

Chest imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016134>

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c, [Imaging by body site](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Imaging of breast](#)^c, [MRI of chest](#)^c, [Radiographic procedure of chest](#)^c, [Ultrasonography of thorax](#)^c

Chest injury^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037253>

has super-classes

[Disorder of thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Injury of breast](#)^c

Chest pain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037128>

has super-classes

[Finding of region of thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Pain of breast](#)^c

Chest, abdomen, and pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000154>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdomen](#)^c, [Abdomen and Pelvis](#)^c, [Abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)^c, [Chest and abdomen](#)^c

Child^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001034>

has super-classes

[Immediate family member](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Daughter](#)^c, [Son](#)^c

Child-Pugh score^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047413>

A standardized rating scale used to assess the severity of liver cirrhosis and determine the prognosis, the required strength of treatment, and the necessity of liver transplantation. This instrument uses the following clinical and lab criteria: encephalopathy grade, ascites, bilirubin, albumin, and prothrombin index. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Performance Status Assessment](#)^c

Child-Pugh score class A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048245>

has super-classes

[Liver finding](#) ^c

Child-Pugh score class B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046426>

has super-classes

[Liver finding](#) ^c

Child-Pugh score class C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046463>

has super-classes

[Liver finding](#) ^c

Chinese^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001071>

has super-classes

[Asian](#) ^c, [Ethnicity](#) ^c

Cholangiocarcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047713>

A carcinoma that arises from the intrahepatic bile ducts, the hepatic ducts, or the common bile duct distal to the insertion of the cystic duct. The vast majority of tumors are adenocarcinomas. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c

Cholangitis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038935>

has super-classes

[Disorder of abdomen](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Sclerosing cholangitis](#) ^c

Cholesterol [Mass/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033575>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#) ^c, [Cholesterol measurement](#) ^c, [Cholesterol|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#) ^c, [Cholesterol|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma|386.664 g/mole](#) ^c

Cholesterol in HDL [Mass/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033635>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#) ^c, [Cholesterol in HDL|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#) ^c, [Cholesterol in HDL|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma](#) ^c, [High density lipoprotein cholesterol measurement](#) ^c

Cholesterol in LDL [Mass/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033680>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#) ^c, [Cholesterol in LDL|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#) ^c, [Cholesterol in LDL|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma](#) ^c, [Low density lipoprotein cholesterol measurement](#) ^c

Cholesterol measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033557>

has super-classes

[Lipids measurement^c](#), [Steroid measurement^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Cholesterol \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma^c](#), [High density lipoprotein cholesterol measurement^c](#), [Low density lipoprotein cholesterol measurement^c](#)

Cholesterol.in HDL|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049798>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Cholesterol in HDL \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma^c](#)

Cholesterol.in HDL|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050014>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Cholesterol in HDL \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma^c](#)

Cholesterol.in LDL|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049804>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Cholesterol in LDL \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma^c](#)

Cholesterol.in LDL|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050036>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Cholesterol in LDL \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma^c](#)

Cholesterol|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049811>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Cholesterol \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma^c](#)

Cholesterol|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma|386.664 g/mole^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050059>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Cholesterol \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma^c](#)

Chromosome region 6q22 rearrangements in Tissue by FISH^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051917>

has super-classes

[Gene rearrangement](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

Chronic digestive system disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039877>

has super-classes

[Disorder of digestive system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chronic liver disease](#)^c

Chronic disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040312>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chronic inflammatory disorder](#)^c

Chronic disease monitoring^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1009957>

has super-classes

[Monitoring of patient](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Monitoring of patient with cancer](#)^c

Chronic hepatitis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046355>

An active inflammatory process affecting the liver for more than six months. Causes include viral infections, autoimmune disorders, drugs, and metabolic disorders. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Chronic inflammatory disorder](#)^c, [Chronic liver disease](#)^c, [Inflammatory disease of liver](#)^c

Chronic inflammatory disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040402>

has super-classes

[Chronic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chronic hepatitis](#)^c

Chronic liver disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037342>

has super-classes

[Chronic digestive system disorder](#)^c, [Disease of liver](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chronic hepatitis](#)^c, [Cirrhosis of liver](#)^c

Cigarette smoker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059167>

has super-classes

[Smoker](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Heavy cigarette smoker \(20-39 cigarettes per day\)](#)^c, [Light cigarette smoker \(1-9 cigarettes per day\)](#)^c, [Moderate cigarette smoker \(10-19 cigarettes per day\)](#)^c, [Trivial cigarette smoker \(0-1 cigarettes per day\)](#)^c, [Very heavy cigarette smoker \(more or equal to 40 cigarettes per day\)](#)^c

Cigarettes pack-years smoked during life^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056702>

has super-classes

[Finding of tobacco use and exposure](#)^c

Circumferential (Radial) Margin Involved by Tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063691>

has super-classes

[Surgical circumferential margin finding](#)^c

Circumferential (Radial) Margin Uninvolved by Tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063704>

has super-classes

[Surgical circumferential margin finding](#)^c

Circumscribed margin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005419>

PI-RADS: Well defined. BI-RADS: Mammo: At least 75% of the margin is sharply demarcated, with an abrupt transition between the lesion and surrounding tissue (historically, "well defined" or "sharply defined"). MRI: Entire margin is sharply demarcated with abrupt transition between the lesion and surrounding tissue (historically, "smooth"). US: Entire margin is well defined or sharp, with an abrupt transition between the lesion and surrounding tissue (historically, "well defined" or "sharply defined"). [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Margin](#)^c

Cirrhosis of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045775>

has super-classes

[Chronic liver disease](#)^c, [Hepatic fibrosis](#)^c, [Liver regeneration](#)^c

Classification system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001055>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[National Public Health Classification data](#)^c

Clinical & Biological Module^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000001>

This module defines the categories/entities that are specified in clinical context (e.g., cancer types, histologic types, body parts, lab tests, treatments, surgical procedures, staging/grading methods or systems, etc.).

has super-classes

[thing](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Body structure](#)^c, [Clinical Test Result](#)^c, [Clinical finding](#)^c, [Diagnostic/Screening Processes or Results](#)^c, [Disease](#)^c, [Health Status Assessment](#)^c, [Histology/Morphology](#)^c, [Measurement](#)^c, [Medication](#)^c, [Metastasis](#)^c, [Observable entity](#)^c, [Procedure](#)^c, [Risk Assessment](#)^c, [Situation with explicit context](#)^c, [Specimen](#)^c, [Staging and scales](#)^c

Clinical equipment and/or device^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000106>

has super-classes

[device](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biomedical device](#)^c

Clinical finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000004>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Administrative statuses](#)^c, [Bleeding](#)^c, [Body measurement finding](#)^c, [Digestive system finding](#)^c, [Edema](#)^c, [Evaluation finding](#)^c, [Finding of blood, lymphatics and immune system](#)^c, [Finding of grade](#)^c, [Finding of lesion](#)^c, [Finding of pelvic region of trunk](#)^c, [Finding of trunk structure](#)^c, [Finding of urinary tract proper](#)^c, [Functional finding](#)^c, [Gastrointestinal tract finding](#)^c, [General clinical state finding](#)^c, [General finding of observation of patient](#)^c, [Infant feeding method - finding](#)^c, [Leukemia Finding](#)^c, [Mass of body structure](#)^c, [Mass of digestive structure](#)^c, [Menopause finding](#)^c, [Mental state, behavior and/or psychosocial function finding](#)^c, [Metabolic finding](#)^c, [Micturition finding](#)^c, [Pathophysiologic finding](#)^c, [Patient status finding](#)^c, [Performance Status Assessment Answer Finding](#)^c, [Pregnancy status](#)^c, [Respiratory finding](#)^c, [Skin AND/OR mucosa finding](#)^c, [Urine finding](#)^c, [Uses contraception](#)^c, [Viscus structure finding](#)^c

is in domain of

[SymptomAssociatedWith](#)^{op}

Clinical history/examination observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040048>

has super-classes

[Observable entity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lesion observable](#)^c, [Mental state, behavior / psychosocial function observable](#)^c, [Pregnancy, childbirth / puerperium observable](#)^c, [Respiratory observable](#)^c, [Skin observable](#)^c, [Survival time](#)^c

Clinical specialty^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036560>

has super-classes

[Common Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Pathology \(qualifier value\)](#)^c

Clinical Test Result^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000200>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Laboratory Test Result](#)^c, [Negative Test Result](#)^c

Clip^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000113>

has super-classes

[Biomedical device](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Surgical clip](#)^c

cM category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033341>

has super-classes

[M category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[TNM Clin M](#)^c

cM0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001860>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical M category allowable value](#)^c

cM1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000246>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical M category allowable value](#)^c

cM1a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000258>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical M category allowable value](#)^c

cM1b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000271>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical M category allowable value](#)^c

cM1c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001876>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical M category allowable value](#)^c

cN category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033358>

has super-classes

[N category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[TNM Clin N](#)^c

cN0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000285>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN0i+^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002767>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN0i^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002764>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN0m^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002776>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN0m^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002771>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000300>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN1a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002782>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN1b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002789>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN1c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002797>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN1mi^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001397>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001399>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN2a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001402>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN2b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001406>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001411>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN3a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001417>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN3b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001424>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cN3c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001432>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

cNX^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001441>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical N category allowable value](#)^c

Co-morbid conditions^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048316>

has super-classes

[General problem AND/OR complaint](#)^c

Cohort^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002627>

has super-classes

[Collection method](#)^c, [National Public Health Classification data](#)^c

Collection method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000002>

has super-classes

[Specific Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Case-control](#)^c, [Cohort](#)^c, [Disease-specific](#)^c, [Longitudinal](#)^c, [Only-Image](#)^c, [Patient-based](#)^c

is in range of

[collectionMethod](#)^{op}

Colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063722>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Ascending colon](#)^c, [Cecum](#)^c, [Colon, NOS](#)^c, [Descending colon](#)^c, [Hepatic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Splenic flexure of colon](#)^c,
[Transverse colon](#)^c

Colon and rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000170>

has super-classes

[Combined site](#)^c

Colon part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063276>

has super-classes

[Colon structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Region of colon](#)^c

Colon structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000257>

The part of the large intestine measured from the cecum to the rectum consisting of ascending, transverse, descending and sigmoid portions. The purpose of the colon is to remove water from digested food prior to excretion. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[Colon, NOS](#)^c

has super-classes

[Structure of cecum and/or colon and/or rectum](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Colon part](#)^c, [Entire colon](#)^c

Colon, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063766>

has super-classes

[Colon](#)^c

Colonic lesion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051680>

has super-classes

[Disorder of colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of colon](#)^c

Colonoscopy Video Recording^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004466>

has super-classes

[Video imaging](#)^c

Combined chemotherapy and radiation therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035091>

has super-classes

[Chemotherapy](#)^c, [Drug therapy](#)^c, [Radiation therapy procedure or service](#)^c, [Radiotherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radiochemotherapy via intravenous route](#)^c

combined modalities^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004454>

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#)^c

has sub-classes

[PET-CT](#)^c, [PET-MR](#)^c, [SPECT-CT](#)^c

Combined posterior acoustic pattern^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016617>

BI-RADS US: more than one pattern of posterior attenuation both shadowing and enhancement. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Posterior acoustic feature](#)^c

Combined site^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000012>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bronchus and lung](#)^c, [Colon and rectum](#)^c, [Uterus and fallopian tubes](#)^c

Common Module^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000001>

This module defines the categories/entities or values that are not specified as imaging or clinical context (e.g., qualifiers, age, sex/gender, unit of measure, staging/grading values, presence/absence values, etc.).

has super-classes

[thing](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Age AND/OR growth period](#)^c, [Attribute](#)^c, [Clinical specialty](#)^c, [Gender](#)^c, [Person](#)^c, [Physical object](#)^c, [Qualifier](#)^c, [Sex assigned at birth](#)^c, [Value](#)^c

Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059992>

has super-classes

[National Cancer Institute common terminology criteria for adverse event grade finding](#)^c

Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060036>

has super-classes

[National Cancer Institute common terminology criteria for adverse event grade finding](#)^c

Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060081>

has super-classes

[National Cancer Institute common terminology criteria for adverse event grade finding](#)^c

Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060127>

has super-classes

[National Cancer Institute common terminology criteria for adverse event grade finding](#)^c

Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060174>

has super-classes

[National Cancer Institute common terminology criteria for adverse event grade finding](#)^c

Complete^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000187>

has super-classes

[Completeness](#)^c

Complete excision^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004692>

has super-classes

[Excision](#)^c, [Procedure on organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radical mastectomy](#)^c, [Removal of entire genital organ](#)^c, [Simple mastectomy](#)^c, [Total pneumonectomy](#)^c

Complete Resection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004585>

Complete clearance of the tumor with histologically proved negative margins. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Extent of Resection](#)^c

Complete response^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001312>

has super-classes

[Treatment response value](#)^c

Complete response (CR)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001222>

has super-classes

[Neoadjuvant Therapy response value](#)^c

Completeness^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000184>

has super-classes

[Finding value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Complete](#)^c

Complex cystic and solid echogenicity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016624>

BI-RADS US: A complex mass contains both anechoic (cystic) and echogenic (solid) components. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Echogenicity characteristic](#)^c

Complex epithelial neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049194>

has super-classes

[Epithelial neoplasm](#)^c, [ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma](#)^c

Computed radiography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000024>

has super-classes

[Projection radiography](#)^c

Computed tomography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000026>

A method of examining structures within the body by scanning them with X rays and using a computer to construct a series of cross-sectional scans along a single axis. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Radiographic imaging procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[CT of chest](#)^c, [Computerized Tomography \(CT Scan\) of Chest, Abdomen and Pelvis](#)^c, [Single photon emission computed tomography with computed tomography](#)^c

Computed tomography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000042>

has super-classes

[Imaging sequence](#)^c, [Radiographic imaging - action](#)^c, [Tomography](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Dual-energy CT](#)^c, [Low-Dose Computed Tomography](#)^c, [Photon Counting Computed Tomography](#)^c

Computed Tomography Dose Index Volume^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000144>

The International Electrotechnical Commission preferred expression of radiation dose in computed tomography (CT) dosimetry. It is calculated by averaging the radiation dose delivered over x,y and z directions and expressed in the SI unit of Gray (Gy). [NCIT]

has super-classes

[CT procedure attribute](#)^c

has sub-classes

[CT Imaging Acquisition Protocol Element CTDI VOL](#)^c

Computerized Tomography (CT Scan) of Chest, Abdomen and Pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000027>

has super-classes

[Computed tomography](#)^c

Condition clinical status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004583>

has super-classes

[Situation with explicit context](#)^c

Condition clinical status value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001176>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Active](#)^c, [Inactive](#)^c, [Recurrence](#)^c, [Relapse](#)^c, [Remission](#)^c, [Resolved](#)^c

is in range of

[hasClinicalStatus](#)^{op}

Condition stability status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001190>

LOINC: - ANSWER LIST CODE: LL5946-0 - ANSWER LIST NAME: Condition stability status

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Improved](#)^c, [No evidence of disease](#)^c, [Stable](#)^c, [Undetermined](#)^c, [Worsened](#)^c

Conformal radiotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005280>

has super-classes

[Radiotherapy](#)^c, [Three dimensional external beam radiation therapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intensity modulated radiation therapy](#)^c, [Three dimensional conformal radiotherapy](#)^c

Conformal radiotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015948>

has super-classes

[Destructive procedure](#)^c, [Radiotherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[3D CRT three dimensional conformal radiation therapy](#)^c

Congenital disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052340>

has super-classes

[Disorder of fetus and/or newborn](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Congenital hamartoma](#)^c, [Congenital melanosis](#)^c, [Neurocutaneous syndrome](#)^c

Congenital hamartoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052355>

has super-classes

[Congenital disease^c](#), [Hamartoma^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Peutz-Jeghers syndrome^c](#)

Congenital melanosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052371>

has super-classes

[Congenital disease^c](#), [Melanosis^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Peutz-Jeghers syndrome^c](#)

Connective, subcutaneous and other soft tissues^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000308>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Connective, Subcutaneous and other soft tissues of lower limb and hip^c](#), [Connective, Subcutaneous and other soft tissues of upper limb and shoulder^c](#)

Connective, Subcutaneous and other soft tissues of lower limb and hip^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000309>

has super-classes

[Connective, subcutaneous and other soft tissues^c](#), [Lower extremity part^c](#)

Connective, Subcutaneous and other soft tissues of upper limb and shoulder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000410>

has super-classes

[Connective, subcutaneous and other soft tissues^c](#), [Upper extremity part^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Structure of soft tissues of left upper extremity^c](#), [Structure of soft tissues of right upper extremity^c](#)

Construction^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056703>

has super-classes

[Surgical repair^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Construction of anastomosis^c](#)

Construction of anastomosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056706>

has super-classes

[Construction^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Gastrointestinal and digestive anastomosis^c](#)

Contact Date^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001947>

The date on which a direct or indirect interaction between individuals or organizations occurred. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Date](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Date of Last Contact](#)^c

Context values^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001061>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Finding context value](#)^c, [Temporal context value](#)^c

Continent of urine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024607>

has super-classes

[Bladder control - finding](#)^c, [Bladder finding](#)^c

Contouring^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000089>

Annotation type (INCISIVE, Annotation Definitions and guidelines)

has super-classes

[Annotation Type](#)^c

Contrast agent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016756>

has super-classes

[Pharmaceutical / biologic product](#)^c

Control group^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002625>

has super-classes

[National Public Health Classification data](#)^c, [Population](#)^c

Conventional tomography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000084>

has super-classes

[Tomography](#)^c

Core needle biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057690>

has super-classes

[Needle biopsy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Core needle biopsy of breast](#)^c, [Core needle biopsy of prostate](#)^c

Core needle biopsy of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060274>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of breast](#)^c, [Core needle biopsy](#)^c

Core needle biopsy of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001937>

has super-classes

[Core needle biopsy](#)^c, [Needle biopsy of prostate](#)^c

Corpus callosum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000378>

has super-classes

[Brain Deep White Matter Structure](#)^c, [Brain Lesion Site](#)^c, [Cerebral white matter structure](#)^c

Correspondence^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000001>

This module defines the OMOP domain and FHIR resourceType as defined in local CDMs).

has super-classes

[Specific Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[FHIR](#)^c, [OMOP](#)^c

Cortical Involvement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016723>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Cortical Involvement value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016723>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Absent](#)^c, [No](#)^c, [Present](#)^c, [Yes](#)^c

Cortisol [Mass/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033932>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#)^c, [Cortisol measurement](#)^c, [Cortisol|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cortisol|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma|362,466 g/mole](#)^c

Cortisol measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050691>

has super-classes

[17-hydroxycorticosteroid measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cortisol \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Cortisol|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049819>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cortisol \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Cortisol|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma|362.466 g/mole^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050083>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cortisol \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Cough^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051879>

has super-classes

[Respiratory function finding](#)^c

Couinaud hepatic segment II^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000436>

has super-classes

[Couinaud liver segment](#)^c

Couinaud hepatic segment III^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000435>

has super-classes

[Couinaud liver segment](#)^c

Couinaud hepatic segment IV^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000434>

has super-classes

[Couinaud liver segment](#)^c

Couinaud hepatic segment V^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000429>

has super-classes

[Couinaud liver segment](#)^c, [Liver lobe part](#)^c

Couinaud hepatic segment VI^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000430>

has super-classes

[Couinaud liver segment](#)^c, [Liver lobe part](#)^c

Couinaud hepatic segment VII^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000431>

has super-classes

[Couinaud liver segment](#)^c, [Liver lobe part](#)^c

Couinaud hepatic segment VIII^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000432>

has super-classes

[Couinaud liver segment](#)^c, [Liver lobe part](#)^c

Couinaud liver segment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000433>

has super-classes

[Liver segment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Couinaud hepatic segment II](#)^c, [Couinaud hepatic segment III](#)^c, [Couinaud hepatic segment IV](#)^c, [Couinaud hepatic segment V](#)^c, [Couinaud hepatic segment VI](#)^c, [Couinaud hepatic segment VII](#)^c, [Couinaud hepatic segment VIII](#)^c, [Structure of caudate lobe of liver](#)^c

Counseling^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058187>

has super-classes

[Procedure Category](#)^c, [Procedure by method](#)^c

Creatinine [Mass/volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033482>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#)^c, [Creatinine measurement](#)^c, [Creatinine|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Creatinine|Moment in time|Blood|113.12 g/mole](#)^c

Creatinine [Mass/volume] in Urine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034107>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#)^c, [Creatinine measurement, urine](#)^c, [Creatinine|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Any Urine specimen](#)^c, [Creatinine|Mass Concentration|Urine](#)^c, [Creatinine|Moment in time|Urine|113.12 g/mole](#)^c

Creatinine measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050739>

has super-classes

[Measurement of substance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Creatinine \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Creatinine measurement, urine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050622>

has super-classes

[Urine substance measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Creatinine \[Mass/volume\] in Urine](#)^c

Creatinine|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Any Urine specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049838>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Creatinine \[Mass/volume\] in Urine](#)^c

Creatinine|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049828>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Creatinine \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Creatinine|Mass Concentration|Urine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050378>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Creatinine \[Mass/volume\] in Urine](#)^c

Creatinine|Moment in time|Blood|113.12 g/mole^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050108>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Creatinine \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Creatinine|Moment in time|Urine|113.12 g/mole^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050134>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Creatinine \[Mass/volume\] in Urine](#)^c

Cribriform tumor pattern^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049744>

has super-classes

[Tumor configuration](#)^c

Cross-sectional abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000087>

has super-classes

[Abdominopelvic cross-sectional segment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Liver and/or biliary structure](#)^c, [Structure of organ within abdomen proper cavity](#)^c

Cross-sectional attenuation correction method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016771>

has super-classes

[Attenuation correction method](#)^c

has sub-classes

[CT attenuation correction](#)^c

Cross-sectional pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000238>

This cross-sectional segment is bounded superiorly by a virtual horizontal plane at the level of the plane traversing the superior boundary of the iliac crest; and inferiorly it extends to the perineum and includes part but not necessarily the entire external genitalia. The segment includes the volume of the true and false pelvic cavities (and also part of the lower abdominal volume below the level of the virtual superior boundary). The volume includes the entire transverse thickness of the body over the longitudinal extent between the superior (upper) and inferior (lower) boundaries including the skin and subcutaneous tissue. The segment relates to the cross-sectional or projectional volume as perceived by transmissive or emissive imaging. [SNOMEDCT]

has super-classes

[Abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Pelvis](#)^c

cross-sectional procedure attribute^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016625>

has super-classes

[Imaging procedure property](#)^c

has sub-classes

[CT procedure attribute](#)^c, [MR procedure attribute](#)^c, [radiography procedure attribute](#)^c

Cross-sectional thorax^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000126>

has super-classes

[Structure of subregion of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Thoracic segment of trunk](#)^c

CT attenuation correction^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016772>

has super-classes

[Cross-sectional attenuation correction method](#)^c

cT category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033379>

has super-classes

[T category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[TNM Clin T](#)^c

CT Imaging Acquisition Protocol Element CTDI VOL^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000141>

The average dose over the total volume scanned for the selected CT conditions of operation (calculated according to IEC 60601-2-44, Ed.2.1 (Clause 29.1.103.4)). EXAMPLE(S): OTHER NAME(S): Computed Tomography Dose Index (CTDI) Volume NOTE(S): The units are energy dose, e.g. mGy. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Computed Tomography Dose Index Volume](#)^c

CT of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000078>

has super-classes

[CT of chest](#)^c, [Mammography](#)^c

CT of chest^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000077>

has super-classes

[Computed tomography](#)^c, [Radiographic procedure of chest](#)^c

has sub-classes

[CT of breast](#)^c, [CT of thorax with contrast](#)^c

CT of thorax with contrast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000076>

has super-classes

[CT of chest](#)^c

CT procedure attribute^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016633>

has super-classes

[cross-sectional procedure attribute](#)^c

has sub-classes

[CT scan mode](#)^c, [Computed Tomography Dose Index Volume](#)^c

CT scan mode^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000145>

has super-classes

[CT procedure attribute](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Axial scan mode](#)^c

cT0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000316>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000333>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT1a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001451>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT1b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001462>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT1c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001474>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT1mi^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001487>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000351>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT2a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000370>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT2b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000390>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT2c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000411>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000433>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT3a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000456>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT3b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000480>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000505>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT4a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001501>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT4b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001516>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT4c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001532>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cT4d^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001549>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cTis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002251>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cTisDCIs^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001818>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cTisPaget^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001831>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cTX^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002762>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical T category allowable value](#)^c

cubic centimeter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000148>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

cubic millimeter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000149>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

Curative therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034118>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c

Current^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001067>

has super-classes

[Alcohol drinker status value](#)^c, [Current or specified](#)^c, [Smoking status value](#)^c

Current drinker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056333>

has super-classes

[Finding relating to alcohol drinking behavior](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Fairly heavy drinker](#)^c, [Heavy drinker](#)^c, [Light drinker](#)^c, [Moderate drinker](#)^c, [Occasional drinker](#)^c, [Very heavy drinker](#)^c

Current drinker of alcohol^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001142>

has super-classes

[Alcohol use pattern value](#)^c

Current non-drinker of alcohol^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001140>

has super-classes

[Alcohol use pattern value](#)^c

Current or past^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001064>

has super-classes

[Temporal context value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Current or specified](#)^c, [Past](#)^c

Current or specified^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001062>

has super-classes

[Current or past](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Current](#)^c, [Specified time](#)^c

Cyclophosphamide^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035871>

A synthetic alkylating agent chemically related to the nitrogen mustards with antineoplastic and immunosuppressive activities. In the liver, cyclophosphamide is converted to the active metabolites aldophosphamide and phosphoramidate mustard, which bind to DNA, thereby inhibiting DNA

replication and initiating cell death. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Alkylating agent](#)^c, [Antineoplastic agent](#)^c, [Immunologic agent](#)^c

Cyst^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051018>

Any fluid-filled closed cavity or sac that is lined by an epithelium. Cysts can be of normal, abnormal, non-neoplastic, or neoplastic tissues. [MeSH] Pathology.—A cyst is any round circumscribed space that is surrounded by an epithelial or fibrous wall of variable thickness (51). BI-RADS MRI: Circumscribed, round or oval fluid-filled mass with an imperceptible wall, bright on T2-weighted images. Radiographs and CT scans.—A cyst appears as a round parenchymal lucency or low-attenuating area with a well-defined interface with normal lung. Cysts have variable wall thickness but are usually thin-walled (<2 mm) and occur without associated pulmonary emphysema (Fig 21). Cysts in the lung usually contain air but occasionally contain fluid or solid material. The term is often used to describe enlarged thin-walled airspaces in patients with lymphangiomyomatosis (52) or Langerhans cell histiocytosis (53); thicker-walled honeycomb cysts are seen in patients with end-stage fibrosis (54). (See also bleb, bulla, honeycombing, pneumatocele.) [Fleischner Society] [PI-RADS] On MR: A circumscribed T2 hyperintense fluid containing sac-like structure. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Mass](#)^c, [Mechanical lesion](#)^c

Cyst of abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038260>

has super-classes

[Abdominal mass](#)^c, [Disorder of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cyst of liver](#)^c

Cyst of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047905>

A cystic lesion located in the liver. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Cyst of abdomen](#)^c, [Disease of liver](#)^c, [Liver mass](#)^c

Cystadenoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049509>

has super-classes

[Benign adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Cystic, mucinous AND/OR serous neoplasm](#)^c

Cystadenoma of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045763>

has super-classes

[Adenoma of liver](#)^c

Cystadenoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049580>

has super-classes

[Cystic, mucinous and serous neoplasms](#)^c

Cystic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001075>

has super-classes

[Formations](#)^c

Cystic, mucinous and serous neoplasms^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046888>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cystadenoma, NOS](#)^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma](#)^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma](#)^c

Cystic, mucinous AND/OR serous neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049104>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Basal cell neoplasm \(morphology\)](#)^c, [Cystadenoma](#)^c

Cysts^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016749>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Cysts value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016749>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Absent](#)^c, [Present](#)^c

Cytologic test^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034155>

has super-classes

[Evidence Type](#)^c, [Laboratory test](#)^c

Cytopenia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051843>

has super-classes

[Blood cell count outside reference range](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Blood leukocyte number below reference range](#)^c, [Red blood cell count below reference range](#)^c

Cytotoxic antibiotic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035834>

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic antibiotic](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anthracycline](#)^c

Damage^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016586>

has super-classes

[Lesion](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Necrosis](#)^c, [focal damage](#)^c

Data Value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000007>

The information contained in a data field. It may represent a numeric quantity, a textual characterization, a date or time measurement, or some other state, depending on the nature of the attribute. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[+2](#)^c, [0](#)^c, [1+](#)^c, [2+](#)^c, [3+](#)^c

Dataset Access Condition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000021>

has super-classes

[Specific Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Authorisation to access, view and process in-situ the datasets](#)^c, [Authorisation to download the datasets](#)^c, [Authorisation to remotely process the datasets without the ability to access and visualise data, even remotely](#)^c

Dataset Type^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000017>

has super-classes

[Specific Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Annotated Dataset](#)^c, [Original Dataset](#)^c, [Processed Dataset](#)^c

Date^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001946>

The particular day, month and year an event has happened or will happen. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Temporal Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Contact Date](#)^c, [Date of Diagnosis](#)^c, [Date of death](#)^c, [Image Acquisition Date](#)^c, [Image Date](#)^c

Date of death^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001939>

has super-classes

[Date](#)^c

Date of Diagnosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001941>

The date on which a diagnosis of disease was made. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Date](#)^c

Date of Last Contact^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001949>

has super-classes

[Contact Date](#)^c

is in range of

[has date of last contact](#)^{op}

Daughter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001020>

has super-classes

[Child](#)^c

day^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000153>

has super-classes

[Unit of time](#)^c

DCIS (Ductal carcinoma in situ) of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002303>

has super-classes

[Carcinoma in situ of breast](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Mixed ductal and lobular carcinoma in situ of breast](#)^c

Dead^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024687>

has super-classes

[General clinical state finding](#)^c

Deep White Matter Invasion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016725>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Degenerative disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038077>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[steatosis of liver](#)^c

Degree findings^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002020>

has super-classes

[Finding value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Improved](#)^c, [Inadequate](#)^c, [Increased](#)^c, [Low](#)^c, [Poorly defined](#)^c, [Well defined](#)^c

Degrees of severity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001335>

has super-classes

[Ranked categories](#)^c

has sub-classes

[First degree](#)^c, [Second degree](#)^c

Delayed phase^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016767>

has super-classes

[enhancement phase](#)^c

Delivered radiation dose^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050897>

has super-classes

[Drug observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Total radiation dose delivered](#)^c

Demographic history detail^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040047>

has super-classes

[Social / personal history observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Ethnic group](#)^c

Density descriptor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016690>

[BI-RADS] This is used to define the x-ray attenuation of the lesion relative to the expected attenuation of an equal volume of fibroglandular breast tissue. It is important that most breast cancers that form a visible mass are of equal or higher density than an equal volume of fibroglandular tissue. It is rare (although not impossible) for breast cancer to be lower in density. breast cancers are never fat-containing (radiolucent) although they may trap fat. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c, [Tumor Observation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[High density](#)^c

Deposit^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000220>

has super-classes

[Morphologic Finding](#)^c, [Tumor Observation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Calcification disorder](#)^c

Derived^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000012>

An indication that a data element has been derived from one or more data elements. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[General adjectival modifier](#)^c

Derived Unit of International System of Units^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000145>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

Descending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063749>

has super-classes

[Colon^c](#)

Descending colon structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063294>

is equivalent to

[Descending colon^c](#)

has super-classes

[Left colon structure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Structure of left colic flexure^c](#)

Descriptor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002040>

has super-classes

[Qualifier^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Age^c](#), [Behavior descriptors^c](#), [Distributions^c](#), [Extents^c](#), [Formations^c](#), [Natures^c](#), [Negative descriptors^c](#), [Origins^c](#), [Pathogeneses^c](#)

Destructive procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1014088>

has super-classes

[Surgical procedure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Conformal radiotherapy^c](#), [Destructive procedure by anatomic site^c](#), [Intensity modulated radiation therapy^c](#)

Destructive procedure by anatomic site^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056805>

has super-classes

[Destructive procedure^c](#)

device^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000104>

has super-classes

[Physical object^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Clinical equipment and/or device^c](#)

Diagnosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000008>

has super-classes

[Episode^c](#)

Diagnostic Imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016307>

Any method that uses a visual display of structural or functional patterns of organs or tissues for diagnostic evaluation. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Image Study](#)^c

Diagnostic intent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002606>

has super-classes

[Intents](#)^c

Diagnostic/Screening Processes or Results^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018455>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[High risk of recurrence, prostate cancer](#)^c, [Intermediate risk of recurrence, prostate cancer](#)^c, [Low risk of recurrence, prostate cancer](#)^c, [Prostate cancer risk of recurrence not determined or neither low, intermediate nor high](#)^c

Diencephalon part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000395>

has super-classes

[Structure of diencephalon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hypothalamus](#)^c, [Thalamus](#)^c

Difficulty breathing^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051871>

has super-classes

[Ease of respiration - finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Dyspnea](#)^c

Difficulty initiating bladder emptying^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000356>

has super-classes

[Difficulty passing urine](#)^c

Difficulty passing urine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000366>

has super-classes

[Finding related to ability to pass urine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Difficulty initiating bladder emptying](#)^c

Diffuse hemorrhage^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051021>

has super-classes

[Hemorrhage](#)^c

Diffuse intrinsic pontine glioma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000062>

A glioma that grows diffusely in the pons. It usually affects children and has a poor prognosis. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Malignant glioma of brainstem](#)^c

Diffuse non-Hodgkin's lymphoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046322>

has super-classes

[Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma \(clinical\)](#)^c

Diffuse tumor configuration^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049746>

has super-classes

[Tumor configuration](#)^c

Diffusion Characteristics^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016720>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Facilitated diffusion](#)^c, [Restricted diffusion](#)^c

Diffusion Characteristics value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016720>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Facilitated](#)^c, [Indeterminate](#)^c, [Mixed](#)^c, [No ADC images](#)^c, [Restricted](#)^c

Diffusion MRI^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004467>

MRI method that measure the diffusion of water in the tissue, rather than the content of water as measured in conventional MRI. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Diffusion Spectrum Imaging](#)^c, [Diffusion tensor imaging](#)^c

Diffusion Spectrum Imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004468>

A high angular resolution diffusion MRI technique that maps complex tissue structures at the scale of single MRI voxels. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Diffusion MRI](#)^c

Diffusion tensor imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004460>

has super-classes

[Diffusion MRI](#)^c

Diffusion weighted^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016653>

has super-classes

[Imaging sequence](#)^c, [Tissue Contrast](#)^c

Diffusion weighted imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005452>

has super-classes

[Imaging observation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ADC value](#)^c, [Facilitated diffusion](#)^c, [Restricted diffusion](#)^c

Digestive organ structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000114>

has super-classes

[Body organ structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Esophagus](#)^c, [Liver and/or biliary structure](#)^c, [Pancreas](#)^c

Digestive system finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051455>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of digestive system](#)^c, [Gastrointestinal tract finding](#)^c

Digestive system hereditary disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052445>

has super-classes

[Disorder of digestive system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Peutz-Jeghers syndrome](#)^c

Digestive tract part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063456>

has super-classes

[Digestive tract structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gastrointestinal tract structure](#)^c

Digestive tract structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063437>

has super-classes

[Structure of digestive system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Digestive tract part](#)^c

Digital examination^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018533>

has super-classes

[Examination by method](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Digital examination of rectum](#)^c

Digital examination of rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1028950>

has super-classes

[Digital examination](#)^c, [Palpation of abdomen](#)^c, [Rectal examination](#)^c

Digital Microscopy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004458>

has super-classes

[Microscopy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Whole Slide Imaging](#)^c

Digital Radiography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000028>

has super-classes

[Projection radiography](#)^c

Digitized hematoxylin-eosin (HE) slides^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004463>

is equivalent to

[Whole Slide Imaging](#)^c and ([involve_staining_method](#)^{op} some [Hematoxylin and eosin stain method](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Whole Slide Imaging](#)^c

Discoloration of skin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059069>

has super-classes

[Finding of color of skin](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Discoloration of skin of breast](#)^c

Discoloration of skin of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059066>

has super-classes

[Discoloration of skin](#)^c

Disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002855>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abscess](#)^c, [Autoimmune disease](#)^c, [Chronic disease](#)^c, [Degenerative disorder](#)^c, [Disorder due to infection](#)^c, [Disorder of body cavity](#)^c, [Disorder of body system](#)^c, [Disorder of breast](#)^c, [Disorder of cellular component of blood](#)^c, [Disorder of digestive organ](#)^c, [Disorder of digestive system](#)^c, [Disorder of fetus and/or newborn](#)^c, [Disorder of immune function](#)^c, [Disorder of pigmentation](#)^c, [Disorder of soft tissue](#)^c, [Disorder of trunk](#)^c,

[Drug-related disorder](#)^c, [Genetic disease](#)^c, [Inflammation of specific body organs](#)^c, [Liver disorder due to infection](#)^c, [Metabolic disease](#)^c,
[Neoplasm and/or hamartoma](#)^c, [Nutritional deficiency associated condition](#)^c

is in domain of

[hasResultingEffect](#)^{op}

is in range of

[Has condition](#)^{op}, [Suffers from](#)^{op}, [hasComorbidity](#)^{op}

Disease caused by parasite^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036310>

has super-classes

[Disorder due to infection](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disease due to Taeniidae](#)^c, [Infection of liver caused by parasite](#)^c

Disease Clinical Qualifier^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000102>

has super-classes

[Disease qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Aggressive](#)^c, [Localized](#)^c, [Primary](#)^c, [Recurrent](#)^c, [Secondary](#)^c

Disease due to Taeniidae^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036317>

has super-classes

[Disease caused by parasite](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Echinococcosis](#)^c

Disease Grade Qualifier^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001768>

has super-classes

[Disease morphology qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Histological grades](#)^c, [Tumor Regression Grade 0|Complete response: No viable cancer cells|No residual tumor](#)^c, [Tumor Regression Grade 1|Moderate response: Single cells or small groups of cancer cells](#)^c, [Tumor Regression Grade 2|Minimal response: Residual cancer outgrown by fibrosis](#)^c, [Tumor Regression Grade 3|Poor response: Minimal or no tumor kill; extensive residual cancer](#)^c, [Tumor Regression Score 0](#)^c, [Tumor Regression Score 1](#)^c, [Tumor Regression Score 2](#)^c, [Tumor Regression Score 3](#)^c, [Unknown or no information|Not documented in patient record](#)^c

Disease morphology qualifier^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000029>

has super-classes

[Disease qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Benign](#)^c, [Disease Grade Qualifier](#)^c, [Invasive](#)^c, [Malignant](#)^c

Disease of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036385>

has super-classes

[Disorder of abdomen](#)^c, [Disorder of digestive organ](#)^c, [Liver finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abscess of liver](#)^c, [Autoimmune liver disease](#)^c, [Chronic liver disease](#)^c, [Cyst of liver](#)^c, [Drug-induced disorder of liver](#)^c, [Focal nodular hyperplasia of liver](#)^c, [Hepatic fibrosis](#)^c, [Inflammatory disease of liver](#)^c, [Lesion of liver](#)^c, [Liver damage](#)^c, [Liver regeneration](#)^c, [steatosis of liver](#)^c

Disease phases^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001339>

has super-classes

[Time patterns](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Relapse](#)^c, [Remission](#)^c

Disease qualifier^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000026>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Asymptomatic](#)^c, [Disease Clinical Qualifier](#)^c, [Disease morphology qualifier](#)^c, [Metastatic](#)^c, [Symptomatic](#)^c

Disease-specific^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000007>

has super-classes

[Collection method](#)^c

Disorder caused by alcohol^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036460>

has super-classes

[Drug-related disorder](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alcoholic liver damage](#)^c

Disorder due to infection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036308>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disease caused by parasite](#)^c

Disorder of abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002712>

has super-classes

[Disorder of abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)^c, [Finding of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdominal abscess](#)^c, [Cholangitis](#)^c, [Cyst of abdomen](#)^c, [Disease of liver](#)^c, [Disorder of lower gastrointestinal tract](#)^c, [Disorder of prostate](#)^c, [Disorder of retroperitoneum](#)^c, [Disorder of uterus](#)^c, [Injury of abdomen](#)^c, [Intra-abdominal collection](#)^c

Disorder of abdominopelvic segment of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003002>

has super-classes

[Disorder of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of abdomen](#)^c, [Disorder of pelvic region of trunk](#)^c

Disorder of body cavity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036973>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intraabdominal bile collection](#)^c

Disorder of body system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051202>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of digestive system](#)^c, [Disorder of endocrine system](#)^c, [Disorder of hematopoietic structure](#)^c, [Disorder of integument](#)^c, [Disorder of nervous system](#)^c, [Disorder of respiratory system](#)^c, [Disorder of skin and/or subcutaneous tissue](#)^c

Disorder of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037532>

has super-classes

[Breast finding](#)^c, [Disease](#)^c, [Disorder of thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Injury of breast](#)^c, [Mammary duct ectasia](#)^c, [Neoplasm of breast](#)^c

Disorder of cellular component of blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051185>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c, [Finding of blood, lymphatics and immune system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anemia](#)^c

Disorder of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051259>

has super-classes

[Disorder of large intestine](#)^c, [Finding of colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Colonic lesion](#)^c

Disorder of digestive organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038585>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c, [Disorder of digestive system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disease of liver](#)^c, [Disorder of intestine](#)^c

Disorder of digestive system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036685>

has super-classes

[Digestive system finding](#)^c, [Disease](#)^c, [Disorder of body system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chronic digestive system disorder](#)^c, [Digestive system hereditary disorder](#)^c, [Disorder of digestive organ](#)^c, [Disorder of digestive tract](#)^c, [Gastrointestinal and digestive injury](#)^c

Disorder of digestive tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051052>

has super-classes

[Disorder of digestive system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of gastrointestinal tract](#)^c

Disorder of endocrine system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059397>

has super-classes

[Disorder of body system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of thyroid gland](#)^c, [Neoplasm of endocrine system](#)^c

Disorder of female genital organs^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003151>

has super-classes

[Disorder of female reproductive system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of uterus](#)^c, [Disorder of vagina](#)^c

Disorder of female reproductive system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003152>

has super-classes

[Disorder of pelvic region of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of female genital organs](#)^c

Disorder of fetus and/or newborn^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052326>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Congenital disease](#)^c

Disorder of gastrointestinal tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051055>

has super-classes

[Disorder of digestive tract](#)^c, [Gastrointestinal tract finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anorectal disorder](#)^c, [Disorder of lower gastrointestinal tract](#)^c, [Drug-induced gastrointestinal disturbance](#)^c, [Gastrointestinal obstruction](#)^c, [Neoplasm of gastrointestinal tract](#)^c

Disorder of hematopoietic structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052425>

has super-classes

[Disorder of body system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bone marrow disorder](#)^c

Disorder of immune function^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036515>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[White blood cell disorder](#)^c

Disorder of integument^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052466>

has super-classes

[Disorder of body system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of skin and/or subcutaneous tissue](#)^c, [Hereditary disorder of the integument](#)^c

Disorder of intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051094>

has super-classes

[Bowel finding](#)^c, [Disorder of digestive organ](#)^c, [Disorder of lower gastrointestinal tract](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of large intestine](#)^c, [Hamartoma of intestine](#)^c, [Intestinal obstruction](#)^c, [Neoplasm of intestinal tract](#)^c

Disorder of kidney and/or ureter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052670>

has super-classes

[Disorder of the urinary system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Kidney disease](#)^c

Disorder of large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051104>

has super-classes

[Disorder of intestine](#)^c, [Finding of large intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of colon](#)^c, [Disorder of rectum](#)^c, [Neoplasm of large intestine](#)^c

Disorder of lipoprotein AND/OR lipid metabolism^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036519>

has super-classes

[Metabolic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Dyslipidemia](#)^c

Disorder of lower gastrointestinal tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051700>

has super-classes

[Disorder of abdomen](#)^c, [Disorder of gastrointestinal tract](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of intestine](#)^c

Disorder of lower respiratory system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051239>

has super-classes

[Disorder of respiratory system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of lung](#)^c, [Inflammatory disorder of lower respiratory tract](#)^c, [Neoplasm of lower respiratory tract](#)^c

Disorder of lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051610>

has super-classes

[Disorder of lower respiratory system](#)^c, [Disorder of thorax](#)^c, [Lung finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lesion of lung](#)^c, [Pneumonitis](#)^c

Disorder of male genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003230>

has super-classes

[Disorder of male reproductive system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of prostate](#)^c, [Neoplasm of male genital organ](#)^c

Disorder of male reproductive system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003153>

has super-classes

[Disorder of pelvic region of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of male genital organ](#)^c

Disorder of nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052560>

has super-classes

[Disorder of body system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hereditary disorder of nervous system](#)^c, [Neoplasm of nervous system](#)^c

Disorder of pelvic region of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003077>

has super-classes

[Disorder of abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)^c, [Finding of pelvic region of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anorectal disorder](#)^c, [Disorder of female reproductive system](#)^c, [Disorder of male reproductive system](#)^c, [Disorder of pelvis](#)^c

Disorder of pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003387>

has super-classes

[Disorder of pelvic region of trunk](#)^c, [Finding of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of prostate](#)^c, [Disorder of rectum](#)^c, [Disorder of uterus](#)^c, [Neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c

Disorder of pigmentation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053138>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of skin pigmentation](#)^c, [Melanosis](#)^c

Disorder of pleura and pleural cavity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051708>

has super-classes

[Disorder of thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Pleural effusion](#)^c

Disorder of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002783>

has super-classes

[Disorder of abdomen](#)^c, [Disorder of male genital organ](#)^c, [Disorder of pelvis](#)^c, [Prostate finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hyperplasia of prostate](#)^c, [Lesion of prostate](#)^c, [Neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Disorder of rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051127>

has super-classes

[Disorder of large intestine](#)^c, [Disorder of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lesion of rectum](#)^c

Disorder of respiratory system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051220>

has super-classes

[Disorder of body system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of lower respiratory system](#)^c, [Tumor of respiratory system](#)^c

Disorder of retroperitoneum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052406>

has super-classes

[Disorder of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Kidney disease](#)^c

Disorder of skin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059067>

has super-classes

[Disorder of skin and/or subcutaneous tissue](#)^c, [Skin finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Skin retraction](#)^c, [Thickening of skin](#)^c

Disorder of skin and/or subcutaneous tissue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052488>

has super-classes

[Disorder of body system](#)^c, [Disorder of integument](#)^c, [Disorder of soft tissue](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of skin](#)^c

Disorder of skin pigmentation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053181>

has super-classes

[Disorder of pigmentation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hyperpigmentation of skin](#)^c, [Lentigo](#)^c

Disorder of soft tissue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052613>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of skin and/or subcutaneous tissue](#)^c

Disorder of the urinary system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052641>

has super-classes

[Urinary system finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of kidney and/or ureter](#)^c

Disorder of thoracic segment of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037168>

has super-classes

[Disorder of trunk](#)^c, [Finding of upper trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of thorax](#)^c

Disorder of thorax^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037210>

has super-classes

[Disorder of thoracic segment of trunk](#)^c, [Finding of region of thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chest injury](#)^c, [Disorder of breast](#)^c, [Disorder of lung](#)^c, [Disorder of pleura and pleural cavity](#)^c, [Neoplasm of thorax](#)^c

Disorder of thyroid gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059396>

has super-classes

[Disorder of endocrine system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of thyroid gland](#)^c

Disorder of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002928>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c, [Finding of trunk structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)^c, [Disorder of thoracic segment of trunk](#)^c, [Neoplasm of trunk](#)^c

Disorder of uterus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003154>

has super-classes

[Disorder of abdomen](#)^c, [Disorder of female genital organs](#)^c, [Disorder of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lesion of uterus](#)^c

Disorder of vagina^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003150>

has super-classes

[Disorder of female genital organs](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Vaginal lesion](#)^c

Dissection of lymph node^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049783>

has super-classes

[Operation on lymph node](#)^c

Distant Metastasis (NOS)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031222>

has super-classes

[Metastasis](#)^c

Distant metastasis present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059641>

has super-classes

[Tumor finding](#)^c

Distributions^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002278>

has super-classes

[Descriptor](#)^c, [Special disorder atoms](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Focal](#)^c, [Multicentric](#)^c, [Multifocal](#)^c, [Unifocal](#)^c

DNA mismatch repair protein Msh3 [Presence] in Cancer specimen by Immune stain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051986>

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c

Docetaxel^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035856>

A semi-synthetic, second-generation taxane derived from a compound found in the European yew tree, *Taxus baccata*. Docetaxel displays potent and broad antineoplastic properties; it binds to and stabilizes tubulin, thereby inhibiting microtubule disassembly which results in cell-cycle arrest at the G2/M phase and cell death. This agent also inhibits pro-angiogenic factors such as vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and displays

immunomodulatory and pro-inflammatory properties by inducing various mediators of the inflammatory response. Docetaxel has been studied for use as a radiation-sensitizing agent. (NCI04)

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c, [Immunologic agent](#)^c

Docetaxel Injection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033193>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Domain: Condition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000067>

has super-classes

[OMOP](#)^c

Domain: Drug^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000100>

has super-classes

[OMOP](#)^c

Domain: Meas Value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000058>

has super-classes

[OMOP](#)^c

Domain: Measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000050>

has super-classes

[OMOP](#)^c

Domain: Observation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000043>

has super-classes

[OMOP](#)^c

Domain: Person^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000027>

has super-classes

[OMOP](#)^c

Domain: Procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000088>

has super-classes

[OMOP](#)^c

Domain: Spec Anatomic Site^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000077>

has super-classes

[OMOP](#)^c

Domain: Specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000068>

has super-classes

[OMOP](#)^c

Domain: Unit^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000047>

has super-classes

[OMOP](#)^c

Don't know/refused^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001150>

has super-classes

[Number of cigarettes per day](#)^c

dose area product^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016636>

has super-classes

[radiation exposure measure](#)^c

Doxorubicin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035838>

An anthracycline antibiotic with antineoplastic activity. Doxorubicin, isolated from the bacterium *Streptomyces peucetius* var. *caesius*, is the hydroxylated congener of daunorubicin. Doxorubicin intercalates between base pairs in the DNA helix, thereby preventing DNA replication and ultimately inhibiting protein synthesis. Additionally, doxorubicin inhibits topoisomerase II which results in an increased and stabilized cleavable enzyme-DNA linked complex during DNA replication and subsequently prevents the ligation of the nucleotide strand after double-strand breakage. Doxorubicin also forms oxygen free radicals resulting in cytotoxicity secondary to lipid peroxidation of cell membrane lipids; the formation of oxygen free radicals also contributes to the toxicity of the anthracycline antibiotics, namely the cardiac and cutaneous vascular effects. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Doxorubicin liposomal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035845>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Drug measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1008873>

has super-classes

[Measurement of substance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hormone measurement](#)^c, [Measurement of level of drug in blood](#)^c

Drug observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050886>

has super-classes

[Drug therapy observable](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Delivered radiation dose](#) ^c

Drug or medicament^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034110>

has super-classes

[Medication](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[ANTINEOPLASTIC AND IMMUNOMODULATING AGENTS](#) ^c, [Abemaciclib](#) ^c, [Alkylating agent](#) ^c, [Antineoplastic agent](#) ^c, [Carbamazepine Injection](#) ^c, [Chemotherapy protective agent](#) ^c, [Docetaxel Injection](#) ^c, [Doxorubicin liposomal](#) ^c, [FOLFIRI](#) ^c, [FOLFIRINOX](#) ^c, [FOLFOX](#) ^c, [Fulvestrant](#) ^c, [Granulocyte colony-stimulating factor](#) ^c, [Hormone](#) ^c, [Immunologic agent](#) ^c, [Immunotherapeutic agent](#) ^c, [Palbociclib](#) ^c, [Sacituzumab govitecan](#) ^c, [TDMI](#) ^c, [Tamoxifen](#) ^c, [Trastuzumab deruxtecan](#) ^c, [floxuridine](#) ^c

Drug therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1014762>

has super-classes

[Administration of medication](#) ^c, [Therapeutic procedure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Chemotherapy Regimen](#) ^c, [Combined chemotherapy and radiation therapy](#) ^c, [Hormone therapy](#) ^c

Drug therapy observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050876>

has super-classes

[Observable entity](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Drug observable](#) ^c

Drug-induced^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002583>

has super-classes

[Pathogeneses](#) ^c

Drug-induced disorder of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036803>

has super-classes

[Disease of liver](#) ^c, [Drug-related disorder](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Alcoholic liver damage](#) ^c

Drug-induced gastrointestinal disturbance^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059074>

has super-classes

[Disorder of gastrointestinal tract](#) ^c, [Drug-related disorder](#) ^c

Drug-induced lesion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037010>

has super-classes

[Drug-related disorder](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Alcoholic liver damage](#)^c

Drug-induced pneumonitis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059082>

has super-classes

[Drug-related disorder](#)^c, [Pneumonitis](#)^c

Drug-related disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036443>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder caused by alcohol](#)^c, [Drug-induced disorder of liver](#)^c, [Drug-induced gastrointestinal disturbance](#)^c, [Drug-induced lesion](#)^c, [Drug-induced pneumonitis](#)^c

Dual-energy CT^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016768>

has super-classes

[Computed tomography](#)^c

DUCT CARCINOMA/ Invasive carcinoma of no special type^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047035>

is equivalent to

[Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS](#)^c

has super-classes

[Ductal and lobular neoplasms](#)^c

Duct changes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051844>

[BI-RADS] US: Manifested by cystic dilation of a duct or ducts involving irregularities in caliber and/or arborization, extension of duct(s) to or from a malignant mass, or the presence of an intraductal mass, thrombus, or detritus. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Mechanical disorder](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Duct ectasia](#)^c

Duct ectasia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051842>

has super-classes

[Duct changes](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Mammary duct ectasia](#)^c

Ductal and lobular neoplasms^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046985>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[DUCT CARCINOMA/ Invasive carcinoma of no special type](#)^c, [Infiltrating duct and lobular carcinoma](#)^c, [Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS](#)^c, [Infiltrating duct mixed with other types of carcinoma](#)^c, [Intraductal carcinoma and lobular carcinoma in situ](#)^c, [Intraductal carcinoma](#),

[noninfiltrating, NOS](#)^c, [Lobular carcinoma in situ, NOS](#)^c, [Lobular carcinoma, NOS](#)^c

Ductal carcinoma in situ, solid type^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045782>

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#)^c

Ductal carcinoma in situ, solid type of breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021458>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Ductal, lobular AND/OR medullary neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049124>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Infiltrating carcinoma with ductal and lobular features](#)^c, [Infiltrating duct carcinoma](#)^c, [Lobular carcinoma](#)^c, [Non-infiltrating intraductal carcinoma](#)^c

Durvalumab^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036186>

A monoclonal antibody directed against B7H1 (B7 homolog 1; programmed cell death ligand 1) with potential immunostimulating activity. Upon intravenous administration, durvalumab binds to the cell surface antigen B7H1, thereby blocking B7H1 signaling. This may activate the immune system to exert a cytotoxic T-lymphocyte (CTL) response against B7H1-expressing tumor cells. B7H1, a member of the B7 protein superfamily and a negative regulator of cytokine synthesis, is overexpressed on certain tumor cell types. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004461>

An imaging method with a timed series of T1-weighted images used to detect and measure signal intensity change (enhancement) over time following administration of intravenous contrast agent to noninvasively access tissue vascular characteristics. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c

Dynamic nuclear imaging acquisition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016760>

has super-classes

[Nuclear imaging acquisition](#)^c

Dyslipidemia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036520>

has super-classes

[Disorder of lipoprotein AND/OR lipid metabolism](#)^c

Dysplasia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016582>

has super-classes

[Growth alteration](#)^c, [Lesion](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Dysplastic nodule](#)^c

Dysplastic nodule^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016592>

has super-classes

[Dysplasia](#)^c, [Nodule](#)^c

Dyspnea^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051877>

has super-classes

[Difficulty breathing](#)^c

Dysuria^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000353>

has super-classes

[Urinary tract pain](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Scalding pain on urination](#)^c

E - Extrahepatic marker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044445>

has super-classes

[Markers for liver tumor staging](#)^c

Ear^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000163>

A sense organ needed for the detection of sound and for establishing balance. The outer ear consists of the auricle, the ear canal as well as the tympanic membrane. The middle ear is made up of an air-filled cavity behind the tympanic membrane that contains the ossicles (malleus, incus and stapes). The inner ear is made up of the cochlea needed for hearing and the vestibular apparatus required for balance. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Auricular region structure](#)^c, [Ear, nose and throat structure](#)^c, [Structure of peripheral auditory system](#)^c

Ear, nose and throat structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000155>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Ear](#)^c

Early arterial phase^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016762>

has super-classes

[Arterial phase](#)^c

Early venous phase^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016765>

has super-classes

[Postarterial phase](#)^c

Ease of respiration - finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051873>

has super-classes

[Finding of respiration](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Difficulty breathing](#)^c

Echinococcosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036322>

has super-classes

[Disease due to Taeniidae](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Echinococcosis of liver](#)^c

Echinococcosis of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045766>

has super-classes

[Echinococcosis](#)^c, [Infection of liver caused by parasite](#)^c

Echo planar^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016664>

has super-classes

[MR Echo Type](#)^c

Echo time^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016641>

has super-classes

[MR procedure attribute](#)^c

Echogenicity characteristic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016606>

has super-classes

[Modality-related characteristic](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anechoic](#)^c, [Complex cystic and solid echogenicity](#)^c, [Heterogenously echogenic](#)^c, [Hyperechoic](#)^c, [Hypoechoic](#)^c, [Isoechoic](#)^c

ECOG performance status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043685>

has super-classes

[General physical performance status](#)^c

ECOG performance status - grade 0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024768>

has super-classes

[ECOG performance status finding](#)^c

ECOG performance status - grade 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024850>

has super-classes

[ECOG performance status finding](#)^c

ECOG performance status - grade 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024933>

has super-classes

[ECOG performance status finding](#)^c

ECOG performance status - grade 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1025017>

has super-classes

[ECOG performance status finding](#)^c

ECOG performance status - grade 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1025102>

has super-classes

[ECOG performance status finding](#)^c

ECOG performance status - grade 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1025188>

has super-classes

[ECOG performance status finding](#)^c

ECOG performance status finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015980>

has super-classes

[General clinical state finding](#)^c, [Performance Status Assessment Answer Finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ECOG performance status - grade 0](#)^c, [ECOG performance status - grade 1](#)^c, [ECOG performance status - grade 2](#)^c, [ECOG performance status - grade 3](#)^c, [ECOG performance status - grade 4](#)^c, [ECOG performance status - grade 5](#)^c

ECOG Performance Status score^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004580>

A performance status scale designed to assess disease progression and its affect on the daily living abilities of the patient. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Performance Status Assessment](#)^c

Edema^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051008>

has super-classes

[Fluid disturbance](#)^c

is in domain of

[EdemaVolumeValue](#)^{dp}

Edema^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051862>

Abnormal fluid accumulation in tissues or body cavities. Most cases of edema are present under the skin in subcutaneous tissue. [MeSH] [BI-RADS MRI: Trabecular thickening with associated skin thickening. US: Increased echogenicity of surrounding tissue and reticulation (angular network of hypochoic lines). [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c, [Fluid disorder](#)^c

Edema Volume^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1003885>

has super-classes

[Volumetric Imaging Criteria](#)^c

Edition of American Joint Commission on Cancer, Cancer Staging Manual used for TNM staging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045761>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

Effective dose^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016612>

The sum of the equivalent doses to all organs in the body, each adjusted to account for the sensitivity of the organ to radiation. Effective dose is calculated for the whole body. Effective dose is expressed in millisieverts (mSv). [RBO]

has super-classes

[Radiation dose](#)^c

EGFR gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051882>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

Electrons^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001178>

has super-classes

[Modality radiation value](#)^c

Eloquent Brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016750>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Eloquent Brain Areas^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000438>

Areas of the brain that control speech, motor functions, and sensory processing which are required for an individual to understand and interact with others and the environment. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brain stem](#)^c, [Cerebellar nucleus](#)^c, [Cerebellar peduncle](#)^c, [Internal capsule](#)^c, [Motor area](#)^c, [Motor cortex](#)^c, [Structure of Broca's area](#)^c, [Structure of Brodmann areas 17 \(striate cortex\), 18 \(parastriate cortex\) and 19 \(peristriate cortex\) of the occipital lobe](#)^c, [Thalamus](#)^c, [Wernicke's area](#)^c

Elsaint^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000055>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Embryonal neuroepithelial tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000113>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neuroblastoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Emphysema^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051049>

has super-classes

[Gas retention](#)^c

Encapsulated papillary carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049677>

has super-classes

[Carcinoma in situ \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Solid papillary carcinoma in situ](#)^c

Endocrine gland structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000243>

has super-classes

[Structure of endocrine system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adrenal gland](#)^c, [Thyroid and/or parathyroid structures](#)^c

ENDOCRINE THERAPY^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001605>

has super-classes

[ANTINEOPLASTIC AND IMMUNOMODULATING AGENTS](#)^c

has sub-classes

[HORMONE ANTAGONISTS AND RELATED AGENTS](#)^c, [HORMONES AND RELATED AGENTS](#)^c

endoluminal coil^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016644>

has super-classes

[internally inserted coil](#)^c

has sub-classes

[endorectal coil](#)^c

endorectal coil^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016643>

has super-classes
[endoluminal coil](#)^c

Endoscopic operation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003713>

has super-classes
[Endoscopic procedure](#)^c, [Surgical procedure](#)^c
has sub-classes
[Robotic assisted surgery](#)^c

Endoscopic procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003630>

has super-classes
[Endoscopy](#)^c
has sub-classes
[Endoscopic operation](#)^c, [Laparoscopic procedure](#)^c

Endoscopy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018535>

has super-classes
[Inspection](#)^c
has sub-classes
[Endoscopic procedure](#)^c

Energy and stamina finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051848>

has super-classes
[Metabolic finding](#)^c
has sub-classes
[Fatigue](#)^c

Enhancement pattern^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005498>

has super-classes
[Imaging observation](#)^c, [Tumor Observation](#)^c
has sub-classes
[Background parenchymal enhancement pattern](#)^c, [Enhancing](#)^c, [Nonenhancing](#)^c, [Spatial enhancement pattern](#)^c

enhancement phase^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016757>

has super-classes
[Imaging procedure property](#)^c
has sub-classes
[Arterial phase](#)^c, [Delayed phase](#)^c, [Postarterial phase](#)^c

Enhancement Quality^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016743>

has super-classes
[VASARICriteria](#)^c

Enhancement Quality value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016743>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Marked](#)^c, [Mild](#)^c, [Minimal](#)^c, [No contrast enhancement](#)^c, [No contrast injected](#)^c, [None](#)^c

Enhancing^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005495>

has super-classes

[Enhancement pattern](#)^c

Enhancing margin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016736>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Enhancing margin value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016736>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Poorly defined](#)^c, [Well defined](#)^c

Enhancing tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016513>

A well-defined area of unequivocally increased signal intensity on MRI or CT scan images compared with the normal-appearing surrounding tissues, following intravenous injection of an enhancing agent. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Radiologic finding](#)^c

is in domain of

[EnhancingTumorVolumeValue](#)^{dp}

Enhancing tumor Crosses Midline^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016727>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Enhancing tumor Crosses Midline value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016727>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[No](#)^c, [Yes](#)^c

Enhancing Tumor Volume^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1003887>

has super-classes

[Volumetric Imaging Criteria](#)^c

Enterectomy with anastomosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056728>

has super-classes

[Anastomosis of intestine](#)^c, [Excision of intestinal structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Proctectomy and anastomosis of colon to anus](#)^c

Entire^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002502>

has super-classes

[Extensiveness](#)^c

Entire body region^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000145>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

Entire breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000264>

has super-classes

[Breast structure](#)^c

Entire Broca's area^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000387>

has super-classes

[Structure of Broca's area](#)^c

Entire cerebral cingulum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000408>

has super-classes

[Structure of cerebral cingulum](#)^c

Entire colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063648>

has super-classes

[Colon structure](#)^c

Entire face and neck^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000292>

has super-classes

[Face and/or neck structure](#)^c

Entire limb^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000152>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Arm](#)^c

Entire ovary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063725>

has super-classes

[Ovary](#)^c

Entire thyroid gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000288>

has super-classes

[Thyroid](#)^c

Entire uterus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000296>

has super-classes

[Uterus](#)^c

Entire vulva^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000402>

has super-classes

[Vulva](#)^c

Enzyme level - finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018612>

has super-classes

[Protein level - finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Prostate specific antigen normal](#)^c

Enzyme measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1012788>

has super-classes

[Measurement of substance](#)^c, [Protein measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lactate dehydrogenase measurement](#)^c, [Measurement of liver enzyme](#)^c, [Prostate specific antigen measurement](#)^c

enzyme unit per liter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001956>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

enzyme unit per milliliter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001959>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

Ependymal Extension^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016722>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Ependymal Extension value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016722>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Absent](#)^c, [No](#)^c, [Present](#)^c, [Yes](#)^c

Epirubicin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035841>

A 4'-epi-isomer of the anthracycline antineoplastic antibiotic doxorubicin. Epirubicin intercalates into DNA and inhibits topoisomerase II, thereby inhibiting DNA replication and ultimately, interfering with RNA and protein synthesis. This agent also produces toxic free-radical intermediates and interacts with cell membrane lipids causing lipid peroxidation. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Episode^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000002>

A high-level temporal entity with start and end time during which specific clinical processes occur (e.g., diagnosis, treatment, remission).

has super-classes

[Event](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Active Surveillance](#)^c, [Diagnosis](#)^c, [Progression](#)^c, [Relapse](#)^c, [Remission](#)^c, [Treatment](#)^c

is in domain of

[SequenceNumber](#)^{dp}, [hasEpisodeEventRelatedEntity](#)^{op}

Epithelial neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049113>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenoma AND/OR adenocarcinoma](#)^c, [Benign epithelial neoplasm](#)^c, [Carcinoma in situ \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Complex epithelial neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Squamous cell neoplasm](#)^c, [Transitional cell neoplasm](#)^c

Epithelial neoplasms, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049546>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS](#)^c, [Large cell carcinoma, NOS](#)^c, [Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma](#)^c, [Non-small cell carcinoma](#)^c, [Small cell carcinoma, NOS](#)^c

Epithelioid glioblastoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000069>

has super-classes

[Glioblastoma](#)^c

ER negative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048920>

The absence of detectable estrogen receptor alpha in a tissue sample. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

([Has Associated Tumor Marker Test](#)^{op} some [Estrogen receptor Ag \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c) and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} only [Negative](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Hormone receptor negative neoplasm](#)^c

ER positive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046663>

An indication that estrogen receptor alpha expression has been detected in a sample. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

([Has Associated Tumor Marker Test](#)^{op} some [Estrogen receptor Ag \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c) and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} only [Positive](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Hormone receptor positive tumor](#)^c

ERBB2 gene duplication [Presence] in Breast cancer specimen by FISH^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045805>

A fluorescent in situ hybridization-based procedure that detects ERBB2 gene duplications in a breast cancer specimen. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Molecular pathology](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

ERBB2 Gene Mutation measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063268>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ERBB2 gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c

ERBB2 gene mutations found [Identifier] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051896>

has super-classes

[ERBB2 Gene Mutation measurement](#)^c

ERBB2 Gene Variant measurement (HER2)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063266>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

Eribulin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035880>

An analogue of halichondrin B, a substance derived from a marine sponge (*Lissodendoryx* sp.) with antineoplastic activity. Eribulin binds to the vinca domain of tubulin and inhibits the polymerization of tubulin and the assembly of microtubules, resulting in inhibition of mitotic spindle assembly, induction of cell cycle arrest at G2/M phase, and, potentially, tumor regression. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Esaote^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000049>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Esophagus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000303>

has super-classes

[Digestive organ structure](#)^c, [ICDO3Topography](#)^c

Estrogen receptor Ag [Presence] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045815>

An immune staining procedure that detects estrogen receptor in a breast cancer specimen. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[Intensity of stain of estrogen receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)^c

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

Ethnic group^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040046>

has super-classes

[Demographic history detail](#)^c

Ethnicity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001058>

has super-classes

[National Public Health Classification data](#)^c

has sub-classes

[African](#)^c, [Arab](#)^c, [Asian Indian](#)^c, [Chinese](#)^c, [Hispanic or Latino](#)^c, [Not Hispanic or Latino](#)^c, [Other Hispanic/Latino/Spanish](#)^c, [White](#)^c

is in range of

[hasEthnicity](#)^{op}

European^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001322>

has super-classes

[White](#)^c

EuroSpine Morbidity state^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001192>

LOINC: - ANSWER LIST CODE: LL5905-6 - ANSWER LIST NAME: EuroSpine Morbidity state

has super-classes

[Performance Status Assessment Answer Value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ASA1 \(no disturbance\)](#)^c, [ASA2 \(mild/moderate\)](#)^c, [ASA3 \(severe\)](#)^c, [ASA4 \(life threatening\)](#)^c, [ASA5 \(moribund\)](#)^c

Evaluation finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002372>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abnormal finding on evaluation procedure](#)^c, [Biopsy finding](#)^c, [Finding of immune status](#)^c, [Genetic finding](#)^c, [Histopathology finding](#)^c,
[Imaging finding](#)^c, [Measurement finding](#)^c, [Microscopic specimen observation](#)^c

Evaluation of gastrointestinal tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004143>

has super-classes

[Evaluation procedure](#)^c

Evaluation of test results^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004144>

has super-classes

[Evaluation procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Laboratory data interpretation](#)^c

Evaluation of urine specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050486>

has super-classes

[Evaluation procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Urine substance measurement](#)^c

Evaluation procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004055>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Evaluation of gastrointestinal tract](#)^c, [Evaluation of test results](#)^c, [Evaluation of urine specimen](#)^c, [Examination by method](#)^c, [Laboratory test](#)^c,
[Measurement](#)^c, [Monitoring of patient](#)^c

Event^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000003>

has super-classes

[Generic Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adverse Event](#)^c, [Episode](#)^c, [Treatment](#)^c

Evidence Type^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000016>

has super-classes

[Generic Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anatomic pathology procedure](#)^c, [Cytologic test](#)^c, [Histologic test](#)^c, [Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c, [Laboratory data interpretation](#)^c, [Physical examination](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

is in range of

[hasEvidenceType](#)^{op}

Ex-drinker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056334>

has super-classes

[Non - drinker](#)^c

Ex-smoker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059047>

has super-classes

[Non-smoker](#)^c

Exam^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000019>

has super-classes

[Observation Category](#)^c

Examination by method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004232>

has super-classes

[Evaluation procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Digital examination](#)^c, [Inspection](#)^c, [Palpation](#)^c, [Physical examination](#)^c

Examination of abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1010667>

has super-classes

[Procedure on abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Palpation of abdomen](#)^c, [Rectal examination](#)^c

Excision^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004598>

has super-classes

[Surgical removal](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Complete excision](#)^c, [Excision of head structure](#)^c, [Excision of lung or bronchus](#)^c, [Excision of mass](#)^c, [Immune system excision](#)^c, [Lobectomy](#)^c, [Local excision](#)^c, [Lymphatic system excision](#)^c, [Radical excision](#)^c, [Reexcision](#)^c, [Trunk excision](#)^c

Excision of abdominal lymph node^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004883>

has super-classes

[Abdomen excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of pelvic lymph node](#)^c

Excision of axillary lymph node^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056890>

has super-classes

[Excision of regional lymph nodes](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of axillary lymph nodes group](#)^c

Excision of axillary lymph nodes group^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056910>

has super-classes

[Excision of axillary lymph node](#)^c, [Excision of group of lymph nodes](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Level 1 axillary clearance of lymph nodes](#)^c, [Level 2 axillary clearance of lymph nodes](#)^c, [Level 3 axillary clearance of lymph nodes](#)^c

Excision of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004597>

has super-classes

[Excision of head structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lobectomy of brain](#)^c

Excision of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034672>

has super-classes

[Operation on breast](#)^c, [Thorax excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of lesion of breast](#)^c, [Partial mastectomy](#)^c, [Radical mastectomy](#)^c, [Re-excision of breast for clearance of tumor margins](#)^c, [Simple mastectomy](#)^c, [Subcutaneous mastectomy](#)^c

Excision of breast tissue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056953>

has super-classes

[Operation on breast](#)^c, [Thorax excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Partial mastectomy](#)^c, [Radical mastectomy](#)^c, [Re-excision of breast for clearance of tumor margins](#)^c, [Simple mastectomy](#)^c, [Subcutaneous mastectomy](#)^c

Excision of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057025>

has super-classes

[Operation on colon](#)^c, [Partial excision of large intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Partial resection of colon](#)^c, [Total colectomy](#)^c

Excision of group of lymph nodes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057078>

has super-classes

[Excision of lymph node](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of axillary lymph nodes group](#)^c

Excision of head structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004596>

has super-classes

[Excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of brain](#)^c

Excision of intestinal structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057106>

has super-classes

[Abdomen excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Enterectomy with anastomosis](#)^c, [Large intestine excision](#)^c

Excision of lesion of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057135>

has super-classes

[Excision of breast](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of mass of breast](#)^c

Excision of lesion of large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057228>

has super-classes

[Large intestine excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of lesion of rectum](#)^c, [Excision of polyp of large intestine](#)^c

Excision of lesion of rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057261>

has super-classes

[Excision of lesion of large intestine](#)^c, [Resection of rectum](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of lesion of rectum by transanal approach](#)^c, [Rectal polypectomy](#)^c

Excision of lesion of rectum by transanal approach^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057330>

has super-classes

[Excision of lesion of rectum](#)^c, [Excision of rectum by transanal approach](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of malignant tumor of rectum by transanal approach](#)^c

Excision of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000243>

has super-classes

[Abdomen excision](#)^c

Excision of lung or bronchus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056853>

has super-classes

[Excision](#)^c, [Operation on lower respiratory tract](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung excision](#)^c

Excision of lymph node^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051004>

has super-classes

[Immune system excision](#)^c, [Lymphatic system excision](#)^c, [Operation on lymph node](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of group of lymph nodes](#)^c, [Excision of regional lymph nodes](#)^c

Excision of malignant lesion of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057480>

has super-classes

[Excision of malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Trunk excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of malignant tumor of rectum by transanal approach](#)^c

Excision of malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057441>

has super-classes

[Excision of neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of malignant lesion of trunk](#)^c

Excision of malignant tumor of rectum by transanal approach^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060391>

has super-classes

[Excision of lesion of rectum by transanal approach](#)^c, [Excision of malignant lesion of trunk](#)^c, [Excision of mass of pelvic region](#)^c

Excision of mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057366>

has super-classes

[Excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of mass of breast](#)^c, [Excision of mass of pelvic region](#)^c, [Excision of neoplasm](#)^c, [Resection of polyp](#)^c

Excision of mass of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057165>

has super-classes

[Excision of lesion of breast](#)^c, [Excision of mass](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lumpectomy of breast](#)^c

Excision of mass of pelvic region^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057520>

has super-classes

[Excision of mass](#)^c, [Operation on pelvic region of trunk](#)^c, [Trunk excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of malignant tumor of rectum by transanal approach](#)^c, [Rectal polypectomy](#)^c

Excision of neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057403>

has super-classes

[Excision of mass](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Excision of pelvic lymph node^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004980>

has super-classes

[Excision of abdominal lymph node](#) ^c, [Excision of pelvis](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Block dissection of pelvic lymph nodes](#) ^c

Excision of pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005078>

has super-classes

[Operation on pelvic region of trunk](#) ^c, [Operative procedure on pelvis](#) ^c, [Trunk excision](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of pelvic lymph node](#) ^c, [Prostatectomy](#) ^c, [Resection of rectum](#) ^c, [Sigmoid colectomy](#) ^c

Excision of polyp of large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057295>

has super-classes

[Excision of lesion of large intestine](#) ^c, [Resection of polyp](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Rectal polypectomy](#) ^c

Excision of rectum by transanal approach^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057603>

has super-classes

[Resection of rectum](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of lesion of rectum by transanal approach](#) ^c

Excision of regional lymph nodes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056871>

has super-classes

[Excision of lymph node](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of axillary lymph node](#) ^c

Exemestane^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036066>

An irreversible steroidal aromatase inhibitor, with antiestrogen and antineoplastic activities. Upon oral administration, exemestane binds irreversibly to and inhibits the enzyme aromatase, thereby blocking the peripheral aromatization of androgens, including androstenedione and testosterone, to estrogens. This lowers estrogen levels in the blood circulation. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#) ^c

Expression Negative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052163>

has super-classes

[Negative Test Result](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[MKI67 Negative](#) ^c

Expression Positive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052178>

has super-classes

[Positive Laboratory Test Result](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MK167 Positive](#)^c

Extensiveness^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002323>

has super-classes

[Extents](#)^c, [Special disorder atoms](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Entire](#)^c, [Limited](#)^c, [Local](#)^c, [Maximal](#)^c, [Minimal](#)^c, [Partial](#)^c

Extent of Resection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1004576>

has super-classes

[Resection](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Complete Resection](#)^c, [Gross Total Resection](#)^c, [Subtotal Resection](#)^c

Extents^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002312>

has super-classes

[Descriptor](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Extensiveness](#)^c

External beam radiation therapy procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005277>

has super-classes

[Radiotherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[External beam radiation therapy using electrons](#)^c, [External beam radiation therapy using photons](#)^c, [External radiation therapy using superficial radiation](#)^c, [Neutron capture therapy](#)^c, [Stereotactic radiotherapy](#)^c, [Three dimensional external beam radiation therapy](#)^c, [Two dimensional external beam radiation therapy](#)^c, [Ultra high dose rate radiotherapy](#)^c

External beam radiation therapy using electrons^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057646>

has super-classes

[External beam radiation therapy procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[IOERT - intraoperative electron radiotherapy](#)^c

External beam radiation therapy using photons^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005273>

has super-classes

[External beam radiation therapy procedure](#)^c

External radiation therapy using superficial radiation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005278>

has super-classes

[External beam radiation therapy procedure](#) ^c

Extramural vein invasion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1041767>

has super-classes

[Pathology](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Extramural vein invasion](#) | [Colorectal cancer specimen](#) | [Pathology](#) ^c

Extramural vein invasion [Presence] in Colorectal cancer specimen by Light microscopy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045796>

has super-classes

[Extramural vein invasion](#) | [Colorectal cancer specimen](#) | [Pathology](#) ^c

Extramural vein invasion | Colorectal cancer specimen | Pathology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1041872>

has super-classes

[Extramural vein invasion](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Extramural vein invasion \[Presence\] in Colorectal cancer specimen by Light microscopy](#) ^c

Extraprostatic Extension (EPE)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033248>

has super-classes

[Tumor extension finding](#) ^c

Extraprostatic extension of tumor present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049699>

has super-classes

[Tumor extension finding](#) ^c

Extreme fibroglandular tissue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016684>

has super-classes

[Tissue composition](#) ^c

Extremely dense^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016693>

[BI-RADS] >75% glandular [RadLex]

has super-classes

[High density](#) ^c

Extremity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000171>

A body region referring to an upper or lower extremity. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Body part structure](#) ^c, [Structure of half of body lateral to midsagittal plane](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Arm](#)^c, [Extremity part](#)^c, [Structure of long bone of lower limb](#)^c

Extremity part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000083>

has super-classes

[Extremity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lower extremity part](#)^c, [Lymph node structure of limb](#)^c, [Upper extremity part](#)^c

Eye region structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000231>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of orbital region](#)^c

Face^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000293>

has super-classes

[Face and/or neck structure](#)^c

Face and/or neck structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000098>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c, [Head and neck](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Entire face and neck](#)^c, [Face](#)^c, [Neck](#)^c

Facilitated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002286>

has super-classes

[Behavior descriptors](#)^c, [Diffusion Characteristics value](#)^c

Facilitated diffusion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005449>

has super-classes

[Diffusion Characteristics](#)^c, [Diffusion weighted imaging](#)^c

Fairly heavy drinker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056342>

has super-classes

[Current drinker](#)^c

False^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000035>

has super-classes

[Boolean value](#)^c

Family history of breast cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048389>

has super-classes

[Family history of cancer^c](#), [Family history of neoplasm of breast^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Family history of malignant neoplasm of breast at under age 50 in second degree relative^c](#), [Family history of malignant neoplasm of breast diagnosed before 45 years of age^c](#), [Family history of malignant neoplasm of breast in first degree relative^c](#)

Family history of cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048388>

["A record of a patient's medical background regarding the cancer and cancer-related problems of blood relatives."]

has super-classes

[Family history of neoplasm^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Family history of breast cancer^c](#), [Family history of malignant neoplasm of genital structure^c](#)

Family history of clinical finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1029073>

has super-classes

[Family history with explicit context^c](#), [Finding suspected or known present^c](#), [Finding with explicit context^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Family history of disorder^c](#)

Family history of disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037960>

has super-classes

[Family history of clinical finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[FH: Breast disease^c](#), [FH: Genitourinary disease^c](#), [Family history of endocrine disorders^c](#), [Family history of neoplasm^c](#)

Family history of endocrine disorders^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052700>

has super-classes

[Family history of disorder^c](#)

has sub-classes

[FH: neoplasm of ovary^c](#)

Family history of female genital tract disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052763>

has super-classes

[FH: Genitourinary disease^c](#)

has sub-classes

[FH: neoplasm of ovary^c](#)

Family history of malignant neoplasm of breast at under age 50 in second degree relative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048385>

has super-classes

[Family history of breast cancer^c](#)

Family history of malignant neoplasm of breast diagnosed before 45 years of age^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048384>

has super-classes

[Family history of breast cancer](#)^c

Family history of malignant neoplasm of breast in first degree relative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048386>

has super-classes

[Family history of breast cancer](#)^c

Family history of malignant neoplasm of genital structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051870>

has super-classes

[FH: Genitourinary disease](#)^c, [Family history of cancer](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Family history of malignant neoplasm of ovary](#)^c, [Family history of prostate cancer](#)^c

Family history of malignant neoplasm of ovary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051867>

has super-classes

[FH: neoplasm of ovary](#)^c, [Family history of malignant neoplasm of genital structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Family history of malignant neoplasm of ovary in first degree relative](#)^c, [Family history of malignant neoplasm of ovary in second degree relative](#)^c

Family history of malignant neoplasm of ovary in first degree relative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051868>

has super-classes

[Family history of malignant neoplasm of ovary](#)^c

Family history of malignant neoplasm of ovary in second degree relative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051869>

has super-classes

[Family history of malignant neoplasm of ovary](#)^c

Family history of neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038018>

has super-classes

[Family history of disorder](#)^c

has sub-classes

[FH: neoplasm of female genital organ](#)^c, [FH: neoplasm of male genital organ](#)^c, [Family history of cancer](#)^c, [Family history of neoplasm of breast](#)^c

Family history of neoplasm of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048387>

has super-classes

[FH: Breast disease](#)^c, [Family history of neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Family history of breast cancer](#)^c

Family history of prostate cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051866>

has super-classes

[EH: neoplasm of male genital organ](#)^c, [Family history of malignant neoplasm of genital structure](#)^c

Family history unknown^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1029197>

has super-classes

[Family history with explicit context](#)^c, [Finding with explicit context](#)^c

Family history with explicit context^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018692>

has super-classes

[Situation with explicit context](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Family history of clinical finding](#)^c, [Family history unknown](#)^c, [No family history of clinical finding](#)^c

Father^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001035>

has super-classes

[Parent](#)^c

Fatigue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051847>

has super-classes

[Energy and stamina finding](#)^c

Fatty^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1010770>

has super-classes

[Morphologic descriptor](#)^c

Feet first orientation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016709>

has super-classes

[Patient Orientation](#)^c

FEMALE^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000178>

is equivalent to

[Female](#)^c

has super-classes

[Gender](#)^c

is disjoint with

[MALE](#)^c

Female^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001370>

has super-classes

[Sex assigned at birth](#)^c

is disjoint with

[Male](#)^c

Female (finding)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001370>

has super-classes

[Finding related to biological sex](#)^c

Female genital organ structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000267>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Vagina](#)^c

Female genital tract functions^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043933>

has super-classes

[Sexual function](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Menopause, function](#)^c

Female genital tract structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000210>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Uterus](#)^c, [Vulva](#)^c

Female genitalia finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039388>

has super-classes

[Finding of pelvic region of trunk](#)^c, [Genital finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Mass of female genital structure](#)^c, [Premenopause - Menopause absent](#)^c

Female reproductive finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053888>

has super-classes

[Functional finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Menstruation finding](#)^c

FH: Breast disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052796>

has super-classes

[Family history of disorder](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Family history of neoplasm of breast](#)^c

FH: Genitourinary disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052731>

has super-classes

[Family history of disorder^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Family history of female genital tract disorder^c](#), [Family history of malignant neoplasm of genital structure^c](#)

FH: neoplasm of female genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051864>

has super-classes

[Family history of neoplasm^c](#)

has sub-classes

[FH: neoplasm of ovary^c](#)

FH: neoplasm of male genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051863>

has super-classes

[Family history of neoplasm^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Family history of prostate cancer^c](#)

FH: neoplasm of ovary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051865>

has super-classes

[FH: neoplasm of female genital organ^c](#), [Family history of endocrine disorders^c](#), [Family history of female genital tract disorder^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Family history of malignant neoplasm of ovary^c](#)

FHIR^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000002>

has super-classes

[Correspondence^c](#)

has sub-classes

[ResourceType: Condition^c](#), [ResourceType: Diagnostic Report^c](#), [ResourceType: Measurement^c](#), [ResourceType: Medication^c](#), [ResourceType: Medication Administration^c](#), [ResourceType: Observation^c](#), [ResourceType: Patient^c](#), [ResourceType: Procedure^c](#)

Fibroepithelial neoplasms^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063600>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Phyllodes tumor, malignant^c](#)

Fibrolamellar hepatocellular carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043567>

A distinctive type of liver cell carcinoma that arises in non-cirrhotic livers and is seen predominantly in young patients. The tumor cells are polygonal and deeply eosinophilic, and are embedded in a fibrous stroma. The prognosis is similar to classical hepatocellular carcinoma that arises in non-cirrhotic livers, and better than hepatocellular carcinoma that arises in cirrhotic livers. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Liver cell carcinoma^c](#)

Fibromatous neoplasms^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049534>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Myxofibrosarcoma](#)^c

Fibrosis of lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000160>

has super-classes

[Lesion of lung](#)^c

FIGO grade 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022115>

has super-classes

[Grade 1 tumor](#)^c

FIGO grade 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022116>

has super-classes

[Grade 2 tumor](#)^c

FIGO grade 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022117>

has super-classes

[Grade 3 tumor](#)^c

FIGO ovarian tumor staging system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044310>

has super-classes

[FIGO staging system of gynecological malignancy](#)^c

FIGO Stage 0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000424>

has super-classes

[Stage 0](#)^c

FIGO Stage 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000425>

has super-classes

[Stage 1](#)^c

FIGO Stage 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000426>

has super-classes

[Stage 2](#)^c

FIGO Stage 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000427>

has super-classes

[Stage 3](#)^c

FIGO Stage 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000428>

has super-classes

[Stage 4](#)^c

FIGO staging system of gynecological malignancy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044306>

has super-classes

[Tumor staging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[FIGO Vaginal tumor staging system](#)^c, [FIGO ovarian tumor staging system](#)^c

FIGO Vaginal tumor staging system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044307>

has super-classes

[FIGO staging system of gynecological malignancy](#)^c

Final^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001213>

has super-classes

[Annotation Status](#)^c

Finding context value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001066>

has super-classes

[Context values](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Known](#)^c, [Unknown](#)^c, [Unspecified](#)^c

Finding of abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000272>

has super-classes

[Finding of abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdominal mass](#)^c, [Abdominal organ finding](#)^c, [Disorder of abdomen](#)^c, [Prostate finding](#)^c

Finding of abdominopelvic segment of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000263>

has super-classes

[Finding of trunk structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Finding of abdomen](#)^c, [Urogenital finding](#)^c

Finding of American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052866>

has super-classes

[Performance Status Assessment Answer Finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ASA physical status class 1](#)^c, [ASA physical status class 2](#)^c, [ASA physical status class 3](#)^c, [ASA physical status class 4](#)^c, [ASA physical status class 5](#)^c, [ASA physical status class 6](#)^c

Finding of blood, lymphatics and immune system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051679>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of cellular component of blood](#)^c

Finding of bowel action^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050797>

has super-classes

[Finding of defecation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Altered bowel function](#)^c

Finding of bowel continence^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018773>

has super-classes

[Finding of defecation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bowels: fully continent](#)^c, [Incontinence of feces](#)^c

Finding of change compared to previous radiologic examination^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016335>

has super-classes

[Radiologic finding](#)^c

Finding of change compared to previous radiologic examination finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016597>

has super-classes

[Radiologic finding](#)^c

Finding of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051280>

has super-classes

[Finding of large intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of colon](#)^c, [Mass of colon](#)^c

Finding of color of skin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059068>

has super-classes

[Skin finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Discoloration of skin](#)^c

Finding of defecation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1006222>

has super-classes

[Functional finding of gastrointestinal tract](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Finding of bowel action](#)^c, [Finding of bowel continence](#)^c

Finding of frequency of urination^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000359>

has super-classes

[Finding of pattern of urination](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Increased frequency of urination](#)^c

Finding of grade^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052830>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[National Cancer Institute common terminology criteria for adverse event grade finding](#)^c

Finding of Hepatitis B status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048038>

has super-classes

[Finding of immune status](#)^c

Finding of Hepatitis C status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049081>

has super-classes

[Measurement finding](#)^c

Finding of histologic grading differentiation AND/OR behavior^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052901>

has super-classes

[General pathology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Tumor invasion finding](#)^c

Finding of immune status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038863>

has super-classes

[Evaluation finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Finding of Hepatitis B status](#)^c

Finding of large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018855>

has super-classes

[Bowel finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bowels: fully continent](#)^c, [Disorder of large intestine](#)^c, [Finding of colon](#)^c, [Rectum finding](#)^c

Finding of lesion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002438>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Tumor finding](#)^c

Finding of pattern of urination^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000360>

has super-classes

[Micturition finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Finding of frequency of urination](#)^c

Finding of pelvic region of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005583>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of pelvic region of trunk](#)^c, [Female genitalia finding](#)^c, [Finding of pelvis](#)^c, [Incontinence](#)^c, [Pain in pelvis](#)^c

Finding of pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005687>

has super-classes

[Finding of pelvic region of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of pelvis](#)^c, [Pelvic mass](#)^c, [Pelvic organ finding](#)^c, [Rectum finding](#)^c

Finding of region of thorax^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037087>

has super-classes

[Finding of upper trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast finding](#)^c, [Chest pain](#)^c, [Disorder of thorax](#)^c, [Lung finding](#)^c, [Mass of thoracic structure](#)^c

Finding of respiration^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051872>

has super-classes

[Respiratory finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Ease of respiration - finding](#)^c

Finding of sexual function^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018938>

has super-classes

[Functional finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abnormal sexual function](#)^c, [Normal sexual function](#)^c, [Sexual function painful](#)^c

Finding of substance level^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005792>

has super-classes

[Measurement finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Protein level - finding](#)^c

Finding of thickness of skin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055011>

has super-classes

[Skin finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Thick skin](#)^c, [Thin skin](#)^c

Finding of tobacco use and exposure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056330>

has super-classes

[Health-related behavior finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cigarettes pack-years smoked during life](#)^c, [Tobacco smoking behavior - finding](#)^c, [Tobacco user](#)^c

Finding of trunk structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000255>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of trunk](#)^c, [Finding of abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)^c, [Finding of upper trunk](#)^c

Finding of upper trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037048>

has super-classes

[Finding of trunk structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of thoracic segment of trunk](#)^c, [Finding of region of thorax](#)^c

Finding of urinary bladder emptying^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000362>

has super-classes

[Functional finding](#)^c, [Micturition finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Incomplete emptying of urinary bladder](#)^c

Finding of urinary tract proper^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000355>

has super-classes

[Urinary system finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Urinary tract pain](#)^c

Finding of urinary tract proper^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1006005>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

Finding related to ability to pass urine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000365>

has super-classes

[Micturition finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Difficulty passing urine](#)^c

Finding related to biological sex^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038792>

has super-classes

[General clinical state finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Female \(finding\)](#)^c, [Male \(finding\)](#)^c

Finding related to menstrual cycle^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054065>

has super-classes

[Menstruation finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Premenopausal state](#)^c

Finding relating to alcohol drinking behavior^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056331>

has super-classes

[Health-related behavior finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Current drinker](#)^c, [Non - drinker](#)^c

Finding status values^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000182>

has super-classes

[Finding value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Change values](#)^c, [Subjects of information](#)^c

Finding suspected or known present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016013>

has super-classes

[Finding with explicit context](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Family history of clinical finding](#)^c, [History of clinical finding in subject](#)^c

Finding value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000181>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#)^c, [Completeness](#)^c, [Degree findings](#)^c, [Finding status values](#)^c,
[Increased](#)^c, [Normality findings](#)^c, [Presence findings](#)^c, [Undetermined](#)^c

is in range of

[hasAnswer](#)^{op}, [hasInterpretationValue](#)^{op}, [hasResultValue](#)^{op}

Finding with explicit context^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1013593>

has super-classes

[Situation with explicit context](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Family history of clinical finding](#)^c, [Family history unknown](#)^c, [Finding suspected or known present](#)^c, [History of clinical finding in subject](#)^c,
[No family history of clinical finding](#)^c

Fine needle aspiration biopsy of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001936>

has super-classes

[Needle biopsy of prostate](#)^c

Fine needle aspiration of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001715>

has super-classes

[Fine needle biopsy](#)^c, [Non-surgical breast biopsy](#)^c

Fine needle biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001714>

has super-classes

[Needle biopsy](#)^c, [Non-surgical biopsy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Fine needle aspiration of breast](#)^c

First degree^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001361>

has super-classes

[Degrees of severity](#)^c

First degree blood relative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001049>

has super-classes

[Blood relative](#)^c

First line treatment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060571>

has super-classes

[Procedure by intent](#)^c

FLAIR^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016654>

has super-classes

[Imaging sequence](#)^c, [Tissue Contrast](#)^c

Flow of urine - finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000367>

has super-classes

[Micturition finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Strength of stream of urine - finding](#)^c, [Urine stream interrupted](#)^c

Flowsheet - laboratory^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN103823>

has super-classes

[Laboratory procedure](#)^c, [Measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alanine aminotransferase|Catalytic Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Albumin|Protein.total|Mass Fraction|Urine](#)^c, [Alkaline phosphatase|Catalytic Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Aspartate aminotransferase|Catalytic Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Calcium|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cancer Ag 15-3|Arbitrary Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Carcinoembryonic Ag|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cholesterol.in HDL|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cholesterol.in LDL|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cholesterol|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cortisol|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Creatinine|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Any Urine specimen](#)^c, [Creatinine|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Creatinine|Mass Concentration|Urine](#)^c, [Glucose|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Hemoglobin A1c|Hemoglobin.total|Mass Fraction|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Natriuretic peptide.B|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Platelets|Number Concentration \(count/vol\)|Moment in time|Blood](#)^c, [Potassium|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Prostate specific Ag|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Sodium|Substance Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Thyroglobulin Ab|Arbitrary Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Thyrotropin|Arbitrary Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Triglyceride|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Urate|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Urea|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c

floxuridine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063649>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Fluid disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051840>

has super-classes

[Mechanical disorder](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Edema](#)^c

Fluid disturbance^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051006>

has super-classes

[Mechanical abnormality](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Edema](#)^c

Fluid sample albumin measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050465>

has super-classes

[Albumin measurement](#)^c, [Measurement of substance in specimen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Urine albumin measurement](#)^c

Fluorescence imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016138>

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c

Fluoroscopy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000041>

has super-classes

[Radiographic imaging - action](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MR fluoroscopy](#)^c, [Radiofluoroscopy](#)^c

Fluorouracil^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035901>

An antimetabolite fluoropyrimidine analog of the nucleoside pyrimidine with antineoplastic activity. Fluorouracil and its metabolites possess a number of different mechanisms of action. In vivo, fluorouracil is converted to the active metabolite 5-fluorouridylic acid (F-UMP); replacing uracil, F-UMP incorporates into RNA and inhibits RNA processing, thereby inhibiting cell growth. Another active metabolite, 5-fluoro-2'-deoxyuridine-5'-O-monophosphate (F-dUMP), inhibits thymidylate synthase, resulting in the depletion of thymidine triphosphate (TTP), one of the four nucleotide triphosphates used in the in vivo synthesis of DNA. Other fluorouracil metabolites incorporate into both RNA and DNA; incorporation into RNA results in major effects on both RNA processing and functions. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c, [Immunologic agent](#)^c

Focal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002409>

has super-classes

[Distributions](#)^c, [Multifocal or Multicentric value](#)^c

focal damage^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016594>

has super-classes

[Damage](#)^c

Focal nodular hyperplasia of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047651>

A non-neoplastic, regenerating hepatocellular hyperplasia, secondary to the presence of focal vascular abnormalities in the liver. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Disease of liver](#)^c

FOLFIRI^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036303>

A regimen consisting of leucovorin, fluorouracil and irinotecan (FOLFIRI), plus ziv-aflibercept that is used for the treatment of appendiceal adenocarcinoma and colorectal cancer. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

FOLFIRINOX^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036306>

A regimen consisting of fluorouracil, irinotecan, leucovorin and oxaliplatin that can be used for the treatment of pancreatic and colorectal cancers; occult primary, ampullary, appendiceal and small bowel adenocarcinomas; well-differentiated grade 3 neuroendocrine tumors (NETs), and extrapulmonary poorly differentiated neuroendocrine carcinoma, large or small cell carcinoma and mixed neuroendocrine-non-neuroendocrine neoplasm. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

FOLFOX^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036301>

One of several chemotherapy regimens that include leucovorin calcium (calcium folinate), 5-fluorouracil and oxaliplatin and which may be used in the treatment of advanced-stage and metastatic colorectal cancer. FOLFOX regimens differ in agent dosing and administration schedule and include FOLFOX 4, FOLFOX 6, modified FOLFOX 6 (mFOLFOX 6) and FOLFOX 7. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Follicular adenocarcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049459>

is equivalent to

[Follicular carcinoma, NOS](#)^c

has super-classes

[Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Follicular carcinoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049604>

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#)^c

Follow-up^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001952>

has super-classes

[Timepoint](#)^c

Follow-up Examination After Treatment for Malignant Neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047417>

An evaluation of a patient that follows their treatment for a malignant neoplasm. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Medical Assessment](#)^c

Follow-up status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035758>

has super-classes

[Administrative statuses](#)^c

Foot^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000020>

The structure found below the ankle joint. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Structure of ankle and/or foot](#)^c

Formations^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002042>

has super-classes

[Descriptor](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cystic](#)^c, [Nodular](#)^c, [Non-solid](#)^c, [Partially solid](#)^c, [Solid](#)^c

Fotemustine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035873>

has super-classes

[Alkylating agent](#)^c

Free prostate specific antigen level^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022987>

has super-classes

[Prostate specific antigen measurement](#)^c

Free:total PSA ratio^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1023043>

has super-classes

[Prostate specific antigen measurement](#)^c

French Federation of Cancer Centers Sarcoma Group (FNCLCC) grading system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037302>

has super-classes

[Histological grading systems](#)^c

Frequencies^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001338>

has super-classes

[Time patterns](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Never](#)^c, [Regular frequency](#)^c

Frequency interval^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001347>

has super-classes

[Regular frequency](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intervals of weeks and months](#)^c

Frontal brain region^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000420>

has super-classes

[Brain region](#)^c, [Structure of subregion of head](#)^c

Frontal lobe^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000351>

has super-classes

[Brain](#)^c, [Brain Lesion Site](#)^c

Fujifilm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000060>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Fulvestrant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035832>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Function^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043688>

has super-classes

[Observable entity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast function](#)^c, [Sexual function](#)^c

Functional finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002505>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bladder control - finding](#)^c, [Female reproductive finding](#)^c, [Finding of sexual function](#)^c, [Finding of urinary bladder emptying](#)^c, [Functional finding of gastrointestinal tract](#)^c, [Impaired urinary system function](#)^c

Functional finding of gastrointestinal tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1006113>

has super-classes

[Functional finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Finding of defecation](#)^c

Functional magnetic resonance imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004464>

has super-classes

[Magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c

gen1000029^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000029>

has super-classes

[Generic Category](#)^c

G1 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001750>

is equivalent to

[G1: Well differentiated](#)^c

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical grade allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological grade allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer yp grade allowable value](#)^c

G1: Well differentiated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002679>

Describes tumor cells that generally retain the appearance of normal cells and tend to grow and spread at a slower rate than undifferentiated or poorly differentiated tumor cells. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Histological grades](#)^c

G2 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001755>

is equivalent to

[G2: Moderately differentiated](#)^c

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical grade allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological grade allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer yp grade allowable value](#)^c

G2: Moderately differentiated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002684>

Describes tumor cells that have lost some of the appearance of normal cells. They tend to grow and spread at a faster rate than well differentiated tumor cells. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Histological grades](#)^c

G3 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001761>

is equivalent to

[G3: Poorly differentiated](#)^c

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical grade allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological grade allowable value](#)^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer yp grade allowable value](#)^c

G3: Poorly differentiated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002690>

Describes tumor cells that generally have lost most of the appearance of normal cells. They tend to grow and spread. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Histological grades](#)^c

G4 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001751>

is equivalent to

[G4: Undifferentiated](#)^c

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical grade allowable value](#) ^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological grade allowable value](#) ^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer yp grade allowable value](#) ^c

G4: Undifferentiated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002697>

Describes tumor cells that generally have lost all of the appearance of normal cells. They tend to grow and spread quickly and aggressively. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Histological grades](#) ^c

G5 - American Joint Committee on Cancer grade G5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001752>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical grade allowable value](#) ^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological grade allowable value](#) ^c, [American Joint Committee on Cancer yp grade allowable value](#) ^c

Gallbladder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000142>

A pear-shaped organ located under the liver that stores and concentrates bile secreted by the liver. From the gallbladder the bile is delivered through the bile ducts into the intestine thereby aiding the digestion of fat-containing foods. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Biliary tract structure](#) ^c, [ICDO3Topography](#) ^c, [Structure of organ within abdomen proper cavity](#) ^c

Gamma glutamyl transferase [Enzymatic activity/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033810>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#) ^c, [Gamma glutamyl transferase measurement](#) ^c

Gamma glutamyl transferase measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050757>

has super-classes

[Measurement of liver enzyme](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Gamma glutamyl transferase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#) ^c

Gas retention^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051025>

has super-classes

[Retention](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Emphysema](#) ^c

Gastrointestinal anastomosis procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056715>

has super-classes

[Gastrointestinal and digestive anastomosis](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Anastomosis of intestine](#) ^c

Gastrointestinal and digestive anastomosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056710>

has super-classes

[Construction of anastomosis](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Gastrointestinal anastomosis procedure](#) ^c

Gastrointestinal and digestive injury^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036713>

has super-classes

[Disorder of digestive system](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Liver damage](#) ^c

Gastrointestinal obstruction^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051735>

has super-classes

[Disorder of gastrointestinal tract](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Intestinal obstruction](#) ^c

Gastrointestinal tract finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1006332>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#) ^c, [Digestive system finding](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Bowel finding](#) ^c, [Disorder of gastrointestinal tract](#) ^c

Gastrointestinal tract structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063476>

has super-classes

[Digestive tract part](#) ^c

Gemcitabine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035926>

A broad-spectrum antimetabolite and deoxycytidine analogue with antineoplastic activity. Upon administration, gemcitabine is converted into the active metabolites difluorodeoxycytidine diphosphate (dFdCDP) and difluorodeoxycytidine triphosphate (dFdCTP) by deoxycytidine kinase. dFdCTP competes with deoxycytidine triphosphate (dCTP) and is incorporated into DNA. This locks DNA polymerase thereby resulting in "masked termination" during DNA replication. On the other hand, dFdCDP inhibits ribonucleotide reductase, thereby decreasing the deoxynucleotide pool available for DNA synthesis. The reduction in the intracellular concentration of dCTP potentiates the incorporation of dFdCTP into DNA. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#) ^c, [Immunologic agent](#) ^c

Gender^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000175>

has super-classes

[Common Module](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[FEMALE](#) ^c, [MALE](#) ^c, [Non Binary](#) ^c, [Transgender](#) ^c

is in range of

[hasGender](#) ^{op}

Gene deletion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052071>

has super-classes

[Molecular pathology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[18q chromosome deletion \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c

Gene mutation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1042523>

has super-classes

[Molecular pathology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ALK gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c, [ATM \(ATM serine/threonine kinase\).gene variant](#)^c, [ATRX \(ATRX chromatin remodeler\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [ATRX gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c, [BRAF \(B-Raf proto-oncogene, serine/threonine kinase\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [BRCA1 \(BRCA1 DNA repair associated\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [BRCA1+BRCA2 gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c, [BRCA2 \(BRCA2 DNA repair associated\).gene variant](#)^c, [CDH1 \(cadherin 1\).gene variant](#)^c, [CHEK2 \(checkpoint kinase 2\).gene variant](#)^c, [EGFR gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c, [ERBB2 Gene Mutation measurement](#)^c, [ERBB2.Gene Variant measurement \(HER2\)](#)^c, [IDH1 \(isocitrate dehydrogenase \(NADP\(±\)\)1\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [IDH1 gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c, [IDH2 \(isocitrate dehydrogenase \(NADP\(±\)\)2\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [KRAS \(KRAS proto-oncogene, GTPase\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [MET gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c, [MGMT \(O-6-methylguanine-DNA methyltransferase\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [MGMT gene methylation \[Presence\] in Tissue by Molecular genetics method](#)^c, [MKI67 \(marker of proliferation Ki-67\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [NBN \(nibrin\).gene variant](#)^c, [NF1 Gene Mutation](#)^c, [NRAS Gene Mutation measurement](#)^c, [PALB2 \(partner and localizer of BRCA2\).gene variant](#)^c, [PIK3CA gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c, [PTEN Gene Mutation](#)^c, [RET gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c, [STK11 \(serine/threonine kinase 11\).gene variant](#)^c, [TERT \(telomerase reverse transcriptase\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [TGFBR1 gene+TGFBR2 gene targeted mutation analysis in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method](#)^c, [TP53 \(tumor protein p53\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [TP53 Gene Mutation](#)^c, [TP53 gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c

Gene rearrangement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051909>

has super-classes

[Molecular pathology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chromosome region 6q22 rearrangements in Tissue by FISH](#)^c

General adjectival modifier^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000033>

has super-classes

[Adjectival modifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Active](#)^c, [Benign](#)^c, [Binary](#)^c, [Boolean value](#)^c, [Derived](#)^c, [Inactive](#)^c, [Inadequate](#)^c, [Indeterminate](#)^c, [Low](#)^c, [Malignant](#)^c, [Mixed](#)^c, [Multifocal](#)^c, [Positive](#)^c, [Primary](#)^c, [Spontaneous](#)^c, [Thick](#)^c

General body state finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045487>

has super-classes

[General finding of observation of patient](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Surviving free of recurrence of neoplastic disease](#)^c

General clinical stage for disease AND/OR neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002670>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Histologic grading differentiation AND/OR behavior](#)^c

General clinical state^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043687>

has super-classes

[Observable entity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[General physical performance status](#)^c

General clinical state finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002573>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alive](#)^c, [Dead](#)^c, [ECOG performance status finding](#)^c, [Finding related to biological sex](#)^c

General Electric^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000047>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

General finding of observation of patient^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045218>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[General body state finding](#)^c, [General problem AND/OR complaint](#)^c

General pathology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049714>

has super-classes

[Histopathology finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Finding of histologic grading differentiation AND/OR behavior](#)^c, [Pathology examination findings present](#)^c

General physical performance status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043686>

has super-classes

[General clinical state](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ECOG performance status](#)^c

General problem AND/OR complaint^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045352>

has super-classes

[General finding of observation of patient](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Co-morbid conditions](#)^c

Generic anatomical site tumor invasion status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044436>

has super-classes

[Cancer staging](#)^c, [Malignant tumor staging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[H+](#)^c, [Lung involvement stages](#)^c

Generic Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000011>

Possible values are: Observation, Condition, Measurement, Medication, Procedure

has super-classes

[Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Procedure](#)^c, [g e n1000029](#)^c

is in domain of

[hasGenericCategory](#)^{op}

Generic Module^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000001>

This module defines categories required for the semantic integration with the EUCAIM CDM

has sub-classes

[Category](#)^c, [Event](#)^c, [Evidence Type](#)^c, [Tumor Observation](#)^c, [Tumor Size Method](#)^c

Generic tumor staging descriptor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044435>

has super-classes

[Cancer staging](#)^c, [Malignant tumor staging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[TNM tumor staging classifications](#)^c, [Tumor histopathological grade status values](#)^c

Genetic disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052263>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hereditary disease](#)^c

Genetic finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034515>

has super-classes

[Evaluation finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Genetic finding detected](#)^c, [Genetic finding not detected](#)^c

Genetic finding detected^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034544>

has super-classes

[Genetic finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast cancer genetic marker of susceptibility detected](#)^c

Genetic finding not detected^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034605>

has super-classes

[Genetic finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast cancer genetic marker of susceptibility not detected](#)^c

Genetic test^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034460>

has super-classes

[Laboratory test](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Molecular genetic test](#)^c

Genital finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1041357>

has super-classes

[Urogenital finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Female genitalia finding](#)^c

Genitourinary sample^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1006443>

has super-classes

[Human Specimen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Specimen from genital system](#)^c

Giant cell glioblastoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000073>

has super-classes

[Glioblastoma](#)^c

Giant cell glioblastoma of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007994>

has super-classes

[Glioblastoma multiforme of brain](#)^c

Glandular zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000149>

has super-classes

[Region of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Central zone of prostate](#)^c, [Peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Gleason finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022077>

has super-classes

[Tumor finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 1^c](#), [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 2^c](#), [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 3^c](#), [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 4^c](#), [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 5^c](#), [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 1^c](#), [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 2^c](#), [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 3^c](#), [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 4^c](#), [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 5^c](#), [Primary Gleason Pattern 1^c](#), [Primary Gleason Pattern 2^c](#), [Primary Gleason Pattern 3^c](#), [Primary Gleason Pattern 4^c](#), [Primary Gleason Pattern 5^c](#), [Primary pattern unknown, secondary pattern unknown^c](#), [Secondary Gleason Pattern 1^c](#), [Secondary Gleason Pattern 2^c](#), [Secondary Gleason Pattern 3^c](#), [Secondary Gleason Pattern 4^c](#), [Secondary Gleason Pattern 5^c](#)

Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016047>

has super-classes

[Tumor finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Gleason grade group 1^c](#), [Gleason grade group 2^c](#), [Gleason grade group 3^c](#), [Gleason grade group 4^c](#), [Gleason grade group 5^c](#), [Gleason grade score 10 out of 10^c](#), [Gleason grade score 2 out of 10^c](#), [Gleason grade score 3 out of 10^c](#), [Gleason grade score 4 out of 10^c](#), [Gleason grade score 5 out of 10^c](#), [Gleason grade score 6 out of 10^c](#), [Gleason grade score 7 out of 10^c](#), [Gleason grade score 8 out of 10^c](#), [Gleason grade score 9 out of 10^c](#)

Gleason grade group 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1025275>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer^c](#)

Gleason grade group 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1025363>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer^c](#)

Gleason grade group 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1025452>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer^c](#)

Gleason grade group 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1025542>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer^c](#)

Gleason grade group 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1025633>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer^c](#)

Gleason grade score 10 out of 10^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1025725>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer](#)^c

Gleason grade score 2 out of 10^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1025818>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer](#)^c

Gleason grade score 3 out of 10^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1025912>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer](#)^c

Gleason grade score 4 out of 10^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1026007>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer](#)^c

Gleason grade score 5 out of 10^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1026103>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer](#)^c

Gleason grade score 6 out of 10^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1026200>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer](#)^c

Gleason grade score 7 out of 10^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1026298>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer](#)^c

Gleason grade score 8 out of 10^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1026397>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer](#)^c

Gleason grade score 9 out of 10^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1026497>

has super-classes

[Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer](#)^c

Gleason grading system for prostatic cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037295>

has super-classes

[Histological grading systems](#)^c

Gleason pattern^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049689>

has super-classes

[Histologic grade of primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary Gleason pattern](#)^c, [Secondary Gleason pattern](#)^c

Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022267>

is equivalent to

[Primary Gleason Pattern 1](#)^c

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 1 tumor](#)^c, [Primary Gleason pattern](#)^c

Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022308>

is equivalent to

[Primary Gleason Pattern 2](#)^c

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 2 tumor](#)^c, [Primary Gleason pattern](#)^c

Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022350>

is equivalent to

[Primary Gleason Pattern 3](#)^c

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 3 tumor](#)^c, [Primary Gleason pattern](#)^c

Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022393>

is equivalent to

[Primary Gleason Pattern 4](#)^c

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 4 tumor](#)^c, [Primary Gleason pattern](#)^c

Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022528>

is equivalent to

[Primary Gleason Pattern 5](#)^c

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Primary Gleason pattern](#)^c

Gleason score^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049688>

has super-classes

[Histologic grade of primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Gleason scoring system for malignant neoplasm of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037294>

has super-classes

[Histological grading systems](#)^c

Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022575>

is equivalent to

[Secondary Gleason Pattern 1](#)^c

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 1 tumor](#)^c, [Secondary Gleason pattern](#)^c

Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022623>

is equivalent to

[Secondary Gleason Pattern 2](#)^c

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 2 tumor](#)^c, [Secondary Gleason pattern](#)^c

Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022672>

is equivalent to

[Secondary Gleason Pattern 3](#)^c

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 3 tumor](#)^c, [Secondary Gleason pattern](#)^c

Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022722>

is equivalent to

[Secondary Gleason Pattern 4](#)^c

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 4 tumor](#)^c, [Secondary Gleason pattern](#)^c

Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022773>

is equivalent to

[Secondary Gleason Pattern 5](#)^c

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Secondary Gleason pattern](#)^c

Glioblastoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000067>

has super-classes

[High grade glioma](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Epithelioid glioblastoma](#)^c, [Giant cell glioblastoma](#)^c

Glioblastoma multiforme^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007990>

The most malignant astrocytic tumor (WHO grade 4). It is composed of poorly differentiated neoplastic astrocytes and is characterized by the presence of cellular polymorphism, nuclear atypia, brisk mitotic activity, vascular thrombosis, microvascular proliferation, and necrosis. It typically affects adults and is preferentially located in the cerebral hemispheres. (Adapted from WHO) [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Glioma](#)^c, [Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glioblastoma multiforme of central nervous system](#)^c, [Glioblastoma, NOS, of nervous system, NOS](#)^c

Glioblastoma multiforme of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007993>

has super-classes

[Glioblastoma multiforme of central nervous system](#)^c, [Malignant glioma of brain](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Giant cell glioblastoma of brain](#)^c

Glioblastoma multiforme of central nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007992>

has super-classes

[Glioblastoma multiforme](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glioblastoma multiforme of brain](#)^c

Glioblastoma, NOS, of nervous system, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007991>

has super-classes

[Glioblastoma multiforme](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of nervous system](#)^c

Glioma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007995>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glioblastoma multiforme](#)^c

Glioma (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049102>

has super-classes

[Central nervous system tumor morphology](#)^c

Gliomatosis cerebri^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000302>

A diffuse glial tumor which infiltrates the brain extensively, involving more than two lobes. It is frequently bilateral and often extends to the infratentorial structures, even to the spinal cord. It is probably of astrocytic origin, although GFAP expression may be scant or absent. (Adapted from WHO.) [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Malignant glioma](#)^c

Gliomatosis cerebri^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007971>

has super-classes

[Malignant glioma of brain](#)^c

Gliosarcoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000082>

has super-classes

[Malignant glioma](#)^c, [Sarcoma](#)^c

Globulin measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050570>

has super-classes

[Protein measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[C-reactive protein measurement](#)^c, [Thyroglobulin measurement](#)^c

Glucose [Mass/volume] in Venous blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033440>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#)^c, [Glucose measurement, blood](#)^c, [Glucose measurement, quantitative](#)^c, [Glucose|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Glucose|Moment in time|Blood venous|180.156 g/mole](#)^c

Glucose measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050528>

has super-classes

[Carbohydrate measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glucose measurement, blood](#)^c, [Glucose measurement, quantitative](#)^c

Glucose measurement, blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050614>

has super-classes

[Glucose measurement](#)^c, [Measurement of level of substance in blood](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glucose \[Mass/volume\] in Venous blood](#)^c

Glucose measurement, quantitative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050592>

has super-classes

[Glucose measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glucose \[Mass/volume\] in Venous blood](#)^c

Glucose|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049849>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glucose \[Mass/volume\] in Venous blood](#)^c

Glucose|Moment in time|Blood venous|180.156 g/mole^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050161>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glucose \[Mass/volume\] in Venous blood](#)^c

Glycoproteins measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1041978>

has super-classes

[Protein measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cancer antigen 15-3 measurement](#)^c

Gonadotropin releasing hormone analogues^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021450>

has super-classes

[HORMONES AND RELATED AGENTS](#)^c

Grade 1 on a scale of 0 to 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001386>

is equivalent to

([Answer of](#)^{op} some [Miller and Payne Classification](#)^c) and ([hasEquivalentPathologicClassification](#)^{op} some [No response \(NR\)](#)^c or [ypT2](#)^c or [ypT4](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Numeric grade on a scale 0 to 5](#)^c

Grade 1 tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022113>

has super-classes

[Tumor grade](#)^c

has sub-classes

[FIGO grade 1](#)^c, [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 1](#)^c, [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 1](#)^c, [Nottingham Grade 1](#)^c, [Primary Gleason Pattern 1](#)^c, [Secondary Gleason Pattern 1](#)^c

Grade 2 on a scale of 0 to 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001385>

has super-classes

[Numeric grade on a scale 0 to 5](#)^c

Grade 2 tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022150>

has super-classes

[Tumor grade](#)^c

has sub-classes

[FIGO grade 2](#)^c, [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 2](#)^c, [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 2](#)^c, [Nottingham Grade 2](#)^c, [Primary Gleason Pattern 2](#)^c, [Secondary Gleason Pattern 2](#)^c

Grade 3 on a scale of 0 to 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001384>

is equivalent to

([Answer of](#)^{op} some [Miller and Payne Classification](#)^c) and ([hasEquivalentPathologicClassification](#)^{op} some [Partial response \(PR\)](#)^c or [ypT1](#)^c or [ypT2](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Numeric grade on a scale 0 to 5](#)^c

Grade 3 tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022188>

has super-classes

[Tumor grade](#)^c

has sub-classes

[FIGO grade 3](#)^c, [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 3](#)^c, [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 3](#)^c, [Nottingham Grade 3](#)^c, [Primary Gleason Pattern 3](#)^c, [Secondary Gleason Pattern 3](#)^c

Grade 4 on a scale of 0 to 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001383>

has super-classes

[Numeric grade on a scale 0 to 5](#)^c

Grade 4 tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022227>

has super-classes

[Tumor grade](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 4](#)^c, [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 4](#)^c, [Primary Gleason Pattern 4](#)^c, [Secondary Gleason Pattern 4](#)^c

Grade 5 on a scale of 0 to 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001382>

is equivalent to

([Answer of](#)^{op} some [Miller and Payne Classification](#)^c) and ([hasEquivalentPathologicClassification](#)^{op} some [Complete response \(CR\)](#)^c or ([ypN0](#)^c and [ypT0](#)^c) or ([ypN0](#)^c and [ypTis](#)^c))

has super-classes

[Numeric grade on a scale 0 to 5](#)^c

Grade cannot be assessed (GX); Unknown^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002705>

has super-classes

[Histological grades](#)^c

Grade group 1 (Gleason score 3 + 3 = 6)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001355>

is equivalent to

[Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 3](#)^c and [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 3](#)^c

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 1](#)^c

Grade group 2 (Gleason score 3 + 4 = 7)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001343>

is equivalent to

[Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 3](#)^c and [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 4](#)^c

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 2](#)^c

Grade group 3 (Gleason score 4 + 3 = 7)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001341>

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 3](#) ^c

Grade group 4 (Gleason score 3 + 5 = 8)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001358>

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 4](#) ^c

Grade group 4 (Gleason score 4 + 4 = 8)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001357>

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 4](#) ^c

Grade group 4 (Gleason score 5 + 3 = 8)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001356>

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 4](#) ^c

Grade group 5 (Gleason score 4 + 5 = 9)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001359>

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 5](#) ^c

Grade group 5 (Gleason score 5 + 4 = 9)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001354>

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 5](#) ^c

Grade group 5 (Gleason score 5 + 5 = 10)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001352>

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 5](#) ^c

Grade Pathological^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037301>

has super-classes

[Staging and scales](#) ^c

Grades^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001353>

has super-classes

[Ranked categories](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Histological grades](#) ^c, [Numeric grade](#) ^c, [Severities](#) ^c

Gradient echo^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016663>

has super-classes

[MR Echo Type](#)^c

gram per deciliter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001963>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

Granulocyte colony-stimulating factor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035830>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Gravida^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048535>

has super-classes

[Measure of pregnancy](#)^c

Gross examination and sampling of tissue specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035079>

has super-classes

[Sampling of tissue specimen](#)^c, [Tumor Size Method](#)^c

Gross Total Resection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004587>

Surgical removal of an entire visible lesion, with no obvious lesion detected on post-operative evaluation; microscopic residual disease may be present. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Extent of Resection](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brain@Gross total resection of lobe of brain \(lobectomy\)](#)^c

Gross total resection of lobe of brain (lobectomy) |(Tumor involves more than half of lobe)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1004569>

has super-classes

[Surgical resection status](#)^c

Growth alteration^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016565>

has super-classes

[Morphologically abnormal structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Dysplasia](#)^c, [Proliferation](#)^c, [Tumor budding](#)^c

GSTP1 gene+APC gene methylation [Presence] in Tissue by Molecular genetics method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052134>

has super-classes

[Molecular pathology](#)^c

GX: Histologic grade cannot be assessed^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001371>

is equivalent to

[Grade cannot be assessed \(GX\); Unknown^c](#)

has super-classes

[Histological grades^c](#)

Gy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001950>

has super-classes

[Unit of radiation dose^c](#)

H+^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044440>

has super-classes

[Generic anatomical site tumor invasion status^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Markers for liver tumor staging^c](#)

Haemorrhage Volume^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1003886>

has super-classes

[Volumetric Imaging Criteria^c](#)

Hamartoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052938>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm and/or hamartoma^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Congenital hamartoma^c](#), [Hamartoma of intestine^c](#), [Lentiginosis^c](#)

Hamartoma (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063522>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm and/or hamartoma \(morphologic abnormality\)^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Hamartomatous polyp^c](#), [Lentigo^c](#)

Hamartoma of intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052236>

has super-classes

[Abdominal mass^c](#), [Disorder of intestine^c](#), [Hamartoma^c](#), [Mass of digestive structure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Peutz-Jeghers syndrome^c](#)

Hamartomatous polyp^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063520>

has super-classes

[Hamartoma \(morphologic abnormality\)^c](#), [Polyp^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Peutz Jeghers polyp](#) ^c

Head^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000120>

The anterior and superior part of a human bearing the mouth, the brain and sensory organs. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Head and neck](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Head part](#) ^c

Head and neck^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000008>

For oncology, an area of the body generally construed to comprise the base of skull and facial bones, sinuses, orbits, salivary glands, oral cavity, oropharynx, larynx, thyroid, facial and neck musculature and lymph nodes draining these areas. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Upper body part structure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Face and/or neck structure](#) ^c, [Head](#) ^c

Head first orientation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016724>

has super-classes

[Patient Orientation](#) ^c

Head part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000417>

has super-classes

[Head](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of subregion of head](#) ^c

Health Status Assessment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037292>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Medical Assessment](#) ^c, [Performance Status Assessment](#) ^c

is in range of

[hasHealthStatusAssessment](#) ^{op}

Health-related behavior^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050936>

has super-classes

[Behavior observable](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Substance use behavior](#) ^c

Health-related behavior finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056240>

has super-classes

[Behavior finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Finding of tobacco use and exposure](#)^c, [Finding relating to alcohol drinking behavior](#)^c

Healthcare professional^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001109>

has super-classes

[Person in the healthcare environment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Medical practitioner](#)^c

Healthy patient^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000039>

has super-classes

[Physical status qualifier](#)^c

Heart^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000075>

A hollow organ located slightly to the left of the middle portion of the chest. It is composed of muscle and it is divided by a septum into two sides: the right side which receives de-oxygenated blood from the body and the left side which sends newly oxygenated blood to the body. Each side is composed of two chambers: the atrium (receiving blood) and ventricle (ejecting blood). [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Heart and/or pericardium structure](#)^c, [Heart, mediastinum, and pleura](#)^c, [ICDO3Topography](#)^c, [Structure of thoracic viscus](#)^c

Heart and/or pericardium structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000056>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Heart](#)^c

Heart, mediastinum, and pleura^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000025>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Heart](#)^c

Heavy cigarette smoker (20-39 cigarettes per day)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059172>

has super-classes

[Cigarette smoker](#)^c

Heavy drinker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056340>

has super-classes

[Current drinker](#)^c

Hemangioma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046540>

A benign vascular lesion characterized by the formation of capillary-sized or cavernous vascular channels. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Benign neoplastic disease](#)^c

Hematocrit [Volume Fraction] of Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033425>

has super-classes

[Laboratory test](#)^c

Hematopoietic neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049139>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lymphoid neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant hematopoietic neoplasm](#)^c

Hematoxylin and eosin stain method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035162>

has super-classes

[Hematoxylin stain method](#)^c

Hematoxylin stain method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035161>

has super-classes

[Staining method](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hematoxylin and eosin stain method](#)^c

Hemoglobin [Mass/volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033419>

has super-classes

[Hemoglobin|Moment in time|Blood](#)^c

Hemoglobin A1c/Hemoglobin.total in Blood by HPLC^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034034>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#)^c, [Hemoglobin A1c/Hemoglobin.total|Mass Fraction|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Hemoglobin A1c/Hemoglobin.total|Mass Fraction|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050449>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hemoglobin A1c/Hemoglobin.total in Blood by HPLC](#)^c

Hemoglobin below reference range^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051812>

has super-classes

[Hemoglobin level outside reference range](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Iron deficiency anemia](#)^c

Hemoglobin level outside reference range^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051798>

has super-classes

[Measurement finding outside reference range](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hemoglobin below reference range](#)^c

Hemoglobin|Moment in time|Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050189>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hemoglobin \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Hemoptysis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051881>

has super-classes

[Bleeding](#)^c

Hemorrhage^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051020>

has super-classes

[Mechanical abnormality](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Diffuse hemorrhage](#)^c

is in domain of

[HaemorrhageVolumeValue](#)^{dp}

Hemorrhage volume^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016739>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Hemorrhage volume value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016739>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Indeterminate](#)^c, [No](#)^c, [Yes](#)^c

Hemorrhagic tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049745>

has super-classes

[Tumor configuration](#)^c

Hepatic cystadenoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037483>

has super-classes

[Adenoma of liver](#)^c

Hepatic fibrosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036868>

has super-classes

[Disease of liver](#)^c, [Lesion of liver](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cirrhosis of liver](#)^c

Hepatic flexure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063385>

has super-classes

[Structure of right colic flexure](#)^c

Hepatic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000261>

is equivalent to

[Structure of right colic flexure](#)^c

has super-classes

[Colon](#)^c

Hepatocellular carcinoma (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049516>

has super-classes

[Liver tumor morphology](#)^c, [Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hepatocellular carcinoma, fibrolamellar](#)^c

Hepatocellular carcinoma, fibrolamellar^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049525>

has super-classes

[Hepatocellular carcinoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

HER2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044953>

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[HER2 | Breast cancer specimen | Pathology](#)^c, [HER2 | Tissue and Smears | Pathology](#)^c

HER2 [Presence] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045851>

An immunoassay procedure that detects receptor tyrosine-protein kinase erbb-2 in a breast cancer specimen. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[HER2 | Breast cancer specimen | Pathology](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

HER2 Ag [Presence] in Tissue by Immune stain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051884>

has super-classes

[HER2 | Tissue and Smears | Pathology](#)^c, [Pathology](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

HER2 negative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048106>

A breast adenocarcinoma that is negative for the expression of the HER2 receptor. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[Carcinoma of breast](#)^c and ([Has Associated Tumor Marker Test](#)^{op} some [HER2 \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} only [Negative](#)^c))

has super-classes

[Breast Carcinoma by Gene Expression Profile](#)^c, [Carcinoma of breast](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Triple-negative breast cancer](#)^c

is disjoint with

[HER2 positive](#)^c

HER2 positive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046795>

A biologic subset of breast carcinoma defined by high expression of HER2, GRB7, and TRAP100, and by lack of expression of estrogen receptor (ER). [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[Carcinoma of breast](#)^c and ([Has Associated Tumor Marker Test](#)^{op} some [HER2 \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c and ([hasAnswer](#)^{op} only [Positive](#)^c))

has super-classes

[Breast Carcinoma by Gene Expression Profile](#)^c, [Carcinoma of breast](#)^c

is disjoint with

[HER2 negative](#)^c

HER2 positive (enriched)/HR positive (luminal)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007981>

is equivalent to

[ER positive](#)^c and [HER2 positive](#)^c and [PR positive](#)^c and [MKI67 Positive](#)^c

HER2 positive(enriched)/HR negative (non-luminal)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007980>

is equivalent to

[HER2 positive](#)^c and [ER negative](#)^c and [PR negative](#)^c

HER2 | Breast cancer specimen | Pathology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045085>

has super-classes

[HER2](#)^c

has sub-classes

[HER2 \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c

HER2 | Tissue and Smears | Pathology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045086>

has super-classes

[HER2](#)^c

has sub-classes

[HER2 Ag \[Presence\] in Tissue by Immune stain](#)^c

Hereditary cancer-predisposing syndrome^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053015>

has super-classes

[Hereditary disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lynch syndrome](#)^c, [Peutz-Jeghers syndrome](#)^c

Hereditary disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052271>

has super-classes

[Genetic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Autosomal hereditary disorder](#)^c, [Hereditary cancer-predisposing syndrome](#)^c

Hereditary disorder of nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052586>

has super-classes

[Disorder of nervous system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Peutz-Jeghers syndrome](#)^c

Hereditary disorder of the integument^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052511>

has super-classes

[Disorder of integument](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Peutz-Jeghers syndrome](#)^c

Heterogeneous fibroglandular tissue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016683>

has super-classes

[Tissue composition](#)^c

Heterogeneously dense^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016692>

[BI-RADS] 50-75% glandular [RadLex]

has super-classes

[High density](#)^c

Heterogeneously echogenic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016628>

BI-RADS: US: A mixture of echogenic patterns within a solid mass [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Echogenicity characteristic](#)^c

High^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002025>

has super-classes

[Increased](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Very high](#)^c

High ADC value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005447>

has super-classes

[ADC value](#)^c

High density^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016691>

[BI-RADS] Mammo: x-ray attenuation of the mass is greater than the expected attenuation of an equal volume of fibroglandular breast tissue [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Density descriptor](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Extremely dense](#)^c, [Heterogeneously dense](#)^c, [Homogeneously dense](#)^c

High density lipoprotein cholesterol measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033614>

has super-classes

[Cholesterol measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cholesterol in HDL \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

High dose rate brachytherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058846>

has super-classes

[Brachytherapy](#)^c

High grade glioma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000063>

has super-classes

[Malignant glioma](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glioblastoma](#)^c

High histologic grade^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001374>

Used to describe tumor samples that exhibit poorly differentiated or undifferentiated cells. They are generally expected to be fast growing and aggressive. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Histological grades](#)^c

High risk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000137>

The potential future harm that may arise from some present action or attribute or condition is almost certain. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Adjectival modifier](#)^c, [Risk assessment value](#)^c

High Risk Acute Leukemia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002171>

Acute leukemia patients are stratified into the high risk group when their minimal residual disease levels are higher than 0.05%. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Risk assessment value](#)^c

High risk of recurrence, prostate cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1023158>

has super-classes

[Diagnostic/Screening Processes or Results](#)^c

Hip joint^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000229>

A ball-and-socket joint between the head of the femur and the acetabulum. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Hip region structure](#)^c, [Joint structure of lower extremity](#)^c, [Joint structure of pelvic girdle](#)^c, [Structure of spheroidal joint](#)^c

Hip region structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000053>

The body part defined by the hip joint and surrounding structures, including the region from the iliac crest to the thigh

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hip joint](#)^c

Hispanic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001209>

has super-classes

[Hispanic or Latino](#)^c

Hispanic or Latino^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001206>

has super-classes

[Ethnicity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hispanic](#)^c, [Latino](#)^c

Histologic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000029>

Pertaining to the combined microscopic physical features of cells and their surrounding extracellular environment in tissues. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#)^c

Histologic Behavior and Type^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049521>

has super-classes

[Histology/Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

Histologic feature of neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039082>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Histologic grade of neoplasm](#)^c, [Histologic type of malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Histologic grade of neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049681>

has super-classes

[Histologic feature of neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Histologic grade of primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [WHO grade for central nervous system tumor](#)^c

is in range of

[hasHistologicGrade](#)^{op}, [hasHistologicGradeType](#)^{op}

Histologic grade of primary malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049684>

has super-classes

[Histologic grade of neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gleason pattern](#)^c, [Gleason score](#)^c, [Histologic grade of primary malignant neoplasm of prostate by International Society of Urological Pathology technique](#)^c, [Nottingham grade of primary malignant neoplasm of breast](#)^c

Histologic grade of primary malignant neoplasm of prostate by International Society of Urological Pathology technique^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049685>

has super-classes

[Histologic grade of primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Histologic grades^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002675>

has super-classes

[Histologic grading differentiation AND/OR behavior](#)^c

Histologic grading differentiation AND/OR behavior^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002672>

has super-classes

[General clinical stage for disease AND/OR neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Histologic grades](#)^c

Histologic test^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034154>

has super-classes

[Evidence Type](#)^c, [Laboratory test](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Histopathology test](#)^c

Histologic type of malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039157>

has super-classes

[Histologic feature of neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Histologic type of primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Histologic type of primary malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046060>

has super-classes

[Histologic type of malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Histological grades^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001360>

has super-classes

[Disease Grade Qualifier](#)^c, [Grades](#)^c

has sub-classes

[G1: Well differentiated](#)^c, [G2: Moderately differentiated](#)^c, [G3: Poorly differentiated](#)^c, [G4: Undifferentiated](#)^c, [GX: Histologic grade cannot be assessed](#)^c, [Grade cannot be assessed \(GX\); Unknown](#)^c, [High histologic grade](#)^c, [Intermediate histologic grade](#)^c, [International Society of Pathology histologic grade group](#)^c, [Low histologic grade](#)^c

is in range of

[hasHistologicGradeValue](#)^{op}

Histological grading systems^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037296>

has super-classes

[Staging and scales](#)^c

has sub-classes

[French Federation of Cancer Centers Sarcoma Group \(FNCLCC\) grading system](#)^c, [Gleason grading system for prostatic cancer](#)^c, [Gleason scoring system for malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c, [International Society of Urological Pathology prostate cancer staging system](#)^c, [Nottingham histologic grading system](#)^c, [WHO CNS tumor grading system](#)^c

is in domain of

[CancerGradingMethodFor](#)^{op}

is in range of

[hasHistologicalGradingSystem](#)^{op}

Histology/Morphology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000033>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Histologic Behavior and Type](#)^c, [Tumor Morphology](#)^c

is in range of

[hasHistologyMorphologyBehavior](#)^{op}

Histopathology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048686>

The microscopic study of characteristic tissue abnormalities by employing various cytochemical and immunocytochemical stains. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Pathology \(qualifier value\)](#)^c

Histopathology finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1006668>

has super-classes

[Evaluation finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[General pathology](#)^c, [Surgical margin finding](#)^c

Histopathology Result^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000209>

has super-classes

[Pathology Result](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Morphologic Finding](#)^c

Histopathology test^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035076>

has super-classes

[Anatomic pathology procedure](#)^c, [Histologic test](#)^c

History of cancer metastatic to bone^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004573>

has super-classes

[History of metastatic cancer](#)^c

History of cancer metastatic to brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004574>

has super-classes

[History of metastatic cancer](#)^c

History of cancer metastatic to liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004575>

has super-classes

[History of metastatic cancer](#)^c

History of cancer metastatic to lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004576>

has super-classes

[History of metastatic cancer](#)^c

History of cancer metastatic to lymph nodes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004577>

has super-classes

[History of metastatic cancer](#)^c

History of clinical finding in subject^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046288>

has super-classes

[Finding suspected or known present](#)^c, [Finding with explicit context](#)^c

History of disseminated malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004578>

has super-classes

[History of metastatic cancer](#)^c

History of metastatic cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004579>

has super-classes

[Situation with explicit context](#)^c

has sub-classes

[History of cancer metastatic to bone](#)^c, [History of cancer metastatic to brain](#)^c, [History of cancer metastatic to liver](#)^c, [History of cancer metastatic to lung](#)^c, [History of cancer metastatic to lymph nodes](#)^c, [History of disseminated malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Hitachi^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000057>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Hologic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000064>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Homogeneously dense^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016694>

has super-classes

[High density](#)^c

Hormone^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050985>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hypothalamic or pituitary hormone](#)^c, [Hypothalamic releasing factor](#)^c

HORMONE ANTAGONISTS AND RELATED AGENTS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1019022>

has super-classes

[ENDOCRINE THERAPY](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Other hormone antagonists and related agents](#)^c

Hormone measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1006782>

has super-classes

[Drug measurement](#)^c, [Laboratory procedure](#)^c, [Measurement](#)^c, [Measurement of substance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[17-hydroxycorticosteroid measurement](#)^c, [Androgen level](#)^c, [Brain natriuretic peptide measurement](#)^c, [Insulin measurement](#)^c, [Thyroid stimulating hormone measurement](#)^c

Hormone receptor negative neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044057>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ER negative](#)^c, [PR negative](#)^c, [Triple-negative breast cancer](#)^c

is disjoint with

[Hormone receptor positive tumor](#)^c

Hormone receptor positive tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1041560>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ER positive](#)^c, [PR positive](#)^c

is disjoint with

[Hormone receptor negative neoplasm](#)^c

Hormone refractory prostate cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1023100>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Hormone replacement therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035175>

has super-classes

[Hormone therapy](#)^c

Hormone sensitive prostate cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1023217>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Hormone therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016082>

has super-classes

[Administration of hormone](#)^c, [Drug therapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Androgen deprivation therapy](#)^c, [Hormone replacement therapy](#)^c

HORMONES AND RELATED AGENTS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1019107>

has super-classes

[ENDOCRINE THERAPY](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gonadotropin releasing hormone analogues](#)^c

Human Specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002056>

has super-classes

[Specimen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Body substance specimen](#)^c, [Genitourinary sample](#)^c, [Specimen from digestive system](#)^c, [Specimen from respiratory system](#)^c, [Specimen from trunk](#)^c

Husband^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001038>

has super-classes

[Spouse](#)^c

Hyperechoic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016623>

BI-RADS US: having increased echogenicity relative to fat or equal to fibroglandular tissue. [TI-RADS]: Increased echogenicity relative to thyroid tissue [LI-RADS] Echogenicity more than background liver. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Echogenicity characteristic](#)^c

Hypermethylated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001315>

has super-classes

[Methylated](#)^c

Hyperpigmentation of skin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053226>

has super-classes

[Disorder of skin pigmentation](#)^c

Hyperplasia of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1019193>

has super-classes

[Disorder of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Benign prostatic hyperplasia](#)^c

Hyperthermia Treatment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1014764>

has super-classes

[Therapeutic procedure](#)^c

Hypoechoic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016627>

BI-RADS US: defined relative to subcutaneous fat; less echogenic than fat; characterized by low-level echoes throughout (e.g. complicated cysts or fibroadenomas). [TI-RADS}: Decreased echogenicity relative to thyroid tissue. [LI-RADS] Echogenicity less than background liver. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Echogenicity characteristic](#)^c

Hypofractionated radiation therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058411>

has super-classes

[Radiotherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hypofractionated whole breast radiation therapy](#)^c

Hypofractionated stereotactic radiotherapy using megavoltage radiation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1029448>

has super-classes

[Stereotactic radiation therapy using megavoltage radiation](#)^c

Hypofractionated whole breast radiation therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060799>

has super-classes

[Hypofractionated radiation therapy](#)^c, [Radiotherapy to breast](#)^c

Hypothalamic or pituitary hormone^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050987>

has super-classes

[Hormone](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hypothalamic releasing factor](#)^c, [Melanocyte stimulating hormone releasing factor](#)^c

Hypothalamic releasing factor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050990>

has super-classes

[Hormone](#)^c, [Hypothalamic or pituitary hormone](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Melanocyte stimulating hormone releasing factor](#)^c

Hypothalamus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000397>

has super-classes

[Diencephalon part](#)^c

I^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000040>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)^c

I^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000072>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#)^c

I.M.S^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000048>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

ICDO3Morphology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049526>

Morphology encodes the histology of the neoplasm

has super-classes

[Histologic Behavior and Type](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Acinar cell neoplasms](#)^c, [Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#)^c, [Adnexal and skin appendage neoplasms](#)^c, [Complex epithelial neoplasm](#)^c, [Cystic, mucinous and serous neoplasms](#)^c, [Ductal and lobular neoplasms](#)^c, [Epithelial neoplasms, NOS](#)^c, [Fibroepithelial neoplasms](#)^c, [Fibromatous neoplasms](#)^c, [Malignant lymphomas, NOS or diffuse](#)^c, [Neoplasms, NOS](#)^c, [Nerve sheath tumors](#)^c, [Squamous cell neoplasms](#)^c, [Transitional cell papillomas and carcinomas](#)^c

is in range of

[hasHistologyICDO](#)^{op}

ICDO3Topography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000265>

has super-classes

[Body structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bladder](#)^c, [Brain](#)^c, [Breast](#)^c, [Bronchus and lung](#)^c, [Cervix uteri](#)^c, [Colon](#)^c, [Connective, subcutaneous and other soft tissues](#)^c, [Esophagus](#)^c, [Gallbladder](#)^c, [Heart](#)^c, [Kidney](#)^c, [Liver](#)^c, [Meninges](#)^c, [Ovary](#)^c, [Pancreas](#)^c, [Prostate](#)^c, [Rectum](#)^c, [Stomach](#)^c, [Thyroid](#)^c, [Uterus, NOS](#)^c, [Vagina](#)^c

is in range of

[hasTopographyICDO](#)^{op}

ICDO3Tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031178>

A tumour consists of a topography code and a morphology code. [ICDO3]

has super-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Acinar cell carcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation of prostate gland](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of ascending colon](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of cecum](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of colon, NOS](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of descending colon](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of hepatic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of lung, NOS](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of rectum, NOS](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of transverse colon](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of ascending colon](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of cecum](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of colon, NOS](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of descending colon](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of rectum, NOS](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of transverse colon](#)^c, [Apocrine adenocarcinoma of breast, NOS](#)^c, [Basal cell adenocarcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of ascending colon](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of cecum](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of colon, NOS](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of descending colon](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of hepatic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of rectum, NOS](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of transverse colon](#)^c, [Ductal carcinoma in situ, solid type of breast, NOS](#)^c, [Infiltrating duct and lobular carcinoma of breast, NOS](#)^c, [Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS, of breast, NOS](#)^c, [Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#)^c, [Intraductal carcinoma, noninfiltrating, NOS, of prostate gland](#)^c, [Large cell carcinoma, NOS, of lung, NOS](#)^c, [Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c, [Lobular carcinoma in situ, NOS, of breast, NOS](#)^c, [Lobular carcinoma in situ, pleomorphic of breast, NOS](#)^c, [Lobular carcinoma, NOS, of breast, NOS](#)^c, [Malignant lymphoma, non-Hodgkin, NOS, of unknown primary site](#)^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of ascending colon](#)^c,

[Mucinous adenocarcinoma of breast, NOS](#) ^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of cecum](#) ^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of colon, NOS](#) ^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of descending colon](#) ^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon](#) ^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of rectum, NOS](#) ^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of sigmoid colon](#) ^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of splenic flexure of colon](#) ^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of transverse colon](#) ^c, [Neoplasm, malignant of ascending colon](#) ^c, [Neoplasm, malignant of breast, NOS](#) ^c, [Neoplasm, malignant of cecum](#) ^c, [Neoplasm, malignant of colon, NOS](#) ^c, [Neoplasm, malignant of descending colon](#) ^c, [Neoplasm, malignant of hepatic flexure of colon](#) ^c, [Neoplasm, malignant of prostate gland](#) ^c, [Neoplasm, malignant of rectum, NOS](#) ^c, [Neoplasm, malignant of sigmoid colon](#) ^c, [Neoplasm, malignant of splenic flexure of colon](#) ^c, [Neoplasm, malignant of transverse colon](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of ascending colon](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of cecum](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of colon, NOS](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of descending colon](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of hepatic flexure of colon](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of rectum, NOS](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of sigmoid colon](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of splenic flexure of colon](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of transverse colon](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine tumor, NOS, of prostate gland](#) ^c, [Non-small cell carcinoma of lung, NOS](#) ^c, [Papillary carcinoma, NOS, of breast, NOS](#) ^c, [Phyllodes tumor, malignant of breast, NOS](#) ^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of ascending colon](#) ^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of cecum](#) ^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of colon, NOS](#) ^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of descending colon](#) ^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon](#) ^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of rectum, NOS](#) ^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of sigmoid colon](#) ^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of splenic flexure of colon](#) ^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of transverse colon](#) ^c, [Small cell carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#) ^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS, of lung, NOS](#) ^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#) ^c, [Transitional cell carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#) ^c, [Tubular adenocarcinoma of breast, NOS](#) ^c

IDH1 (isocitrate dehydrogenase (NADP(+)) 1) gene variant measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051952>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#) ^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#) ^c

IDH1 and IDH2 genes targeted mutation analysis in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045804>

has super-classes

[Molecular pathology](#) ^c

IDH1 gene mutations found [Identifier] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051946>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#) ^c

IDH2 (isocitrate dehydrogenase (NADP(+)) 2) gene variant measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051953>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#) ^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#) ^c

IGRT (image-guided radiation therapy)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033259>

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#) ^c

II^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000041>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#) ^c

II^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000071>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#) ^c

IIA^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000060>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#) ^c

IIA^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000070>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#) ^c

IIB^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000052>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#) ^c

IIB^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000061>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#) ^c

IIC^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000058>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#) ^c

IIC^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000069>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#) ^c

III^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000042>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#) ^c

III^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000067>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#) ^c

IIIA^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000054>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)^c

IIIA^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000066>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#)^c

IIIB^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000053>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)^c

IIIB^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000065>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#)^c

IIIC^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000050>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)^c

IIIC^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000062>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#)^c

Image^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016310>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

Image acquisition mode^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016758>

has super-classes

[Imaging procedure property](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Nuclear imaging acquisition](#)^c

Image Acquisition Date^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001938>

The date that imaging data was acquired for a sample. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Date](#)^c

Image Coordinate System^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001216>

has super-classes

[Annotation/Segmentation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Physical](#)^c, [Pixel](#)^c

Image Date^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001937>

The date the image pixel data creation started. Required if image is part of a Series in which the images are temporally related. May be present otherwise. Note This Attribute was formerly known as Image Date. Source:DICOM

has super-classes

[Date](#)^c

Image processing attribute^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016769>

has super-classes

[Imaging procedure property](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Attenuation correction method](#)^c

Image Series^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016309>

A collection of images with a common element. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

is in domain of

[ImageSeriesDescription](#)^{dp}, [ImageSeriesNumber](#)^{dp}, [image_series_u_i_d](#)^{dp}

Image Study^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016308>

A radiographic technique used to evaluate a specific anatomic location for a specific purpose.

has super-classes

[Diagnostic Imaging](#)^c

is in domain of

[ImageStudyUID](#)^{dp}

Imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000023>

has super-classes

[Observation Category](#)^c

Imaging (Procedure)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005453>

has super-classes

[Evidence Type](#)^c, [Imaging Module](#)^c, [Procedure](#)^c, [Procedure Category](#)^c, [Tumor Size Method](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Angiography](#)^c, [Chest imaging](#)^c, [Fluorescence imaging](#)^c, [IGRT \(image-guided radiation therapy\)](#)^c, [Imaging by body site](#)^c, [Imaging guidance](#)^c, [Imaging of central nervous system](#)^c, [Imaging of pelvis](#)^c, [Imaging without IV contrast](#)^c, [Magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c, [Nuclear medicine](#)^c,

[Radiographic imaging.procedure](#)^c, [Ultrasound](#)^c, [Video imaging](#)^c
is in range of
[hasImageProcedure](#)^{op}

Imaging by body site^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005458>

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chest imaging](#)^c, [Imaging of abdomen](#)^c, [Imaging of genitourinary system](#)^c

Imaging Criteria^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1003888>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c, [Tumor Observation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c, [Volumetric Imaging Criteria](#)^c

Imaging finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1003882>

has super-classes

[Evaluation finding](#)^c, [Imaging Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Imaging result abnormal](#)^c, [Imaging result normal](#)^c, [Radiologic finding](#)^c, [Ultrasound scan finding](#)^c

Imaging guidance^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005455>

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Imaging guided biopsy](#)^c, [Magnetic resonance imaging guidance](#)^c, [Stereotactic radiotherapy](#)^c, [Ultrasonic guidance procedure](#)^c

Imaging guided biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001823>

has super-classes

[Biopsy](#)^c, [Imaging guidance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI guided biopsy](#)^c, [US-guided systematic biopsy](#)^c, [Ultrasound guided biopsy](#)^c, [X-ray guided biopsy](#)^c

Imaging modality^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000009>

Form of imaging that depends on the way the image is produced [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Histologic](#)^c, [Magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c, [Magnetic resonance spectroscopy](#)^c, [Microscopy](#)^c, [Nuclear medicine imaging](#)^c, [Other modality \(DICOM\)](#)^c, [Projection radiography](#)^c, [Radiographic imaging - action](#)^c, [Radionuclide imaging - action](#)^c, [Tomography](#)^c, [Ultrasound](#)^c, [Video imaging - action](#)^c, [combined modalities](#)^c

is in domain of

[hasAcquisitionParameter](#)^{op}, [hasAcquisitionParameterValue](#)^{op}, [hasModalityDescriptor](#)^{op}

is in range of

[hasImageModality](#)^{op}

Imaging Module^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG100001>

This module defines the categories/entities that are specified in imaging context (e.g., image modalities, procedures, manufacturers, imaging assessments, imaging descriptors, etc.).

has super-classes

[thing](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anatomical Plane](#)^c, [Density descriptor](#)^c, [Diagnostic Imaging](#)^c, [Image](#)^c, [Image Series](#)^c, [Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c, [Imaging Criteria](#)^c, [Imaging finding](#)^c, [Imaging modality](#)^c, [Imaging observable](#)^c, [Imaging observation](#)^c, [Imaging observation descriptor](#)^c, [Imaging procedure descriptor](#)^c, [Imaging procedure property](#)^c, [Laterality](#)^c, [MR imaging coil](#)^c, [Manufacturer](#)^c, [Modality descriptor](#)^c, [Morphologic descriptor](#)^c, [Orientation descriptor](#)^c, [Patient Position](#)^c, [Screening procedure](#)^c, [Tissue composition](#)^c, [Tumor vascularity](#)^c

Imaging observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016238>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c, [Observable entity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Ultrasonographic observable](#)^c

Imaging observation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005454>

To discuss integration-combination with findings (APHP radiologist suggestion)

Features seen and reported by a radiologist during interpretation of an image that are specific to imaging. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Assessment](#)^c, [Diffusion weighted imaging](#)^c, [Enhancement pattern](#)^c, [Lesion](#)^c, [Margin](#)^c

Imaging observation descriptor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016608>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c, [Tumor Observation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Modality-related characteristic](#)^c

Imaging of abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005467>

has super-classes

[Imaging by body site](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI of prostate](#)^c, [Ultrasonography of abdomen](#)^c

Imaging of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016595>

has super-classes

[Imaging of central nervous system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI of brain](#)^c

Imaging of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016147>

has super-classes

[Chest imaging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI of breast](#)^c

Imaging of central nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016139>

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Imaging of brain](#)^c

Imaging of genitourinary system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005473>

has super-classes

[Imaging by body site](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI of prostate](#)^c, [US scan of genitourinary system](#)^c

Imaging of pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005462>

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI of pelvis](#)^c, [Pelvic echography](#)^c

Imaging procedure descriptor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016607>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Patient Orientation](#)^c, [Radiation dose](#)^c

Imaging procedure property^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016619>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Image acquisition mode](#)^c, [Image processing attribute](#)^c, [cross-sectional procedure attribute](#)^c, [enhancement phase](#)^c

is in range of

[hasAcquisitionParameter](#)^{op}, [hasAcquisitionParameterValue](#)^{op}

Imaging result abnormal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016118>

has super-classes

[Abnormal finding on evaluation procedure](#)^c, [Imaging finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI scan abnormal](#)^c

Imaging result normal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005611>

has super-classes

[Imaging finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI scan normal](#)^c, [Radiology result normal](#)^c

Imaging sequence^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001214>

Sequences used for segmentation

has super-classes

[Annotation/Segmentation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ADC map](#)^c, [Computed tomography](#)^c, [Diffusion weighted](#)^c, [FLAIR](#)^c, [PET-CT](#)^c, [PW](#)^c, [T1W-CE](#)^c, [T2 weighted](#)^c

Imaging technician^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001102>

has super-classes

[Annotator Specialty](#)^c, [Person in the healthcare environment](#)^c

Imaging without IV contrast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016755>

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c

Immediate family member^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001059>

has super-classes

[Relative](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Child](#)^c, [Parent](#)^c, [Sibling](#)^c, [Spouse](#)^c

Immune system excision^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050997>

has super-classes

[Excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of lymph node](#)^c

Immune system surgical procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051875>

has super-classes

[Surgical procedure](#)^c

Immunologic agent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035056>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Capecitabine](#)^c, [Cyclophosphamide](#)^c, [Docetaxel](#)^c, [Fluorouracil](#)^c, [Gemcitabine](#)^c, [Methotrexate](#)^c, [Nab paclitaxel](#)^c, [Paclitaxel](#)^c, [Vinorelbine](#)^c

Immunological therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035133>

Therapy designed to induce changes in a patient's immune status in order to treat disease. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Biological Therapy](#)^c, [Medical therapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Immunotherapy for cancer](#)^c

Immunomodulatory^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046260>

has super-classes

[Triple-negative breast cancer](#)^c

Immunotherapeutic agent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034112>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Immunotherapy for cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034262>

has super-classes

[Immunological therapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Antineoplastic chemoimmunotherapy](#)^c

Impaired urinary system function^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1019280>

has super-classes

[Functional finding](#)^c, [Urinary system finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Urinary incontinence](#)^c

Improved^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002075>

has super-classes

[Condition stability status](#)^c, [Degree findings](#)^c

In situ neoplasm (morphology)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049118>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma in situ \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Inactive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001173>

has super-classes

[Condition clinical status value](#)^c, [General adjectival modifier](#)^c

Inadequate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002074>

has super-classes

[Degree findings^c](#), [General adjectival modifier^c](#)

Incomplete emptying of urinary bladder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000361>

has super-classes

[Finding of urinary bladder emptying^c](#)

Incontinence^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1019368>

has super-classes

[Finding of pelvic region of trunk^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Incontinence of feces^c](#), [Urinary incontinence^c](#)

Incontinence of feces^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1026598>

has super-classes

[Finding of bowel continence^c](#), [Incontinence^c](#)

Increased^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002022>

has super-classes

[Degree findings^c](#), [Finding value^c](#)

has sub-classes

[High^c](#), [Moderate^c](#)

Increased frequency of urination^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000358>

has super-classes

[Finding of frequency of urination^c](#)

Indeterminate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000044>

Image annotation label (INCISIVE, Annotation Definitions and guidelines)

Cannot distinguish between two or more possible values in the current context. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Diffusion Characteristics value^c](#), [General adjectival modifier^c](#), [Hemorrhage volume value^c](#)

Indistinct margin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005422>

PI-RADS: blurred. BI-RADS Mammo: No clear demarcation of the entire margin or any portion of it from the surrounding tissue (historically, "ill defined"). US: no clear demarcation between a mass and the surrounding tissue anywhere on the margin. [TI-RADS]: Border of the nodule is difficult to distinguish from thyroid parenchyma; the nodule lacks irregular or lobulated margins. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Non-circumscribed margin^c](#)

Infant feeding method - finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036835>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast fed](#)^c

Infection control management^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060767>

has super-classes

[Procedure with a procedure focus](#)^c

Infection of liver caused by parasite^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036313>

has super-classes

[Disease caused by parasite](#)^c, [Liver disorder due to infection](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Echinococcosis of liver](#)^c

Infiltrating carcinoma with ductal and lobular features^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049483>

has super-classes

[Ductal, lobular AND/OR medullary neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Infiltrating duct and lobular carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052193>

has super-classes

[Ductal and lobular neoplasms](#)^c

Infiltrating duct and lobular carcinoma of breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060853>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Infiltrating duct carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049482>

has super-classes

[Ductal, lobular AND/OR medullary neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Invasive ductal carcinoma with an extensive intraductal component](#)^c

Infiltrating duct carcinoma of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007973>

is equivalent to

[Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS, of breast, NOS](#)^c

has super-classes

[Carcinoma of breast](#)^c

Infiltrating duct carcinoma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016155>

has super-classes

[Malignant epithelial neoplasm](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#)^c

Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063589>

has super-classes

[Ductal and lobular neoplasms](#)^c

Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS, of breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060842>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Infiltrating duct carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1023862>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Infiltrating duct carcinoma of prostate](#)^c

Infiltrating duct mixed with other types of carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052202>

has super-classes

[Ductal and lobular neoplasms](#)^c

Infiltrating lobular carcinoma of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007972>

is equivalent to

[Lobular carcinoma, NOS, of breast, NOS](#)^c

has super-classes

[Carcinoma of breast](#)^c

Inflammation of specific body organs^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1042635>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Inflammatory disease of liver](#)^c

Inflammatory disease of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037582>

has super-classes

[Disease of liver](#)^c, [Inflammation of specific body organs](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Autoimmune hepatitis](#)^c, [Chronic hepatitis](#)^c

Inflammatory disorder of lower respiratory tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053096>

has super-classes

[Disorder of lower respiratory system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Pneumonitis](#)^c

Inflammatory morphology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063534>

has super-classes

[Morphologically abnormal structure](#)^c

Infratentorial brain part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000372>

has super-classes

[Infratentorial brain structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cerebellum](#)^c

Infratentorial brain structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000371>

has super-classes

[Brain region](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Infratentorial brain part](#)^c

Injury of abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1041158>

has super-classes

[Disorder of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdominal cavity injury](#)^c

Injury of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045991>

has super-classes

[Chest injury](#)^c, [Disorder of breast](#)^c

Inspection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018530>

has super-classes

[Examination by method](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Endoscopy](#)^c, [Microscopy \(procedure\)](#)^c

Insula and opercula structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000370>

has super-classes

[Cerebral hemisphere part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Insular structure](#)^c

Insular carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049458>

has super-classes

[Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Insular structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000364>

has super-classes

[Brain Lesion Site](#)^c, [Cerebral lobe structure](#)^c, [Insula and opercula structure](#)^c

Insulin [Units/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033459>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#)^c, [Insulin measurement](#)^c

Insulin measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033449>

has super-classes

[Hormone measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Insulin \[Units/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Insulin-like growth factor-I receptor Ag [Presence] in Tissue by Immune stain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051891>

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c

Intensity modulated external beam neutron radiation therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005285>

has super-classes

[Intensity modulated radiation therapy](#)^c

Intensity modulated intracavitary brachytherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005268>

has super-classes

[Intracavitary brachytherapy](#)^c

Intensity modulated radiation therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005281>

has super-classes

[Conformal radiotherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intensity modulated external beam neutron radiation therapy](#)^c, [Tomotherapy](#)^c, [Volumetric modulated arc therapy](#)^c

Intensity modulated radiation therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1023277>

has super-classes

[Destructive procedure](#)^c, [Radiotherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Volumetric modulated arc therapy](#)^c

Intensity of stain of estrogen receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049759>

has super-classes

[Presence of estrogen receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)^c

Intensity of stain of progesterone receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049764>

has super-classes

[Presence of progesterone receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)^c

Intents^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002393>

has super-classes

[Nature of procedure values](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Diagnostic intent](#)^c, [Palliative intent](#)^c, [Preventive intent](#)^c, [Therapeutic](#)^c

is in range of

[hasTreatmentIntent](#)^{op}

Intergroup Rhabdomyosarcoma Study Group Clinical Staging and Grouping System^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044304>

Staging and grouping for rhabdomyosarcoma that groups patients into low, intermediate, or high clinical risk groups based on: histologic type, tumor site, tumor size, and pathologic TNM. Note: this is not the TNM system described in AJCC. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Risk Assessment](#)^c, [Tumor staging](#)^c

Intermediate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002034>

has super-classes

[Topographical modifier](#)^c

Intermediate histologic grade^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001372>

A term referring to the degree of differentiation of a malignant neoplasm and indicating that it is moderately differentiated. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Histological grades](#)^c

Intermediate Risk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002174>

The potential future harm that may arise from some present action or attribute or condition is moderate. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Risk assessment value](#)^c

Intermediate risk of recurrence, prostate cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1023338>

has super-classes

[Diagnostic/Screening Processes or Results](#) ^c

Intermediate weighted^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016642>

has super-classes

[Tissue Contrast](#) ^c

Internal capsule^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000380>

has super-classes

[Brain Deep White Matter Structure](#) ^c, [Cerebral hemisphere white matter part](#) ^c, [Eloquent Brain Areas](#) ^c

internally inserted coil^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016645>

has super-classes

[MR imaging coil](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[endoluminal coil](#) ^c

International Society of Pathology histologic grade group^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001364>

has super-classes

[Histological grades](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 1](#) ^c, [International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 2](#) ^c, [International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 3](#) ^c, [International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 4](#) ^c, [International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 5](#) ^c

International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001362>

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Grade group 1 \(Gleason score 3 + 3 = 6\)](#) ^c

International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001365>

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Grade group 2 \(Gleason score 3 + 4 = 7\)](#) ^c

International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001367>

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Grade group 3 \(Gleason score 4 + 3 = 7\)](#) ^c

International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001368>

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Grade group 4 \(Gleason score 3 + 5 = 8\)](#)^c, [Grade group 4 \(Gleason score 4 + 4 = 8\)](#)^c, [Grade group 4 \(Gleason score 5 + 3 = 8\)](#)^c

International Society of Pathology histologic grade group 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001369>

has super-classes

[International Society of Pathology histologic grade group](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Grade group 5 \(Gleason score 4 + 5 = 9\)](#)^c, [Grade group 5 \(Gleason score 5 + 4 = 9\)](#)^c, [Grade group 5 \(Gleason score 5 + 5 = 10\)](#)^c

International Society of Urological Pathology prostate cancer staging system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037300>

has super-classes

[Histological grading systems](#)^c

international unit per milliliter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000168>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

Interoperability level^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000008>

has super-classes

[Specific Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Tier 1](#)^c, [Tier 2](#)^c, [Tier 3](#)^c

is in range of

[interoperabilityLevel](#)^{op}

Interpretation of findings^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035055>

has super-classes

[Observable entity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Residual cancer burden class](#)^c

Intervals of weeks and months^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046750>

has super-classes

[Frequency interval](#)^c

Interventional radiology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060481>

has super-classes

[Provider-specific procedure](#)^c

Intestinal obstruction^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051762>

has super-classes

[Disorder of intestine](#)^c, [Gastrointestinal obstruction](#)^c

Intestinal polyposis syndrome^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054380>

has super-classes

[Polyp of intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MYH-associated polyposis](#)^c, [Peutz-Jeghers syndrome](#)^c

Intestinal structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000228>

has super-classes

[Structure of abdominopelvic viscus](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Small intestine](#)^c, [Structure of large intestine](#)^c

Intra-abdominal collection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044692>

has super-classes

[Disorder of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intraabdominal bile collection](#)^c

Intra-abdominal digestive structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000023>

has super-classes

[Intra-abdominopelvic structure](#)^c, [Structure of compartment of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Liver and/or biliary structure](#)^c, [Pancreas](#)^c

Intra-abdominal proper structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000040>

has super-classes

[Abdomen proper](#)^c, [Intra-abdominopelvic structure](#)^c, [Subdivision of intra-abdominopelvic structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of organ within abdomen proper cavity](#)^c

Intra-abdominal urinary structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000205>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Kidney structure](#)^c

Intra-abdominopelvic structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000123>

has super-classes

[Abdomen](#)^c, [Body part structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intra-abdominal digestive structure](#)^c, [Intra-abdominal proper structure](#)^c, [Intra-pelvic structure of true pelvis](#)^c, [Organ within abdominopelvic cavity](#)^c, [Subdivision of intra-abdominopelvic structure](#)^c

Intra-pelvic structure of true pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000248>

has super-classes

[Intra-abdominopelvic structure](#)^c, [Pelvis](#)^c, [Subdivision of intra-abdominopelvic structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lower bowel structures](#)^c, [Pelvic alimentary structure](#)^c

Intraabdominal bile collection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047471>

has super-classes

[Disorder of body cavity](#)^c, [Intra-abdominal collection](#)^c

Intracavitary brachytherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005279>

has super-classes

[Brachytherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intensity modulated intracavitary brachytherapy](#)^c, [Intraluminal brachytherapy](#)^c

Intracranial structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000003>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brain](#)^c, [Meninges part](#)^c

Intraductal calcifications^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000103>

has super-classes

[Calcifications](#)^c

Intraductal carcinoma and lobular carcinoma in situ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052235>

has super-classes

[Ductal and lobular neoplasms](#)^c

Intraductal carcinoma, noninfiltrating, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049616>

has super-classes

[Ductal and lobular neoplasms](#)^c

Intraductal carcinoma, noninfiltrating, NOS, of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1023932>

has super-classes

[Carcinoma in situ of prostate](#)^c, [ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Intraluminal brachytherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005270>

has super-classes

[Intracavitary brachytherapy](#)^c

Intraoperative Rad Rx (IORT)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001183>

has super-classes

[Modality radiation value](#)^c

Intravascular brachytherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005269>

has super-classes

[Brachytherapy](#)^c

Invasion into the Seminal vesicle^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033271>

has super-classes

[Tumor invasion finding](#)^c

Invasive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000101>

Marked by a tendency to spread, especially into healthy surrounding tissue. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Disease morphology qualifier](#)^c

Invasive carcinoma of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052313>

has super-classes

[Carcinoma of breast](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Invasive carcinoma of breast with extensive intraductal component](#)^c, [Invasive carcinoma of breast without extensive intraductal component](#)^c

Invasive carcinoma of breast with extensive intraductal component^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059481>

has super-classes

[Invasive carcinoma of breast](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Invasive carcinoma of breast without extensive intraductal component^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059511>

has super-classes

[Invasive carcinoma of breast](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Invasive ductal carcinoma with an extensive intraductal component^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063529>

has super-classes

[Infiltrating duct carcinoma](#)^c

IOERT - intraoperative electron radiotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060307>

has super-classes

[External beam radiation therapy using electrons](#)^c

IPATASERTIB^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035831>

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic Agents](#)^c

Ipilimumab^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063676>

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

irinotecan^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063663>

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Iron deficiency anemia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051773>

has super-classes

[Hemoglobin below reference range](#)^c, [Nutritional anemia](#)^c, [Nutritional deficiency associated condition](#)^c, [Red blood cell count below reference range](#)^c

Irregular^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1010771>

[PI-RADS]: Lacking symmetry or evenness. [BI-RADS] For a mass: neither round nor oval [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Morphologic descriptor](#)^c

Irregular mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016516>

[BI-RADS} MR: Neither oval nor round [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Mass](#)^c

Isoechoic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016622>

BI-RADS US: having the same echogenicity as subcutaneous fat. [TI-RADS]: Similar echogenicity relative to thyroid tissue [LI-RADS] Echogenicity equal to background liver [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Echogenicity characteristic](#)^c

IV^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000043>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)^c

IV^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000074>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#)^c

IVA^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000047>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)^c

IVA^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000063>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#)^c

IVB^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000046>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)^c

IVB^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000064>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological stage group allowable value](#)^c

IVC^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000073>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer clinical stage group allowable value](#)^c

Joint structure of lower extremity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000230>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hip joint](#)^c

Joint structure of pelvic girdle^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000144>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Hip joint](#) ^c

Karnofsky Performance Scale (KPS) 0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000020>

has super-classes

[Performance status qualifier](#) ^c

Karnofsky performance status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047415>

An index designed for classifying patients 16 years of age or older by their functional impairment. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Performance Status Assessment](#) ^c

KERMA area product^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016637>

has super-classes

[radiation exposure measure](#) ^c

Kidney^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000298>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Kidney structure](#) ^c

Kidney disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059256>

has super-classes

[Disorder of kidney and/or ureter](#) ^c, [Disorder of retroperitoneum](#) ^c, [Kidney finding](#) ^c

Kidney finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052238>

has super-classes

[Abdominal organ finding](#) ^c, [Urinary system finding](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Kidney disease](#) ^c

Kidney structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000151>

Body organ that filters blood for the secretion of urine and that regulates ion concentrations. [MeSH]

has super-classes

[Intra-abdominal urinary structure](#) ^c, [Kidney](#) ^c, [Retroperitoneal compartment structure](#) ^c, [Structure of organ within abdomen proper cavity](#) ^c,
[Structure of upper urinary system](#) ^c, [Structure of urinary organ](#) ^c

Knee^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000112>

A joint connecting the lower part of the femur with the upper part of the tibia. The lower part of the femur and the upper part of the tibia are attached to each other by ligaments. Other structures of the knee joint include the upper part of the fibula, located below and parallel to the tibia, and the patella which moves as the knee bends. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Structure of free lower limb](#)^c, [Structure of joint region of lower limb](#)^c

Known^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000135>

has super-classes

[Finding context value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Known absent](#)^c, [Known present](#)^c

Known absent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000140>

has super-classes

[Known](#)^c

Known present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000146>

has super-classes

[Known](#)^c

KPS 10^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000010>

has super-classes

[Performance status qualifier](#)^c

KPS 100^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000022>

Normal; no complaints; no evidence of disease. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Performance status qualifier](#)^c

KPS 20^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000016>

has super-classes

[Performance status qualifier](#)^c

KPS 30^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000015>

has super-classes

[Performance status qualifier](#)^c

KPS 40^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000014>

has super-classes

[Performance status qualifier](#)^c

KPS 50^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000021>

has super-classes

[Performance status qualifier](#)^c

KPS 60^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000011>

has super-classes

[Performance status qualifier](#)^c

KPS 70^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000099>

has super-classes

[Performance status qualifier](#)^c

KPS 80^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000098>

has super-classes

[Performance status qualifier](#)^c

KPS 90^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000013>

has super-classes

[Performance status qualifier](#)^c

KRAS (KRAS proto-oncogene, GTPase) gene variant measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063257>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[KRAS gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c

KRAS gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051887>

has super-classes

[KRAS \(KRAS proto-oncogene, GTPase\) gene variant measurement](#)^c

Laboratory^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000022>

has super-classes

[Observation Category](#)^c

Laboratory data interpretation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004145>

has super-classes

[Evaluation of test results](#)^c, [Evidence Type](#)^c

Laboratory procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033405>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anatomic pathology procedure](#)^c, [Chemistry](#)^c, [Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c, [Hormone measurement](#)^c, [Laboratory procedure categorized by method](#)^c, [Laboratory test](#)^c, [Mass-Molar conversion](#)^c, [Measurement of substance](#)^c, [Molecular pathology](#)^c, [Pathology](#)^c

Laboratory procedure categorized by method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034409>

has super-classes

[Laboratory procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Staining method](#)^c

Laboratory procedure performed^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035065>

has super-classes

[Laboratory procedures -general](#)^c, [Procedure carried out on subject](#)^c

Laboratory procedures -general^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034130>

has super-classes

[Procedure with explicit context](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Laboratory procedure performed](#)^c

Laboratory test^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033407>

has super-classes

[Evaluation procedure](#)^c, [Laboratory procedure](#)^c, [Procedure Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cytologic test](#)^c, [Genetic test](#)^c, [Hematocrit \[Volume Fraction\] of Blood](#)^c, [Histologic test](#)^c, [Leukocytes \[# /volume\] in Stem cell product](#)^c

Laboratory Test Result^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000202>

has super-classes

[Clinical Test Result](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Pathology Result](#)^c, [Positive Laboratory Test Result](#)^c

Lactate dehydrogenase [Enzymatic activity/volume] in Red Blood Cells^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033869>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#)^c, [Lactate dehydrogenase measurement](#)^c

Lactate dehydrogenase measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050587>

has super-classes

[Enzyme measurement](#)^c, [Protein measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lactate dehydrogenase \[Enzymatic activity/volume\] in Red Blood Cells](#)^c

Laparoscopic procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1019457>

has super-classes

[Endoscopic procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Robot assisted laparoscopic radical prostatectomy](#)^c

Laparoscopic Procedures on the Prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1019547>

has super-classes

[Surgical Procedures on the Prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Laparoscopy, surgical prostatectomy, retropubic radical, including nerve sparing, includes robotic assistance, when performed](#)^c

Laparoscopic prostatectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016193>

has super-classes

[Prostatectomy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Laparoscopic radical prostatectomy](#)^c

Laparoscopic radical prostatectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024148>

has super-classes

[Laparoscopic prostatectomy](#)^c

Laparoscopy, surgical prostatectomy, retropubic radical, including nerve sparing, includes robotic assistance, when performed^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1023400>

has super-classes

[Laparoscopic Procedures on the Prostate](#)^c

Lapatinib^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036006>

A synthetic, orally-active quinazoline with potential antineoplastic properties. Lapatinib reversibly blocks phosphorylation of the epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), ErbB2, and the Erk-1 and-2 and AKT kinases; it also inhibits cyclin D protein levels in human tumor cell lines and xenografts. EGFR and ErbB2 have been implicated in the growth of various tumor types. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Large cell carcinoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063535>

has super-classes

[Epithelial neoplasms, NOS](#)^c

Large cell carcinoma, NOS, of lung, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063110>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049475>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049645>

has super-classes

[Epithelial neoplasms, NOS](#)^c

Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024003>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Large intestine excision^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057196>

has super-classes

[Excision of intestinal structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of lesion of large intestine](#)^c, [Partial excision of large intestine](#)^c

Large intestine part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000141>

has super-classes

[Structure of large intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Region of large intestine](#)^c

Late arterial phase^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016763>

has super-classes

[Arterial phase](#)^c

Late venous phase^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016766>

has super-classes

[Postarterial phase](#)^c

Laterality^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016305>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bilateral](#)^c, [Left](#)^c, [Right](#)^c, [Unilateral](#)^c

is in range of

[hasLaterality](#)^{op}

Latino^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001205>

has super-classes

[Hispanic or Latino](#)^c

LCIS (lobular carcinoma in situ) of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002304>

has super-classes

[Carcinoma in situ of breast](#)^c

Left^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016670>

has super-classes

[Laterality](#)^c, [Side](#)^c, [Topographical modifier](#)^c

Left anterior apical part of transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000217>

has super-classes

[Left apical transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

Left anterior apical peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000256>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the anterior portion of the apical division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Left apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

Left anterior basal peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000235>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the anterior portion of the basal division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Left basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

Left anterior basal transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000089>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the anterior portion of the basal division of the transition zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Left basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

Left anterior middle peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000216>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the anterior portion of the middle division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Left lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

Left anterior middle transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000036>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the anterior portion of the middle division of the transition zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Left middle transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

Left apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000140>

The portion of the fibromuscular stroma of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the apical division of the anterior lobe. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of left half of prostate](#)^c

Left apical peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000090>

has super-classes

[Apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of left half of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left anterior apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left posterolateral apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left posteromedial apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c

Left apical transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000188>

has super-classes

[Apical transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of left half of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left anterior apical part of transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left posterior apical part of transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Left basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000206>

has super-classes

[Basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of left half of prostate](#)^c

Left basal peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000004>

has super-classes

[Basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of left half of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left anterior basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left posterolateral basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c

Left basal transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000255>

has super-classes

[Basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of left half of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left anterior basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left posterior basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Left breast structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000165>

has super-classes

[Breast structure^c](#), [Left thorax structure^c](#)

Left colectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060292>

has super-classes

[Partial resection of colon^c](#)

Left colon structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063287>

has super-classes

[Region of colon^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Descending colon structure^c](#)

Left lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000082>

has super-classes

[Middle peripheral zone of prostate^c](#), [Structure of left half of prostate^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Left anterior middle peripheral zone of prostate^c](#), [Left posterolateral middle peripheral zone of prostate^c](#), [Left posteromedial middle peripheral zone of prostate^c](#)

Left middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000148>

The portion of the fibromuscular stroma of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the middle division of the anterior lobe. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate^c](#), [Structure of left half of prostate^c](#)

Left middle transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000197>

has super-classes

[Middle transition zone of prostate^c](#), [Structure of left half of prostate^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Left anterior middle transition zone of prostate^c](#), [Left posterior middle transition zone of prostate^c](#)

Left posterior apical part of transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000226>

has super-classes

[Left apical transition zone of prostate^c](#), [Structure of posterior section of prostate^c](#)

Left posterior basal transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000245>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the posterior portion of the basal division of the transition zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Left basal transition zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#) ^c

Left posterior middle transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000038>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the posterior portion of the middle division of the transition zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Left middle transition zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#) ^c

Left posterolateral apical peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000026>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the posterolateral portion of the apical division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Left apical peripheral zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#) ^c

Left posterolateral basal peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000176>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the posterolateral portion of the basal division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Left basal peripheral zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#) ^c

Left posterolateral middle peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000167>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the posterolateral portion of the middle division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Left lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#) ^c

Left posteromedial apical peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000016>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the posteromedial portion of the apical division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Left apical peripheral zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#) ^c

Left posteromedial middle peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000244>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical left side of the posteromedial portion of the middle division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Left lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#) ^c

Left thorax structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000260>

has super-classes

[Structure of half of thorax lateral to midsagittal plane](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Left breast structure](#) ^c

Length dimension of neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034812>

has super-classes

[Measurement](#)^c, [Neoplasm observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary tumor size](#)^c

Length of lymph node in excised specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050846>

has super-classes

[Lymph node observable](#)^c

Lentiginosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052976>

has super-classes

[Hamartoma](#)^c, [Lentigo](#)^c, [Mass of body structure](#)^c, [Melanosis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Peutz-Jeghers syndrome](#)^c

Lentigo^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053225>

has super-classes

[Disorder of skin pigmentation](#)^c, [Hamartoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lentiginosis](#)^c

Lesion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016402>

[PI-RADS] A localized pathological or traumatic structural change, damage, deformity, or discontinuity of tissue, organ, or body part. [LI-RADS]: An observation that represents a pathologic abnormality. [RADLEX]

has super-classes

[Imaging observation](#)^c, [Morphologically abnormal structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Damage](#)^c, [Dysplasia](#)^c, [Mass](#)^c, [Mechanical lesion](#)^c

is in domain of

[TumorIdentifier](#)^{dp}

is in range of

[hasRelatedTumor](#)^{op}

Lesion observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047971>

has super-classes

[Clinical history/examination observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lesion size](#)^c

Lesion of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044822>

has super-classes

[Disease of liver](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hepatic fibrosis](#)^c, [Liver damage](#)^c, [Liver mass](#)^c

Lesion of lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051644>

has super-classes

[Disorder of lung](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Fibrosis of lung](#)^c, [Neoplasm of lung](#)^c, [Nodule of lung](#)^c

Lesion of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007130>

has super-classes

[Disorder of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Prostate mass](#)^c

Lesion of rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051707>

has super-classes

[Disorder of rectum](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of rectum](#)^c

Lesion of uterus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003155>

has super-classes

[Disorder of uterus](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of uterus](#)^c

Lesion Site^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063492>

Specifies the anatomic site of a localized pathological or traumatic structural change, damage, deformity, or discontinuity of tissue, organ, or body part. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Anatomic Site](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brain Lesion Site](#)^c

Lesion size^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1019638>

has super-classes

[Lesion observable](#)^c, [Measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lesion size, additional dimension](#)^c, [Lesion size, greatest dimension](#)^c

is in range of

[Has Associated Dimension](#)^{op}

Lesion size, additional dimension^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1029703>

has super-classes

[Lesion size](#)^c

Lesion size, greatest dimension^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1029832>

has super-classes

[Lesion size](#)^c

Less than one cigarette per day^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001154>

has super-classes

[Number of cigarettes per day](#)^c

Letrozole^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036088>

A nonsteroidal inhibitor of estrogen synthesis with antineoplastic activity. As a third-generation aromatase inhibitor, letrozole selectively and reversibly inhibits aromatase, which may result in growth inhibition of estrogen-dependent breast cancer cells. Aromatase, a cytochrome P-450 enzyme localized to the endoplasmic reticulum of the cell and found in many tissues including those of the premenopausal ovary, liver, and breast, catalyzes the aromatization of androstenedione and testosterone into estrone and estradiol, the final step in estrogen biosynthesis. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

leucovorin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063654>

has super-classes

[Chemotherapy protective agent](#)^c

Leukemia Finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051858>

A term that refers to clinicopathologic findings related to leukemias. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c, [Risk Assessment](#)^c

Leukocytes [#]/volume] in Stem cell product^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033414>

has super-classes

[Laboratory test](#)^c

Leukopenia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036513>

has super-classes

[Blood leukocyte number below reference range](#)^c, [White blood cell disorder](#)^c

Level 1 axillary clearance of lymph nodes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060502>

has super-classes

[Excision of axillary lymph nodes group](#)^c

Level 2 axillary clearance of lymph nodes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060524>

has super-classes

[Excision of axillary lymph nodes group](#)^c

Level 3 axillary clearance of lymph nodes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060547>

has super-classes

[Excision of axillary lymph nodes group](#)^c

LI-RADS 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005506>

Definitely benign. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[LI-RADS assessment](#)^c

LI-RADS 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005505>

Probably benign. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[LI-RADS assessment](#)^c

LI-RADS 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005504>

Intermediate probability for HCC. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[LI-RADS assessment](#)^c

LI-RADS 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005503>

Probably HCC. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[LI-RADS assessment](#)^c

LI-RADS 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005502>

Definitely HCC. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[LI-RADS assessment](#)^c

LI-RADS assessment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005501>

has super-classes

[Assessment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[LI-RADS 1](#)^c, [LI-RADS 2](#)^c, [LI-RADS 3](#)^c, [LI-RADS 4](#)^c, [LI-RADS 5](#)^c, [LI-RADS M](#)^c, [LI-RADS Treated](#)^c

LI-RADS M^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005509>

Probably malignant, not specific for HCC. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[LI-RADS assessment](#)^c

LI-RADS Treated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005508>

Treated observation. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[LI-RADS assessment](#)^c

Lifetime non-drinker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056336>

has super-classes

[Non - drinker](#)^c

Lifetime non-drinker of alcohol^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056335>

has super-classes

[Non - drinker](#)^c

Light cigarette smoker (1-9 cigarettes per day)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059171>

has super-classes

[Cigarette smoker](#)^c

Light drinker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056339>

has super-classes

[Current drinker](#)^c

Light microscopy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018531>

has super-classes

[Microscopy \(procedure\)](#)^c, [Tumor Size Method](#)^c

Likert scale^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037291>

A psychometric scale commonly used in questionnaires where a respondent is asked to evaluate an opinion according to subjective or objective criteria, by rating their level of agreement or disagreement with a statement. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Assessment scales](#)^c

Limited^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002501>

has super-classes

[Extensiveness](#)^c

Lipids measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050453>

has super-classes

[Measurement of substance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cholesterol measurement](#)^c, [Triglycerides measurement](#)^c

Liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063728>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Liver structure](#)^c

Liver and intrahepatic bile ducts^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000035>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Liver structure](#)^c

Liver and/or biliary structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000115>

has super-classes

[Cross-sectional abdomen](#)^c, [Digestive organ structure](#)^c, [Intra-abdominal digestive structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Liver structure](#)^c

Liver cell carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043447>

A malignant tumor that arises from hepatocytes. Hepatocellular carcinoma is relatively rare in the United States but very common in all African countries south of the Sahara and in Southeast Asia. Most cases are seen in patients over the age of 50 years, but this tumor can also occur in younger individuals and even in children. Hepatocellular carcinoma is more common in males than females and is associated with hepatitis B, hepatitis C, chronic alcohol abuse and cirrhosis. Serum elevation of alpha-fetoprotein occurs in a large percentage of patients with hepatocellular carcinoma. Grossly, hepatocellular carcinoma may present as a single mass, as multiple nodules, or as diffuse liver involvement. Microscopically, there is a wide range of differentiation from tumor to tumor (well differentiated to poorly differentiated tumors). Hepatocellular carcinomas quickly metastasize to regional lymph nodes and lung. The overall median survival of untreated liver cell carcinoma is about 4 months. The most effective treatment of hepatocellular carcinoma is complete resection of the tumor. Lately, an increasing number of tumors have been treated with liver transplantation. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Adenocarcinoma of liver](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Fibrolamellar hepatocellular carcinoma](#)^c

Liver damage^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036742>

has super-classes

[Abdominal cavity injury](#)^c, [Disease of liver](#)^c, [Gastrointestinal and digestive injury](#)^c, [Lesion of liver](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alcoholic liver damage](#)^c

Liver disorder due to infection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038518>

has super-classes

[Disease^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Infection of liver caused by parasite^c](#)

Liver finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043328>

has super-classes

[Abdominal organ finding^c](#), [Performance Status Assessment Answer Finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Child-Pugh score class A^c](#), [Child-Pugh score class B^c](#), [Child-Pugh score class C^c](#), [Disease of liver^c](#)

Liver lobe part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000437>

has super-classes

[Lobe of liver^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Couinaud hepatic segment V^c](#), [Couinaud hepatic segment VI^c](#), [Couinaud hepatic segment VII^c](#), [Couinaud hepatic segment VIII^c](#)

Liver mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037903>

has super-classes

[Abdominal mass^c](#), [Lesion of liver^c](#), [Mass of digestive structure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Abscess of liver^c](#), [Cyst of liver^c](#)

Liver part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000425>

has super-classes

[Liver structure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Liver segment^c](#), [Lobe of liver^c](#)

Liver regeneration^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036412>

has super-classes

[Disease of liver^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Cirrhosis of liver^c](#)

Liver segment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000428>

has super-classes

[Liver part^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Couinaud liver segment^c](#)

Liver structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000105>

A triangular-shaped organ located under the diaphragm in the right hypochondrium. It is the largest internal organ of the body, weighting up to 2 kg. Metabolism and bile secretion are its main functions. It is composed of cells which have the ability to regenerate. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Liver](#)^c, [Liver and intrahepatic bile ducts](#)^c, [Liver and/or biliary structure](#)^c, [Structure of organ within abdomen proper cavity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Liver part](#)^c

Liver tumor morphology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049454>

has super-classes

[Adenoma AND/OR adenocarcinoma](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hepatocellular carcinoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Lobe of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000426>

has super-classes

[Liver part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Liver lobe part](#)^c, [Structure of caudate lobe of liver](#)^c

Lobectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004599>

has super-classes

[Excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lobectomy of brain](#)^c

Lobectomy of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004595>

Surgical removal of a lobe of the brain. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Excision of brain](#)^c, [Lobectomy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Partial lobectomy of brain](#)^c, [Total lobectomy of brain](#)^c

Lobular^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1010772>

[PI-RADS]: Composed of lobules with undulating contour [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Morphologic descriptor](#)^c

Lobular carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049481>

is equivalent to

[Lobular carcinoma, NOS](#)^c

has super-classes

[Ductal, lobular AND/OR medullary neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Lobular carcinoma in situ (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049675>

is equivalent to

[Lobular carcinoma in situ, NOS](#)^c

has super-classes

[Carcinoma in situ \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Lobular carcinoma in situ, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052223>

has super-classes

[Ductal and lobular neoplasms](#)^c

Lobular carcinoma in situ, NOS, of breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060835>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Lobular carcinoma in situ, pleomorphic of breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060838>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Lobular carcinoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052212>

has super-classes

[Ductal and lobular neoplasms](#)^c

Lobular carcinoma, NOS, of breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060847>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Local^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002498>

has super-classes

[Extensiveness](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Localized](#)^c

Local excision^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060326>

has super-classes

[Excision](#)^c

Localized^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002497>

has super-classes

[Disease Clinical Qualifier](#)^c, [Local](#)^c

Longitudinal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000019>

has super-classes

[Topographical modifier](#)^c

Longitudinal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000006>

has super-classes

[Collection method](#)^c

Low^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002172>

has super-classes

[Degree findings](#)^c, [General adjectival modifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Very low](#)^c

Low ADC value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005446>

has super-classes

[ADC value](#)^c

Low anterior resection of rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060272>

has super-classes

[Anterior resection of rectum](#)^c

Low density lipoprotein cholesterol measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033657>

has super-classes

[Cholesterol measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cholesterol in LDL \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Low dose^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016778>

has super-classes

[Modality descriptor](#)^c

Low dose rate brachytherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058847>

has super-classes

[Brachytherapy](#)^c

Low histologic grade^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001373>

Used to describe tumor samples that exhibit well to moderately well differentiated cells. They are generally expected to be slow growing and less aggressive. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Histological grades](#) ^c

Low risk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000136>

The potential future harm that may arise from some present action or attribute or condition is small. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Adjectival modifier](#) ^c, [Risk assessment value](#) ^c

Low risk of recurrence, prostate cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1023463>

has super-classes

[Diagnostic/Screening Processes or Results](#) ^c

Low-Dose Computed Tomography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000086>

is equivalent to

[Computed tomography](#) ^c and ([hasModalityDescriptor](#) ^{op} some [Low dose](#) ^c)

has super-classes

[Computed tomography](#) ^c

Lower body part structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000022>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#) ^c, [Pelvis and lower extremities](#) ^c

Lower bowel structures^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000236>

has super-classes

[Intra-pelvic structure of true pelvis](#) ^c, [Structure of large intestine](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Rectum structure](#) ^c

Lower extremity part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000409>

has super-classes

[Extremity part](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Connective, Subcutaneous and other soft tissues of lower limb and hip](#) ^c

Lower gastrointestinal procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1010812>

has super-classes

[Procedure on abdomen](#) ^c

Lower respiratory tract observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050834>

has super-classes

[Respiratory observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung observable](#)^c

Lower respiratory tract specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055721>

has super-classes

[Specimen from respiratory system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Specimen from lung](#)^c

Lower respiratory tract structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000164>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung structure](#)^c

Lower-inner quadrant of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000283>

has super-classes

[Breast](#)^c

Lower-outer quadrant of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000282>

has super-classes

[Breast](#)^c

Lumbar spine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000064>

Those vertebrae between the ribs and the pelvis, L1-L5 in man. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Spine](#)^c, [Structure of musculoskeletal system of lumbar spine](#)^c, [Structure of vertebral region of lumbar part of back](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lumbosacral spine](#)^c

Lumbosacral region of spine structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000068>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Sacrum](#)^c

Lumbosacral spine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000199>

The part of the spine in the lower back that consists of the lumbar region and the sacrum. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Lumbar spine](#)^c

Luminal A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007983>

A biologic subset of breast carcinoma defined by high expression of genes characteristic of luminal epithelial cells, including estrogen receptor (ER), estrogen regulated protein LIV-1, and the transcription factors hepatocyte nuclear factor 3, HNF3A, XBP1, and GATA 3. This subtype of breast cancer is associated with a good prognosis. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[HER2 negative](#)^c and [MKI67 Negative](#)^c and ([ER positive](#)^c or [PR positive](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Breast Carcinoma by Gene Expression Profile](#)^c

Luminal androgen receptor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046257>

has super-classes

[Triple-negative breast cancer](#)^c

Luminal B^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007982>

A biologic subset of breast carcinoma defined by low to moderate expression of genes characteristic of luminal epithelial cells including estrogen receptor (ER), and high expression of GGH, LAPTM4B, and CCNE1. This subtype of breast cancer is associated with a good prognosis, although not as favorable as the luminal A subtype. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[MKI67 Positive](#)^c and ([ER positive](#)^c or [PR positive](#)^c) and ([HER2 positive](#)^c or [HER2 negative](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Breast Carcinoma by Gene Expression Profile](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Luminal B- HER2 negative](#)^c, [Luminal B- HER2 positive](#)^c

Luminal B- HER2 negative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007985>

is equivalent to

[HER2 negative](#)^c and [MKI67 Positive](#)^c and ([ER positive](#)^c or [PR positive](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Luminal B](#)^c

Luminal B- HER2 positive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007984>

is equivalent to

[HER2 positive](#)^c and [MKI67 Positive](#)^c and ([ER positive](#)^c or [PR positive](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Luminal B](#)^c

Lumpectomy of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060316>

has super-classes

[Excision of mass of breast](#)^c, [Partial mastectomy](#)^c

Lung excision^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060442>

has super-classes

[Excision of lung or bronchus](#)^c, [Thorax excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Total pneumonectomy](#)^c

Lung finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051427>

has super-classes

[Finding of region of thorax](#)^c, [Viscus structure finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of lung](#)^c, [Lung mass](#)^c

Lung involvement stages^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044437>

has super-classes

[Generic anatomical site tumor invasion status](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung stage L1](#)^c, [Lung stage L2](#)^c, [Lung stage L3](#)^c

Lung mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051545>

has super-classes

[Lung finding](#)^c, [Mass of respiratory structure](#)^c, [Mass of thoracic structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of lung](#)^c, [Nodule of lung](#)^c

Lung observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050837>

has super-classes

[Lower respiratory tract observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung volume AND/OR capacity](#)^c

Lung part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000050>

has super-classes

[Lung structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of lobe of lung](#)^c

Lung stage L1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044434>

has super-classes

[Lung involvement stages](#)^c

Lung stage L2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044439>

has super-classes

[Lung involvement stages](#)^c

Lung stage L3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044438>

has super-classes

[Lung involvement stages](#)^c

Lung structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000113>

Either of the pair of organs occupying the cavity of the thorax that effect the aeration of the blood. [MeSH]

is equivalent to

[Lung, NOS](#)^c

has super-classes

[Lower respiratory tract structure](#)^c, [Pulmonary structure including vessels and lymphoid tissue](#)^c, [Structure of organ in respiratory system](#)^c,

[Structure of pulmopleural compartment](#)^c, [Structure of thoracic viscus](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung part](#)^c

Lung volume^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050867>

has super-classes

[Lung volume AND/OR capacity](#)^c

Lung volume AND/OR capacity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050841>

has super-classes

[Lung observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung volume](#)^c

Lung, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063787>

has super-classes

[Bronchus and lung](#)^c

Lymph node observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035012>

has super-classes

[Observable entity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Length of lymph node in excised specimen](#)^c, [Lymph node station of involved lymph nodes](#)^c, [Number of lymph nodes containing metastatic neoplasm in excised specimen](#)^c, [Number of lymph nodes examined by microscopy in excised specimen](#)^c

Lymph node station of involved lymph nodes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050852>

has super-classes

[Lymph node observable](#)^c

Lymph node structure of limb^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000150>

has super-classes

[Extremity part](#)^c, [Regional lymph node structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Upper limb lymph node structure](#)^c

Lymph Nodes with Metastasis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033229>

has super-classes

[Metastasis](#)^c

Lymphatic (small vessel) tumor invasion finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016232>

has super-classes

[Tumor invasion finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lymphatic small vessel invasion by tumor absent](#)^c, [Lymphatic small vessel invasion by tumor present](#)^c

Lymphatic small vessel invasion by tumor absent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1026803>

has super-classes

[Lymphatic \(small vessel\) tumor invasion finding](#)^c

Lymphatic small vessel invasion by tumor present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1026907>

has super-classes

[Lymphatic \(small vessel\) tumor invasion finding](#)^c

Lymphatic system excision^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050995>

has super-classes

[Excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of lymph node](#)^c

Lymphoid neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049379>

has super-classes

[Hematopoietic neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant lymphoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Lymphovascular invasion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036607>

A term referring to the presence of tumor emboli or tumor masses within lymphatic vessels. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lymphovascular invasion extent](#)^c

Lymphovascular invasion extent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036632>

has super-classes

[Lymphovascular invasion](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lymphovascular invasion extent](#) | [Cancer specimen](#) | [Pathology](#)^c

Lymphovascular invasion extent in Cancer specimen Qualitative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045826>

has super-classes

[Lymphovascular invasion extent](#) | [Cancer specimen](#) | [Pathology](#)^c, [Pathology](#)^c

Lymphovascular invasion extent | Cancer specimen | Pathology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036658>

has super-classes

[Lymphovascular invasion extent](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lymphovascular invasion extent in Cancer specimen Qualitative](#)^c

Lynch syndrome^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059052>

has super-classes

[Autosomal dominant hereditary disorder](#)^c, [Hereditary cancer-predisposing syndrome](#)^c

M - Metastatic marker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044444>

has super-classes

[Markers for liver tumor staging](#)^c

M category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033323>

One criteria of the TNM staging system. M refers to the presence of metastasis. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[TNM category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[cM category](#)^c, [pM category](#)^c

Macrocalcifications^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000221>

Image annotation label (INCISIVE, Annotation Definitions and guidelines)

BI-RADS US:Macrocalcifications are coarse calcifications that are 0.5mm or greater in size. As in other areas of the body, macrocalcifications will attenuate the acoustic beam and cause acoustic shadowing. [RADLEX]

has super-classes

[Calcification disorder](#)^c

Magnetic resonance angiography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004462>

Non-invasive method of vascular imaging and determination of internal anatomy without injection of contrast media or radiation exposure. The technique is used especially in cerebral angiography as well as for studies of other vascular structures. [MeSH]

has super-classes

[Magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Magnetic resonance venography](#)^c

Magnetic resonance imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000022>

Imaging that uses radiofrequency waves and a strong magnetic field rather than x-rays to provide detailed pictures of internal organs and tissues. The technique is valuable for the diagnosis of many pathologic conditions, including cancer, heart and vascular disease, stroke, and joint and musculoskeletal disorders. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI of chest](#)^c, [MRI of pelvis](#)^c, [Magnetic resonance imaging guidance](#)^c, [Multiparametric magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c

Magnetic resonance imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000038>

Non-invasive method of demonstrating internal anatomy based on the principle that atomic nuclei in a strong magnetic field absorb pulses of radiofrequency energy and emit them as radiowaves which can be reconstructed into computerized images. The concept includes proton spin tomographic techniques. [MeSH]

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Diffusion MRI](#)^c, [Dynamic contrast-enhanced magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c, [Functional magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c, [Magnetic resonance angiography](#)^c, [Perfusion Magnetic Resonance Imaging](#)^c, [T1-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging](#)^c

Magnetic resonance imaging guidance^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005480>

has super-classes

[Imaging guidance](#)^c, [Magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI guided biopsy](#)^c

Magnetic resonance imaging of breast for screening for malignant neoplasm procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016600>

has super-classes

[MRI of breast for screening](#)^c, [Screening for malignant neoplasm of breast](#)^c

Magnetic resonance spectroscopy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000083>

Spectroscopic method of measuring the magnetic moment of elementary particles such as atomic nuclei, protons or electrons. It is employed in clinical applications such as nmr tomography (magnetic resonance imaging). [MeSH]

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#)^c

Magnetic resonance venography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004469>

has super-classes

[Magnetic resonance angiography](#)^c

MALE^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000176>

is equivalent to

[Male](#)^c

has super-classes

[Gender](#)^c

is disjoint with

[FEMALE](#)^c

Male^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001366>

has super-classes

[Sex assigned at birth](#)^c

is disjoint with

[Female](#)^c

Male (finding)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001366>

has super-classes

[Finding related to biological sex](#)^c

Male genital organ structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000193>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

Male genital sample^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1013757>

has super-classes

[Specimen from genital system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Specimen from prostate](#)^c

Malignant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000051>

Image annotation label (INCISIVE, Annotation Definitions and guidelines)

Refers to abnormal cell activity manifested by decreased control over growth and function, causing tumor growth or spread into surrounding tissue and adverse effects to the host. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Disease morphology qualifier](#)^c, [General adjectival modifier](#)^c

Malignant adenomatous neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007248>

has super-classes

[Malignant epithelial neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma of liver](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma of pelvis](#)^c, [Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#)^c

Malignant adenomatous neoplasm (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036902>

has super-classes

[Adenoma AND/OR adenocarcinoma](#) ^c, [Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation](#) ^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma](#) ^c, [Apocrine adenocarcinoma](#) ^c, [Basal cell adenocarcinoma](#) ^c, [Cholangiocarcinoma](#) ^c, [Follicular adenocarcinoma](#) ^c, [Hepatocellular carcinoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c, [Insular carcinoma](#) ^c, [Oxyphilic adenocarcinoma](#) ^c, [Papillary adenocarcinoma](#) ^c, [Papillary carcinoma, follicular variant](#) ^c, [Trabecular adenocarcinoma](#) ^c

Malignant basal cell tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049356>

has super-classes

[Basal cell neoplasm \(morphology\)](#) ^c, [Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Basal cell adenocarcinoma](#) ^c

Malignant colorectal neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053270>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of large intestine](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of cecum](#) ^c

Malignant epithelial neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000171>

A malignant tumor arising from epithelial cells. Carcinomas that arise from glandular epithelium are called adenocarcinomas, those that arise from squamous epithelium are called squamous cell carcinomas, and those that arise from transitional epithelium are called transitional cell carcinomas. Morphologically, the malignant epithelial cells may display abnormal mitotic figures, anaplasia, and necrosis. Carcinomas are graded by the degree of cellular differentiation as well, moderately, or poorly differentiated. Carcinomas invade the surrounding tissues and tend to metastasize to other anatomic sites. Lung carcinoma, skin carcinoma, breast carcinoma, colon carcinoma, and prostate carcinoma are the most frequently seen carcinomas. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma of breast](#) ^c, [Carcinoma of colon](#) ^c, [Carcinoma of uterus](#) ^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of ascending colon](#) ^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of colon, NOS](#) ^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of descending colon](#) ^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of rectum, NOS](#) ^c, [Infiltrating duct carcinoma of prostate](#) ^c, [Malignant adenomatous neoplasm](#) ^c, [Small cell carcinoma](#) ^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma](#) ^c

Malignant epithelial neoplasm (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049181>

has super-classes

[Epithelial neoplasm](#) ^c, [Malignant neoplasm](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma](#) ^c, [Carcinoma with osteoclast-like giant cells](#) ^c, [Infiltrating carcinoma with ductal and lobular features](#) ^c, [Infiltrating duct carcinoma](#) ^c, [Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c, [Malignant basal cell tumor](#) ^c, [Malignant squamous cell neoplasm](#) ^c, [Small cell carcinoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c

is disjoint with

[Benign epithelial neoplasm](#) ^c

Malignant glioma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000061>

A grade 3 or grade 4 glioma arising from the central nervous system. This category includes glioblastoma, anaplastic astrocytoma, anaplastic ependymoma, anaplastic oligodendroglioma, and anaplastic oligoastrocytoma. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Gliomatosis cerebri](#)^c, [Gliosarcoma](#)^c, [High grade glioma](#)^c, [Oligodendroglioma](#)^c

Malignant glioma of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007970>

has super-classes

[Malignant glioma of central nervous system](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of brain](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glioblastoma multiforme of brain](#)^c, [Gliomatosis cerebri](#)^c

Malignant glioma of brainstem^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007974>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of brainstem](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Diffuse intrinsic pontine glioma](#)^c

Malignant glioma of central nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054130>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of central nervous system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant glioma of brain](#)^c

Malignant hematopoietic neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049293>

has super-classes

[Hematopoietic neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant lymphoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Malignant lymphoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039310>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of lymphoid hemopoietic and related tissue](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant lymphoma of liver](#)^c, [Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma \(clinical\)](#)^c

Malignant lymphoma (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049334>

has super-classes

[Lymphoid neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant hematopoietic neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Non-Hodgkin lymphoma](#)^c

Malignant lymphoma of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046321>

has super-classes

[Malignant lymphoma](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of liver](#)^c

Malignant lymphoma, non-Hodgkin, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049660>

has super-classes

[Malignant lymphomas, NOS or diffuse](#)^c

Malignant lymphoma, non-Hodgkin, NOS, of unknown primary site^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021456>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Malignant lymphoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049661>

has super-classes

[Malignant lymphomas, NOS or diffuse](#)^c

Malignant lymphomas, NOS or diffuse^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049553>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant lymphoma, NOS](#)^c, [Malignant lymphoma, non-Hodgkin, NOS](#)^c

Malignant meningeal neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049492>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Meningioma, malignant](#)^c

Malignant meningioma of meninges of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059402>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of cerebral meninges](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant meningioma of meninges of brain](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049106>

is equivalent to

[Neoplasm, malignant](#)^c

has super-classes

[Neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Acinar cell carcinoma](#)^c, [Infiltrating duct carcinoma](#)^c, [Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma](#)^c, [Lobular carcinoma](#)^c, [Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Malignant glioma](#)^c, [Malignant hematopoietic neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant meningeal neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm, epithelial](#)^c, [Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm, neural](#)^c, [Malignant phyllodes tumor](#)^c, [Neoplasm, metastatic](#)^c, [Sarcoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Small cell carcinoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Transitional cell carcinoma](#)^c

is disjoint with

[Neoplasm, benign](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007367>

has super-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of intraabdominal organ](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of abdomen](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of anorectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000105>

has super-classes

[Anorectal disorder](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of gastrointestinal tract](#)^c, [Neoplasm of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of rectum](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of areola^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000211>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of breast](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm: Nipple and areola](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of bladder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000181>

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{OP} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{OP} some [Bladder](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of urinary bladder](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of bone^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000172>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of skeletal system](#)^c, [Neoplasm of bone](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007976>

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{OP} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{OP} some [Brain](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of central nervous system](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of head and neck](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant glioma of brain](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of brainstem](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of brain](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of brainstem^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007975>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of brain](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant glioma of brainstem](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000060>

A carcinoma arising from the breast, most commonly the terminal ductal-lobular unit. It is the most common malignant tumor in females. Risk factors include country of birth, family history, menstrual and reproductive history, fibrocystic disease and epithelial hyperplasia, exogenous estrogens, contraceptive agents, and ionizing radiation. The vast majority of breast carcinomas are adenocarcinomas (ductal or lobular). Breast carcinoma spreads by direct invasion, by the lymphatic route, and by the blood vessel route. The most common site of lymph node involvement is the axilla. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#) ^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#) ^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#) ^{op} some [Breast](#) ^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of thorax](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of breast](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma of breast](#) ^c, [Malignant neoplasm of areola](#) ^c, [Malignant neoplasm of female breast](#) ^c, [Malignant neoplasm of nipple](#) ^c, [Malignant neoplasm: Nipple and areola](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of breast](#) ^c

Malignant neoplasm of bronchus and lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000084>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of lower respiratory tract](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of bronchus](#) ^c, [Malignant tumor of lung](#) ^c

Malignant neoplasm of central nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054129>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of nervous system](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant glioma of central nervous system](#) ^c, [Malignant neoplasm of brain](#) ^c, [Malignant tumor of meninges](#) ^c

Malignant neoplasm of cerebral meninges^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059401>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of head and neck](#) ^c, [Malignant tumor of meninges](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant meningioma of meninges of brain](#) ^c

Malignant neoplasm of cervix uteri^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003317>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of uterus](#) ^c, [Malignant tumor of female genital organ](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma of cervix](#) ^c, [Carcinoma of cervix](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of uterine cervix](#) ^c

Malignant neoplasm of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000057>

A malignant epithelial neoplasm that arises from the colon and invades through the muscularis mucosa into the submucosa. The vast majority are adenocarcinomas. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#) ^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#) ^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#) ^{op} some [Colon](#) ^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of colon and/or rectum](#) ^c, [Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of colon](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma of colon](#) ^c, [Malignant tumor of ascending colon](#) ^c, [Malignant tumor of descending colon](#) ^c, [Malignant tumor of sigmoid colon](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of colon](#) ^c

Malignant neoplasm of colon and/or rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000054>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of large intestine^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of colon^c](#), [Malignant neoplasm of rectum^c](#)

Malignant neoplasm of digestive system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051070>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of digestive system^c](#), [Primary Cancer Condition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of gastrointestinal tract^c](#), [Malignant tumor of digestive organ^c](#)

Malignant neoplasm of female breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046621>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of breast^c](#), [Neoplasm of female breast^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of female breast^c](#)

Malignant neoplasm of gallbladder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000089>

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology^{op}](#) some [Malignant neoplasm^c](#)) and ([hasFindingSite^{op}](#) some [Gallbladder^c](#))

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of intraabdominal organ^c](#), [Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of gallbladder^c](#)

Malignant neoplasm of gastrointestinal tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051085>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of digestive system^c](#), [Neoplasm of gastrointestinal tract^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of anorectum^c](#), [Malignant tumor of intestine^c](#)

Malignant neoplasm of genital structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003548>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of genitourinary organ^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma of genital organ^c](#), [Malignant tumor of male genital organ^c](#)

Malignant neoplasm of genitourinary organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007853>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of trunk^c](#), [Primary Cancer Condition^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of genital structure^c](#)

Malignant neoplasm of intraabdominal organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000098>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of abdomen](#)^c, [Neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of gallbladder](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of liver](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of uterus](#)^c,
[Malignant tumor of intestine](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of kidney](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000071>

A carcinoma that arises from the hepatocytes or intrahepatic bile ducts. The main subtypes are hepatocellular carcinoma (hepatoma) and cholangiocarcinoma. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Liver](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of intraabdominal organ](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of digestive organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of liver](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma of liver](#)^c, [Malignant lymphoma of liver](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of liver](#)^c, [Sarcoma of liver](#)^c

is disjoint with

[Benign neoplasm of liver](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of lower respiratory tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000083>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of respiratory system](#)^c, [Neoplasm of lower respiratory tract](#)^c, [Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of bronchus and lung](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of bronchus](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of lung](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054127>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of nervous system](#)^c, [Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of central nervous system](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of nervous system](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of nipple^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000212>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of breast](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm: Nipple and areola](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of oesophagus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000094>

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Esophagus](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of digestive organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of esophagus](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of other connective and soft tissue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007996>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of soft tissue](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of ovary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003311>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of female genital organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of ovary](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of ovary](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of pancreas^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000079>

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Pancreas](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of digestive organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma of pancreas](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000075>

One of the most common malignant tumors afflicting men. The majority of carcinomas arise in the peripheral zone and a minority occur in the central or the transitional zone of the prostate gland. Grossly, prostatic carcinomas appear as ill-defined yellow areas of discoloration in the prostate gland lobes. Adenocarcinomas represent the overwhelming majority of prostatic carcinomas. Prostatic-specific antigen (PSA) serum test is widely used as a screening test for the early detection of prostatic carcinoma. Treatment options include radical prostatectomy, radiation therapy, androgen ablation and cryotherapy. Watchful waiting or surveillance alone is an option for older patients with low-grade or low-stage disease. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Prostate](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of intraabdominal organ](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of male genital organ](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of pelvis](#)^c, [Neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma of prostate](#)^c, [Hormone refractory prostate cancer](#)^c, [Hormone sensitive prostate cancer](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma of prostate](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000077>

A malignant epithelial neoplasm that arises from the rectum. The vast majority are adenocarcinomas. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Rectum](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of anorectum](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of colon and/or rectum](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of pelvis](#)^c, [Neoplasm of rectum](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of rectum](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of respiratory system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051577>

has super-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c, [Tumor of respiratory system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of lower respiratory tract](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of respiratory tract](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of skeletal system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000170>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of skeletal system](#)^c, [Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of bone](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of soft tissue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007997>

has super-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of other connective and soft tissue](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of stomach^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000090>

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Stomach](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of stomach](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of thorax^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000078>

A primary or metastatic malignant neoplasm affecting the tissues of the thorax. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of thorax](#)^c, [Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of breast](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of bronchus](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of lung](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intrathoracic organs](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of thyroid gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059392>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of neck](#)^c, [Neoplasm of thyroid gland](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of uterus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003316>

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Uterus](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of intraabdominal organ](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of female genital organ](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of pelvis](#)^c, [Neoplasm of uterus](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma of uterus](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of cervix uteri](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of uterus](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of vagina^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003315>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of female genital organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of vagina](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma of vagina](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of vagina](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm of vulva^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003314>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of female genital organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma of vulva](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of vulva](#)^c

Malignant neoplasm: Nipple and areola^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000210>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of areola](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of breast](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of nipple](#)^c

Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000184>

has super-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of colon](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of gallbladder](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of liver](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of oesophagus](#)^c,
[Malignant neoplasm of pancreas](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of rectum](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of stomach](#)^c

Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000180>

has super-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of bladder](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of kidney](#)^c

Malignant neoplastic disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007977>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c, [Secondary Cancer Condition](#)^c

is in domain of

[Has staging](#)^{op}

is in range of

[CancerGradingMethodFor](#)^{op}, [CancerStagingMethodFor](#)^{op}, [Surgically treats](#)^{op}, [SymptomAssociatedWith](#)^{op}, [hasCondition](#)^{op},
[hasRelatedCondition](#)^{op}

is disjoint with

[Benign neoplastic disease](#)^c

Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049512>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm, epithelial^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049256>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm, neural^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000132>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neuroblastoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Malignant neuroendocrine tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1008102>

has super-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neuroendocrine carcinoma](#)^c

Malignant peripheral nerve sheath tumor, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049536>

has super-classes

[Nerve sheath tumors](#)^c

Malignant phyllodes tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049491>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Malignant squamous cell neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049530>

has super-classes

[Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Papillary carcinoma](#)^c

Malignant tumor of ascending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053411>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of hepatic flexure](#)^c

Malignant tumor of axilla^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037685>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of upper limb](#)^c

Malignant tumor of bronchus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000045>

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Bronchial structure](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of bronchus and lung](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of lower respiratory tract](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of thorax](#)^c

Malignant tumor of cecum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053316>

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Cecum](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant colorectal neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of cecum](#)^c

Malignant tumor of descending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053666>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of splenic flexure](#)^c

Malignant tumor of digestive organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040585>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of digestive system](#)^c, [Neoplasm of digestive organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of liver](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of oesophagus](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of pancreas](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of intestine](#)^c

Malignant tumor of female genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003312>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of female genital organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of cervix uteri](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of ovary](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of uterus](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of vagina](#)^c,
[Malignant neoplasm of vulva](#)^c

Malignant tumor of head and neck^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059399>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of head and neck](#)^c, [Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of brain](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of cerebral meninges](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of neck](#)^c

Malignant tumor of hepatic flexure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053460>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of ascending colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of hepatic flexure of colon](#)^c

Malignant tumor of intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000080>

A primary or metastatic malignant neoplasm involving the small intestine, large intestine, or both. Representative examples are carcinomas, lymphomas, and sarcomas. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of gastrointestinal tract](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of intraabdominal organ](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of digestive organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of intestinal tract](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of large intestine](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intestinal tract](#)^c

Malignant tumor of kidney^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000058>

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Kidney](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of intraabdominal organ](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract](#)^c, [Neoplasm of kidney](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of kidney](#)^c

Malignant tumor of large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000053>

A primary or metastatic malignant neoplasm that affects the colon or rectum. Representative examples include carcinoma, lymphoma, and sarcoma. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of intestine](#)^c, [Neoplasm of large intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma of large intestine](#)^c, [Malignant colorectal neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of colon and/or rectum](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of large intestine](#)^c

Malignant tumor of lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000065>

A carcinoma originating in the lung. Lung carcinomas usually arise from the epithelium that lines the bronchial tree (bronchogenic carcinomas), and are classified as small cell or non-small cell carcinomas. Non-small cell lung carcinomas are usually adenocarcinomas, squamous cell carcinomas, or large cell carcinomas. Metastatic carcinomas to the lung are also common, and can be difficult to distinguish from primary tumors. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Lung structure](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of bronchus and lung](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of lower respiratory tract](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of thorax](#)^c, [Neoplasm of lung](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of lung](#)^c

Malignant tumor of lymphoid hemopoietic and related tissue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039233>

has super-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant lymphoma](#)^c

Malignant tumor of male genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000092>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of genital structure](#)^c, [Neoplasm of male genital organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of male genital organ](#)^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma of male genital](#)^c

Malignant tumor of meninges^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054131>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of central nervous system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of cerebral meninges](#)^c

Malignant tumor of neck^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059400>

is equivalent to

([hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op} some [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c) and ([hasFindingSite](#)^{op} some [Neck](#)^c)

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of head and neck](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of thyroid gland](#)^c

Malignant tumor of pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000087>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c, [Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma of pelvis](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of rectum](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of uterus](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c

Malignant tumor of sigmoid colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053561>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of colon](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of sigmoid colon](#)^c

Malignant tumor of splenic flexure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053720>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of descending colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c

Malignant tumor of upper limb^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037633>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of upper limb](#)^c, [Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of axilla](#)^c

Malignant tumor staging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044308>

is equivalent to

[Cancer staging](#)^c

has super-classes

[Tumor staging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Generic anatomical site tumor invasion status](#)^c, [Generic tumor staging descriptor](#)^c

Mammary duct ectasia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051841>

has super-classes

[Disorder of breast](#)^c, [Duct ectasia](#)^c

Mammographic architectural distortion of breast finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016604>

has super-classes

[Mammographic breast tissue appearance](#)^c

Mammographic breast composition finding (finding)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016347>

has super-classes

[Mammography finding](#)^c

Mammographic breast tissue appearance^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034850>

has super-classes

[Mammography finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Architectural distortion of breast](#)^c, [Mammographic architectural distortion of breast finding](#)^c

Mammography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000030>

A type of radiography used specifically to examine breast tissue. The procedure utilizes a low-dose of x-rays or radiation to generate an image. A mammography exam or mammogram, is used as a screening tool to detect early breast cancer in women experiencing no symptoms and to detect and diagnose breast disease. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Radiographic imaging procedure](#)^c, [Radiographic procedure of chest](#)^c

has sub-classes

[CT of breast](#)^c

Mammography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004455>

has super-classes

[Projection radiography](#)^c

Mammography assessment (Category 0) - Need additional imaging evaluation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002085>

is equivalent to

[BI-RADS 0](#)^c

has super-classes

[Mammography assessment finding](#)^c

Mammography assessment (Category 1) - Negative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002097>

is equivalent to

[BI-RADS 1](#) ^c

has super-classes

[Mammography assessment finding](#) ^c

Mammography assessment (Category 2) - Benign finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002110>

is equivalent to

[BI-RADS 2](#) ^c

has super-classes

[Mammography assessment finding](#) ^c

Mammography assessment (Category 3) - Probably benign finding, short interval follow-up^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002139>

is equivalent to

[BI-RADS 3](#) ^c

has super-classes

[Mammography assessment finding](#) ^c

Mammography assessment (Category 4) - Suspicious abnormality, biopsy should be considered^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002155>

is equivalent to

[BI-RADS 4](#) ^c

has super-classes

[Mammography assessment finding](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Mammography assessment \(Category 4A\) - low suspicion of malignancy](#) ^c, [Mammography assessment \(Category 4B\) - moderate suspicion of malignancy](#) ^c, [Mammography assessment \(Category 4C\) - high suspicion of malignancy](#) ^c

Mammography assessment (Category 4A) - low suspicion of malignancy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002209>

is equivalent to

[BI-RADS 4A](#) ^c

has super-classes

[Mammography assessment \(Category 4\) - Suspicious abnormality, biopsy should be considered](#) ^c

Mammography assessment (Category 4B) - moderate suspicion of malignancy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002229>

is equivalent to

[BI-RADS 4B](#) ^c

has super-classes

[Mammography assessment \(Category 4\) - Suspicious abnormality, biopsy should be considered](#) ^c

Mammography assessment (Category 4C) - high suspicion of malignancy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002250>

is equivalent to

[BI-RADS 4C](#) ^c

has super-classes

[Mammography assessment \(Category 4\) - Suspicious abnormality, biopsy should be considered](#) ^c

Mammography assessment (Category 5) - Highly suggestive of malignancy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002124>

is equivalent to

[BI-RADS 5](#) ^c

has super-classes

[Mammography assessment finding](#) ^c

Mammography assessment (Category 6) - known biopsy, proven malignancy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002190>

is equivalent to

[BI-RADS 6](#) ^c

has super-classes

[Mammography assessment finding](#) ^c

Mammography assessment finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016284>

has super-classes

[Mammography finding](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Mammography assessment \(Category 0\) - Need additional imaging evaluation](#) ^c, [Mammography assessment \(Category 1\) - Negative](#) ^c, [Mammography assessment \(Category 2\) - Benign finding](#) ^c, [Mammography assessment \(Category 3\) - Probably benign finding, short interval follow-up](#) ^c, [Mammography assessment \(Category 4\) - Suspicious abnormality, biopsy should be considered](#) ^c, [Mammography assessment \(Category 5\) - Highly suggestive of malignancy](#) ^c, [Mammography assessment \(Category 6\) - known biopsy, proven malignancy](#) ^c

Mammography finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034775>

has super-classes

[Radiologic finding](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Breast composition](#) ^c, [Mammographic breast composition finding \(finding\)](#) ^c, [Mammographic breast tissue appearance](#) ^c, [Mammography assessment finding](#) ^c, [Mammography normal](#) ^c

Mammography normal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016374>

has super-classes

[Mammography finding](#) ^c, [Radiology result normal](#) ^c

Mammography reference location^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016324>

has super-classes

[Radiologic finding](#) ^c

Management of drug regimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034340>

has super-classes

[Procedure by method](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Pharmacological assessment](#) ^c

Manual^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000003>

Values for segmentation method (ProCancer-I, Prostate gland segmentation UC)

Of or related to the hands; reference to a task or activity being done by hand (as opposed as being performed with the assistance of automation or other supportive means). [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Modifier mainly for procedure](#)^c, [Segmentation Method](#)^c

Manufacturer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000010>

A person, enterprise, or entity that produces finished goods. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[3DHISTECH](#)^c, [ADAC](#)^c, [Agfa](#)^c, [Canon](#)^c, [Elsint](#)^c, [Esaote](#)^c, [Fujifilm](#)^c, [General Electric](#)^c, [Hitachi](#)^c, [Hologic](#)^c, [I.M.S](#)^c, [Marconi](#)^c, [Mediso](#)^c, [MiE](#)^c, [Philips](#)^c, [Picker International](#)^c, [Shimadzu](#)^c, [Siemens](#)^c, [Toshiba](#)^c, [UIH](#)^c

is in range of

[hasEquipmentManufacturer](#)^{op}, [hasImageVendor](#)^{op}

Marconi^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000053>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Margin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005439>

BI-RADS: Mammo, MRI, US -The edge or border of the lesion. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Imaging observation](#)^c, [Tumor Observation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Circumscribed margin](#)^c, [Non-circumscribed margin](#)^c

Marked^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002030>

has super-classes

[Enhancement Quality value](#)^c, [Severities](#)^c

Markers for liver tumor staging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044441>

has super-classes

[H+](#)^c

has sub-classes

[E - Extrahepatic marker](#)^c, [M - Metastatic marker](#)^c, [P - Portal vein marker](#)^c, [V - Hepatic vein marker](#)^c

Mask^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000139>

has super-classes

[Annotation Type](#)^c

Mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016511>

has super-classes

[Lesion](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cyst](#)^c, [Irregular mass](#)^c, [Nodule](#)^c, [Non-enhancing tumor](#)^c, [Oval mass](#)^c, [Proliferative mass](#)^c, [Round mass](#)^c

Mass of body structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051484>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lentiginosis](#)^c, [Mass of respiratory structure](#)^c

Mass of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051694>

has super-classes

[Abdominal mass](#)^c, [Finding of colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of colon](#)^c

Mass of digestive structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037847>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hamartoma of intestine](#)^c, [Liver mass](#)^c, [Rectal mass](#)^c

Mass of female genital structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039387>

has super-classes

[Female genitalia finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Mass of uterus](#)^c, [Vaginal mass](#)^c

Mass of respiratory structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051514>

has super-classes

[Mass of body structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung mass](#)^c, [Tumor of respiratory system](#)^c

Mass of thoracic structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051059>

has super-classes

[Finding of region of thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung mass](#)^c, [Neoplasm of thorax](#)^c

Mass of uterus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039389>

has super-classes

[Abdominal mass](#)^c, [Mass of female genital structure](#)^c, [Pelvic mass](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of uterus](#)^c

Mass-Molar conversion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036478>

has super-classes

[Laboratory procedure](#)^c, [Measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Calcium|Moment in time|Blood|40.078 g/mole](#)^c, [Carcinoembryonic Ag|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cholesterol.in HDL|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cholesterol.in LDL|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Cholesterol|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma|386.664 g/mole](#)^c, [Cortisol|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma|362.466 g/mole](#)^c, [Creatinine|Moment in time|Blood|113.12 g/mole](#)^c, [Creatinine|Moment in time|Urine|113.12 g/mole](#)^c, [Glucose|Moment in time|Blood venous|180.156 g/mole](#)^c, [Hemoglobin|Moment in time|Blood](#)^c, [Potassium|Moment in time|Blood|39.098 g/mole](#)^c, [Prostate specific Ag|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Triglyceride|Moment in time|Blood](#)^c, [Urea|Moment in time|Blood|60.056 g/mole](#)^c

Mathematical sign^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002260>

has super-classes

[Alphanumeric](#)^c

has sub-classes

\leq ^c, $=$ ^c, \geq ^c

Maximal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002500>

has super-classes

[Extensiveness](#)^c

Measure of pregnancy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045760>

has super-classes

[Pregnancy observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gravida](#)^c, [Number of births at term](#)^c

Measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000003>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c, [Evaluation procedure](#)^c, [Procedure Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cancer disease progression](#)^c, [Chemistry](#)^c, [Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c, [Hormone measurement](#)^c, [Length dimension of neoplasm](#)^c, [Lesion size](#)^c, [Mass-Molar conversion](#)^c, [Measurement of substance](#)^c, [Modality Radiation treatment](#)^c, [Molecular pathology](#)^c, [Pathology](#)^c, [Perineural Invasion](#)^c, [Regional lymph nodes examined.\[#\].Specimen](#)^c, [Smoking - history](#)^c, [Surgical Resection](#)^c

Measurement finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003968>

has super-classes

[Evaluation finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Finding of Hepatitis C status](#)^c, [Finding of substance level](#)^c, [Measurement finding outside reference range](#)^c, [Measurement finding within reference range](#)^c

Measurement finding outside reference range^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051785>

has super-classes

[Measurement finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Blood cell count outside reference range](#)^c, [Hemoglobin level outside reference range](#)^c

Measurement finding within reference range^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1019730>

has super-classes

[Measurement finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Prostate specific antigen normal](#)^c

Measurement of level of drug in blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1019823>

has super-classes

[Drug measurement](#)^c, [Measurement of substance in specimen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Serum testosterone measurement](#)^c

Measurement of level of substance in blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1019917>

has super-classes

[Measurement of substance in specimen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ALT - blood measurement](#)^c, [Blood calcium measurement](#)^c, [Blood urate measurement](#)^c, [Blood urea measurement](#)^c, [Glucose measurement, blood](#)^c, [Serum testosterone measurement](#)^c

Measurement of liver enzyme^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033704>

has super-classes

[Enzyme measurement](#)^c, [Protein measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alkaline phosphatase measurement](#)^c, [Aspartate aminotransferase measurement](#)^c, [Gamma glutamyl transferase measurement](#)^c

Measurement of substance^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000222>

has super-classes

[Laboratory procedure](#)^c, [Measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Calcium measurement](#)^c, [Carbohydrate measurement](#)^c, [Creatinine measurement](#)^c, [Drug measurement](#)^c, [Enzyme measurement](#)^c, [Hormone measurement](#)^c, [Lipids measurement](#)^c, [Measurement of substance in specimen](#)^c, [Potassium measurement](#)^c, [Protein measurement](#)^c, [Steroid measurement](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c, [Uric acid measurement](#)^c

Measurement of substance in specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1009005>

has super-classes

[Measurement of substance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Fluid sample albumin measurement](#)^c, [Measurement of level of drug in blood](#)^c, [Measurement of level of substance in blood](#)^c, [Urine substance measurement](#)^c

Mechanical abnormality^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051005>

has super-classes

[Morphologically abnormal structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Fluid disturbance](#)^c, [Hemorrhage](#)^c, [Mechanical lesion](#)^c, [Retention](#)^c

Mechanical disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051845>

has super-classes

[Pathophysiologic finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Duct changes](#)^c, [Fluid disorder](#)^c

Mechanical lesion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051014>

has super-classes

[Lesion](#)^c, [Mechanical abnormality](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cavity](#)^c, [Cyst](#)^c

Mechanisms^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001097>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Surgery](#)^c

Mediastinum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000107>

An anatomic site along the midline and under the sternum that contains the heart and pericardium, the bases of the great vessels, the trachea and bronchi, esophagus, thymus, lymph nodes, thoracic duct, phrenic and vagus nerves, and other structures and tissues. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Chest](#)^c, [Structure of lung and/or mediastinum](#)^c, [Structure of thoracic cavity and/or content](#)^c

Medical Assessment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047419>

An appraisal or evaluation of a patient's condition by a clinician that is based on a physical exam, medical history, and the patient's account of symptoms. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Health Status Assessment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Follow-up Examination After Treatment for Malignant Neoplasm](#)^c, [Physical Examination](#)^c, [Tumor Examination](#)^c

is in range of

[hasMedicalAssessment](#)^{op}

Medical Oncologist^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001103>

has super-classes

[Annotator Specialty](#)^c, [Specialized physician](#)^c

Medical practitioner^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001108>

has super-classes

[Healthcare professional](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Physician](#)^c

Medical therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034229>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Immunological therapy](#)^c

Medication^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034109>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c, [Pharmaceutical / biologic product](#)^c

Medication Review^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034385>

has super-classes

[Pharmacological assessment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Targeted medication therapy review](#)^c

Mediso^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000056>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Melan-A and Ki67 Ag [Identifier] in Tissue by Immune stain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047191>

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c

Melanocyte stimulating hormone releasing factor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050994>

has super-classes

[Hypothalamic or pituitary hormone](#)^c, [Hypothalamic releasing factor](#)^c

Melanosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053831>

has super-classes

[Disorder of pigmentation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Congenital melanosis](#)^c, [Lentiginosis](#)^c

Meninges^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000304>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cerebral meninges](#)^c, [Meninges, NOS](#)^c, [Spinal meninges](#)^c

Meninges part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063278>

has super-classes

[Intracranial structure](#)^c, [Meninges structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of brain meninges](#)^c

Meninges structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063277>

has super-classes

[Central nervous system part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Meninges part](#)^c

Meninges, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000306>

is equivalent to

[Meninges structure](#)^c

has super-classes

[Meninges](#)^c

Meningioma, malignant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049493>

has super-classes

[Malignant meningeal neoplasm](#)^c

Menopausal flushing^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059373>

has super-classes

[Menopausal symptom](#)^c

Menopausal symptom^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059372>

has super-classes

[Menopause finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Menopausal flushing](#)^c

Menopause finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039467>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Menopausal symptom](#)^c, [Perimenopausal state](#)^c, [Postmenopausal state](#)^c, [Postmenopause - Menopause present](#)^c, [Premenopausal state](#)^c, [Premenopause - Menopause absent](#)^c

Menopause, function^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045770>

has super-classes

[Female genital tract functions](#)^c

Menstruation absent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054005>

has super-classes

[Menstruation finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Postmenopausal state](#)^c

Menstruation finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053946>

has super-classes

[Female reproductive finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Finding related to menstrual cycle](#)^c, [Menstruation absent](#)^c

Mental state, behavior / psychosocial function observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050909>

has super-classes

[Clinical history/examination observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Behavior observable](#)^c

Mental state, behavior and/or psychosocial function finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056063>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Behavior finding](#)^c

Mesenchymal stem-like^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046258>

has super-classes

[Triple-negative breast cancer](#)^c

Mesenchymal-like^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046259>

has super-classes

[Triple-negative breast cancer](#)^c

Mesh^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000138>

has super-classes

[Annotation Type](#)^c

MET gene mutations found [Identifier] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051972>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

Metabolic disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036518>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of lipoprotein AND/OR lipid metabolism](#)^c

Metabolic finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051849>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Energy and stamina finding](#)^c

Metastasis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1009407>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Distant Metastasis \(NOS\)](#)^c, [Lymph Nodes with Metastasis](#)^c, [Metastasis to bone](#)^c, [Metastasis to digestive organ](#)^c, [Metastasis to endocrine gland](#)^c, [Metastasis to nervous system](#)^c, [Metastasis to pleura](#)^c, [Metastasis to retroperitoneum](#)^c, [Metastasis to the Muscle](#)^c, [Metastasis to the Viscera](#)^c

Metastasis to adrenal gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022825>

has super-classes

[Metastasis to endocrine gland](#)^c, [Metastasis to retroperitoneum](#)^c

Metastasis to bone^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1026700>

has super-classes

[Metastasis](#)^c

Metastasis to brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022878>

has super-classes

[Metastasis to central nervous system](#)^c

Metastasis to central nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1020012>

has super-classes

[Metastasis to nervous system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Metastasis to brain](#)^c

Metastasis to digestive organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016272>

has super-classes

[Metastasis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Metastasis to Liver](#)^c

Metastasis to digestive organs^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000191>

has super-classes

[Metastatic malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Secondary malignant neoplasm of liver](#)^c

Metastasis to endocrine gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016313>

has super-classes

[Metastasis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Metastasis to adrenal gland](#)^c

Metastasis to intrathoracic organs^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1020108>

has super-classes

[Metastasis to the Viscera](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Metastasis to lung](#)^c

Metastasis to kidney^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1027663>

has super-classes

[Metastasis to retroperitoneum](#)^c

Metastasis to Liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063712>

has super-classes

[Metastasis to digestive organ](#)^c

Metastasis to lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022932>

has super-classes

[Metastasis to intrathoracic organs](#)^c

Metastasis to nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1009543>

has super-classes

[Metastasis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Metastasis to central nervous system](#)^c

Metastasis to pleura^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060271>

has super-classes

[Metastasis](#)^c

Metastasis to retroperitoneum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016355>

has super-classes

[Metastasis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Metastasis to adrenal gland](#)^c, [Metastasis to kidney](#)^c

Metastasis to the Muscle^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063721>

has super-classes

[Metastasis](#)^c

Metastasis to the Viscera^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1029322>

has super-classes

[Metastasis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Metastasis to intrathoracic organs](#)^c

Metastatic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000129>

A term referring to the clinical or pathologic observation of a tumor extension from its original site of growth to another anatomic site. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Disease qualifier](#)^c

Metastatic malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038722>

has super-classes

[Secondary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Metastasis to digestive organs](#)^c, [Secondary malignant neoplasm of axilla](#)^c, [Secondary malignant neoplasm of trunk](#)^c, [Secondary malignant neoplasm of viscera](#)^c

Methodrexate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035890>

An antimetabolite and antifolate agent with antineoplastic and immunosuppressant activities. Methotrexate binds to and inhibits the enzyme dihydrofolate reductase, resulting in inhibition of purine nucleotide and thymidylate synthesis and, subsequently, inhibition of DNA and RNA syntheses. Methotrexate also exhibits potent immunosuppressant activity although the mechanism(s) of actions is unclear. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c, [Immunologic agent](#)^c

Methylated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001314>

has super-classes

[Presence findings](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hypermethylated](#)^c, [Partial Methylated](#)^c

mg/kg^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001897>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

mg/m²^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001904>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

MGMT (O-6-methylguanine-DNA methyltransferase) gene variant measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051955>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

MGMT gene methylation [Presence] in Tissue by Molecular genetics method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051951>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

mGy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001957>

has super-classes

[Unit of radiation dose](#)^c

Microcalcifications^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000108>

has super-classes

[Calcification disorder](#)^c

Microlobulated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1010761>

the short cycles of the margin produce small undulations [BI-RADS]. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Morphologic descriptor](#)^c

Microlobulated margin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005421>

BI-RADS Mammo/US: A margin characterized by short-cycle undulations. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Non-circumscribed margin](#)^c

Microsatellite markers exhibiting instability/Microsatellite instability markers assessed in Cancer specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052112>

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c

Microsatellite stability measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063264>

has super-classes

[Molecular pathology](#)^c

Microscopic specimen observation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048763>

has super-classes

[Evaluation finding](#)^c

Microscopy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004457>

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Digital Microscopy](#)^c, [Slide Microscopy](#)^c

Microscopy (procedure)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018532>

has super-classes

[Inspection](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Light microscopy](#)^c

Microsurgery - action^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059236>

has super-classes

[Surgical action](#)^c

Micturition finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000364>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Finding of pattern of urination](#)^c, [Finding of urinary bladder emptying](#)^c, [Finding related to ability to pass urine](#)^c, [Flow of urine - finding](#)^c

Middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000118>

has super-classes

[Middle region of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Right middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c

Middle peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000101>

has super-classes

[Middle region of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c

Middle region of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000060>

has super-classes

[Region of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Middle transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Middle transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000159>

has super-classes

[Middle region of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left middle transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right middle transition zone of prostate](#)^c

MiE^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000058>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Mild^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001378>

has super-classes

[Enhancement Quality value](#)^c, [Severities](#)^c

Mild systemic disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000037>

has super-classes

[Physical status qualifier](#)^c

Miller and Payne Classification^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049086>

A classification system for grading pathological remission based purely on microscopic assessment. It classifies patients into five groups with significantly different disease-free and overall survival and grades pathological remission in both the primary tumor and the axillary lymph nodes, with comparison of negative nodes with those that have already responded to chemotherapy. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Staging and scales](#)^c

milli-international unit per liter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000169>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

milli-international unit per liter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001968>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

milligram^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001903>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

milligram per 24 hours^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001974>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

milligram per deciliter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001981>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

milliliter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001966>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

millimeter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000152>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

millimole per liter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001989>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

millisecond^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001955>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

milliunit per liter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000170>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

Minimal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002496>

has super-classes

[Enhancement Quality value^c](#), [Extensiveness^c](#), [Proportion Enhancing value^c](#), [Proportion Necrosis value^c](#), [Proportion nCET value^c](#), [Proportion of Edema value^c](#), [Thickness of enhancing margin value^c](#)

Missing Value Reason^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001912>

has super-classes

[Qualifier^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Not identified^c](#)

Mixed^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001201>

has super-classes

[Diffusion Characteristics value^c](#), [General adjectival modifier^c](#)

Mixed ductal and lobular carcinoma in situ of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002302>

has super-classes

[DCIS \(Ductal carcinoma in situ\) of breast^c](#)

Mixed ductal and lobular carcinoma of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007963>

has super-classes

[Carcinoma of breast^c](#)

Mixed neuroendocrine non-neuroendocrine neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047086>

A rare neoplasm that consists of neuroendocrine and non-neuroendocrine cellular components. At least 30% of either component should be present for the diagnosis to be made. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas^c](#)

MKI67 (marker of proliferation Ki-67) gene variant measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051957>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation^c](#)

MKI67 Negative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052167>

has super-classes

[Expression Negative^c](#)

MKI67 Positive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052185>

has super-classes

[Expression Positive](#)^c

Modality descriptor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016776>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Low dose](#)^c, [Proton-density](#)^c

is in range of

[hasModalityDescriptor](#)^{op}

Modality Radiation treatment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004588>

has super-classes

[Measurement](#)^c

Modality radiation value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001181>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brachytherapy](#), [High Dose rate \(HDR\)](#)^c, [Electrons](#)^c, [Intraoperative Rad Rx \(IORT\)](#)^c, [Protons](#)^c

Modality-related characteristic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016609>

has super-classes

[Imaging observation descriptor](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Attenuation characteristic](#)^c, [Echogenicity characteristic](#)^c

Moderate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001130>

has super-classes

[Increased](#)^c

Moderate alcohol use^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001146>

has super-classes

[Alcohol use pattern value](#)^c

Moderate cigarette smoker (10-19 cigarettes per day)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059170>

has super-classes

[Cigarette smoker](#)^c

Moderate drinker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056338>

has super-classes

[Current drinker](#)^c

Modified radical mastectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060706>

has super-classes

[Radical mastectomy](#)^c

Modified Ryan Scheme for Tumor Regression^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049085>

A four-point tumor regression grading system that is used to measure therapeutic response of primary tumors and to predict patient outcomes. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Tumor Regression Grade](#)^c

Modifier mainly for procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000103>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Automatic](#)^c, [Manual](#)^c, [Semiautomatic](#)^c

Molecular genetic test^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034487>

has super-classes

[Genetic test](#)^c

has sub-classes

[BRCA1 mutation carrier detection test](#)^c, [BRCA2 mutation carrier detection test](#)^c

Molecular imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000073>

has super-classes

[Nuclear medicine imaging](#)^c

Molecular pathology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1042412>

has super-classes

[Laboratory procedure](#)^c, [Measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ERBB2 gene duplication \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by FISH](#)^c, [GSTP1 gene+APC gene methylation \[Presence\] in Tissue by Molecular genetics method](#)^c, [Gene deletion](#)^c, [Gene mutation](#)^c, [Gene rearrangement](#)^c, [IDH1 and IDH2 genes targeted mutation analysis in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method](#)^c, [Microsatellite stability measurement](#)^c, [PALB2 gene targeted mutation analysis in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method](#)^c, [PIK3CA gene \[VCF\] in Cancer specimen by Sequencing](#)^c, [TERT gene promotor region targeted mutation analysis in Tissue by Molecular genetics method](#)^c

Monitoring of patient^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1009818>

has super-classes

[Evaluation procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chronic disease monitoring](#)^c

Monitoring of patient with cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1020205>

has super-classes

[Chronic disease monitoring](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Active surveillance of prostate cancer](#)^c

Monitoring procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1028585>

has super-classes

[Regimes and therapies](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Surveillance](#)^c

month^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000154>

has super-classes

[Unit of time](#)^c

More than 35 cigarettes per day (about 2 packs or more)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001152>

has super-classes

[Number of cigarettes per day](#)^c

moribund patient who is not expected to survive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000030>

has super-classes

[Physical status qualifier](#)^c

Morphologic descriptor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1010777>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Fatty](#)^c, [Irregular](#)^c, [Lobular](#)^c, [Microlobulated](#)^c, [Oval](#)^c, [Round](#)^c, [Rounded](#)^c, [Spiculated](#)^c, [Symmetrical](#)^c, [Targetoid](#)^c, [Wedge-shaped](#)^c

Morphologic Finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000214>

has super-classes

[Histopathology Result](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Deposit](#)^c

Morphologically abnormal structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016395>

has super-classes

[Morphologically altered structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Growth alteration](#)^c, [Inflammatory morphology](#)^c, [Lesion](#)^c, [Mechanical abnormality](#)^c

Morphologically altered structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016389>

has super-classes

[Body structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Morphologically abnormal structure](#)^c

Mother^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001036>

has super-classes

[Parent](#)^c

Motor area^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000392>

has super-classes

[Eloquent Brain Areas](#)^c, [Region of frontal cortex](#)^c

Motor cortex^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000391>

has super-classes

[Eloquent Brain Areas](#)^c, [Region of cerebral cortex](#)^c

MR Echo Type^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016640>

has super-classes

[MR procedure attribute](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Echo planar](#)^c, [Gradient echo](#)^c, [Spin echo](#)^c

MR fluoroscopy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000082>

has super-classes

[Fluoroscopy](#)^c

MR imaging coil^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016648>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[internally inserted coil](#)^c

MR preparation or modification technique^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016646>

has super-classes

[MR procedure attribute](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Spin labeling](#)^c

MR procedure attribute^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016632>

has super-classes

[cross-sectional procedure attribute](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Echo time](#) ^c, [MR Echo Type](#) ^c, [MR preparation or modification technique](#) ^c, [Slice Thickness](#) ^c, [Tissue Contrast](#) ^c

MRI guided biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005488>

has super-classes

[Imaging guided biopsy](#) ^c, [Magnetic resonance imaging guidance](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[MRI guided biopsy of prostate](#) ^c

MRI guided biopsy of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005608>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of prostate](#) ^c, [MRI guided biopsy](#) ^c, [MRI of prostate](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[MRI-US fusion guided prostate biopsy](#) ^c

MRI of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016596>

has super-classes

[Imaging of brain](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[MRI of brain with arterial spin labeling](#) ^c

MRI of brain with arterial spin labeling^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016598>

has super-classes

[MRI of brain](#) ^c

MRI of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016224>

has super-classes

[Imaging of breast](#) ^c, [MRI of chest](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[MRI of breast for screening](#) ^c

MRI of breast for screening^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016199>

has super-classes

[MRI of breast](#) ^c, [Screening procedure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[MRI of breast for screening for malignant neoplasm](#) ^c, [Magnetic resonance imaging of breast for screening for malignant neoplasm procedure](#) ^c

MRI of breast for screening for malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016279>

has super-classes

[MRI of breast for screening](#) ^c, [Screening for malignant neoplasm of breast](#) ^c

MRI of chest^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016211>

Enrich other types of MRI for lung cancer for an example

has super-classes

[Chest imaging](#)^c, [Magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI of breast](#)^c

MRI of pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005530>

has super-classes

[Imaging of pelvis](#)^c, [Magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI of prostate](#)^c

MRI of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005507>

has super-classes

[Imaging of abdomen](#)^c, [Imaging of genitourinary system](#)^c, [MRI of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI guided biopsy of prostate](#)^c, [Multiparametric MRI of prostate](#)^c

MRI scan abnormal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016121>

has super-classes

[Imaging result abnormal](#)^c

MRI scan normal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016124>

has super-classes

[Imaging result normal](#)^c

MRI-US fusion guided prostate biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016128>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of abdomen using ultrasound guidance](#)^c, [MRI guided biopsy of prostate](#)^c, [US scan and biopsy of prostate](#)^c

mSv^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001951>

has super-classes

[Unit of radiation dose](#)^c

Mucinous adenocarcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046936>

An invasive adenocarcinoma composed of malignant glandular cells which contain intracytoplasmic mucin. Often, the infiltrating glandular structures are associated with mucoid stromal formation. It may arise from the large and small intestine, appendix, stomach, lung, ovary, breast, corpus uteri, cervix, vagina, and salivary gland. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Cystic, mucinous and serous neoplasms](#)^c

Mucinous adenocarcinoma of ascending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061003>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Mucinous adenocarcinoma of breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060860>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Mucinous adenocarcinoma of cecum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060910>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Mucinous adenocarcinoma of colon, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062210>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Mucinous adenocarcinoma of descending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061693>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Mucinous adenocarcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061157>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Mucinous adenocarcinoma of rectum, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062602>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of rectum](#)^c

Mucinous adenocarcinoma of sigmoid colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059112>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of sigmoid colon](#)^c

Mucinous adenocarcinoma of splenic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061535>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c

Mucinous adenocarcinoma of transverse colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059949>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor^c](#), [Primary adenocarcinoma of colon^c](#), [Primary mucinous carcinoma of digestive organ^c](#)

Multicentric^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002421>

has super-classes

[Distributions^c](#), [Multifocal or Multicentric value^c](#)

Multifocal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002408>

has super-classes

[Distributions^c](#), [General adjectival modifier^c](#), [Multifocal or Multicentric value^c](#)

Multifocal or Multicentric^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016730>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria^c](#)

Multifocal or Multicentric value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016730>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Focal^c](#), [Multicentric^c](#), [Multifocal^c](#)

Multiparametric magnetic resonance imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005606>

has super-classes

[Magnetic resonance imaging^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Multiparametric MRI of prostate^c](#)

Multiparametric MRI of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016133>

has super-classes

[MRI of prostate^c](#), [Multiparametric magnetic resonance imaging^c](#)

Musculoskeletal structure of sacral spine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000166>

has super-classes

[Body region structure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Sacrum^c](#)

Musculoskeletal structure of spine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000127>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Spine](#)^c

Mutated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001313>

An indication that gene variants were detected in a sample. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Presence findings](#)^c

Mutated/c.1-124C>T^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001317>

has super-classes

[Presence findings](#)^c

Mutated/c.1-146C>T^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001318>

has super-classes

[Presence findings](#)^c

MYH-associated polyposis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059277>

has super-classes

[Intestinal polyposis syndrome](#)^c

Myxofibrosarcoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049514>

has super-classes

[Fibromatous neoplasms](#)^c, [Sarcoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

N category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033328>

has super-classes

[TNM category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[cN category](#)^c, [pN category](#)^c

N/A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001334>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c

Nab paclitaxel^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035061>

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c, [Immunologic agent](#)^c

nanogram per deciliter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000167>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

nanogram per milliliter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000156>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

nanomole per liter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000174>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

National Cancer Institute common terminology criteria for adverse event grade finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052865>

has super-classes

[Finding of grade](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 1](#)^c, [Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 2](#)^c, [Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 3](#)^c, [Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 4](#)^c, [Common terminology criteria for adverse events grade 5](#)^c

National Public Health Classification data^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001056>

has super-classes

[Classification system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cohort](#)^c, [Control group](#)^c, [Ethnicity](#)^c, [Race](#)^c, [Screening](#)^c

Natriuretic peptide B [Mass/volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033999>

has super-classes

[Brain natriuretic peptide measurement](#)^c, [Chemistry](#)^c, [Natriuretic peptide.B|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Natriuretic peptide.B|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049861>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Natriuretic peptide B \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Nature of procedure values^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002267>

has super-classes

[Natures](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intents](#)^c, [Reoperation](#)^c

Natures^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002263>

has super-classes

[Descriptor](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Nature of procedure values](#)^c

NBN (nibrin) gene variant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063256>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

nCET tumor Crosses Midline^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016729>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

nCET tumor Crosses Midline value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016729>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[No](#)^c, [Yes](#)^c

Neck^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000121>

The region that connects the head to the rest of the body. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Face and/or neck structure](#)^c, [Neck and chest](#)^c, [Scalp and/or neck structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Thyroid and/or parathyroid structures](#)^c

Neck and chest^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000233>

has super-classes

[Neck, chest and abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chest](#)^c, [Neck](#)^c

Neck, chest and abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000204>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chest and abdomen](#)^c, [Neck and chest](#)^c

Necrosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051010>

has super-classes

[Damage](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Zonal necrosis](#)^c

is in domain of

[NecrosisVolumeValue](#)^{dp}

Necrosis Volume^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1003884>

has super-classes

[Volumetric Imaging Criteria](#)^c

Necrotic tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049747>

has super-classes

[Tumor configuration](#)^c

Needle aspiration of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058530>

has super-classes

[Aspiration of breast](#)^c

Needle biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001713>

has super-classes

[Biopsy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Core needle biopsy](#)^c, [Fine needle biopsy](#)^c, [Needle biopsy of prostate](#)^c

Needle biopsy of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001939>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of prostate](#)^c, [Needle biopsy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Core needle biopsy of prostate](#)^c, [Fine needle aspiration biopsy of prostate](#)^c, [Systematic Prostate Biopsy](#)^c, [Targeted Prostate Biopsy](#)^c, [Transperineal needle biopsy of prostate](#)^c, [Transrectal needle biopsy of prostate](#)^c

Needle biopsy specimen tumor quantitation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050706>

has super-classes

[Tumor quantitation](#)^c

Negative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001332>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c

Negative descriptors^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002047>

has super-classes

[Descriptor](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Not performed](#)^c

Negative screening^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002626>

has super-classes

[Population](#)^c

Negative Test Result^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052160>

has super-classes

[Clinical Test Result](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Expression Negative](#)^c

Neo-adjuvant - intent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002484>

has super-classes

[Therapeutic](#)^c

Neoadjuvant antineoplastic therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049098>

has super-classes

[Therapeutic procedure](#)^c

Neoadjuvant chemotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024529>

has super-classes

[Chemotherapy](#)^c

Neoadjuvant Therapy response value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001217>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Complete response \(CR\)](#)^c, [No response \(NR\)](#)^c, [Not applicable: Neoadjuvant therapy not given](#)^c, [Partial response \(PR\)](#)^c, [Unknown or no information/Not documented in patient record](#)^c

Neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036328>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm and/or hamartoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Acinar cell neoplasm](#)^c, [Cystic, mucinous AND/OR serous neoplasm](#)^c, [Ductal, lobular AND/OR medullary neoplasm](#)^c, [Embryonal neuroepithelial tumor](#)^c, [Epithelial neoplasm](#)^c, [Hematopoietic neoplasm](#)^c, [In situ neoplasm \(morphology\)](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Neoplasm, benign](#)^c, [Nervous system tumor morphology](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Soft tissue tumor AND/OR sarcoma](#)^c

Neoplasm and/or hamartoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1010097>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hamartoma](#)^c, [Neoplastic disease](#)^c

Neoplasm and/or hamartoma (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016731>

has super-classes

[Tumor Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hamartoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Neoplasm](#)^c

Neoplasm by body site^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051050>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of trunk](#)^c, [Tumor of respiratory system](#)^c

Neoplasm observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034929>

has super-classes

[Observable entity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anatomic location of neoplasm](#)^c, [Edition of American Joint Commission on Cancer, Cancer Staging Manual used for TNM staging](#)^c, [Histologic feature of neoplasm](#)^c, [Length dimension of neoplasm](#)^c, [Number of lymph nodes containing metastatic neoplasm in excised specimen](#)^c, [Number of tumor nodules](#)^c, [Percent of cell nuclei positive for proliferation marker protein Ki-67 in primary malignant neoplasm by immunohistochemistry](#)^c, [Presence of direct invasion by neoplasm](#)^c, [Presence of estrogen receptor in neoplasm](#)^c, [Presence of metastatic discontinuous spread of primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Presence of progesterone receptor in neoplasm](#)^c, [Status of regression of tumor](#)^c, [Tumor configuration](#)^c, [Tumor configuration \(finding\)](#)^c, [Tumor configuration observable entity](#)^c, [Tumor focality](#)^c, [Tumor measurable](#)^c, [Tumor quantitation](#)^c

Neoplasm of axilla^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043093>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of shoulder](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of axillary lymph nodes](#)^c

Neoplasm of axillary lymph nodes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043210>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of axilla](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Secondary malignant neoplasm of axillary lymph nodes](#)^c

Neoplasm of bone^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000176>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of skeletal system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of bone](#)^c

Neoplasm of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000059>

A benign or malignant neoplasm of the breast parenchyma. It can originate from the ducts, lobules or the breast adipose tissue. Breast neoplasms are much more common in females than males. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Disorder of breast](#)^c, [Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma in situ of breast](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of breast](#)^c, [Neoplasm of female breast](#)^c

Neoplasm of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000056>

A benign or malignant neoplasm that affects the colon. Representative examples of benign neoplasms include lipoma and leiomyoma. Representative examples of malignant neoplasms include carcinoma, lymphoma, and sarcoma. Colonic adenomas always exhibit epithelial dysplasia and are considered premalignant neoplasms. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Colonic lesion](#)^c, [Mass of colon](#)^c, [Neoplasm of large intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of colon](#)^c

Neoplasm of digestive organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040493>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of digestive organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of intestinal tract](#)^c, [Neoplasm of liver](#)^c

Neoplasm of digestive system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051077>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of digestive system](#)^c

Neoplasm of endocrine gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059393>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of endocrine system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of thyroid gland](#)^c

Neoplasm of endocrine system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059394>

has super-classes

[Disorder of endocrine system](#)^c, [Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of endocrine gland](#)^c

Neoplasm of extremity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1042748>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of upper limb](#)^c

Neoplasm of female breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036352>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of breast](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of female breast](#)^c

Neoplasm of female genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003309>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of female genital organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of ovary](#)^c, [Neoplasm of uterus](#)^c, [Neoplasm of vagina](#)^c

Neoplasm of gastrointestinal tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051064>

has super-classes

[Disorder of gastrointestinal tract](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of gastrointestinal tract](#)^c, [Neoplasm of intestinal tract](#)^c

Neoplasm of head and neck^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059398>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of head and neck](#)^c

Neoplasm of integumentary system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054188>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of skin](#)^c

Neoplasm of intestinal tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051115>

has super-classes

[Disorder of intestine](#)^c, [Neoplasm of digestive organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of gastrointestinal tract](#)^c, [Neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of intestine](#)^c, [Neoplasm of large intestine](#)^c

Neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000332>

has super-classes

[Abdominal organ finding](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of trunk](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of intraabdominal organ](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of intestinal tract](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of kidney](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of liver](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of uterus](#) ^c

Neoplasm of intrathoracic organs^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051325>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of thorax](#) ^c, [Viscus structure finding](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of lung](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intrathoracic organs](#) ^c

Neoplasm of kidney^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003330>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of kidney](#) ^c

Neoplasm of large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000052>

has super-classes

[Disorder of large intestine](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of intestinal tract](#) ^c, [Neoplastic disease](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of large intestine](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of colon](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of rectum](#) ^c

Neoplasm of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000070>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of digestive organ](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Benign neoplasm of liver](#) ^c, [Malignant neoplasm of liver](#) ^c

Neoplasm of lower respiratory tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051400>

has super-classes

[Disorder of lower respiratory system](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of respiratory tract](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of lower respiratory tract](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of lung](#) ^c

Neoplasm of lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000064>

A benign or malignant, primary or metastatic neoplasm involving the lungs. Representative examples of benign neoplasms include adenoma, papilloma, chondroma, and endobronchial lipoma. Representative examples of malignant neoplasms include carcinoma, carcinoid tumor, sarcoma, and lymphoma. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Lesion of lung](#) ^c, [Lung mass](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of intrathoracic organs](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of lower respiratory tract](#) ^c, [Neoplastic disease](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of lung](#) ^c

Neoplasm of male genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003308>

has super-classes

[Disorder of male genital organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma in situ of male genital organ](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of male genital organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Neoplasm of nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054126>

has super-classes

[Disorder of nervous system](#)^c, [Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of nervous system](#)^c, [Neurocutaneous syndrome](#)^c

Neoplasm of ovary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003310>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of female genital organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of ovary](#)^c

Neoplasm of pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003467>

has super-classes

[Disorder of pelvis](#)^c, [Neoplasm of trunk](#)^c, [Pelvic mass](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of pelvis](#)^c, [Neoplasm of prostate](#)^c, [Neoplasm of rectum](#)^c, [Neoplasm of uterus](#)^c

Neoplasm of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000074>

A benign, borderline, or malignant neoplasm that affects the prostate gland. Representative examples include benign prostate phyllodes tumor, prostatic intraepithelial neoplasia, prostate carcinoma, and prostate sarcoma. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Disorder of prostate](#)^c, [Neoplasm of male genital organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c, [Prostate mass](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma in situ of prostate](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Neoplasm of rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000076>

A benign or malignant neoplasm that affects the rectum. Representative examples of benign neoplasms include lipoma and leiomyoma. Representative examples of malignant neoplasms include carcinoma, lymphoma, and sarcoma. Rectal adenomas always exhibit epithelial dysplasia and are considered premalignant neoplasms. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Lesion of rectum](#)^c, [Neoplasm of large intestine](#)^c, [Neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c, [Rectal mass](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of rectum](#)^c

Neoplasm of respiratory tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051374>

has super-classes

[Tumor of respiratory system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of lower respiratory tract](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of respiratory tract](#)^c

Neoplasm of shoulder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1042977>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of upper limb](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of axilla](#)^c

Neoplasm of skeletal system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000175>

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of skeletal system](#)^c, [Neoplasm of bone](#)^c

Neoplasm of skin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054251>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of integumentary system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neurocutaneous syndrome](#)^c

Neoplasm of thorax^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051302>

has super-classes

[Disorder of thorax](#)^c, [Mass of thoracic structure](#)^c, [Neoplasm of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of thorax](#)^c, [Neoplasm of intrathoracic organs](#)^c

Neoplasm of thyroid gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059395>

has super-classes

[Disorder of thyroid gland](#)^c, [Neoplasm of endocrine gland](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of thyroid gland](#)^c

Neoplasm of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1010380>

has super-classes

[Disorder of trunk](#)^c, [Neoplasm by body site](#)^c, [Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of anorectum](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of genitourinary organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of female genital organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c, [Neoplasm of male genital organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c, [Neoplasm of thorax](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of trunk](#)^c

Neoplasm of upper limb^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1042862>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of extremity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant tumor of upper limb](#)^c, [Neoplasm of shoulder](#)^c

Neoplasm of uterus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003329>

has super-classes

[Lesion of uterus^c](#), [Mass of uterus^c](#), [Neoplasm of female genital organ^c](#), [Neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs^c](#), [Neoplasm of pelvis^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of uterus^c](#)

Neoplasm of vagina^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003328>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of female genital organ^c](#), [Vaginal lesion^c](#), [Vaginal mass^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of vagina^c](#)

Neoplasm, benign^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046166>

A neoplasm characterized by the absence of atypical or malignant cytological and architectural features, and absence of invasive features or metastatic potential. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Neoplasm^c](#), [Neoplasms, NOS^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Benign epithelial neoplasm^c](#)

is disjoint with

[Malignant neoplasm^c](#)

Neoplasm, malignant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049561>

has super-classes

[Neoplasms, NOS^c](#)

Neoplasm, malignant of ascending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061132>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor^c](#)

Neoplasm, malignant of breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060898>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor^c](#)

Neoplasm, malignant of cecum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060985>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor^c](#)

Neoplasm, malignant of colon, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062543>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Neoplasm, malignant of descending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061913>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Neoplasm, malignant of hepatic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061297>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Neoplasm, malignant of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1030093>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Neoplasm, malignant of rectum, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062912>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Neoplasm, malignant of sigmoid colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062158>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Neoplasm, malignant of splenic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061652>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Neoplasm, malignant of transverse colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061498>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Neoplasm, metastatic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049523>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Neoplasms, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049528>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm, benign](#)^c, [Neoplasm, malignant](#)^c

Neoplastic disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1010238>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm and/or hamartoma](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Benign neoplastic disease](#)^c, [Carcinoma in situ](#)^c, [Glioma](#)^c, [Hormone receptor negative neoplasm](#)^c, [Hormone receptor positive tumor](#)^c, [Malignant neoplastic disease](#)^c, [Neoplasm by body site](#)^c, [Neoplasm of breast](#)^c, [Neoplasm of digestive organ](#)^c, [Neoplasm of digestive system](#)^c, [Neoplasm of endocrine system](#)^c, [Neoplasm of extremity](#)^c, [Neoplasm of head and neck](#)^c, [Neoplasm of integumentary system](#)^c, [Neoplasm of large intestine](#)^c, [Neoplasm of lung](#)^c, [Neoplasm of nervous system](#)^c, [Neoplasm of skeletal system](#)^c, [Neoplasm of trunk](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine tumor](#)^c, [Tumor of respiratory system](#)^c

is in range of

[diagnosedWith](#)^{op}

Nerve sheath tumors^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049533>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant peripheral nerve sheath tumor, NOS](#)^c

Nervous system tumor morphology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049108>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Central nervous system tumor morphology](#)^c

Neuroblastoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049513>

has super-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Neuroblastoma (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000066>

A common neoplasm of early childhood arising from neural crest cells in the sympathetic nervous system, and characterized by diverse clinical behavior, ranging from spontaneous remission to rapid metastatic progression and death. This tumor is the most common intraabdominal malignancy of childhood, but it may also arise from thorax, neck, or rarely occur in the central nervous system. Histologic features include uniform round cells with hyperchromatic nuclei arranged in nests and separated by fibrovascular septa. Neuroblastomas may be associated with the opsoclonus-myoelonus syndrome. (From DeVita et al., Cancer: Principles and Practice of Oncology, 5th ed, pp2099-2101; Curr Opin Oncol 1998 Jan;10(1):43-51) [MeSH]

has super-classes

[Embryonal neuroepithelial tumor](#)^c, [Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm, neural](#)^c

Neurocutaneous syndrome^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052388>

has super-classes

[Congenital disease](#)^c, [Neoplasm of nervous system](#)^c, [Neoplasm of skin](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Peutz-Jeghers syndrome](#)^c

Neuroendocrine carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1020303>

has super-classes

[Malignant neuroendocrine tumor^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Neuroendocrine tumor, NOS, of prostate gland^c](#)

Neuroendocrine Carcinoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046841>

A usually aggressive carcinoma composed of malignant cells exhibiting neuroendocrine differentiation. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas^c](#)

Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of ascending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061063>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor^c](#)

Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of cecum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060952>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor^c](#)

Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of colon, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062372>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor^c](#)

Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of descending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061778>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor^c](#), [Primary malignant neoplasm of descending colon^c](#)

Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of hepatic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061210>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor^c](#), [Primary malignant neoplasm of hepatic flexure of colon^c](#)

Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of rectum, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062723>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor^c](#)

Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of sigmoid colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062057>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of sigmoid colon](#)^c

Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of splenic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059124>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c

Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of transverse colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061393>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of transverse colon](#)^c

Neuroendocrine neoplasm (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049510>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation](#)^c, [Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma](#)^c, [Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm](#)^c,
[Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm, epithelial](#)^c, [Malignant neuroendocrine neoplasm, neural](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine tumor grade 1](#)^c

Neuroendocrine neoplasm, malignant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000096>

has super-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

Neuroendocrine tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000122>

A well-differentiated epithelial neuroendocrine neoplasm of low, intermediate, or high grade. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation of prostate gland](#)^c, [Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c

Neuroendocrine tumor grade 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049469>

has super-classes

[Neuroendocrine neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Neuroendocrine tumor, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049603>

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#)^c

Neuroendocrine tumor, NOS, of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1023793>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Neutron capture therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005267>

has super-classes

[External beam radiation therapy procedure^c](#)

Never^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001344>

has super-classes

[Alcohol drinker status value^c](#), [Frequencies^c](#), [Smoking status value^c](#)

NF1 Gene Mutation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063233>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation^c](#)

Nipple discharge symptom^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037122>

has super-classes

[Nipple finding^c](#)

Nipple finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037123>

has super-classes

[Breast finding^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Nipple discharge symptom^c](#), [No nipple discharge^c](#), [Retraction of nipple^c](#)

Nipple structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063634>

has super-classes

[Breast part^c](#)

Nivolumab^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063669>

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent^c](#)

No^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001078>

has super-classes

[Absence findings^c](#), [Cortical Involvement value^c](#), [Enhancing tumor Crosses Midline value^c](#), [Ependymal Extension value^c](#), [Hemorrhage volume value^c](#), [Pial Invasion value^c](#), [nCET tumor Crosses Midline value^c](#)

No ADC images^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001893>

has super-classes

[Absence findings^c](#), [Diffusion Characteristics value^c](#)

No anti-cancer treatment - watchful waiting^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1027012>

has super-classes

[Reason for no specific anti-cancer treatment](#)^c

No contrast enhancement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001890>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c, [Enhancement Quality value](#)^c

No contrast injected^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001892>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c, [Enhancement Quality value](#)^c

No eloquent brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001899>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c

No evidence of disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001896>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c, [Condition stability status](#)^c

No family history of clinical finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1029962>

has super-classes

[Family history with explicit context](#)^c, [Finding with explicit context](#)^c

has sub-classes

[No family history of malignancy](#)^c

No family history of malignancy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1029963>

has super-classes

[No family history of clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[No FH: breast carcinoma](#)^c, [No family history of ovarian cancer](#)^c

No family history of ovarian cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1029965>

has super-classes

[No family history of malignancy](#)^c

No FH: breast carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1029964>

has super-classes

[No family history of malignancy](#)^c

No FLAIR images^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001895>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c, [T1/FLAIR Ratio value](#)^c

No nCET^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001894>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c, [Proportion nCET value](#)^c

No nipple discharge^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037124>

has super-classes

[Nipple finding](#)^c

No posterior acoustic features^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016616>

BI-RADS US: No shadowing or enhancement is present deep to the mass. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Posterior acoustic feature](#)^c

No response (NR)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001221>

has super-classes

[Neoadjuvant Therapy response value](#)^c

No vascular invasion by tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1027118>

has super-classes

[Tumor invasion finding](#)^c

Nodes removed^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059826>

has super-classes

[Unapproved attribute](#)^c

Nodular^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002043>

has super-classes

[Formations](#)^c

Nodule^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016591>

has super-classes

[Mass](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Dysplastic nodule](#)^c

Nodule of lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051728>

has super-classes

[Lesion of lung](#)^c, [Lung mass](#)^c

Non - drinker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056332>

has super-classes

[Finding relating to alcohol drinking behavior](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Ex-drinker](#)^c, [Lifetime non-drinker](#)^c, [Lifetime non-drinker of alcohol](#)^c

Non Binary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000173>

has super-classes

[Gender](#)^c

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049088>

has super-classes

[steatosis of liver](#)^c

Non-circumscribed margin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005429>

PI-RADS: III-defined. BI-RADS US: the mass has one or more of the following features: indistinct, angular, microlobulated, or spiculated in any portion of the margin. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Margin](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Angular margin](#)^c, [Indistinct margin](#)^c, [Microlobulated margin](#)^c, [Spiculated margin](#)^c

Non-coronary systemic artery structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000041>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Aorta](#)^c

Non-curative therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034117>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c

Non-enhancing margin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016738>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Non-enhancing margin value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016738>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Poorly defined](#)^c, [Well defined](#)^c

Non-enhancing tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016512>

Visibly abnormal tissue on a magnetic resonance image (MRI) or computed tomography (CT) that does not enhance with contrast and is not edema. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Mass](#)^c, [Radiologic finding](#)^c

is in domain of

[Non-EnhancingTumorVolumeValue](#)^{dp}

Non-Enhancing Tumor Volume^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1003883>

has super-classes

[Volumetric Imaging Criteria](#)^c

Non-Hodgkin lymphoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049107>

has super-classes

[Malignant lymphoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma (clinical)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046323>

has super-classes

[Malignant lymphoma](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Diffuse non-Hodgkin's lymphoma](#)^c

Non-infiltrating intraductal carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049679>

has super-classes

[Carcinoma in situ \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Ductal, lobular AND/OR medullary neoplasm](#)^c

Non-small cell carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063540>

has super-classes

[Epithelial neoplasms, NOS](#)^c

Non-small cell carcinoma of lung, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063178>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Non-smoker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056513>

has super-classes

[Tobacco smoking behavior - finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Ex-smoker](#)^c

Non-solid^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001073>

has super-classes

[Formations](#)^c

Non-surgical biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057735>

has super-classes

[Biopsy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Fine needle biopsy](#)^c

Non-surgical breast biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056778>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of breast](#)^c, [Non-surgical chest biopsy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Fine needle aspiration of breast](#)^c

Non-surgical chest biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057781>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Non-surgical breast biopsy](#)^c

None^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001375>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c, [Enhancement Quality value](#)^c, [Proportion Necrosis value](#)^c, [Proportion of Edema value](#)^c

Nonenhancing^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005496>

has super-classes

[Enhancement pattern](#)^c

Normal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000055>

has super-classes

[Normality findings](#)^c

Normal sexual function^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1027225>

has super-classes

[Finding of sexual function](#)^c

Normality findings^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001077>

has super-classes

[Finding value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abnormal](#)^c, [Normal](#)^c

Not applicable: Neoadjuvant therapy not given^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001218>

has super-classes

[Neoadjuvant Therapy response value](#)^c

Not assessable/applicable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001162>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c

Not assessed^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001188>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c

Not available^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001163>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c

Not detected^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001388>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c

Not Hispanic or Latino^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001207>

has super-classes

[Ethnicity](#)^c

Not identified^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001921>

has super-classes

[Missing Value Reason](#)^c

Not methylated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001889>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c

Not mutated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001887>

An indication that gene variants were not detected in a sample. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c

Not parallel^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016639>

[BI-RADS] US: Long axis not oriented along the skin line (taller than wide or vertical)--includes round [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Orientation descriptor](#)^c

Not performed^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002055>

has super-classes

[Negative descriptors](#)^c

Not pregnant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001160>

has super-classes

[Pregnancy status value](#)^c

Nothing^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001888>

has super-classes

[Absence findings](#)^c

Nottingham Grade 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022114>

has super-classes

[Grade 1 tumor](#)^c

Nottingham Grade 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022151>

has super-classes

[Grade 2 tumor](#)^c

Nottingham Grade 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1022189>

has super-classes

[Grade 3 tumor](#)^c

Nottingham grade of primary malignant neoplasm of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049683>

has super-classes

[Histologic grade of primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Nottingham histologic grading system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037299>

has super-classes

[Histological grading systems](#)^c

NRAS Gene Mutation measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063259>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

Nuclear imaging acquisition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016759>

has super-classes

[Image acquisition mode](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Dynamic nuclear imaging acquisition](#)^c, [Static nuclear imaging acquisition](#)^c

Nuclear medicine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000034>

Nuclear Medicine is the branch of medicine that uses radioactive materials either to image a patient's body or to destroy diseased cells. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Nuclear medicine imaging procedure](#)^c

Nuclear medicine imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000071>

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Molecular imaging](#)^c, [Positron emission tomography](#)^c, [Scintigraphy](#)^c, [Single photon imaging](#)^c

Nuclear medicine imaging procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016272>

has super-classes

[Nuclear medicine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Positron emission tomography](#)^c, [Radioisotope study of musculoskeletal system](#)^c

Number^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002302>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[0](#)^c, [1](#)^c, [2](#)^c, [3](#)^c, [Cardinal number](#)^c

Number of births at term^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046036>

has super-classes

[Measure of pregnancy](#)^c, [Obstetric history](#)^c

Number of cigarettes per day^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001153>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[1 cigarette per day](#)^c, [16 to 25 cigarettes per day \(about 1 pack\)](#)^c, [2 to 5 cigarettes per day](#)^c, [26 to 35 cigarettes per day \(about 1 1/2 packs\)](#)^c, [6 to 15 cigarettes per day \(about 1/2 pack\)](#)^c, [Don't know/refused](#)^c, [Less than one cigarette per day](#)^c, [More than 35 cigarettes per day \(about 2 packs or more\)](#)^c

Number of lymph nodes containing metastatic neoplasm in excised specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035616>

has super-classes

[Lymph node observable](#)^c, [Neoplasm observable](#)^c, [Tumor measureable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Number of regional lymph nodes containing metastatic neoplasm in excised specimen](#)^c

Number of lymph nodes examined by microscopy in excised specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035721>

has super-classes

[Lymph node observable](#)^c

Number of regional lymph nodes containing metastatic neoplasm in excised specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059907>

has super-classes

[Number of lymph nodes containing metastatic neoplasm in excised specimen](#)^c

Number of tumor nodules^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050859>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c, [Tumor measureable](#)^c

Numeric grade^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001376>

has super-classes

[Grades](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Numeric grade on a scale 0 to 5](#)^c

Numeric grade on a scale 0 to 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001380>

has super-classes

[Numeric grade](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Grade 1 on a scale of 0 to 5](#)^c, [Grade 2 on a scale of 0 to 5](#)^c, [Grade 3 on a scale of 0 to 5](#)^c, [Grade 4 on a scale of 0 to 5](#)^c, [Grade 5 on a scale of 0 to 5](#)^c

Nutritional anemia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051752>

has super-classes

[Anemia](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Iron deficiency anemia](#)^c

Nutritional deficiency associated condition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051743>

has super-classes

[Disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Iron deficiency anemia](#)^c

Observable entity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034889>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Clinical history/examination observable](#)^c, [Drug therapy observable](#)^c, [Function](#)^c, [General clinical state](#)^c, [Imaging observable](#)^c, [Interpretation of findings](#)^c, [Lymph node observable](#)^c, [Neoplasm observable](#)^c, [Pregnancy observable](#)^c, [Social / personal history observable](#)^c, [Substance observable](#)^c

Observation Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000014>

Observation category code: value sets specified in mCODE

has super-classes

[Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Activity](#)^c, [Exam](#)^c, [Imaging](#)^c, [Laboratory](#)^c, [Procedure](#)^c, [Social History](#)^c, [Survey](#)^c, [Symptom](#)^c, [Therapy](#)^c, [Vital Signs](#)^c

is in range of

[hasObservationCategory](#)^{op}

Obstetric history^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040223>

has super-classes

[Pregnancy, childbirth / puerperium observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Number of births at term](#)^c

Occasional drinker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056337>

has super-classes

[Current drinker](#)^c

Occipital lobe^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000354>

has super-classes

[Brain](#)^c, [Brain Lesion Site](#)^c, [Cerebral lobe structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of Brodmann areas 17 \(striate cortex\), 18 \(parastriate cortex\) and 19 \(peristriate cortex\) of the occipital lobe](#)^c

Occipital region^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000419>

has super-classes

[Brain region](#)^c, [Structure of subregion of head](#)^c

Oligodendroglioma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000081>

has super-classes

[Malignant glioma](#)^c

OMOP^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000037>

has super-classes

[Correspondence](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Domain: Condition](#)^c, [Domain: Drug](#)^c, [Domain: Meas Value](#)^c, [Domain: Measurement](#)^c, [Domain: Observation](#)^c, [Domain: Person](#)^c, [Domain: Procedure](#)^c, [Domain: Spec Anatomic Site](#)^c, [Domain: Specimen](#)^c, [Domain: Unit](#)^c

On the number of days you reported you smoked cigarettes during the past 30 days, how many cigarettes did you smoke per day, on average [PhenX]^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004570>

has super-classes

[Smoking-related terms](#)^c

Oncotype DX breast recurrence score^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037298>

has super-classes

[Assessment scales](#)^c

Only-Image^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000003>

has super-classes

[Collection method](#)^c

Open prostatectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1012630>

has super-classes

[Prostatectomy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Perineal prostatectomy](#)^c

Operation on abdominal region^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000237>

has super-classes

[Procedure on abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdomen excision](#)^c

Operation on breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034671>

has super-classes

[Breast procedure](#)^c, [Surgical procedure on thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast Conservation Treatment](#)^c, [Excision of breast](#)^c, [Excision of breast tissue](#)^c

Operation on colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057000>

has super-classes

[Procedure on colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of colon](#)^c, [Operation on sigmoid](#)^c

Operation on lower respiratory tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057925>

has super-classes

[Operation on respiratory tract](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of lung or bronchus](#)^c

Operation on lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058653>

has super-classes

[Procedure on lung](#)^c, [Surgical procedure on thorax](#)^c

Operation on lymph node^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049769>

has super-classes

[Procedure on lymph node](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Dissection of lymph node](#)^c, [Excision of lymph node](#)^c

Operation on male genital system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1011855>

has super-classes

[Procedure on male genital system](#)^c

Operation on pelvic region of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057975>

has super-classes

[Procedure on trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of mass of pelvic region](#)^c, [Excision of pelvis](#)^c, [Operation on rectum](#)^c, [Operation on sigmoid](#)^c

Operation on prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1012473>

has super-classes

[Procedure on prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Prostatectomy](#)^c

Operation on rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058026>

has super-classes

[Operation on pelvic region of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Resection of rectum](#)^c

Operation on respiratory tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057876>

has super-classes

[Procedure by method](#)^c, [Surgical procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Operation on lower respiratory tract](#)^c

Operation on sigmoid^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057828>

has super-classes

[Operation on colon](#)^c, [Operation on pelvic region of trunk](#)^c, [Operative procedure on pelvis](#)^c, [Procedure on sigmoid colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Sigmoid colectomy](#)^c

Operations by approach^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1014255>

has super-classes

[Surgical procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdominoperineal resection](#)^c, [Anterior resection of rectum](#)^c, [Perineal prostatectomy](#)^c, [Retropubic prostatectomy](#)^c

Operative procedure on pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1012317>

has super-classes

[Procedure on pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of pelvis](#)^c, [Operation on sigmoid](#)^c

Optic canal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000200>

has super-classes

[Skull foramen](#)^c, [Structure of body conduit](#)^c, [Structure of lesser wing of sphenoid bone](#)^c

Orbit structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000237>

has super-classes

[Structure of orbital region](#)^c

Organ within abdominopelvic cavity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000103>

has super-classes

[Intra-abdominopelvic structure](#)^c, [Structure of viscus](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of organ within abdomen proper cavity](#)^c

Orientation descriptor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016629>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c, [Tumor Observation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Not parallel](#)^c, [Parallel](#)^c

Original Dataset^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000020>

has super-classes

[Dataset Type](#)^c

Origins^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002293>

has super-classes

[Descriptor](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Spontaneous](#)^c

Other Anatomic Concept^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063490>

has super-classes

[Anatomical structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anatomic Site](#)^c

Other carcinoma in situ of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002306>

has super-classes

[Carcinoma in situ of breast](#)^c

Other Hispanic/Latino/Spanish^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001208>

has super-classes

[Ethnicity](#)^c

Other hormone antagonists and related agents^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021453>

has super-classes

[HORMONE ANTAGONISTS AND RELATED AGENTS](#)^c

Other modality (DICOM)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000074>

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#)^c

has sub-classes

[SEG](#)^c

Others^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001053>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

Oval^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1010760>

[PI-RADS]: The shape of either an oval or an ellipse. [BI-RADS 5]: Elliptical or egg-shaped (may include two or three undulations; i.e. gently lobulated or macrolobulated). [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Morphologic descriptor](#)^c

Oval mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016515>

BI-RADS: Mammo and MRI: Elliptical or egg-shaped (may include two or three undulations). US: Elliptical or egg-shaped (may include two or three undulations, i.e. gently lobulated or microlobulated). [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Mass](#)^c

Ovarian part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063726>

has super-classes

[Ovary](#)^c

Ovary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000274>

has super-classes

[Ovary](#)^c, [Structure of endocrine system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Entire ovary](#)^c, [Ovarian part](#)^c, [Structure of left ovary](#)^c, [Structure of right ovary](#)^c

Ovary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000340>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Ovary](#)^c

Overlapping lesion of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000279>

has super-classes

[Breast](#)^c

oxaliplatin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063658>

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Oxyphilic adenocarcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049463>

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#)^c, [Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

P - Portal vein marker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044443>

has super-classes

[Markers for liver tumor staging](#)^c

P53 protein Ag [Presence] in Tissue by Immune stain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051945>

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c

Paclitaxel^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035850>

A compound extracted from the Pacific yew tree *Taxus brevifolia* with antineoplastic activity. Paclitaxel binds to tubulin and inhibits the disassembly of microtubules, thereby resulting in the inhibition of cell division. This agent also induces apoptosis by binding to and blocking the function of the apoptosis inhibitor protein Bcl-2 (B-cell Leukemia 2). (NCI04)

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c, [Immunologic agent](#)^c

Pain in male pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000348>

has super-classes

[Pain in pelvis](#)^c

Pain in pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000349>

has super-classes

[Finding of pelvic region of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Pain in male pelvis](#)^c

Pain of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037129>

has super-classes

[Chest pain](#)^c

Painful ejaculation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018937>

has super-classes

[Sexual function painful](#)^c

PALB2 (partner and localizer of BRCA2) gene variant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063214>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

PALB2 gene targeted mutation analysis in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049100>

has super-classes

[Molecular pathology](#)^c

Palbociclib^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036241>

An orally available cyclin-dependent kinase (CDK) inhibitor with potential antineoplastic activity. Palbociclib selectively inhibits cyclin-dependent kinase 4 (CDK4) and 6 (CDK6), thereby inhibiting retinoblastoma (Rb) protein phosphorylation early in the G1 phase leading to cell cycle arrest. This suppresses DNA replication and decreases tumor cell proliferation. CDK4 and 6 are serine/threonine kinases that are upregulated in many tumor cell types and play a key role in the regulation of cell cycle progression. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Palliative intent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002603>

has super-classes

[Intents](#)^c

Palpation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004322>

has super-classes

[Examination by method](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Palpation of abdomen](#)^c

Palpation of abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1020402>

has super-classes

[Examination of abdomen](#)^c, [Palpation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Digital examination of rectum](#)^c

Pancreas^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000209>

An organ behind the lower part of the stomach that is the shape of a fish and about the size of a hand. It is a compound gland composed of both exocrine and endocrine tissues. The endocrine pancreas makes insulin so that the body can use glucose (sugar) for energy. The exocrine pancreas makes enzymes that help the body digest food. Spread all over the pancreas are areas called the Islets of Langerhans. The cells in these areas each have a special purpose. The alpha cells make glucagon, which raises the level of glucose in the blood; the beta cells make insulin; the delta cells make somatostatin. There are also PP cells and D1 cells, about which little is known. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Digestive organ structure](#) ^c, [ICDO3Topography](#) ^c, [Intra-abdominal digestive structure](#) ^c, [Retroperitoneal compartment structure](#) ^c, [Structure of endocrine system](#) ^c, [Structure of organ within abdomen proper cavity](#) ^c

Papillary adenocarcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049461>

is equivalent to

[Papillary adenocarcinoma, NOS](#) ^c

has super-classes

[Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Papillary thyroid carcinoma](#) ^c

Papillary adenocarcinoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049465>

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#) ^c

Papillary carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049532>

is equivalent to

[Papillary carcinoma, NOS](#) ^c

has super-classes

[Malignant squamous cell neoplasm](#) ^c

Papillary carcinoma, follicular variant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049605>

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#) ^c, [Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#) ^c

Papillary carcinoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063544>

has super-classes

[Squamous cell neoplasms](#) ^c

Papillary carcinoma, NOS, of breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060868>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#) ^c

Papillary thyroid carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049462>

has super-classes

[Papillary adenocarcinoma](#) ^c

Parallel^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016638>

[BI-RADS] US: Long axis of lesion parallels the skin line (wider than tall or horizontal) [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Orientation descriptor](#)^c

Parent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001033>

has super-classes

[Immediate family member](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Father](#)^c, [Mother](#)^c

Parietal lobe^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000352>

has super-classes

[Brain](#)^c, [Brain Lesion Site](#)^c

Parietal region^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000422>

has super-classes

[Brain region](#)^c

Partial^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002499>

has super-classes

[Extensiveness](#)^c

Partial excision of large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058131>

has super-classes

[Large intestine excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of colon](#)^c, [Resection of rectum](#)^c

Partial lobectomy of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004594>

has super-classes

[Lobectomy of brain](#)^c

Partial mastectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056931>

has super-classes

[Excision of breast](#)^c, [Excision of breast tissue](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lumpectomy of breast](#)^c

Partial Methylated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001316>

has super-classes

[Methylated](#)^c

Partial resection of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057051>

has super-classes

[Excision of colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left colectomy](#)^c, [Right colectomy](#)^c, [Sigmoid colectomy](#)^c, [Transverse colectomy](#)^c

Partial resection of lobe of brain|(Tumor involves more than half of lobe)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1004570>

has super-classes

[Surgical resection status](#)^c

Partial response^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001186>

has super-classes

[Treatment response value](#)^c

Partial response (PR)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001220>

has super-classes

[Neoadjuvant Therapy response value](#)^c

Partially solid^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001074>

has super-classes

[Formations](#)^c

Past^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001063>

has super-classes

[Current or past](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Past - specified](#)^c

Past - specified^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001068>

has super-classes

[Past](#)^c

has sub-classes

[All times past](#)^c

Pathogeneses^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002272>

has super-classes

[Descriptor](#)^c, [Special disorder atoms](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Drug-induced](#)^c

Pathology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036583>

has super-classes

[Laboratory procedure](#)^c, [Measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cells.Ki-67 nuclear Ag/100 cells in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c, [Cells.estrogen receptor/100 cells in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c, [Cells.progesterone receptor/100 cells in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c, [DNA mismatch repair protein Msh3 \[Presence\] in Cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c, [Estrogen receptor Ag \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c, [Extramural vein invasion](#)^c, [HER2](#)^c, [HER2 Ag \[Presence\] in Tissue by Immune stain](#)^c, [Insulin-like growth factor-I receptor Ag \[Presence\] in Tissue by Immune stain](#)^c, [Lymphovascular invasion](#)^c, [Lymphovascular invasion extent in Cancer specimen Qualitative](#)^c, [Melan-A and Ki67 Ag \[Identifier\] in Tissue by Immune stain](#)^c, [Microsatellite markers exhibiting instability/Microsatellite instability markers assessed in Cancer specimen](#)^c, [P53 protein Ag \[Presence\] in Tissue by Immune stain](#)^c, [PD-L1 by Immune stain measurement](#)^c, [PD-L1 by clone 22C3 \[Presence\] in Tissue by Immune stain](#)^c, [Pathology protocols - general](#)^c, [Perineural invasion | Cancer specimen | Pathology](#)^c, [Progesterone receptor Ag \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c

Pathology (qualifier value)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001953>

has super-classes

[Clinical specialty](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Histopathology](#)^c

Pathology examination findings present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049723>

has super-classes

[General pathology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Seminal vesicle invasion by tumor present](#)^c, [Surgical margin involved by tumor](#)^c, [Venous \(large vessel\) invasion by tumor present](#)^c

Pathology protocols - general^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036582>

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Size additional dimension in Tumor](#)^c, [Size maximum dimension in Tumor](#)^c

Pathology Result^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000205>

has super-classes

[Laboratory Test Result](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Histopathology Result](#)^c

Pathophysiologic finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051846>

unknown or uncertain etiology, or associated with multiple diseases; for example, pneumonia is a process [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Mechanical disorder](#)^c

Patient^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001047>

has super-classes

[Person in the healthcare environment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cancer Patient](#)^c

is in domain of

[BirthDate](#)^{dp}, [BirthYear](#)^{dp}, [Deceased](#)^{dp}, [PatientIdentifier](#)^{dp}, [has_date_of_last_contact](#)^{op}, [has_deceased](#)^{op}, [hasAgeAtScan](#)^{op}, [hasBirthSex](#)^{op},
[hasDiagnosticCategory](#)^{op}, [hasEthnicity](#)^{op}

is in range of

[hasSubject](#)^{op}

Patient age^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000124>

clarification from DICOM

has super-classes

[Age](#)^c

is in range of

[hasAgeAtScan](#)^{op}

Patient condition finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051880>

has super-classes

[Patient status finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Patient condition undetermined](#)^c, [Patient's condition improved](#)^c, [Patient's condition stable](#)^c, [Patient's condition worsened](#)^c

is in range of

[hasCancerDiseaseStatus](#)^{op}

Patient condition undetermined^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051885>

has super-classes

[Patient condition finding](#)^c

Patient Orientation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016610>

has super-classes

[Imaging procedure descriptor](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Feet first orientation](#)^c, [Head first orientation](#)^c

Patient Position^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016605>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Standing position](#)^c, [Supine](#)^c, [Upright position](#)^c

Patient status finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051876>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Patient condition finding](#)^c

Patient with Cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001087>

has super-classes

[Population](#)^c

Patient with lesion not being a malignant tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001086>

has super-classes

[Population](#)^c

Patient's condition improved^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051888>

has super-classes

[Patient condition finding](#)^c

Patient's condition stable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051886>

has super-classes

[Patient condition finding](#)^c

Patient's condition worsened^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051883>

has super-classes

[Patient condition finding](#)^c

Patient-based^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000004>

has super-classes

[Collection method](#)^c

PD-L1 by clone 22C3 [Presence] in Tissue by Immune stain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051947>

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c

PD-L1 by Immune stain measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051948>

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c

Pectoral region structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000106>

has super-classes

[Chest](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast structure](#)^c

Pelvic alimentary structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000190>

has super-classes

[Intra-pelvic structure of true pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anorectal structure](#)^c

Pelvic echography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005543>

has super-classes

[Imaging of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[US scan and biopsy of pelvis](#)^c, [US scan of prostate](#)^c

Pelvic lymphadenectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1027333>

has super-classes

[Block dissection of pelvic lymph nodes](#)^c

Pelvic mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051169>

has super-classes

[Finding of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Mass of uterus](#)^c, [Neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c, [Rectal mass](#)^c

Pelvic organ finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000347>

has super-classes

[Abdominal organ finding](#)^c, [Finding of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bladder finding](#)^c

Pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000092>

Subdivision of abdomen, which is demarcated from the abdomen proper by the plane of the superior pelvic aperture, and from the perineum by the inferior surface of the pelvic diaphragm; together with the abdomen proper, it constitutes the abdomen. [FMA]

has super-classes

[Abdomen](#)^c, [Abdomen and Pelvis](#)^c, [Cross-sectional pelvis](#)^c, [Pelvis and lower extremities](#)^c, [Structure of pelvic segment of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intra-pelvic structure of true pelvis](#)^c, [Structure of right half of pelvis](#)^c

Pelvis and lower extremities^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000161>

has super-classes

[Lower body part structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Pelvis](#)^c

Pembrolizumab^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036160>

A humanized monoclonal immunoglobulin (Ig) G4 antibody directed against human cell surface receptor PD-1 (programmed death-1 or programmed cell death-1) with potential immune checkpoint inhibitory and antineoplastic activities. Upon administration, pembrolizumab binds to PD-1, an inhibitory signaling receptor expressed on the surface of activated T cells, and blocks the binding to and activation of PD-1 by its ligands, which results in the activation of T-cell-mediated immune responses against tumor cells. The ligands for PD-1 include programmed cell death ligand 1 (PD-L1), overexpressed on certain cancer cells, and programmed cell death ligand 2 (PD-L2), which is primarily expressed on APCs. Activated PD-1 negatively regulates T-cell activation and plays a key role in in tumor evasion from host immunity. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Pending^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001212>

has super-classes

[Annotation Status](#)^c

per microliter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001998>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

per nanoliter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002008>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

percent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000161>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

Percent of cell nuclei positive for proliferation marker protein Ki-67 in primary malignant neoplasm by immunohistochemistry^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049762>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Percent of cell nuclei positive for proliferation marker protein Ki-67 in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)^c

Percent of cell nuclei positive for proliferation marker protein Ki-67 in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049763>

has super-classes

[Percent of cell nuclei positive for proliferation marker protein Ki-67 in primary malignant neoplasm by immunohistochemistry](#)^c

Performance measure status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035835>

has super-classes

[Administrative statuses](#)^c

Performance Status Assessment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047418>

A measure of how well a patient is able to perform ordinary tasks and carry out daily activities. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Assessment scales](#)^c, [Health Status Assessment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification](#)^c, [American society of anesthesiologists morbidity state](#)^c, [Child-Pugh score](#)^c, [ECOG Performance Status score](#)^c, [Karnofsky performance status](#)^c

is in range of

[hasPerformanceStatusAssessment](#)^{op}

Performance Status Assessment Answer Finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052860>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ECOG performance status finding](#)^c, [Finding of American Society of Anesthesiologists physical status classification](#)^c, [Liver finding](#)^c

is in range of

[hasAnswerAsFinding](#)^{op}

Performance Status Assessment Answer Value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001110>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[EuroSpine Morbidity state](#)^c, [Performance status qualifier](#)^c

Performance status qualifier^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000025>

has super-classes

[Performance Status Assessment Answer Value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[KPS 10](#)^c, [KPS 100](#)^c, [KPS 20](#)^c, [KPS 30](#)^c, [KPS 40](#)^c, [KPS 50](#)^c, [KPS 60](#)^c, [KPS 70](#)^c, [KPS 80](#)^c, [KPS 90](#)^c, [Karnofsky Performance Scale \(KPS\)](#)^c

Perfusion Magnetic Resonance Imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004471>

A diagnostic procedure to assess the circulatory perfusion of an anatomical location using a magnetic resonance imaging machine. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Perfusion-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging](#)^c

Perfusion-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004470>

A magnetic resonance imaging modality used to quantify the blood supply to an organ or tissue using signal measurement as detected from a parenterally administered contrast agent. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Perfusion Magnetic Resonance Imaging](#)^c

Perimenopausal state^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059371>

has super-classes

[Menopause finding](#)^c

Perineal prostatectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1020502>

has super-classes

[Open prostatectomy](#)^c, [Operations by approach](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radical Perineal prostatectomy](#)^c

Perineal structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063615>

has super-classes

[Structure of pelvic segment of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anal region structure](#)^c

Perineural Invasion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033284>

has super-classes

[Measurement](#)^c

Perineural invasion [Presence] in Cancer specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046111>

has super-classes

[Perineural invasion | Cancer specimen | Pathology](#)^c

Perineural invasion by tumor absent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059712>

has super-classes

[Perineural invasion finding](#)^c

Perineural invasion by tumor present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059676>

has super-classes

[Perineural invasion finding](#)^c

Perineural invasion finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056606>

has super-classes

[Tumor invasion finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Perineural invasion by tumor absent](#)^c, [Perineural invasion by tumor present](#)^c

Perineural invasion | Cancer specimen | Pathology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037435>

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Perineural invasion \[Presence\] in Cancer specimen](#)^c

Peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000006>

PI-RADS: The peripheral zone covers the outer posterior, lateral, and apex regions of the prostate. It makes up most of the apex of the prostate. [RADLEX]

has super-classes

[Glandular zone of prostate](#)^c

Person^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001042>

has super-classes

[Common Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Person in the family](#)^c, [Person in the healthcare environment](#)^c

Person in family of subject^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001045>

has super-classes

[Person in the family](#)^c

Person in the family^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001043>

has super-classes

[Person](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Person in family of subject](#)^c, [Relative](#)^c

is in range of

[hasRelationship](#)^{op}

Person in the healthcare environment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001044>

has super-classes

[Person](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Healthcare professional](#)^c, [Imaging technician](#)^c, [Patient](#)^c

Pertuzumab^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035971>

A humanized recombinant monoclonal antibody directed against the extracellular dimerization domain of the HER-2 tyrosine kinase receptor. Binding of the antibody to the dimerization domain of the HER-2 tyrosine kinase receptor protein directly inhibits the ability of the HER-2 tyrosine kinase receptor protein (the most common pairing partner) to dimerize with other HER tyrosine kinase receptor proteins; inhibiting receptor protein dimerization prevents the activation of HER signaling pathways, resulting in tumor cell apoptosis. (NCI04)

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

PET-CT^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004451>

An imaging technique that utilizes positron emission tomography and computed tomography in a single machine. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Imaging sequence](#)^c, [combined modalities](#)^c

PET-MR^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004452>

has super-classes

[combined modalities](#)^c

Peutz Jeghers polyp^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063525>

has super-classes

[Hamartomatous polyp](#)^c

Peutz-Jeghers syndrome^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059049>

has super-classes

[Autosomal dominant hereditary disorder](#)^c, [Congenital hamartoma](#)^c, [Congenital melanosis](#)^c, [Digestive system hereditary disorder](#)^c, [Hamartoma of intestine](#)^c, [Hereditary cancer-predisposing syndrome](#)^c, [Hereditary disorder of nervous system](#)^c, [Hereditary disorder of the integument](#)^c, [Intestinal polyposis syndrome](#)^c, [Lentiginosis](#)^c, [Neurocutaneous syndrome](#)^c

Pharmaceutical / biologic product^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035146>

has super-classes

[Medication](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Contrast agent](#)^c

Pharmacological assessment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034362>

has super-classes

[Management of drug regimen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Medication Review](#)^c

Philips^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000046>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Photon Counting Computed Tomography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000085>

has super-classes

[Computed tomography](#)^c

Phyllodes tumor, malignant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063612>

has super-classes

[Fibroepithelial neoplasms](#)^c

Phyllodes tumor, malignant of breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060877>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Physical^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000133>

has super-classes

[Adjectival modifier](#)^c, [Image Coordinate System](#)^c

Physical examination^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018534>

has super-classes

[Evidence Type](#)^c, [Examination by method](#)^c, [Tumor Size Method](#)^c

Physical Examination^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047420>

A systemic evaluation of the body and its functions using visual inspection, palpation, percussion and auscultation. The purpose is to determine the presence or absence of physical signs of disease or abnormality for an individual's health assessment. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Medical Assessment](#)^c

Physical object^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000004>

has super-classes

[Common Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[device](#)^c

Physical status qualifier^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000027>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Healthy patient](#)^c, [Mild systemic disease](#)^c, [Severe systemic disease](#)^c, [Severe systemic disease that is a threat to life](#)^c, [brain-dead patient, organ donor](#)^c, [moribund patient who is not expected to survive](#)^c

Physician^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001106>

has super-classes

[Medical practitioner](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Specialized physician](#)^c

Physician who performed a surgical procedure was not a surgeon (i.e., radiation oncologist, diagnostic radiologist, or general practitioner)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001101>

has super-classes

[Specialized physician](#) ^c

PI-RADS 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005479>

Clinically significant cancer is highly unlikely to be present in the prostate. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS Overall Assessment Category](#) ^c

PI-RADS 1 - Very low (Lesion)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005487>

Clinically significant cancer is highly unlikely to be present in a lesion. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS Lesion Assessment Category](#) ^c

PI-RADS 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005478>

Clinically significant cancer is unlikely to be present in the prostate. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS Overall Assessment Category](#) ^c

PI-RADS 2 - Low (Lesion)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005486>

Clinically significant cancer is unlikely to be present in a lesion. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS Lesion Assessment Category](#) ^c

PI-RADS 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005477>

The presence of clinically significant cancer in the prostate is equivocal. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS Overall Assessment Category](#) ^c

PI-RADS 3 - Intermediate (Lesion)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005485>

The presence of clinically significant cancer in a lesion is equivocal. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS Lesion Assessment Category](#) ^c

PI-RADS 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005476>

Clinically significant cancer is likely to be present in the prostate. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS Overall Assessment Category](#) ^c

PI-RADS 4 - High (Lesion)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005484>

Clinically significant cancer is likely to be present in a lesion. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS Lesion Assessment Category](#).^c

PI-RADS 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005475>

Clinically significant cancer is highly likely to be present in the prostate. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS Overall Assessment Category](#).^c

PI-RADS 5 - Very high (Lesion)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005483>

Clinically significant cancer is highly likely to be present in a lesion. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS Lesion Assessment Category](#).^c

PI-RADS assessment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005457>

has super-classes

[Assessment](#).^c

has sub-classes

[PI-RADS Lesion Assessment Category](#).^c, [PI-RADS Overall Assessment Category](#).^c

PI-RADS Lesion Assessment Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005481>

A 5-point scale based on the likelihood (probability) that a combination of mpMRI findings on T2W, DWI, and DCE correlates with the presence of clinically significant cancer in a lesion in the prostate gland. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS assessment](#).^c

has sub-classes

[PI-RADS 1 - Very low \(Lesion\)](#).^c, [PI-RADS 2 - Low \(Lesion\)](#).^c, [PI-RADS 3 - Intermediate \(Lesion\)](#).^c, [PI-RADS 4 - High \(Lesion\)](#).^c, [PI-RADS 5 - Very high \(Lesion\)](#).^c, [PI-RADS X - Inadequate or absent \(Lesion\)](#).^c

PI-RADS Overall Assessment Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005451>

has super-classes

[PI-RADS assessment](#).^c

has sub-classes

[PI-RADS 1](#).^c, [PI-RADS 2](#).^c, [PI-RADS 3](#).^c, [PI-RADS 4](#).^c, [PI-RADS 5](#).^c, [PI-RADS X](#).^c

PI-RADS X^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005474>

DWI and DCE are inadequate or absent; assessment is limited to staging for determination of extra-capsular extension. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS Overall Assessment Category](#).^c

PI-RADS X - Inadequate or absent (Lesion)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005482>

DWI and DCE are inadequate or absent; assessment is limited to staging for determination of extra-capsular extension. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[PI-RADS Lesion Assessment Category](#)^c

Pial Invasion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016721>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Pial Invasion value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016721>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Absent](#)^c, [No](#)^c, [Present](#)^c, [Yes](#)^c

Picker International^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000059>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

picogram per milliliter^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002019>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

PIK3CA gene [VCF] in Cancer specimen by Sequencing^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052157>

has super-classes

[Molecular pathology](#)^c

PIK3CA gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051936>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

Pixel^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000134>

The smallest resolvable rectangular area of an image, either on a screen or stored in memory. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Image Coordinate System](#)^c, [Qualifier](#)^c

Plain radiography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016732>

has super-classes

[Radiographic imaging procedure](#)^c

Plain X-ray imaging - action^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000039>

has super-classes

[Radiographic imaging - action](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Tomographic imaging, plain radiologic - action](#)^c

Planar nuclear medicine imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000080>

has super-classes

[Single photon imaging](#)^c

Platelets [# /volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033432>

has super-classes

[Platelets|Number Concentration \(count/vol\)|Moment in time|Blood](#)^c

Platelets|Number Concentration (count/vol)|Moment in time|Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049973>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Platelets \[# /volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Pleural effusion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051717>

has super-classes

[Disorder of pleura and pleural cavity](#)^c

pM category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033349>

has super-classes

[M category](#)^c, [TNM classification of malignant tumor after operation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[TNM Path M](#)^c

pM0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001845>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value](#)^c

pM1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000531>

is equivalent to

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1](#)^c

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value](#)^c

pM1a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000558>

is equivalent to

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1a \(qualifier value\)](#) ^c

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value](#) ^c

pM1b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000586>

is equivalent to

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1b \(qualifier value\)](#) ^c

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value](#) ^c

pM1c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000615>

is equivalent to

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pM1c \(qualifier value\)](#) ^c

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value](#) ^c

pM1d^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001250>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological M category allowable value](#) ^c

pN category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033368>

has super-classes

[N category](#) ^c, [TNM classification of malignant tumor after operation](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[TNM Path N](#) ^c

pN0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000645>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

pN0(i+)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002816>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

pN0(i-)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002806>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

pN0m+^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002839>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

pN0m^{-c} back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002827>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

pN1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000676>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

pN1a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000744>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

pN1b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000745>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

pN2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001550>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

pN3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001552>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

pN3a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001555>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

pN3b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001559>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

pN3c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001564>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value](#) ^c

Pneumonitis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052535>

has super-classes

[Disorder of lung^c](#), [Inflammatory disorder of lower respiratory tract^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Drug-induced pneumonitis^c](#)

pNX^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001570>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological N category allowable value^c](#)

Polyp^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054863>

has super-classes

[Proliferative mass^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Adenomatous polyposis coli^c](#), [Hamartomatous polyp^c](#)

Polyp of intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054315>

has super-classes

[Abdominal mass^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Intestinal polyposis syndrome^c](#)

Poor stream of urine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000369>

has super-classes

[Strength of stream of urine - finding^c](#)

Poorly defined^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002023>

has super-classes

[Degree findings^c](#), [Enhancing margin value^c](#), [Non-enhancing margin value^c](#)

Population^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001084>

has super-classes

[Subjects of information^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Control group^c](#), [Negative screening^c](#), [Patient with Cancer^c](#), [Patient with lesion not being a malignant tumor^c](#), [Screening^c](#), [Subject under discussion with suspicious findings^c](#)

is in range of

[hasDiagnosticCategory^{op}](#)

Positive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001310>

has super-classes

[General adjectival modifier](#)^c, [Presence findings](#)^c

Positive integer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002348>

has super-classes

[Cardinal number](#)^c

has sub-classes

[1](#)^c, [2](#)^c, [3](#)^c

Positive Laboratory Test Result^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052172>

has super-classes

[Laboratory Test Result](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Expression Positive](#)^c

Positron emission tomography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000037>

A technique for measuring the gamma radiation produced by collisions of electrons and positrons (anti-electrons) within living tissue. In positron emission tomography (PET), a subject is given a dose of a positron-emitting radionuclide attached to a metabolically active substance (for example, 2-fluoro-2-deoxy-D-glucose (FDG), which is similar to a naturally occurring sugar, glucose, with the addition of a radioactive fluorine atom). When living tissue containing the positron emitter is bombarded by electrons, gamma radiation produced by collisions of electrons and positrons is detected by a scanner, revealing in fine detail the tissue location of the metabolically-active substance administered. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Nuclear medicine imaging procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Positron emission tomography of whole body](#)^c

Positron emission tomography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000062>

has super-classes

[Nuclear medicine imaging](#)^c, [Radionuclide imaging - action](#)^c

Positron emission tomography of whole body^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016734>

has super-classes

[Positron emission tomography](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Positron emission tomography of whole body using choline C-11](#)^c

Positron emission tomography of whole body using choline C-11^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016737>

has super-classes

[Positron emission tomography of whole body](#)^c

Postarterial phase^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016764>

has super-classes

[enhancement phase](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Early venous phase](#)^c, [Late venous phase](#)^c

Posterior acoustic enhancement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016615>

BI-RADS US: Appears as a column that is more echogenic (whiter) deep to the mass. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Posterior acoustic feature](#)^c

Posterior acoustic feature^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016621>

Posterior acoustic features represent the attenuation characteristics of a mass with respect to its acoustic transmission. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Attenuation characteristic](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Combined posterior acoustic pattern](#)^c, [No posterior acoustic features](#)^c, [Posterior acoustic enhancement](#)^c, [Posterior acoustic shadowing](#)^c

Posterior acoustic shadowing^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016613>

BI-RADS US: the area posterior to the mass appears darker. (Refractive edge shadowing is of no significance.) [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Posterior acoustic feature](#)^c

Postmenopausal state^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059346>

has super-classes

[Menopause finding](#)^c, [Menstruation absent](#)^c

Postmenopause - Menopause present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048610>

has super-classes

[Menopause finding](#)^c

Postoperative chemotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060677>

has super-classes

[Chemotherapy](#)^c

Potassium [Mass/volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033509>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#)^c, [Potassium measurement](#)^c, [Potassium|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Potassium|Moment in time|Blood|39.098.g/mole](#)^c

Potassium measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050664>

has super-classes

[Measurement of substance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Potassium \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#) ^c

Potassium|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049874>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Potassium \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#) ^c

Potassium|Moment in time|Blood|39.098 g/mole^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050218>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Potassium \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#) ^c

PR negative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049000>

An indication that progesterone receptor (PRG; PR) expression has not been detected in a sample. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

([Has Associated Tumor Marker Test](#) ^{op} some [Progesterone receptor Ag.\[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#) ^c) and

([hasAnswer](#) ^{op} only [Negative](#) ^c)

has super-classes

[Hormone receptor negative neoplasm](#) ^c

PR positive^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048841>

An indication that progesterone receptor (PRG; PR) expression has been detected in a sample. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

([Has Associated Tumor Marker Test](#) ^{op} some [Progesterone receptor Ag.\[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#) ^c) and

([hasAnswer](#) ^{op} only [Positive](#) ^c)

has super-classes

[Hormone receptor positive tumor](#) ^c

Pre-operative chemotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060649>

has super-classes

[Chemotherapy](#) ^c

Prefer not to answer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001346>

has super-classes

[Alcohol drinker status value](#) ^c, [Qualifier](#) ^c, [Smoking status value](#) ^c

Pregnancy observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045623>

has super-classes

[Observable entity](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Measure of pregnancy](#)^c

Pregnancy status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051857>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

Pregnancy status value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001172>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Not pregnant](#)^c, [Pregnant](#)^c

Pregnancy, childbirth / puerperium observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040135>

has super-classes

[Clinical history/examination observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Obstetric history](#)^c

Pregnant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001161>

has super-classes

[Pregnancy status value](#)^c

Premenopausal state^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059322>

has super-classes

[Finding related to menstrual cycle](#)^c, [Menopause finding](#)^c

Premenopause - Menopause absent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046580>

has super-classes

[Female genitalia finding](#)^c, [Menopause finding](#)^c

Presence findings^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001072>

has super-classes

[Finding value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Methylated](#)^c, [Mutated](#)^c, [Mutated/c.1-124C>T](#)^c, [Mutated/c.1-146C>T](#)^c, [Positive](#)^c, [Present](#)^c, [Yes](#)^c

is disjoint with

[Absence findings](#)^c

Presence of direct invasion by malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035520>

has super-classes

[Presence of direct invasion by neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Presence of direct invasion by primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Presence of direct invasion by neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035490>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Presence of direct invasion by malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Presence of direct invasion by primary malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035551>

has super-classes

[Presence of direct invasion by malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Presence of direct invasion by primary malignant neoplasm to lymphatic vessel and/or small blood vessel](#)^c

Presence of direct invasion by primary malignant neoplasm to lymphatic vessel and/or small blood vessel^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035583>

has super-classes

[Presence of direct invasion by primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Presence of estrogen receptor in neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049757>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Presence of estrogen receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)^c

Presence of estrogen receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049758>

has super-classes

[Presence of estrogen receptor in neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intensity of stain of estrogen receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)^c

Presence of metastatic discontinuous spread of malignant neoplasm of colon to pericolic tissue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049097>

has super-classes

[Presence of metastatic discontinuous spread of primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Presence of metastatic discontinuous spread of primary malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049092>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Presence of metastatic discontinuous spread of malignant neoplasm of colon to pericolic tissue](#)^c

Presence of progesterone receptor in neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049760>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Presence of progesterone receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)^c

Presence of progesterone receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049761>

has super-classes

[Presence of progesterone receptor in neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intensity of stain of progesterone receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)^c

Present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001942>

has super-classes

[Calvarial Remodeling value](#)^c, [Cortical Involvement value](#)^c, [Cysts value](#)^c, [Ependymal Extension value](#)^c, [Pial Invasion value](#)^c, [Presence findings](#)^c, [Satellites value](#)^c

has sub-classes

["+"](#)^c, ["++"](#)^c, ["+++"](#)^c, ["++++"](#)^c

Preventive intent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002605>

has super-classes

[Intents](#)^c

Previous^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001345>

has super-classes

[Adjectival modifier](#)^c, [Alcohol drinker status value](#)^c, [Smoking status value](#)^c

Primary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000017>

Occurring first in time or sequence; original; of greatest rank or importance or value. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Cancer Condition Type](#)^c, [Disease Clinical Qualifier](#)^c, [General adjectival modifier](#)^c

Primary adenocarcinoma of ascending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054446>

has super-classes

[Primary adenocarcinoma of colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of ascending colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenosquamous carcinoma of ascending colon](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon](#)^c

Primary adenocarcinoma of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052250>

has super-classes

[Adenocarcinoma of large intestine](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenosquamous carcinoma of colon, NOS](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of transverse colon](#)^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of transverse colon](#)^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of ascending colon](#)^c

Primary adenocarcinoma of digestive organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054513>

has super-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary mucinous carcinoma of digestive organ](#)^c

Primary adenocarcinoma of pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016398>

has super-classes

[Adenocarcinoma of pelvis](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation of prostate gland](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of rectum, NOS](#)^c, [Basal cell adenocarcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c

Primary Cancer Condition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007988>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glioblastoma multiforme](#)^c, [ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Malignant epithelial neoplasm](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of abdomen](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of digestive system](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of genitourinary organ](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of lower respiratory tract](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of nervous system](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of respiratory system](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of skeletal system](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of soft tissue](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm of thorax](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract](#)^c, [Malignant neuroendocrine tumor](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of head and neck](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of lymphoid hemopoietic and related tissue](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of pelvis](#)^c, [Malignant tumor of upper limb](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine neoplasm, malignant](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Sarcoma](#)^c

is in range of

[ImagingAssessmentMethodFor](#)^{op}, [hasEpisodeEventRelatedEntity](#)^{op}, [hasFocus](#)^{op}, [hasPrimaryCancerCondition](#)^{op}, [hasRelatedPrimaryCancerCondition](#)^{op}

is disjoint with

[Secondary Cancer Condition](#)^c

Primary Gleason pattern^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049686>

has super-classes

[Gleason pattern](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 1](#)^c, [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 2](#)^c, [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 3](#)^c, [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 4](#)^c, [Gleason Primary Pattern Grade 5](#)^c

Primary Gleason Pattern 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031198>

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 1 tumor](#)^c

Primary Gleason Pattern 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031187>

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 2 tumor](#)^c

Primary Gleason Pattern 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031232>

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 3 tumor](#)^c

Primary Gleason Pattern 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031243>

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 4 tumor](#)^c

Primary Gleason Pattern 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031192>

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c

Primary malignant meningioma of meninges of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059403>

has super-classes

[Malignant meningioma of meninges of brain](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000143>

A malignant tumor at the original site of growth. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#)^c, [Invasive carcinoma of breast with extensive intraductal component](#)^c, [Invasive carcinoma of breast without extensive intraductal component](#)^c, [Neuroblastoma](#)^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of digestive organ](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of nervous system](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of respiratory tract](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of trunk](#)^c, [Small cell carcinoma](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007730>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of abdomen](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of ascending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054650>

has super-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of ascending colon](#)^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of ascending colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of hepatic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of ascending colon](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007978>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of brain](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000068>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of breast](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of breast with axillary lymph node invasion](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of female breast](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of breast with axillary lymph node invasion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046501>

has super-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of breast](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of cecum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053363>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of cecum](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of large intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenocarcinoma, NOS, of cecum](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of cecum](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of cecum](#)^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of cecum](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045970>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of large intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of colon, NOS](#)^c, [Primary adenocarcinoma of colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of ascending colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of descending colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of transverse colon](#)^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of colon, NOS](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of descending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054720>

has super-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of descending colon](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of descending colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of descending colon](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of esophagus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000095>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of oesophagus](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of female breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047300>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of female breast](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of breast](#) ^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of gallbladder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000091>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of gallbladder](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#) ^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of hepatic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053510>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of hepatic flexure](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of ascending colon](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of transverse colon](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Adenosquamous carcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon](#) ^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of hepatic flexure of colon](#) ^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon](#) ^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of intestinal tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036362>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of intestine](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of large intestine](#) ^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000168>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of intraabdominal organ](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of abdomen](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of gallbladder](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of kidney](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of liver](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of ovary](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of stomach](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of uterus](#) ^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of intrathoracic organs^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051710>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of thorax](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of intrathoracic organs](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of trunk](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of lung](#) ^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of kidney^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000088>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of kidney](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#) ^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036373>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of large intestine](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intestinal tract](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of cecum](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of colon](#) ^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of rectum](#) ^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000072>

An epithelial or non-epithelial malignant neoplasm that arises from the liver. Representative examples include hepatocellular carcinoma, intrahepatic cholangiocarcinoma, lymphoma, and sarcoma. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of liver](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051722>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of lung](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intrathoracic organs](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of respiratory tract](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of male genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1008355>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of male genital organ](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054128>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of nervous system](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Glioblastoma, NOS, of nervous system, NOS](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of ovary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003326>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of ovary](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1008612>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of pelvis](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary adenocarcinoma of pelvis](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of rectum](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of urinary bladder](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of uterus](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1008742>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of male genital organ](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Acinar cell carcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c, [Adenocarcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation of prostate gland](#)^c, [Adenosquamous carcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c, [Basal cell adenocarcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c, [Infiltrating duct carcinoma of prostate](#)^c, [Large cell neuroendocrine carcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c, [Neoplasm, malignant of prostate gland](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine tumor, NOS, of prostate gland](#)^c, [Small cell carcinoma of prostate](#)^c, [Transitional cell carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045950>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of rectum](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of large intestine](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of rectum, NOS](#)^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of rectum, NOS](#)^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of rectum, NOS](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of respiratory tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051713>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of respiratory system](#)^c, [Neoplasm of respiratory tract](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of lung](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of sigmoid colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053613>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenosquamous carcinoma of sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of sigmoid colon](#)^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of sigmoid colon](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of splenic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053775>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of splenic flexure](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of descending colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of transverse colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenosquamous carcinoma of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Mucinous adenocarcinoma of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of stomach^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000093>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of stomach](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of transverse colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054791>

has super-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenosquamous carcinoma of transverse colon](#)^c, [Carcinoma, undifferentiated, NOS, of transverse colon](#)^c, [Neuroendocrine carcinoma, NOS, of transverse colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of hepatic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c, [Signet ring cell carcinoma of transverse colon](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000155>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of trunk](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of abdomen](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of breast](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intrathoracic organs](#)^c,
[Primary malignant neoplasm of male genital organ](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of vulva](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of urinary bladder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000182>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of bladder](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of uterine cervix^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003319>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of cervix uteri](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of uterus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003323>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of uterus](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of pelvis](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of vagina^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003324>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of vagina](#)^c

Primary malignant neoplasm of vulva^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003313>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of vulva](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of trunk](#)^c

Primary mucinous carcinoma of digestive organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054581>

has super-classes

[Primary adenocarcinoma of digestive organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Mucinous adenocarcinoma of transverse colon](#)^c

Primary pattern unknown, secondary pattern unknown^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033313>

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c

Primary sclerosing cholangitis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046225>

A chronic, autoimmune inflammatory liver disorder characterized by narrowing and scarring of the lumen of the bile ducts. It is often seen in patients with ulcerative colitis. Signs and symptoms include jaundice, fatigue, and malabsorption. It may lead to cirrhosis and liver failure. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Sclerosing cholangitis](#)^c

Primary tumor size^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035355>

has super-classes

[Length dimension of neoplasm](#)^c

is in range of

[Has Associated Dimension](#)^{op}

problematic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000119>

Image annotation label (INCISIVE, Annotation Definitions and guidelines)

has super-classes

[Qualifier for certainty of diagnosis](#)^c

Procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000005>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Administration of medication](#)^c, [Curative therapy](#)^c, [Evaluation procedure](#)^c, [Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c, [Laboratory procedure](#)^c, [Medical therapy](#)^c, [Non-curative therapy](#)^c, [Procedure by intent](#)^c, [Procedure by method](#)^c, [Procedure on organ](#)^c, [Procedure with a procedure focus](#)^c, [Provider-specific procedure](#)^c, [Regimes and therapies](#)^c, [Surgical procedure](#)^c, [Therapeutic procedure](#)^c

is in range of

[hasProcedure](#)^{op}, [hasRelatedProcedure](#)^{op}

Procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000021>

has super-classes

[Generic Category](#)^c, [Observation Category](#)^c

is in domain of

[hasProcedureCategory](#)^{op}

Procedure by intent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058296>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[First line treatment](#)^c, [Second line treatment](#)^c, [Third line treatment](#)^c

Procedure by method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058185>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Counseling](#)^c, [Management of drug regimen](#)^c, [Operation on respiratory tract](#)^c, [Removal](#)^c

Procedure carried out on subject^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034124>

has super-classes

[Procedure with explicit context](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Laboratory procedure performed](#)^c

Procedure Category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000027>

Procedure Category code: A selection of relevant SNOMED CT codes (mCODE)

has super-classes

[Category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Counseling](#)^c, [Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c, [Laboratory test](#)^c, [Measurement](#)^c, [Removal](#)^c, [Surgical procedure](#)^c

is in range of

[hasProcedureCategory](#)^{op}

Procedure on abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000233>

has super-classes

[Procedure on organ](#)^c, [Procedure on trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Examination of abdomen](#)^c, [Lower gastrointestinal procedure](#)^c, [Operation on abdominal region](#)^c, [Procedure on prostate](#)^c

Procedure on colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056976>

has super-classes

[Procedure on large intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Operation on colon](#)^c, [Procedure on sigmoid colon](#)^c

Procedure on genitourinary system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1011105>

has super-classes

[Procedure on trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Procedure on male genital system](#)^c, [Removal of entire genital organ](#)^c

Procedure on large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1011402>

has super-classes

[Procedure on organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Procedure on colon](#)^c, [Procedure on rectum](#)^c

Procedure on lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058591>

has super-classes

[Procedure on thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Operation on lung](#)^c

Procedure on lymph node^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035083>

has super-classes

[Procedure on lymphoid organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Operation on lymph node](#)^c

Procedure on lymphoid organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034175>

has super-classes

[Procedure on organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Procedure on lymph node](#)^c

Procedure on male genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1011703>

has super-classes

[Procedure on male genital system](#)^c, [Procedure on organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Procedure on prostate](#)^c

Procedure on male genital system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1011253>

has super-classes

[Procedure on genitourinary system](#)^c, [Procedure on pelvic region of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy of male genital system](#)^c, [Operation on male genital system](#)^c, [Procedure on male genital organ](#)^c

Procedure on organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000228>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast procedure](#)^c, [Complete excision](#)^c, [Procedure on abdomen](#)^c, [Procedure on large intestine](#)^c, [Procedure on lymphoid organ](#)^c, [Procedure on male genital organ](#)^c, [Procedure on trunk](#)^c

Procedure on pelvic region of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1012008>

has super-classes

[Procedure on trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Procedure on male genital system](#)^c, [Procedure on pelvis](#)^c

Procedure on pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1012162>

has super-classes

[Procedure on pelvic region of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Operative procedure on pelvis](#)^c, [Procedure on prostate](#)^c, [Procedure on rectum](#)^c

Procedure on prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1010958>

has super-classes

[Procedure on abdomen](#)^c, [Procedure on male genital organ](#)^c, [Procedure on pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy of prostate](#)^c, [Operation on prostate](#)^c

Procedure on rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1011552>

has super-classes

[Procedure on large intestine](#)^c, [Procedure on pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Rectal examination](#)^c

Procedure on sigmoid colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058716>

has super-classes

[Procedure on colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Operation on sigmoid](#)^c

Procedure on thorax^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034704>

has super-classes

[Procedure on trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast procedure](#)^c, [Procedure on lung](#)^c, [Radiotherapy to thorax](#)^c, [Surgical procedure on thorax](#)^c

Procedure on tissue specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035077>

has super-classes

[Anatomic pathology procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Sampling of tissue specimen](#)^c

Procedure on trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000230>

has super-classes

[Procedure on organ](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy of trunk](#)^c, [Operation on pelvic region of trunk](#)^c, [Procedure on abdomen](#)^c, [Procedure on genitourinary system](#)^c, [Procedure on pelvic region of trunk](#)^c, [Procedure on thorax](#)^c

Procedure with a procedure focus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058353>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Infection control management](#)^c

Procedure with explicit context^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034119>

has super-classes

[Situation with explicit context](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Laboratory procedures -general](#)^c, [Procedure carried out on subject](#)^c, [Treatment changed](#)^c

Processed Dataset^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000018>

has super-classes

[Dataset Type](#)^c

Proctectomy and anastomosis of colon to anus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060407>

has super-classes

[Abdominoperineal pull-through procedure](#)^c, [Enterectomy with anastomosis](#)^c, [Resection of rectum](#)^c

Progesterone receptor Ag [Presence] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046085>

is equivalent to

[Intensity of stain of progesterone receptor in primary malignant neoplasm of breast by immunohistochemistry](#)^c

has super-classes

[Pathology](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

Progression^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000010>

has super-classes

[Episode](#)^c

Progressive disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001189>

has super-classes

[Treatment response value](#)^c

Projection radiography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004453>

Examination of any part of the body for diagnostic purposes by means of roentgen rays, recording the image on a sensitized surface (such as photographic film). [MeSH]

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Computed radiography](#)^c, [Digital Radiography](#)^c, [Mammography](#)^c

Proliferation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016726>

has super-classes

[Growth alteration](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Proliferative mass](#)^c

Proliferative mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016728>

has super-classes

[Mass](#)^c, [Proliferation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Polyp](#)^c

Proportion Enhancing^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016744>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Proportion Enhancing value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016744>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[1/3-2/3](#)^c, [<1/3](#)^c, [>2/3](#)^c, [Minimal](#)^c

Proportion nCET^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016745>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Proportion nCET value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016745>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[1/3-2/3](#)^c, [<1/3](#)^c, [>2/3](#)^c, [Minimal](#)^c, [No nCET](#)^c

Proportion Necrosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016747>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Proportion Necrosis value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016747>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[1/3-2/3](#)^c, [<1/3](#)^c, [>2/3](#)^c, [Minimal](#)^c, [None](#)^c

Proportion of Edema^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016748>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Proportion of Edema value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016748>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[1/3-2/3](#)^c, [<1/3](#)^c, [>2/3](#)^c, [Minimal](#)^c, [None](#)^c

Prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000021>

A gland in males that surrounds the neck of the bladder and the urethra. It secretes a substance that liquefies coagulated semen. It is situated in the pelvic cavity behind the lower part of the pubic symphysis, above the deep layer of the triangular ligament, and rests upon the rectum. [MeSH]

has super-classes

[ICD03Topography](#)^c, [Prostate and vas deferens structures](#)^c, [Prostatic and/or seminal vesicle structures](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Prostate part](#)^c

Prostate and vas deferens structures^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000251>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Prostate](#)^c

Prostate cancer risk of recurrence not determined or neither low, intermediate nor high^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1023527>

has super-classes

[Diagnostic/Screening Processes or Results](#)^c

Prostate finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007013>

has super-classes

[Finding of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of prostate](#)^c

Prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000039>

has super-classes

[Prostate part](#)^c

Prostate mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000293>

has super-classes

[Abdominal mass](#)^c, [Lesion of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Prostate part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000208>

has super-classes

[Prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Prostate gland](#)^c, [Region of prostate](#)^c

Prostate specific Ag [Mass/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033410>

A quantitative procedure that measures the concentration (mass/volume) of prostate-specific antigen in a serum or plasma specimen. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Chemistry^c](#), [Prostate specific Ag|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c](#), [Prostate specific Ag|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma^c](#), [Prostate specific antigen measurement^c](#)

Prostate specific Ag|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049888>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Prostate specific Ag \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma^c](#)

Prostate specific Ag|Moment in time|Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050248>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Prostate specific Ag \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma^c](#)

Prostate specific antigen measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000227>

The determination of the prostate specific antigen present in a sample. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Enzyme measurement^c](#), [Protein measurement^c](#), [Tumor marker measurement^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Free prostate specific antigen level^c](#), [Free:total PSA ratio^c](#), [Prostate specific Ag \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma^c](#), [Total prostate specific antigen level^c](#)

Prostate specific antigen normal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1030225>

has super-classes

[Enzyme level - finding^c](#), [Measurement finding within reference range^c](#)

Prostatectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000248>

Complete or partial surgical removal of the prostate. Three primary approaches are commonly employed: suprapubic - removal through an incision above the pubis and through the urinary bladder; retropubic - as for suprapubic but without entering the urinary bladder; and transurethral (transurethral resection of prostate). [MeSH] [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Abdomen excision^c](#), [Excision of pelvis^c](#), [Operation on prostate^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Laparoscopic prostatectomy^c](#), [Open prostatectomy^c](#), [Radical prostatectomy^c](#), [Retropubic prostatectomy^c](#), [Subtotal prostatectomy^c](#)

Prostatic and/or seminal vesicle structures^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000086>

has super-classes

[Body region structure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Prostate](#)^c, [Seminal Vesicles](#)^c

Protein level - finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005898>

has super-classes

[Finding of substance level](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Enzyme level - finding](#)^c

Protein measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1009138>

has super-classes

[Measurement of substance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Albumin measurement](#)^c, [Antibody measurement](#)^c, [Carcinoembryonic antigen measurement](#)^c, [Enzyme measurement](#)^c, [Globulin measurement](#)^c, [Glycoproteins measurement](#)^c, [Lactate dehydrogenase measurement](#)^c, [Measurement of liver enzyme](#)^c, [Prostate specific antigen measurement](#)^c, [Urine protein measurement](#)^c, [Urine protein test](#)^c

Proton-density^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016777>

has super-classes

[Modality descriptor](#)^c

Protons^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001182>

has super-classes

[Modality radiation value](#)^c

Provider-specific procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058240>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Interventional radiology](#)^c

pT category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033391>

has super-classes

[T category](#)^c, [TNM classification of malignant tumor after operation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[TNM Path T](#)^c

pT0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000708>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000741>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT1a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000742>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT1b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000743>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000775>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT2a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000810>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT2b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000846>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT2c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000883>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000921>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT3a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000960>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT3b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001000>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001041>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT4a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001577>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pT4b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001585>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

PTEN Gene Mutation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063193>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

pTis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001594>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

pTX^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001604>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer pathological T category allowable value](#)^c

Pulmonary structure including vessels and lymphoid tissue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000014>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung structure](#)^c

PW^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016655>

has super-classes

[Imaging sequence](#)^c, [Tissue Contrast](#)^c

PZ+TZ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000424>

is equivalent to

[Peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c and [Transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Qualifier^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000002>

A term that helps define and render a concept unique. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Common Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Action](#)^c, [Adjectival modifier](#)^c, [Alphanumeric](#)^c, [Annotation/Segmentation](#)^c, [Answer or Value Set](#)^c, [Classification system](#)^c, [Context values](#)^c, [Descriptor](#)^c, [Disease qualifier](#)^c, [Finding value](#)^c, [General clinical stage for disease AND/OR neoplasm](#)^c, [Mechanisms](#)^c, [Missing Value Reason](#)^c, [Modifier mainly for procedure](#)^c, [Number](#)^c, [Others](#)^c, [Physical status qualifier](#)^c, [Pixel](#)^c, [Prefer not to answer](#)^c, [Qualifier for certainty of diagnosis](#)^c, [Ranked categories](#)^c, [Ratio value](#)^c, [Spatial and relational concepts](#)^c, [Special atomic mapping values](#)^c, [TD identified, number unknown](#)^c, [Temporal Qualifier](#)^c, [Unable to determine](#)^c, [Unit of measure](#)^c, [Voxel](#)^c

Qualifier for certainty of diagnosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000038>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Suspicious](#)^c, [problematic](#)^c

Qualitative distribution of primary malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035433>

has super-classes

[Tumor focality](#)^c

Race^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001200>

has super-classes

[National Public Health Classification data](#)^c

has sub-classes

[African](#)^c, [Arab](#)^c, [Asian](#)^c, [Black or African American](#)^c, [White](#)^c

is in range of

[hasRace](#)^{op}

Radiation dose^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016611>

has super-classes

[Imaging procedure descriptor](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Effective dose](#)^c

radiation exposure measure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016635>

has super-classes

[radiography procedure attribute](#)^c

has sub-classes

[KERMA area product](#)^c, [dose area product](#)^c

Radiation Therapy (Procedure)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1012947>

is equivalent to

[Radiotherapy](#)^c

has super-classes

[Therapeutic procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System \(Procedure\)](#)^c

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System \(Procedure\)](#)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1013107>

has super-classes

[Radiation Therapy \(Procedure\)](#)^c, [Radiotherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radiation Therapy, Male Reproductive System, Beam Radiation](#)^c, [Radiation Therapy, Male Reproductive System, Brachytherapy](#)^c

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Beam Radiation @ Prostate](#) Display label: [Beam Radiation of Prostate](#)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033199>

has super-classes

[Radiation Therapy, Male Reproductive System, Beam Radiation](#)^c

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Brachytherapy @ Prostate](#)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1020603>

has super-classes

[Radiation Therapy, Male Reproductive System, Brachytherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Brachytherapy @ Prostate @ High Dose Rate \(HDR\) \(Display label: Brachytherapy of Prostate - High Dose Rate\)](#)^c, [Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Brachytherapy @ Prostate @ Low Dose Rate \(LDR\) \(Display label: Brachytherapy of Prostate - Low Dose Rate\)](#)^c

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Brachytherapy @ Prostate @ High Dose Rate \(HDR\) \(Display label: Brachytherapy of Prostate - High Dose Rate\)](#)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033203>

has super-classes

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Brachytherapy @ Prostate](#)^c

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Brachytherapy @ Prostate @ Low Dose Rate \(LDR\) \(Display label: Brachytherapy of Prostate - Low Dose Rate\)](#)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033208>

has super-classes

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Brachytherapy @ Prostate](#)^c

[Radiation therapy care](#)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035110>

has super-classes

[Care regime](#)^c, [Radiation therapy procedure or service](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radiation therapy course of treatment](#)^c

[Radiation therapy course of treatment](#)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035111>

has super-classes

[Radiation therapy care](#)^c

Radiation therapy procedure or service^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051000>

has super-classes

[Radiotherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Combined chemotherapy and radiation therapy](#)^c, [Radiation therapy care](#)^c

Radiation Therapy, Male Reproductive System, Beam Radiation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1020705>

has super-classes

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System \(Procedure\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Beam Radiation @ Prostate Display_label: Beam Radiation of Prostate](#)^c

Radiation Therapy, Male Reproductive System, Brachytherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1013268>

has super-classes

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System \(Procedure\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radiation Therapy @ Male Reproductive System @ Brachytherapy @ Prostate](#)^c

Radical excision^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056820>

has super-classes

[Excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radical mastectomy](#)^c

Radical mastectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004693>

has super-classes

[Complete excision](#)^c, [Excision of breast](#)^c, [Excision of breast tissue](#)^c, [Radical excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Modified radical mastectomy](#)^c

Radical Perineal prostatectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1030358>

has super-classes

[Perineal prostatectomy](#)^c, [Removal of entire genital organ](#)^c

Radical prostatectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016442>

has super-classes

[Prostatectomy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Robot assisted laparoscopic radical prostatectomy](#)^c

Radical Retropubic prostatectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1030492>

has super-classes

[Removal of entire genital organ](#)^c, [Retropubic prostatectomy](#)^c

Radiochemotherapy via intravenous route^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060832>

has super-classes

[Combined chemotherapy and radiation therapy](#)^c

Radiofluoroscopy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000081>

Production of an image when x-rays strike a fluorescent screen. [MeSH]

has super-classes

[Fluoroscopy](#)^c

Radiographic imaging - action^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000036>

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Computed tomography](#)^c, [Fluoroscopy](#)^c, [Plain X-ray imaging - action](#)^c, [Tomographic imaging - action](#)^c

Radiographic imaging procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016143>

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c, [Tumor Size Method](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Computed tomography](#)^c, [Mammography](#)^c, [Plain radiography](#)^c, [Radiologic guidance procedure](#)^c, [Tomographic imaging](#)^c

Radiographic lesion margin characteristics^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016314>

has super-classes

[Radiologic finding](#)^c

Radiographic lesion shape finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016297>

has super-classes

[Radiologic finding](#)^c

Radiographic procedure of chest^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016136>

has super-classes

[Chest imaging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[CT of chest](#)^c, [Mammography](#)^c

radiography procedure attribute^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016634>

has super-classes

[cross-sectional procedure attribute](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[radiation exposure measure](#) ^c

Radioisotope study of musculoskeletal system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016746>

has super-classes

[Nuclear medicine imaging procedure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Whole body bone imaging](#) ^c

Radiologic finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034739>

has super-classes

[Imaging finding](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Enhancing tumor](#) ^c, [Finding of change compared to previous radiologic examination](#) ^c, [Finding of change compared to previous radiologic examination finding](#) ^c, [Mammography finding](#) ^c, [Mammography reference location](#) ^c, [Non-enhancing tumor](#) ^c, [Radiographic lesion margin characteristics](#) ^c, [Radiographic lesion shape finding](#) ^c, [Radiology result normal](#) ^c

Radiologic guidance procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016753>

has super-classes

[Radiographic imaging procedure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[X-ray guided biopsy](#) ^c

Radiologist^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001104>

has super-classes

[Annotator Specialty](#) ^c, [Specialized physician](#) ^c

Radiology result normal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016269>

has super-classes

[Imaging result normal](#) ^c, [Radiologic finding](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Mammography normal](#) ^c

Radionuclide imaging - action^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000031>

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Positron emission tomography](#) ^c, [Single photon emission computed tomography](#) ^c

Radionuclide therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058780>

has super-classes

[Radiotherapy](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Brachytherapy](#)^c

Radiotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1014933>

has super-classes

[Therapeutic procedure](#)^c, [Treatment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Boost radiation therapy](#)^c, [Combined chemotherapy and radiation therapy](#)^c, [Conformal radiotherapy](#)^c, [Conformal radiotherapy](#)^c, [External beam radiation therapy procedure](#)^c, [Hypofractionated radiation therapy](#)^c, [Intensity modulated radiation therapy](#)^c, [Radiation Therapy_@_Male Reproductive System \(Procedure\)](#)^c, [Radiation therapy procedure or service](#)^c, [Radionuclide therapy](#)^c, [Radiotherapy - intraoperative control](#)^c, [Radiotherapy to thorax](#)^c

is in domain of

[FractionsDelivered](#)^{dp}, [NumberOfSessions](#)^{dp}

is in range of

[hasRadiationModality](#)^{op}, [hasRadiationTechnique](#)^{op}

Radiotherapy - intraoperative control^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005271>

has super-classes

[Radiotherapy](#)^c

Radiotherapy to breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1014935>

has super-classes

[Radiotherapy to thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hypofractionated whole breast radiation therapy](#)^c

Radiotherapy to thorax^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1014934>

has super-classes

[Procedure on thorax](#)^c, [Radiotherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radiotherapy to breast](#)^c

Ranked categories^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001333>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Degrees of severity](#)^c, [Grades](#)^c

Ratio value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001389>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[1/3-2/3](#)^c, [<1/3](#)^c, [>2/3](#)^c, [T1<<FLAIR](#)^c, [T1<FLAIR](#)^c, [T1~FLAIR](#)^c

Re-excision of breast for clearance of tumor margins^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060337>

has super-classes

[Excision of breast](#)^c, [Excision of breast tissue](#)^c, [Reexcision](#)^c

Reason for no specific anti-cancer treatment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1020808>

has super-classes

[Reasons for treatment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[No anti-cancer treatment - watchful waiting](#)^c

Reasons for treatment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000380>

has super-classes

[Administrative statuses](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Reason for no specific anti-cancer treatment](#)^c

RECIST finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037303>

has super-classes

[Staging and scales](#)^c

has sub-classes

[RECIST: complete response](#)^c, [RECIST: partial response](#)^c, [RECIST: progressive disease](#)^c, [RECIST: stable disease](#)^c

is in range of

[hasTreatmentResponse](#)^{op}

RECIST: complete response^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037307>

has super-classes

[RECIST finding](#)^c

RECIST: partial response^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037306>

has super-classes

[RECIST finding](#)^c

RECIST: progressive disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037305>

has super-classes

[RECIST finding](#)^c

RECIST: stable disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037304>

has super-classes

[RECIST finding](#)^c

Rectal examination^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1020912>

has super-classes

[Examination of abdomen](#)^c, [Procedure on rectum](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Digital examination of rectum](#)^c

Rectal mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051689>

has super-classes

[Abdominal mass](#)^c, [Mass of digestive structure](#)^c, [Pelvic mass](#)^c, [Rectum finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of rectum](#)^c

Rectal polypectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060376>

has super-classes

[Excision of lesion of rectum](#)^c, [Excision of mass of pelvic region](#)^c, [Excision of polyp of large intestine](#)^c

Rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063724>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Rectum, NOS](#)^c

Rectum finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051349>

has super-classes

[Finding of large intestine](#)^c, [Finding of pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Rectal mass](#)^c

Rectum structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000130>

The distal segment of the large intestine, between the sigmoid colon and the anal canal. [MeSH]

is equivalent to

[Rectum, NOS](#)^c

has super-classes

[Anorectal structure](#)^c, [Lower bowel structures](#)^c, [Structure of cecum and/or colon and/or rectum](#)^c

Rectum, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063776>

has super-classes

[Rectum](#)^c

Recurrence^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001174>

has super-classes

[Condition clinical status value](#)^c

Recurrent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000158>

has super-classes

[Disease Clinical Qualifier](#)^c

Recurrent tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1027442>

has super-classes

[Tumor finding](#)^c

Red blood cell count below reference range^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051860>

has super-classes

[Cytopenia](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Iron deficiency anemia](#)^c

Reexcision^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056836>

has super-classes

[Excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Re-excision of breast for clearance of tumor margins](#)^c

Regimes and therapies^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034280>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Care regime](#)^c, [Monitoring procedure](#)^c

Region of cerebral cortex^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000383>

has super-classes

[Cerebral cortex part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Motor cortex](#)^c, [Structure of cortex of frontal lobe](#)^c, [Structure of cortex of occipital lobe](#)^c, [Structure of cortex of parietal lobe](#)^c, [Structure of cortex of temporal lobe](#)^c

Region of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063281>

has super-classes

[Colon part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left colon structure](#)^c, [Right colon structure](#)^c, [Sigmoid colon structure](#)^c, [Transverse colon structure](#)^c

Region of frontal cortex^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000385>

has super-classes

[Structure of cortex of frontal lobe](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Motor area](#)^c, [Structure of Broca's area](#)^c, [Structure of frontal pole](#)^c

Region of large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063302>

has super-classes

[Large intestine part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of cecum and/or colon and/or rectum](#)^c

Region of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000160>

has super-classes

[Prostate part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Base of prostate](#)^c, [Glandular zone of prostate](#)^c, [Middle region of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of apex of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of left half of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of right half of prostate](#)^c

Region of temporal cortex^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000439>

has super-classes

[Structure of cortex of temporal lobe](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Wernicke's area](#)^c

Regional lymph node metastasis present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059607>

has super-classes

[Tumor finding](#)^c

Regional lymph node structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000072>

has super-classes

[Structure of lymph node](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lymph node structure of limb](#)^c

Regional lymph nodes examined [#] Specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1045896>

has super-classes

[Measurement](#)^c

Regular frequency^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001342>

has super-classes

[Frequencies](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Frequency interval](#)^c

Relapse^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001337>

has super-classes

[Condition clinical status value](#) ^c, [Disease phases](#) ^c

Relapse^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000005>

has super-classes

[Episode](#) ^c

Relative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001040>

has super-classes

[Person in the family](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Blood relative](#) ^c, [Immediate family member](#) ^c

Relative sites^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001090>

has super-classes

[Spatial and relational concepts](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Side](#) ^c, [Unilateral](#) ^c

Remission^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001340>

has super-classes

[Condition clinical status value](#) ^c, [Disease phases](#) ^c

Remission^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000006>

has super-classes

[Episode](#) ^c

Removal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058186>

has super-classes

[Procedure Category](#) ^c, [Procedure by method](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy](#) ^c, [Surgical removal](#) ^c

Removal - action^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001057>

has super-classes

[Action](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Sampling - action \(qualifier value\)](#) ^c

Removal of entire genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005177>

has super-classes

[Complete excision](#)^c, [Procedure on genitourinary system](#)^c, [Trunk excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radical Perineal prostatectomy](#)^c, [Radical Retropubic prostatectomy](#)^c

Reoperation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002564>

has super-classes

[Nature of procedure values](#)^c

Resection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004591>

has super-classes

[Surgical removal](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Extent of Resection](#)^c

Resection Margin Involved by tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063677>

has super-classes

[Surgical margin finding](#)^c

Resection Margin Uninvolved by tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063679>

has super-classes

[Surgical margin finding](#)^c

Resection of polyp^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058911>

has super-classes

[Excision of mass](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of polyp of large intestine](#)^c

Resection of rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1057561>

has super-classes

[Excision of pelvis](#)^c, [Operation on rectum](#)^c, [Partial excision of large intestine](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdominoperineal resection](#)^c, [Anterior resection of rectum](#)^c, [Excision of lesion of rectum](#)^c, [Excision of rectum by transanal approach](#)^c,
[Proctectomy and anastomosis of colon to anus](#)^c

Residual cancer burden class^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035685>

Residual cancer burden classes that use pre-defined cut-points representing progressively greater extents of residual cancer and indicating a greater risk of recurrence. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Interpretation of findings](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Residual Cancer Burden Class 0](#)^c, [Residual Cancer Burden Class 1](#)^c, [Residual Cancer Burden Class 2](#)^c, [Residual Cancer Burden Class 3](#)^c

Residual Cancer Burden Class 0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035689>

No traces of residual disease; lowest chance of disease recurrence. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Residual cancer burden class](#)^c

Residual Cancer Burden Class 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035688>

Minimal residual disease; low chance of disease recurrence. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Residual cancer burden class](#)^c

Residual Cancer Burden Class 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035687>

Moderate residual disease; moderate chance of disease recurrence. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Residual cancer burden class](#)^c

Residual Cancer Burden Class 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035686>

Extensive residual disease; highest chance of disease recurrence. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Residual cancer burden class](#)^c

Resolved^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001175>

has super-classes

[Adjectival modifier](#)^c, [Condition clinical status value](#)^c

ResourceType: Condition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000028>

has super-classes

[FHIR](#)^c

ResourceType: Diagnostic Report^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000032>

has super-classes

[FHIR](#)^c

ResourceType: Measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000029>

has super-classes

[FHIR](#)^c

ResourceType: Medication^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000024>

has super-classes

[EHIR](#)^c

ResourceType: Medication Administration^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000023>

has super-classes

[EHIR](#)^c

ResourceType: Observation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000025>

has super-classes

[EHIR](#)^c

ResourceType: Patient^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000026>

has super-classes

[EHIR](#)^c

ResourceType: Procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COR1000022>

has super-classes

[EHIR](#)^c

Respiratory finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051874>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Finding of respiration](#)^c, [Respiratory function finding](#)^c

Respiratory function finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051878>

has super-classes

[Respiratory finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cough](#)^c

Respiratory observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050832>

has super-classes

[Clinical history/examination observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lower respiratory tract observable](#)^c

Response to cancer treatment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049529>

has super-classes

[Response to treatment](#)^c

Response to treatment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049527>

has super-classes

[Situation with explicit context](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Response to cancer treatment](#)^c

Restricted^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002284>

has super-classes

[Behavior descriptors](#)^c, [Diffusion Characteristics value](#)^c

Restricted diffusion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005450>

has super-classes

[Diffusion Characteristics](#)^c, [Diffusion weighted imaging](#)^c

RET gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051902>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

Retention^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051007>

has super-classes

[Mechanical abnormality](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gas retention](#)^c

Retraction of nipple^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037121>

[BI-RADS] Mammo: the nipple is pulled in (should not be confused with nipple inversion, which is often bilateral). MR: Nipple is pulled in; do not confuse with nipple inversion. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Nipple finding](#)^c

Retraction of skin of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037130>

has super-classes

[Breast finding](#)^c, [Skin finding](#)^c

Retroperitoneal compartment structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000045>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adrenal gland](#)^c, [Kidney structure](#)^c, [Pancreas](#)^c

Retropubic prostatectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016487>

has super-classes

[Operations by approach](#)^c, [Prostatectomy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Radical Retropubic prostatectomy](#)^c

Ribociclib^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036300>

An orally available cyclin-dependent kinase (CDK) inhibitor targets at cyclin D1/CDK4 and cyclin D3/CDK6 cell cycle pathway, with potential antineoplastic activity. Ribociclib specifically inhibits CDK4 and 6, thereby inhibiting retinoblastoma (Rb) protein phosphorylation. Inhibition of Rb phosphorylation prevents CDK-mediated G1-S phase transition, thereby arresting the cell cycle in the G1 phase, suppressing DNA synthesis and inhibiting cancer cell growth. Overexpression of CDK4/6, as seen in certain types of cancer, causes cell cycle deregulation. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Right^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016682>

has super-classes

[Laterality](#)^c, [Side](#)^c, [Topographical modifier](#)^c

Right anterior apical part of transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000018>

has super-classes

[Right apical transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right anterior apical peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000247>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the anterior portion of the apical division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Right apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right anterior basal peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000027>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the anterior portion of the basal division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Right basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right anterior basal transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000059>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the anterior portion of the basal division of the transition zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Right basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right anterior middle peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000099>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the anterior portion of the middle division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Right lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right anterior middle transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000069>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the anterior portion of the middle division of the transition zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Right middle transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of anterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000058>

The portion of the fibromuscular stroma of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the apical division of the anterior lobe. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of right half of prostate](#)^c

Right apical peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000189>

has super-classes

[Apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of right half of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Right anterior apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right posterolateral apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right posteromedial apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c

Right apical transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000110>

has super-classes

[Apical transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of right half of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Right anterior apical part of transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right posterior apical part of transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Right basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000139>

The portion of the fibromuscular stroma of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the basal division of the anterior lobe. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of right half of prostate](#)^c

Right basal peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000177>

has super-classes

[Basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of right half of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Right anterior basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right posterolateral basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c

Right basal transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000129>

has super-classes

[Basal transition zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Structure of right half of prostate](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Right anterior basal transition zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Right posterior basal transition zone of prostate](#) ^c

Right breast structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000223>

has super-classes

[Breast structure](#) ^c, [Right thorax structure](#) ^c

Right colectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060299>

has super-classes

[Partial resection of colon](#) ^c

Right colon structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063357>

has super-classes

[Region of colon](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Ascending colon structure](#) ^c

Right lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000218>

has super-classes

[Middle peripheral zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Structure of right half of prostate](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Right anterior middle peripheral zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Right posterolateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Right posteromedial middle peripheral zone of prostate](#) ^c

Right middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000046>

The portion of the fibromuscular stroma of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the middle division of the anterior lobe. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#) ^c, [Structure of right half of prostate](#) ^c

Right middle transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000049>

has super-classes

[Middle transition zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Structure of right half of prostate](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Right anterior middle transition zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Right posterior middle transition zone of prostate](#) ^c

Right posterior apical part of transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000186>

has super-classes

[Right apical transition zone of prostate](#) ^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#) ^c

Right posterior basal transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000196>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the posterior portion of the basal division of the transition zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Right basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right posterior middle transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000079>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the posterior portion of the middle division of the transition zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Right middle transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right posterolateral apical peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000047>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the posterolateral portion of the apical division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Right apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right posterolateral basal peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000080>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the posterolateral portion of the basal division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Right basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right posterolateral middle peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000128>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the posterolateral portion of the middle division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Right lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right posteromedial apical peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000109>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the posteromedial portion of the apical division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Right apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right posteromedial middle peripheral zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000015>

The region of the prostate that is located on the anatomical right side of the posteromedial portion of the middle division of the peripheral zone. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Right lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Structure of posterior section of prostate](#)^c

Right thorax structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000032>

has super-classes

[Structure of half of thorax lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Right breast structure](#)^c

Risk Assessment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051859>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Assessment](#)^c, [Intergroup Rhabdomyosarcoma Study Group Clinical Staging and Grouping System](#)^c, [Leukemia Finding](#)^c

Risk assessment value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001198>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[High Risk Acute Leukemia](#)^c, [High risk](#)^c, [Intermediate Risk](#)^c, [Low risk](#)^c, [Standard Risk Acute Leukemia](#)^c, [Very high](#)^c, [Very low](#)^c

is in range of

[hasRiskAssessmentValue](#)^{op}

Risky alcohol consumption^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001143>

has super-classes

[Alcohol use pattern value](#)^c

Robot assisted laparoscopic radical prostatectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1030763>

has super-classes

[Laparoscopic procedure](#)^c, [Radical prostatectomy](#)^c, [Robotic assisted surgery](#)^c

Robotic assisted surgery^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021017>

has super-classes

[Endoscopic operation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Robot assisted laparoscopic radical prostatectomy](#)^c

Round^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1010778>

BI-RADS 5: Spherical, ball-shaped, circular, or globular. PI-RADS 2: The shape of a circle or sphere. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Morphologic descriptor](#)^c

Round mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016514>

[BI-RADS] Mammo: a mass that is spherical, ball-shaped, circular, or globular in shape MRI: Spherical, ball-shaped, circular, or globular US: A mass that is spherical, ball-shaped, circular or globular. A round mass has an anteroposterior diameter equal to its transverse diameter. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Mass](#)^c

Rounded^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1010779>

[LIRADS] Having a curved boundary. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Morphologic descriptor](#)^c

Sacituzumab govitecan^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035940>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Sacrum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000258>

The triangular bone, made up of 5 fused bones of the spine, located in the lower area of the spine between the fifth lumbar vertebra and the coccyx. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Lumbosacral region of spine structure](#)^c, [Musculoskeletal structure of sacral spine](#)^c, [Spine](#)^c, [Structure of posterior arch of pelvic ring](#)^c

Sampling - action (qualifier value)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001269>

has super-classes

[Removal - action](#)^c

Sampling of tissue specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035078>

has super-classes

[Procedure on tissue specimen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gross examination and sampling of tissue specimen](#)^c

Sarcoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1041458>

has super-classes

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Angiosarcoma](#)^c, [Gliosarcoma](#)^c, [Sarcoma of liver](#)^c

Sarcoma (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049239>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Soft tissue tumor AND/OR sarcoma](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Angiosarcoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Myxofibrosarcoma](#)^c

Sarcoma of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036772>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of liver](#)^c, [Sarcoma](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Angiosarcoma of liver](#)^c

Satellites^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016710>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Satellites value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016710>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Absent](#)^c, [Present](#)^c

Scalding pain on urination^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000352>

has super-classes

[Dysuria](#)^c

Scalp and/or neck structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000066>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neck](#)^c

Scattered fibroglandular tissue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016680>

has super-classes

[Tissue composition](#)^c

Scintigraphy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000079>

has super-classes

[Nuclear medicine imaging](#)^c

Sclerosing cholangitis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039008>

has super-classes

[Cholangitis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Primary sclerosing cholangitis](#)^c

Screening^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002624>

has super-classes

[National Public Health Classification data](#)^c, [Population](#)^c

Screening for cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016178>

has super-classes

[Screening for neoplasm^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Screening for malignant neoplasm of breast^c](#)

Screening for disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016161>

has super-classes

[Screening procedure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Screening for neoplasm^c](#)

Screening for malignant neoplasm of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016188>

has super-classes

[Screening for cancer^c](#)

has sub-classes

[MRI of breast for screening for malignant neoplasm^c](#), [Magnetic resonance imaging of breast for screening for malignant neoplasm procedure^c](#)

Screening for neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016169>

has super-classes

[Screening for disorder^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Screening for cancer^c](#)

Screening procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016154>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module^c](#)

has sub-classes

[MRI of breast for screening^c](#), [Screening for disorder^c](#)

Second degree^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001381>

has super-classes

[Degrees of severity^c](#)

Second degree blood relative^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001050>

has super-classes

[Blood relative^c](#)

Second line treatment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060596>

has super-classes

[Procedure by intent^c](#)

Secondary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000159>

Derived as a result of a primary condition; not direct or immediate; of second rank or importance or value. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Cancer Condition Type](#)^c, [Disease Clinical Qualifier](#)^c

Secondary Cancer Condition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007989>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplastic disease](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Metastatic malignant neoplasm](#)^c

is in range of

[hasSecondaryCancerCondition](#)^{op}

is disjoint with

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^c

Secondary Gleason pattern^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049687>

has super-classes

[Gleason pattern](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 1](#)^c, [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 2](#)^c, [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 3](#)^c, [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 4](#)^c, [Gleason Secondary Pattern Grade 5](#)^c

Secondary Gleason Pattern 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031205>

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 1 tumor](#)^c

Secondary Gleason Pattern 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031213>

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 2 tumor](#)^c

Secondary Gleason Pattern 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031180>

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 3 tumor](#)^c

Secondary Gleason Pattern 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031255>

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c, [Grade 4 tumor](#)^c

Secondary Gleason Pattern 5^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031183>

has super-classes

[Gleason finding](#)^c

Secondary malignant neoplasm of axilla^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037738>

has super-classes

[Metastatic malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Secondary malignant neoplasm of axillary lymph nodes](#)^c

Secondary malignant neoplasm of axillary lymph nodes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037792>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm of axillary lymph nodes](#)^c, [Secondary malignant neoplasm of axilla](#)^c

Secondary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000199>

has super-classes

[Secondary malignant neoplasm of trunk](#)^c, [Secondary malignant neoplasm of viscera](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Secondary malignant neoplasm of liver](#)^c

Secondary malignant neoplasm of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000192>

has super-classes

[Metastasis to digestive organs](#)^c, [Secondary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c

Secondary malignant neoplasm of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039628>

has super-classes

[Metastatic malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Secondary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c

Secondary malignant neoplasm of viscera^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1041663>

has super-classes

[Metastatic malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Secondary malignant neoplasm of intra-abdominal organs](#)^c

SEG^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000075>

An image processing device, process or method that performs segmentation. [DCM]

has super-classes

[Other modality \(DICOM\)](#)^c

Segmentation Method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001204>

has super-classes

[Annotation/Segmentation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Automatic](#)^c, [Manual](#)^c, [Semiautomatic](#)^c

is in range of

[hasAlgorithmType](#)^{op}, [hasSegmentationMethod](#)^{op}

Semiautomatic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000005>

Values for segmentation method (ProCancer-I, Prostate gland segmentation UC)

Of or related to a process performed using a combination of manual and automatic means. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Modifier mainly for procedure](#)^c, [Segmentation Method](#)^c

Seminal vesicle invasion by tumor present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049706>

has super-classes

[Pathology examination findings present](#)^c, [Tumor invasion finding](#)^c

Seminal Vesicles^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000191>

A saclike, glandular diverticulum on each ductus deferens in male vertebrates. It is united with the excretory duct and serves for temporary storage of semen. (From McGraw-Hill Dictionary of Scientific and Technical Terms, 4th ed) [MeSH] PI-RADS: One of the two paired glands in the male genitourinary system, posterior to the bladder and superior to the prostate gland, that produces fructose-rich seminal fluid which is a component of semen. These glands join the ipsilateral ductus (vas) deferens to form the ejaculatory duct at the base of the prostate. [RADLEX]

has super-classes

[Prostatic and/or seminal vesicle structures](#)^c

Sentinel lymph node biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001718>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of lymph node](#)^c

Serum testosterone measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1027552>

has super-classes

[Measurement of level of drug in blood](#)^c, [Measurement of level of substance in blood](#)^c, [Testosterone measurement](#)^c

Severe^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001379>

has super-classes

[Severities](#)^c

Severe systemic disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000032>

has super-classes

[Physical status qualifier](#)^c

Severe systemic disease that is a threat to life^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000031>

has super-classes

[Physical status qualifier](#)^c

Severities^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001377>

has super-classes

[Grades](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Marked](#)^c, [Mild](#)^c, [Severe](#)^c

Sex assigned at birth^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001396>

has super-classes

[Common Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Female](#)^c, [Male](#)^c

is in range of

[hasBirthSex](#)^{op}

Sexual function^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1043810>

has super-classes

[Function](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Female genital tract functions](#)^c

Sexual function painful^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1018939>

has super-classes

[Finding of sexual function](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Painful ejaculation](#)^c

Shimadzu^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000054>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Shoulder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000042>

The body part defined by the shoulder joint and its surrounding structures

has super-classes

[Structure of joint region](#)^c, [Structure of shoulder and/or upper arm](#)^c, [Structure of shoulder girdle region](#)^c

Sibling^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001031>

has super-classes

[Immediate family member](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brother](#)^c, [Sister](#)^c

Side^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001091>

has super-classes

[Relative sites](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left](#)^c, [Right](#)^c

Side of Lesion Center^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016740>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Siemens^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000044>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Sigmoid colectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060281>

has super-classes

[Excision of pelvis](#)^c, [Operation on sigmoid](#)^c, [Partial resection of colon](#)^c

Sigmoid colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063757>

has super-classes

[Colon](#)^c

Sigmoid colon structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063627>

is equivalent to

[Sigmoid colon](#)^c

has super-classes

[Region of colon](#)^c

Signet ring cell carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063579>

has super-classes

[Cystic, mucinous and serous neoplasms](#)^c

Signet ring cell carcinoma of ascending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061085>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of ascending colon](#)^c

Signet ring cell carcinoma of cecum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060968>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of cecum](#)^c

Signet ring cell carcinoma of colon, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062428>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of colon](#)^c

Signet ring cell carcinoma of descending colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061822>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of descending colon](#)^c

Signet ring cell carcinoma of hepatic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061238>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of hepatic flexure of colon](#)^c

Signet ring cell carcinoma of rectum, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062785>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of rectum](#)^c

Signet ring cell carcinoma of sigmoid colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1062107>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of sigmoid colon](#)^c

Signet ring cell carcinoma of splenic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059137>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of splenic flexure of colon](#)^c

Signet ring cell carcinoma of transverse colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1061427>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of transverse colon](#)^c

Similar ADC value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005445>

has super-classes

[ADC value](#)^c

Simple mastectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060362>

has super-classes

[Complete excision](#)^c, [Excision of breast](#)^c, [Excision of breast tissue](#)^c

Single photon emission computed tomography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000061>

has super-classes

[Radionuclide imaging - action](#)^c, [Single photon imaging](#)^c

Single photon emission computed tomography with computed tomography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004158>

has super-classes

[Computed tomography](#)^c

Single photon imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000072>

has super-classes

[Nuclear medicine imaging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Planar nuclear medicine imaging](#)^c, [Single photon emission computed tomography](#)^c

Sister^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001030>

has super-classes

[Sibling](#)^c

Situation with explicit context^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1013430>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Condition clinical status](#)^c, [Family history with explicit context](#)^c, [Finding with explicit context](#)^c, [History of metastatic cancer](#)^c, [Procedure with explicit context](#)^c, [Response to treatment](#)^c

Size additional dimension in Tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036581>

has super-classes

[Pathology protocols - general](#)^c

is in range of

[has other dimension value](#)^{op}

Size.maximum dimension in Tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036580>

has super-classes

[Pathology protocols - general](#)^c

is in range of

[has maximum dimension value](#)^{op}

Skeletal system structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000404>

has super-classes

[Structure of musculoskeletal system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bone structure](#)^c

Skin AND/OR mucosa finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1054936>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Skin finding](#)^c

Skin finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055010>

has super-classes

[Skin AND/OR mucosa finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of skin](#)^c, [Finding of color of skin](#)^c, [Finding of thickness of skin](#)^c, [Retraction of skin of breast](#)^c

Skin observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047970>

has super-classes

[Clinical history/examination observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Thickness of skin](#)^c

Skin retraction^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059060>

BI-RADS Mammo/MR: The skin is pulled in abnormally. US: Skin surface is concave or ill defined and appears pulled in. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Disorder of skin](#)^c

Skin structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063344>

has super-classes

[Structure of skin and/or surface epithelium](#)^c

Skin thickening of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037131>

has super-classes

[Breast finding](#)^c, [Thickening of skin](#)^c

Skull^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000135>

The bones that form the head, made up of the bones of the braincase and face. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Bone and/or joint structure of cranium](#)^c, [Bone structure of head](#)^c

Skull foramen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000215>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Optic canal](#)^c

Slice Thickness^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016306>

has super-classes

[MR procedure attribute](#)^c

Slide Microscopy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004456>

has super-classes

[Microscopy](#)^c

Small cell carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1007608>

has super-classes

[Malignant epithelial neoplasm](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Small cell carcinoma of prostate](#)^c

Small cell carcinoma (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049520>

has super-classes

[Malignant epithelial neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c, [Malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Small cell carcinoma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016533>

has super-classes

[Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c, [Small cell carcinoma](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Small cell carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland](#)^c

Small cell carcinoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049678>

has super-classes

[Epithelial neoplasms, NOS](#)^c

Small cell carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1024075>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Small cell carcinoma of prostate](#)^c

Small intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000007>

Organ with organ cavity which is continuous proximally with the stomach and distally with the large intestine. [FMA]

has super-classes

[Intestinal structure](#)^c

Smoker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059166>

has super-classes

[Tobacco smoking behavior - finding](#)^c, [Tobacco user](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cigarette smoker](#)^c

Smoking - history^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004581>

has super-classes

[Measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Smoking-related terms](#)^c

Smoking status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004528>

This field summarises the current/past smoking status of the participant

has super-classes

[Tobacco use and exposure](#)^c

Smoking status value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001131>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Current](#)^c, [Never](#)^c, [Prefer not to answer](#)^c, [Previous](#)^c

Smoking-related terms^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004584>

has super-classes

[Smoking - history](#)^c

has sub-classes

[On the number of days you reported you smoked cigarettes during the past 30 days, how many cigarettes did you smoke per day, on average \[PhenX\]](#)^c

Social / personal history observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1040049>

has super-classes

[Observable entity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Demographic history detail](#)^c

Social History^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000025>

has super-classes

[Observation Category](#)^c

Sodium [Moles/volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033524>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#)^c, [Sodium|Substance Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Sodium|Substance Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049903>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Sodium \[Moles/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Soft tissue^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP100040608>

has super-classes

[Body tissue structure](#)^c

Soft tissue tumor AND/OR sarcoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049131>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Sarcoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Solid^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002044>

has super-classes

[Formations](#)^c, [Thickness of enhancing margin value](#)^c

Solid papillary carcinoma in situ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049676>

has super-classes

[Encapsulated papillary carcinoma](#)^c

Son^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001039>

has super-classes

[Child](#)^c

Spatial and relational concepts^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001083>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Relative sites](#)^c

Spatial enhancement pattern^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005499>

has super-classes

[Enhancement pattern](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Asymmetric enhancement](#)^c, [Symmetric enhancement](#)^c

Special atomic mapping values^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002362>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Special disorder atoms](#)^c

Special disorder atoms^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002377>

has super-classes

[Special atomic mapping values](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Distributions](#)^c, [Extensiveness](#)^c, [Pathogeneses](#)^c

Specialized physician^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001105>

has super-classes

[Physician](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Medical Oncologist](#)^c, [Physician who performed a surgical procedure was not a surgeon \(i.e., radiation oncologist, diagnostic radiologist, or general practitioner\)](#)^c, [Radiologist](#)^c

Specific Module^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000001>

This module specifies classes required for the semantic integration at the metadata dataset level

has sub-classes

[Collection method](#)^c, [Correspondence](#)^c, [Dataset Access Condition](#)^c, [Dataset Type](#)^c, [Interoperability level](#)^c

Specified time^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001060>

has super-classes

[Current or specified](#)^c

Specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002057>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Human Specimen](#)^c

Specimen from anus and/or rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055316>

has super-classes

[Specimen from gastrointestinal tract](#)^c, [Specimen from trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Specimen from rectum](#)^c

Specimen from breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002059>

has super-classes

[Specimen from trunk](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Specimen from left breast](#) ^c, [Specimen from right breast](#) ^c

Specimen from colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055556>

has super-classes

[Specimen from large intestine](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Tissue specimen from colon](#) ^c

Specimen from digestive system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055085>

has super-classes

[Human Specimen](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Specimen from gastrointestinal tract](#) ^c

Specimen from gastrointestinal tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055161>

has super-classes

[Specimen from digestive system](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Specimen from anus and/or rectum](#) ^c, [Specimen from lower gastrointestinal tract](#) ^c, [Tissue specimen from gastrointestinal tract](#) ^c

Specimen from genital system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1006555>

has super-classes

[Genitourinary sample](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Male genital sample](#) ^c, [Tissue specimen from genital system](#) ^c

Specimen from large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055395>

has super-classes

[Specimen from lower gastrointestinal tract](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Specimen from colon](#) ^c, [Specimen from rectum](#) ^c, [Tissue specimen from large intestine](#) ^c

Specimen from left breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002051>

has super-classes

[Specimen from breast](#) ^c

Specimen from lower gastrointestinal tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055238>

has super-classes

[Specimen from gastrointestinal tract](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Specimen from large intestine](#) ^c

Specimen from lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059299>

has super-classes

[Lower respiratory tract specimen](#) ^c, [Specimen from trunk](#) ^c

Specimen from prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021123>

has super-classes

[Male genital sample](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Tissue specimen from prostate](#) ^c

Specimen from rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059182>

has super-classes

[Specimen from anus and/or rectum](#) ^c, [Specimen from large intestine](#) ^c

Specimen from respiratory system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055638>

has super-classes

[Human Specimen](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Lower respiratory tract specimen](#) ^c

Specimen from right breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059217>

has super-classes

[Specimen from breast](#) ^c

Specimen from trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002058>

has super-classes

[Human Specimen](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Specimen from anus and/or rectum](#) ^c, [Specimen from breast](#) ^c, [Specimen from lung](#) ^c

SPECT-CT^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004450>

A dual-modality imaging technique that merges data from single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) and computed tomography (CT) to provide structural and functional information. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[combined modalities](#) ^c

Spiculated^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1010776>

the lesion is characterized by lines radiating from the margin of a mass [BI-RADS] [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Morphologic descriptor](#) ^c

Spiculated margin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005420>

PI-RADS: Radiating lines extending from the margin of a mass. BI-RADS Mammo/MRI: Margin is characterized by lines radiating from the mass.

US: Margin is characterized by sharp lines radiating from the mass. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Non-circumscribed margin](#) ^c

Spin echo^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016662>

has super-classes

[MR Echo Type](#) ^c

Spin labeling^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016660>

has super-classes

[MR preparation or modification technique](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Arterial Spin Labeling \(ASL\)](#) ^c

Spinal meninges^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000307>

has super-classes

[Meninges](#) ^c

Spine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000077>

A series of bones, muscles, tendons, and other tissues reaching from the base of the skull to the tailbone. The vertebral column forms the axis of the skeleton and encloses as well as protects the spinal cord and the fluid surrounding the spinal cord. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Axial skeleton structure](#) ^c, [Musculoskeletal structure of spine](#) ^c, [Structure of vertebral column and/or spinal cord](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Cervical spine](#) ^c, [Lumbar spine](#) ^c, [Sacrum](#) ^c, [Thoracic spine](#) ^c

Splenic flexure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063384>

has super-classes

[Structure of left colic flexure](#) ^c

Splenic flexure of colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000262>

is equivalent to

[Structure of left colic flexure](#) ^c

has super-classes

[Colon](#) ^c

Spontaneous^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002414>

has super-classes

[General adjectival modifier](#)^c, [Origins](#)^c

Spouse^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001032>

has super-classes

[Immediate family member](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Husband](#)^c, [Wife](#)^c

Squamous cell carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1008228>

has super-classes

[Malignant epithelial neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenosquamous cell carcinoma](#)^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma of male genital](#)^c

Squamous cell carcinoma (morphologic abnormality)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049223>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Squamous cell neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenosquamous carcinoma](#)^c

Squamous cell carcinoma of male genital^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1008483>

has super-classes

[Malignant tumor of male genital organ](#)^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Squamous cell carcinoma of prostate](#)^c

Squamous cell carcinoma of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016580>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma of male genital](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adenosquamous carcinoma of prostate gland](#)^c

Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049630>

has super-classes

[Squamous cell neoplasms](#)^c

Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS, of lung, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063043>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033298>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Squamous cell neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049208>

has super-classes

[Epithelial neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Squamous cell carcinoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Squamous cell neoplasms^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049540>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Papillary carcinoma, NOS](#)^c, [Squamous cell carcinoma, NOS](#)^c

Stable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002078>

has super-classes

[Change patterns](#)^c, [Condition stability status](#)^c

Stable disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001185>

has super-classes

[Treatment response value](#)^c

Stage 0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000423>

has super-classes

[Cancer staging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 0](#)^c, [FIGO Stage 0](#)^c

Stage 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000422>

has super-classes

[Cancer staging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 1](#)^c, [FIGO Stage 1](#)^c

Stage 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000421>

has super-classes

[Cancer staging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 2](#)^c, [FIGO Stage 2](#)^c

Stage 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000420>

has super-classes

[Cancer staging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 3](#)^c, [FIGO Stage 3](#)^c

Stage 4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000419>

has super-classes

[Cancer staging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[AJCC/UICC 8th Stage 4](#)^c, [FIGO Stage 4](#)^c

Staging and scales^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036343>

has super-classes

[Clinical & Biological Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Assessment scales](#)^c, [Grade Pathological](#)^c, [Histological grading systems](#)^c, [Miller and Payne Classification](#)^c, [RECIST finding](#)^c, [Tumor Regression Grade](#)^c, [Tumor grade](#)^c, [Tumor staging](#)^c

Staining method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035160>

has super-classes

[Laboratory procedure categorized by method](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hematoxylin stain method](#)^c

Standard Risk Acute Leukemia^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002170>

Acute leukemia patients are stratified into the standard risk group when their minimal residual disease levels are lower than 0.05%. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Risk assessment value](#)^c

Standing position^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016602>

has super-classes

[Patient Position](#)^c

Start time^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000122>

has super-classes

[Time patterns](#)^c

Static nuclear imaging acquisition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016773>

has super-classes

[Nuclear imaging acquisition](#)^c

Status of regression of tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035650>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

steatosis of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047356>

has super-classes

[Degenerative disorder](#)^c, [Disease of liver](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease](#)^c

Stereotactic radiation therapy using megavoltage radiation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021230>

has super-classes

[Stereotactic radiotherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hypofractionated stereotactic radiotherapy using megavoltage radiation](#)^c

Stereotactic radiotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005378>

has super-classes

[External beam radiation therapy procedure](#)^c, [Imaging guidance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Stereotactic radiation therapy using megavoltage radiation](#)^c

Steroid measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1009272>

has super-classes

[Measurement of substance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[17-hydroxycorticosteroid measurement](#)^c, [Cholesterol measurement](#)^c, [Testosterone measurement](#)^c

Stimulated Thyroglobulin antibody measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050466>

has super-classes

[Thyroglobulin antibody measurement](#)^c

Stimulated Thyroglobulin measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050572>

has super-classes

[Thyroglobulin measurement](#)^c

STK11 (serine/threonine kinase 11) gene variant^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063199>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

Stomach^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000302>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography](#)^c

Stop time^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000125>

has super-classes

[Time patterns](#)^c

Strength of stream of urine - finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000368>

has super-classes

[Flow of urine - finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Poor stream of urine](#)^c

Structure of abdomen proper^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000073>

has super-classes

[Abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of organ within abdomen proper cavity](#)^c

Structure of abdominopelvic organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000122>

has super-classes

[Body organ structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of abdominopelvic viscus](#)^c

Structure of abdominopelvic viscus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000250>

has super-classes

[Structure of abdominopelvic organ](#)^c, [Structure of subdivision of abdominopelvic compartment](#)^c, [Structure of viscus](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intestinal structure](#)^c, [Structure of organ within abdomen proper cavity](#)^c

Structure of ankle and/or foot^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000074>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Foot](#)^c

Structure of anterior section of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000207>

has super-classes

[Region of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Left anterior apical part of transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left anterior apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left anterior basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left anterior basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left anterior middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left anterior middle transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right anterior apical part of transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right anterior apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right anterior basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right anterior basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right anterior middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right anterior middle transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Structure of apex of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000178>

has super-classes

[Region of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Apical transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Structure of body conduit^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000096>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Optic canal](#)^c

Structure of bone organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063267>

has super-classes

[Body organ structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bone marrow structure](#)^c, [Bone structure](#)^c

Structure of brain meninges^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063279>

has super-classes

[Meninges part](#)^c

Structure of breast and/or endocrine system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000033>

has super-classes

[Body system structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast structure](#)^c

Structure of Broca's area^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000386>

has super-classes

[Eloquent Brain Areas](#)^c, [Region of frontal cortex](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Entire Broca's area](#)^c

Structure of Brodmann areas 17 (striate cortex), 18 (parastriate cortex) and 19 (peristriate cortex) of the occipital lobe^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000415>

has super-classes

[Eloquent Brain Areas](#) ^c, [Occipital lobe](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Area striata structure](#) ^c

Structure of caudate lobe of liver^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000427>

has super-classes

[Couinaud liver segment](#) ^c, [Lobe of liver](#) ^c

Structure of cecum and/or colon and/or rectum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063311>

has super-classes

[Region of large intestine](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Cecum structure](#) ^c, [Colon structure](#) ^c, [Rectum structure](#) ^c

Structure of central nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063274>

has super-classes

[Structure of subdivision of nervous system](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Central nervous system part](#) ^c

Structure of cerebral association fiber^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000406>

has super-classes

[Cerebral hemisphere white matter part](#) ^c

Structure of cerebral cingulum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000407>

is equivalent to

[Structure of cerebral association fiber](#) ^c and ([hasCorrespondence](#) ^{op} some [Domain: Spec Anatomic Site](#) ^c)

has sub-classes

[Entire cerebral cingulum](#) ^c

Structure of cerebral cortex^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000381>

has super-classes

[Cerebral hemisphere structure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Cerebral cortex part](#) ^c

Structure of compartment of abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000153>

has super-classes

[Abdomen](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Intra-abdominal digestive structure](#) ^c, [Structure of subdivision of abdominopelvic compartment](#) ^c

Structure of cortex of frontal lobe^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000384>

has super-classes

[Region of cerebral cortex](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Region of frontal cortex](#)^c

Structure of cortex of occipital lobe^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000390>

has super-classes

[Region of cerebral cortex](#)^c

Structure of cortex of parietal lobe^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000389>

has super-classes

[Region of cerebral cortex](#)^c

Structure of cortex of temporal lobe^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000388>

has super-classes

[Region of cerebral cortex](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Region of temporal cortex](#)^c

Structure of diencephalon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000394>

has super-classes

[Cerebrum](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Diencephalon part](#)^c

Structure of digestive system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063419>

has super-classes

[Body system structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Digestive tract structure](#)^c

Structure of endocrine system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000242>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Endocrine gland structure](#)^c, [Ovary](#)^c, [Pancreas](#)^c

Structure of female genital system in pelvic cavity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000162>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Uterus](#)^c

Structure of female internal genital organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000181>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Uterus](#)^c

Structure of femur^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000019>

has super-classes

[Structure of long bone of lower limb](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bone structure of femur](#)^c

Structure of free lower limb^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000088>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Knee](#)^c

Structure of free upper limb^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000009>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Arm](#)^c

Structure of frontal pole^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000393>

has super-classes

[Region of frontal cortex](#)^c

Structure of genitourinary system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000057>

has super-classes

[Body system structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Urinary tract](#)^c

Structure of great blood vessel (organ)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000259>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Aorta](#)^c

Structure of half of body lateral to midsagittal plane^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000043>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Extremity](#)^c, [Structure of half of trunk lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c, [Structure of left half of body](#)^c

Structure of half of brain lateral to midsagittal plane^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000361>

has super-classes

[Brain region](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of lobe of brain](#)^c, [Thalamus](#)^c

Structure of half of thorax lateral to midsagittal plane^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000076>

has super-classes

[Chest](#)^c, [Structure of half of trunk lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast structure](#)^c, [Left thorax structure](#)^c, [Right thorax structure](#)^c

Structure of half of trunk lateral to midsagittal plane^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000063>

has super-classes

[Structure of half of body lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c, [Trunk structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of half of thorax lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c

Structure of joint region^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000010>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Shoulder](#)^c

Structure of joint region of lower limb^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000034>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Knee](#)^c

Structure of large artery^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000104>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Aorta](#)^c

Structure of large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000179>

has super-classes

[Intestinal structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Large intestine part](#)^c, [Lower bowel structures](#)^c

Structure of lateral half of abdomen lateral to midsagittal plane^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000156>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adrenal gland](#)^c

Structure of left colic flexure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063402>

has super-classes

[Descending colon structure](#)^c, [Transverse colon structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Splenic flexure](#)^c

Structure of left half of body^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000052>

has super-classes

[Structure of half of body lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c

Structure of left half of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000070>

has super-classes

[Region of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Left apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left apical transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Left basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Left middle transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Structure of left ovary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063729>

has super-classes

[Ovary](#)^c

Structure of lesser wing of sphenoid bone^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000195>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Optic canal](#)^c

Structure of lobe of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000362>

has super-classes

[Structure of half of brain lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cerebral lobe structure](#)^c

Structure of lobe of lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000111>

has super-classes

[Lung part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of lower lobe of lung](#)^c, [Structure of middle lobe of lung](#)^c, [Structure of upper lobe of lung](#)^c

Structure of long bone of lower limb^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000029>

has super-classes

[Extremity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of femur](#)^c

Structure of lower lobe of left lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000272>

has super-classes

[Structure of lower lobe of lung](#)^c

Structure of lower lobe of lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000271>

has super-classes

[Structure of lobe of lung](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of lower lobe of left lung](#)^c, [Structure of lower lobe of right lung](#)^c

Structure of lower lobe of right lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000273>

has super-classes

[Structure of lower lobe of lung](#)^c

Structure of lung and/or mediastinum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000013>

has super-classes

[Body system structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Mediastinum](#)^c

Structure of lymph node^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000202>

A bean-shaped organ surrounded by a connective tissue capsule. It is part of the lymphatic system and is found throughout the body. It is composed predominantly of lymphocytes and its main function is immune protection. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Structure of lymphatic system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Regional lymph node structure](#)^c

Structure of lymph node of left axilla^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000414>

has super-classes

[Axillary lymph node structure](#)^c

Structure of lymph node of right axilla^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000413>

has super-classes

[Axillary lymph node structure](#)^c

Structure of lymphatic system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000175>

has super-classes

[Body system structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of lymph node](#)^c

Structure of lymphatic system of axilla^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000119>

has super-classes

[Structure of lymphatic system of upper limb](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Axillary lymph node structure](#)^c

Structure of lymphatic system of upper limb^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000081>

has super-classes

[Upper extremity part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of lymphatic system of axilla](#)^c

Structure of mammary region^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000172>

has super-classes

[Chest](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Breast structure](#)^c

Structure of middle lobe of lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000275>

has super-classes

[Structure of lobe of lung](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of middle lobe of right lung](#)^c

Structure of middle lobe of right lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000277>

has super-classes

[Structure of middle lobe of lung](#)^c

Structure of musculoskeletal system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000403>

has super-classes

[Body system structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Skeletal system structure](#)^c

Structure of musculoskeletal system of cervical spine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000065>

has super-classes

[Body system structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cervical spine](#)^c

Structure of musculoskeletal system of lumbar spine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000124>

has super-classes

[Body system structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lumbar spine](#)^c

Structure of musculoskeletal system of thoracic spine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000095>

has super-classes

[Body system structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Thoracic spine](#)^c

Structure of nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063272>

has super-classes

[Body system structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of subdivision of nervous system](#)^c

Structure of nervous tissue of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000357>

has super-classes

[Brain tissue structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of white matter of brain](#)^c

Structure of orbital region^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000102>

has super-classes

[Eye region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Orbit structure](#)^c

Structure of organ in respiratory system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000203>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung structure](#) ^c

Structure of organ within abdomen proper cavity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000030>

has super-classes

[Cross-sectional abdomen](#) ^c, [Intra-abdominal proper structure](#) ^c, [Organ within abdominopelvic cavity](#) ^c, [Structure of abdomen proper](#) ^c, [Structure of abdominopelvic viscus](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Adrenal gland](#) ^c, [Gallbladder](#) ^c, [Kidney structure](#) ^c, [Liver structure](#) ^c, [Pancreas](#) ^c

Structure of organ within cavity of true pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000222>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Uterus](#) ^c

Structure of pelvic segment of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000062>

This segment relates to the volume of the trunk that is bounded superiorly by and includes: superiorly the boundary of the false pelvis, which is an artificial plane from the symphysis pubis to the superior iliac crests (in front it is incomplete, presenting a wide interval between the anterior borders of the ilia); and inferiorly the perineum and external genitalia. The volume includes the entire transverse thickness of the body over the longitudinal extent between these upper (superior) and lower (inferior) boundaries including the overlying muscles, skin and subcutaneous tissue. The segment includes the volume of the true and false pelvic cavities including the bony pelvis and pelvic wall and the entire perineum and external genitalia. Note, the entire bony pelvis is included within the pelvic segment (but is excluded from the abdomen proper segment of trunk); however the pelvic segment of trunk and the abdomen proper segment of trunk both include the volume of the false pelvis. [SNOMEDCT]

has super-classes

[Abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Anorectal structure](#) ^c, [Pelvis](#) ^c, [Perineal structure](#) ^c

Structure of pelvic viscus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000134>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Uterus](#) ^c

Structure of peripheral auditory system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000174>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Ear](#) ^c

Structure of posterior arch of pelvic ring^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000253>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Sacrum](#) ^c

Structure of posterior section of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000005>

has super-classes

[Region of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Left posterior apical part of transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left posterior basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left posterior middle transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left posterolateral apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left posterolateral basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left posterolateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left posteromedial apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Left posteromedial middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right posterior apical part of transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right posterior basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right posterior middle transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right posterolateral apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right posterolateral basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right posterolateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right posteromedial apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right posteromedial middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c

Structure of pulmopleural compartment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000224>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung structure](#)^c

Structure of right colic flexure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063386>

has super-classes

[Ascending colon structure](#)^c, [Transverse colon structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hepatic flexure](#)^c

Structure of right half of pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000132>

has super-classes

[Pelvis](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of right lateral lobe of prostate](#)^c

Structure of right half of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000028>

has super-classes

[Region of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Right apical anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Right apical peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right apical transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right basal anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Right basal peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right basal transition zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right lateral middle peripheral zone of prostate](#)^c, [Right middle anterior fibromuscular stroma of prostate](#)^c, [Right middle transition zone of prostate](#)^c

Structure of right lateral lobe of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000169>

has super-classes

[Structure of right half of pelvis](#)^c

Structure of right ovary^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063730>

has super-classes

[Ovary](#)^c

Structure of shoulder and/or upper arm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000239>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Arm](#)^c, [Shoulder](#)^c

Structure of shoulder girdle region^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000234>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Shoulder](#)^c

Structure of skin and/or mucous membrane^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063519>

has super-classes

[Body system structure](#)^c

Structure of skin and/or surface epithelium^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063332>

has super-classes

[Body system structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Skin structure](#)^c

Structure of soft tissues of left upper extremity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000411>

has super-classes

[Connective, Subcutaneous and other soft tissues of upper limb and shoulder](#)^c

Structure of soft tissues of right upper extremity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000412>

has super-classes

[Connective, Subcutaneous and other soft tissues of upper limb and shoulder](#)^c

Structure of spheroidal joint^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000201>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Hip joint](#)^c

Structure of subdivision of abdominopelvic compartment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000133>

has super-classes

[Structure of compartment of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of abdominopelvic viscus](#)^c

Structure of subdivision of nervous system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063273>

has super-classes

[Structure of nervous system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of central nervous system](#)^c

Structure of subregion of head^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000418>

has super-classes

[Head part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Frontal brain region](#)^c, [Occipital region](#)^c

Structure of subregion of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000241>

has super-classes

[Trunk structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdominopelvic cross-sectional segment](#)^c, [Abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)^c, [Cross-sectional thorax](#)^c

Structure of surface region of upper back^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000281>

has super-classes

[Structure of upper back](#)^c

Structure of thoracic cavity and/or content^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000213>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Bronchial structure](#)^c, [Mediastinum](#)^c

Structure of thoracic viscus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000232>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Heart](#)^c, [Lung structure](#)^c

Structure of upper back^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000280>

has super-classes

[Thoracic segment of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of surface region of upper back](#)^c

Structure of upper lobe of left lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000269>

has super-classes

[Structure of upper lobe of lung^c](#)

Structure of upper lobe of lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000263>

has super-classes

[Structure of lobe of lung^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Structure of upper lobe of left lung^c](#), [Structure of upper lobe of right lung^c](#)

Structure of upper lobe of right lung^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000268>

has super-classes

[Structure of upper lobe of lung^c](#)

Structure of upper urinary system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000117>

has super-classes

[Body region structure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Kidney structure^c](#)

Structure of urinary organ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000147>

has super-classes

[Body region structure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Bladder^c](#), [Kidney structure^c](#)

Structure of vertebral column and/or spinal cord^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000185>

has super-classes

[Body region structure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Spine^c](#)

Structure of vertebral region of cervical part of back^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000182>

has super-classes

[Body part structure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Cervical spine^c](#)

Structure of vertebral region of lumbar part of back^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000054>

has super-classes

[Body part structure^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Lumbar spine](#)^c

Structure of vertebral region of thoracic part of back^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000137>

has super-classes

[Body part structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Thoracic spine](#)^c

Structure of viscus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000093>

has super-classes

[Body organ structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Organ within abdominopelvic cavity](#)^c, [Structure of abdominopelvic viscus](#)^c

Structure of white matter of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000356>

has super-classes

[Structure of nervous tissue of brain](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cerebellar white matter structure](#)^c, [Cerebral white matter structure](#)^c

Subcutaneous mastectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060349>

has super-classes

[Excision of breast](#)^c, [Excision of breast tissue](#)^c

Subdivision of intra-abdominopelvic structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000180>

has super-classes

[Intra-abdominopelvic structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Intra-abdominal proper structure](#)^c, [Intra-pelvic structure of true pelvis](#)^c

Subject under discussion with suspicious findings^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002628>

has super-classes

[Population](#)^c

Subjects of information^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000185>

has super-classes

[Finding status values](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Population](#)^c

Substance observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055805>

has super-classes

[Observable entity](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Tumour marker levels](#)^c

Substance use behavior^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004529>

has super-classes

[Health-related behavior](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Alcohol drinker status](#)^c, [Alcohol use pattern](#)^c, [Tobacco use and exposure](#)^c

Subtotal prostatectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016194>

Surgical removal of part of the prostate. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Prostatectomy](#)^c

Subtotal Resection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004586>

Surgical removal of a part of a lesion; some portion of the lesion is detectable on post-operative evaluation. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Extent of Resection](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Brain@Subtotal resection of tumor, lesion or mass in brain](#)^c

Subtotal resection of tumor, lesion, or mass of brain|(Less than half of lobe involved with tumor)|Specimen sent to pathology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1004579>

has super-classes

[Surgical resection status](#)^c

Supine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016603>

has super-classes

[Patient Position](#)^c

Supratentorial brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000365>

has super-classes

[Brain region](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Supratentorial brain part](#)^c

Supratentorial brain part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000366>

has super-classes

[Supratentorial brain](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cerebrum](#)^c

Surgery^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001099>

has super-classes

[Mechanisms](#)^c

Surgical action^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052241>

has super-classes

[Action](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Microsurgery - action](#)^c

Surgical circumferential margin finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063682>

has super-classes

[Surgical margin finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Circumferential \(Radial\) Margin Involved by Tumor](#)^c, [Circumferential \(Radial\) Margin Uninvolved by Tumor](#)^c, [Surgical circumferential margin involved by malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Surgical circumferential margin uninvolved by malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Surgical circumferential margin involved by malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063686>

has super-classes

[Surgical circumferential margin finding](#)^c

Surgical circumferential margin uninvolved by malignant neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063697>

has super-classes

[Surgical circumferential margin finding](#)^c

Surgical clip^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000078>

Image annotation label (INCISIVE, Annotation Definitions and guidelines)

A type of surgical staple designed to close wounds and control bleeding from blood vessels. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Clip](#)^c

Surgical margin finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1053055>

has super-classes

[Histopathology finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Resection Margin Involved by tumor](#)^c, [Resection Margin Uninvolved by tumor](#)^c, [Surgical circumferential margin finding](#)^c, [Surgical margin involved by tumor](#)^c, [Surgical margin uninvolved by tumor](#)^c

Surgical margin involved by tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059542>

has super-classes

[Pathology examination findings present](#)^c, [Surgical margin finding](#)^c

Surgical margin uninvolved by tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059574>

has super-classes

[Surgical margin finding](#)^c

Surgical procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004413>

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c, [Procedure Category](#)^c, [Treatment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Destructive procedure](#)^c, [Endoscopic operation](#)^c, [Immune system surgical procedure](#)^c, [Operation on respiratory tract](#)^c, [Operations by approach](#)^c, [Surgical Procedures on the Male Genital System](#)^c, [Surgical removal](#)^c, [Surgical repair](#)^c

is in domain of

[Surgically treats](#)^{op}

is in range of

[hasSurgicalProcedure](#)^{op}

Surgical procedure on thorax^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1058978>

has super-classes

[Procedure on thorax](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Operation on breast](#)^c, [Operation on lung](#)^c, [Thorax excision](#)^c

Surgical Procedures on the Male Genital System^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1014423>

has super-classes

[Surgical procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Surgical Procedures on the Prostate](#)^c

Surgical Procedures on the Prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1014592>

has super-classes

[Surgical Procedures on the Male Genital System](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Laparoscopic Procedures on the Prostate](#)^c

Surgical removal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004505>

has super-classes

[Removal](#)^c, [Surgical procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision](#)^c, [Resection](#)^c

Surgical repair^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056701>

has super-classes

[Surgical procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Construction](#)^c

Surgical Resection^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004589>

has super-classes

[Measurement](#)^c

Surgical resection status^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001191>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gross total resection of lobe of brain \(lobectomy\)](#), [\(Tumor involves more than half of lobe\)](#)^c, [Partial resection of lobe of brain](#), [\(Tumor involves more than half of lobe\)](#)^c, [Subtotal resection of tumor, lesion, or mass of brain](#), [\(Less than half of lobe involved with tumor\)](#), [Specimen sent to pathology](#)^c

Surveillance^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1028586>

has super-classes

[Monitoring procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Active Surveillance](#)^c

Survey^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000020>

has super-classes

[Observation Category](#)^c

Survival time^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049082>

has super-classes

[Clinical history/examination observable](#)^c

Surviving free of recurrence of neoplastic disease^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1048175>

has super-classes

[General body state finding](#)^c

Suspicious^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000068>

Image annotation label (INCISIVE, Annotation Definitions and guidelines)
Of a questionable or potentially dangerous nature. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Qualifier for certainty of diagnosis](#)^c

Swelling of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037125>

has super-classes

[Breast finding](#)^c

Symmetric enhancement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005489>

BI-RADS MRI: enhancement in both breasts [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Spatial enhancement pattern](#)^c

Symmetrical^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1010773>

has super-classes

[Morphologic descriptor](#)^c

Symptom^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000030>

has super-classes

[Observation Category](#)^c

Symptomatic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000130>

has super-classes

[Disease qualifier](#)^c

Symptomatic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002049>

has super-classes

[Behavior descriptors](#)^c

Systematic Prostate Biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001934>

A method of needle biopsy where prostate tissue samples are taken from multiple predetermined locations, without targeting specific areas. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Needle biopsy of prostate](#)^c

Systemic artery of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000031>

has super-classes

[Body region structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Aorta](#)^c

T category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033334>

One criteria of the TNM staging system. T refers to the extent of tumor involvement at the primary site (T, followed by a number indicating size and depth of invasion). [NCIT]

has super-classes

[TNM category](#)^c

has sub-classes

[cT category](#)^c, [pT category](#)^c

T1 weighted^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016652>

has super-classes

[Tissue Contrast](#)^c

T1-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004472>

has super-classes

[Magnetic resonance imaging](#)^c

has sub-classes

[T1-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging with Contrast](#)^c

T1-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging with Contrast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004473>

has super-classes

[T1-Weighted Magnetic Resonance Imaging](#)^c

T1/FLAIR Ratio^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016733>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

T1/FLAIR Ratio value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016733>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[No FLAIR images](#)^c, [T1<<FLAIR](#)^c, [T1<FLAIR](#)^c, [T1~FLAIR](#)^c

T1<<FLAIR^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001395>

has super-classes

[Ratio value](#)^c, [T1/FLAIR Ratio value](#)^c

T1<FLAIR^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001394>

has super-classes

[Ratio value](#)^c, [T1/FLAIR Ratio value](#)^c

T1W-CE^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016656>

has super-classes

[Imaging sequence](#)^c, [Tissue Contrast](#)^c

T1~FLAIR^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001393>

has super-classes

[Ratio value](#)^c, [T1/FLAIR Ratio value](#)^c

T2 weighted^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016647>

has super-classes

[Imaging sequence](#)^c, [Tissue Contrast](#)^c

T2* weighted^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016650>

has super-classes

[Tissue Contrast](#)^c

T2/T1 weighted^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016651>

has super-classes

[Tissue Contrast](#)^c

Tamoxifen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036135>

An antineoplastic nonsteroidal selective estrogen receptor modulator (SERM). Tamoxifen competitively inhibits the binding of estradiol to estrogen receptors, thereby preventing the receptor from binding to the estrogen-response element on DNA. The result is a reduction in DNA synthesis and cellular response to estrogen. In addition, tamoxifen up-regulates the production of transforming growth factor B (TGFb), a factor that inhibits tumor cell growth, and down-regulates insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1), a factor that stimulates breast cancer cell growth. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Targeted medication therapy review^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035121>

has super-classes

[Medication Review](#)^c

Targeted Prostate Biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001935>

A method of image-guided needle biopsy which merges previously taken MRI images of suspected cancer with real-time ultrasound prostate tissue so that samples are preferentially taken from areas of interest or suspicion. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Needle biopsy of prostate](#)^c

Targeted Therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034674>

A type of cancer treatment that uses testing and medication to more precisely identify and treat cancer. These treatments target and disable genes or proteins necessary to the proliferation of cancer cells. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Therapeutic procedure](#)^c

Targetoid^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1010775>

[LI-RADS] Target-like imaging morphology. The center and periphery of a mass have different imaging characteristics. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Morphologic descriptor](#)^c

TD identified, number unknown^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002761>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

TDM1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035988>

An antibody-drug conjugate (ADC) consisting of the recombinant anti-epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2) monoclonal antibody trastuzumab conjugated to the maytansinoid DM1 via a nonreducible thioether linkage (MCC) with potential antineoplastic activity. The trastuzumab moiety of this ADC binds to HER2 on tumor cell surfaces; upon internalization, the DM1 moiety is released and binds to tubulin, thereby disrupting microtubule assembly/disassembly dynamics and inhibiting cell division and the proliferation of cancer cells that overexpress HER2. Linkage of antibody and drug through a nonreducible linker has been reported to contribute to the improved efficacy and reduced toxicity of this ADC compared to similar ADCs constructed with reducible linkers. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Drug or medication](#)^c

Technique radiation value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001171>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

Temozolomide^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035872>

has super-classes

[Alkylating agent](#)^c

Temporal brain region^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000421>

has super-classes

[Brain region](#)^c

Temporal context value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001065>

has super-classes

[Context values](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Current or past](#)^c

Temporal lobe^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000350>

has super-classes

[Brain](#)^c, [Brain Lesion Site](#)^c

Temporal Qualifier^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001943>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Date](#)^c, [Time patterns](#)^c, [Timepoint](#)^c

TERT (telomerase reverse transcriptase) gene variant measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051956>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

TERT gene promotor region targeted mutation analysis in Tissue by Molecular genetics method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051950>

has super-classes

[Molecular pathology](#)^c

Testosterone measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021338>

has super-classes

[Androgen level](#)^c, [Steroid measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Serum testosterone measurement](#)^c

TGFBR1 gene+TGFBR2 gene targeted mutation analysis in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052052>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

Thalamus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000376>

has super-classes

[Brain Lesion Site](#)^c, [Diencephalon part](#)^c, [Eloquent Brain Areas](#)^c, [Structure of half of brain lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c

Therapeutic^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002604>

has super-classes

[Intents](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Adjuvant - intent](#)^c, [Neo-adjuvant - intent](#)^c

Therapeutic procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1010523>

An action or administration of therapeutic agents to produce an effect that is intended to alter or stop a pathologic process. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Procedure](#)^c, [Treatment](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biological Therapy](#)^c, [Chemotherapy](#)^c, [Drug therapy](#)^c, [Hyperthermia Treatment](#)^c, [Neoadjuvant antineoplastic therapy](#)^c, [Radiation Therapy \(Procedure\)](#)^c, [Radiotherapy](#)^c, [Targeted Therapy](#)^c, [Thermotherapy](#)^c

Therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000018>

has super-classes

[Observation Category](#)^c

Thermotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1014761>

has super-classes

[Therapeutic procedure](#)^c

Thick^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000057>

has super-classes

[General adjectival modifier](#)^c, [Thickness of enhancing margin value](#)^c

Thick skin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055013>

has super-classes

[Finding of thickness of skin](#)^c

Thickening of skin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059065>

[BI-RADS] Mammo/MR: may be focal or diffuse, and is defined as being > 2mm in thickness. US: May be focal or diffuse, >2mm in thickness (in the periareolar area and inframammary folds up to 4mm) [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Disorder of skin](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Skin thickening of breast](#)^c

Thickness of enhancing margin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016735>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Thickness of enhancing margin value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016735>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria value](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Minimal](#)^c, [Solid](#)^c, [Thick](#)^c

Thickness of skin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047972>

has super-classes

[Skin observable](#)^c

Thin skin^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055012>

has super-classes

[Finding of thickness of skin](#)^c

Third line treatment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060622>

has super-classes

[Procedure by intent](#)^c

Thoracic segment of trunk^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000011>

Subdivision of trunk which has as its parts the thorax and the back of thorax. Examples: There is only one thoracic segment of trunk. [RADLEX]

has super-classes

[Cross-sectional thorax](#)^c, [Upper body part structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Chest](#)^c, [Structure of upper back](#)^c

Thoracic spine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000194>

The vertebrae of the thoracic spine, numbered one through twelve in man. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Spine](#)^c, [Structure of musculoskeletal system of thoracic spine](#)^c, [Structure of vertebral region of thoracic part of back](#)^c

Thorax excision^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059046>

has super-classes

[Surgical procedure on thorax](#)^c, [Trunk excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Excision of breast](#)^c, [Excision of breast tissue](#)^c, [Lung excision](#)^c

Three dimensional conformal radiotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005283>

has super-classes

[Conformal radiotherapy](#)^c

Three dimensional external beam radiation therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005276>

has super-classes

[External beam radiation therapy procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Conformal radiotherapy](#)^c

Thyroglobulin [Mass/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050573>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#)^c, [Thyroglobulin measurement](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

Thyroglobulin Ab [Units/volume] in Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049787>

has super-classes

[Thyroglobulin Ab|Arbitrary Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c](#)

Thyroglobulin Ab|Arbitrary Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049785>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Thyroglobulin Ab \[Units/volume\] in Serum or Plasma^c](#)

Thyroglobulin antibody measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050464>

has super-classes

[Anti-thyroid antibody measurement^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Stimulated Thyroglobulin antibody measurement^c](#)

Thyroglobulin measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050571>

has super-classes

[Globulin measurement^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Stimulated Thyroglobulin measurement^c](#), [Thyroglobulin \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma^c](#)

Thyroid^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000286>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography^c](#), [Thyroid and/or parathyroid structures^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Entire thyroid gland^c](#), [Thyroid part^c](#)

Thyroid and/or parathyroid structures^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000285>

has super-classes

[Endocrine gland structure^c](#), [Neck^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Thyroid^c](#)

Thyroid part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000287>

has super-classes

[Thyroid^c](#)

Thyroid stimulating hormone measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050677>

has super-classes

[Hormone measurement^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Thyrotropin \[Units/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Thyroid stimulating immunoglobulins [Units/volume] in Serum^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033781>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#)^c

Thyrotropin [Units/volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033900>

has super-classes

[Chemistry](#)^c, [Thyroid stimulating hormone measurement](#)^c, [Thyrotropin|Arbitrary Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Thyrotropin|Arbitrary Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049919>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Thyrotropin \[Units/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Tier 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000009>

has super-classes

[Interoperability level](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Tier 1A+](#)^c, [Tier 1C+](#)^c

Tier 1A+^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000012>

has super-classes

[Tier 1](#)^c

Tier 1C+^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000011>

has super-classes

[Tier 1](#)^c

Tier 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000011>

has super-classes

[Interoperability level](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Tier 2A+](#)^c, [Tier 2C+](#)^c

Tier 2A+^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000014>

has super-classes

[Tier 2](#)^c

Tier 2C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000013>

has super-classes

[Tier 2](#)^c

Tier 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000010>

has super-classes

[Interoperability level](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Tier 3A+](#)^c, [Tier 3C+](#)^c

Tier 3A^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000016>

has super-classes

[Tier 3](#)^c

Tier 3C^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SPEC1000015>

has super-classes

[Tier 3](#)^c

Time patterns^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000120>

has super-classes

[Temporal Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disease phases](#)^c, [Frequencies](#)^c, [Start time](#)^c, [Stop time](#)^c

Timepoint^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001945>

has super-classes

[Temporal Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Baseline](#)^c, [Follow-up](#)^c

Tissue composition^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016681>

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c, [Tumor Observation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Almost entirely fat](#)^c, [Extreme fibroglandular tissue](#)^c, [Heterogeneous fibroglandular tissue](#)^c, [Scattered fibroglandular tissue](#)^c

Tissue Contrast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016649>

has super-classes

[MR procedure attribute](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Diffusion weighted](#)^c, [FLAIR](#)^c, [Intermediate weighted](#)^c, [PW](#)^c, [T1 weighted](#)^c, [T1W-CE](#)^c, [T2 weighted](#)^c, [T2* weighted](#)^c, [T2/T1 weighted](#)^c

Tissue specimen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1002180>

has super-classes

[Body substance specimen^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Tissue specimen from genital system^c](#)

Tissue specimen from colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059199>

has super-classes

[Specimen from colon^c](#), [Tissue specimen from large intestine^c](#)

Tissue specimen from gastrointestinal tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055976>

has super-classes

[Specimen from gastrointestinal tract^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Tissue specimen from large intestine^c](#)

Tissue specimen from genital system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1021447>

has super-classes

[Specimen from genital system^c](#), [Tissue specimen^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Tissue specimen from prostate^c](#)

Tissue specimen from large intestine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055475>

has super-classes

[Specimen from large intestine^c](#), [Tissue specimen from gastrointestinal tract^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Tissue specimen from colon^c](#)

Tissue specimen from prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1027775>

has super-classes

[Specimen from prostate^c](#), [Tissue specimen from genital system^c](#)

TNM category^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033316>

has super-classes

[TNM tumor staging classifications^c](#)

has sub-classes

[M category^c](#), [N category^c](#), [T category^c](#), [TNM classification of malignant tumor after operation^c](#)

TNM classification of malignant tumor after operation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1038653>

has super-classes

[TNM category^c](#)

has sub-classes

[pM category](#)^c, [pN category](#)^c, [pT category](#)^c

TNM Clin M^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031282>

has super-classes

[cM category](#)^c

TNM Clin N^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031528>

has super-classes

[cN category](#)^c

TNM Clin Stage Group^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031313>

has super-classes

[TNM stage grouping](#)^c

TNM Clin T^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031297>

has super-classes

[cT category](#)^c

TNM Path M^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033404>

has super-classes

[pM category](#)^c

TNM Path N^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033068>

has super-classes

[pN category](#)^c

TNM Path Stage Group^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031268>

has super-classes

[TNM stage grouping](#)^c

TNM Path T^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033007>

has super-classes

[pT category](#)^c

TNM stage grouping^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033319>

has super-classes

[TNM tumor staging classifications](#)^c

has sub-classes

[TNM Clin Stage Group](#)^c, [TNM Path Stage Group](#)^c

TNM tumor staging classifications^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033314>

has super-classes

[Generic tumor staging descriptor](#)^c

has sub-classes

[TNM category](#)^c, [TNM stage grouping](#)^c

Tobacco smoking behavior - finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056421>

has super-classes

[Finding of tobacco use and exposure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Non-smoker](#)^c, [Smoker](#)^c

Tobacco use and exposure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050951>

has super-classes

[Substance use behavior](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Age at smoking cessation](#)^c, [Smoking status](#)^c

Tobacco user^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056700>

has super-classes

[Finding of tobacco use and exposure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Smoker](#)^c

Tomographic imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000025>

Imaging by sections or sectioning. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Radiographic imaging procedure](#)^c

Tomographic imaging - action^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000043>

has super-classes

[Radiographic imaging - action](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Tomographic imaging, plain radiologic - action](#)^c

Tomographic imaging, plain radiologic - action^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000069>

has super-classes

[Plain X-ray imaging - action](#)^c, [Tomographic imaging - action](#)^c

Tomography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000070>

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Computed tomography](#)^c, [Conventional tomography](#)^c

Tomotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005282>

A type of external beam radiation therapy in which the radiation is delivered slice-by-slice, providing sequential delivery of radiation to different parts of the tumor. This method differs from other forms of radiation therapy in which the entire tumor volume is irradiated at one time. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Intensity modulated radiation therapy](#)^c

Topographical modifier^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002029>

has super-classes

[Adjectival modifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Axial](#)^c, [Intermediate](#)^c, [Left](#)^c, [Longitudinal](#)^c, [Right](#)^c

Topography unknown^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000266>

has super-classes

[Body structure](#)^c

Toshiba^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000045>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Total colectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060277>

has super-classes

[Excision of colon](#)^c

Total lobectomy of brain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004593>

has super-classes

[Lobectomy of brain](#)^c

Total pneumonectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060443>

has super-classes

[Complete excision](#)^c, [Lung excision](#)^c

Total prostate specific antigen level^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1030627>

has super-classes

[Prostate specific antigen measurement](#)^c

Total radiation dose delivered^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050898>

has super-classes

[Delivered radiation dose](#)^c

Total Tumor Volume^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1003881>

has super-classes

[Volumetric Imaging Criteria](#)^c

TP53 (tumor protein p53) gene variant measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051958>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

TP53 Gene Mutation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063188>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c

TP53 gene mutations found [Identifier] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1052001>

has super-classes

[Gene mutation](#)^c, [Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

Trabecular adenocarcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049606>

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#)^c, [Malignant adenomatous neoplasm \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

Transgender^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000179>

has super-classes

[Gender](#)^c

Transition zone of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000100>

PI-RADS: Tissue around the urethra that is separated from the peripheral zone by the “surgical capsule” delineated as a low signal line on T2 weighted MRI. It is the site of most BPH. [RADLEX]

has super-classes

[Glandular zone of prostate](#)^c

Transitional cell carcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049455>

has super-classes

[Malignant neoplasm](#)^c, [Transitional cell neoplasm](#)^c

Transitional cell carcinoma, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049591>

has super-classes

[Transitional cell papillomas and carcinomas](#)^c

Transitional cell carcinoma, NOS, of prostate gland^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031177>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c, [Primary malignant neoplasm of prostate](#)^c

Transitional cell neoplasm^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049169>

has super-classes

[Epithelial neoplasm](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Transitional cell carcinoma](#)^c

Transitional cell papillomas and carcinomas^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049535>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Transitional cell carcinoma, NOS](#)^c

Transperineal needle biopsy of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001933>

has super-classes

[Needle biopsy of prostate](#)^c

Transrectal needle biopsy of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001932>

has super-classes

[Needle biopsy of prostate](#)^c

Transverse colectomy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060286>

has super-classes

[Partial resection of colon](#)^c

Transverse colon^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063742>

has super-classes

[Colon](#)^c

Transverse colon structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063613>

is equivalent to

[Transverse colon](#)^c

has super-classes

[Region of colon](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of left colic flexure](#)^c, [Structure of right colic flexure](#)^c

Trastuzumab^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035955>

A recombinant humanized monoclonal antibody directed against the human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2). After binding to HER2 on the tumor cell surface, trastuzumab induces an antibody-dependent cell-mediated cytotoxicity against tumor cells that overexpress HER2. HER2 is overexpressed by many adenocarcinomas, particularly breast adenocarcinomas. (NCI04)

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Trastuzumab deruxtecan^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036025>

has super-classes

[Drug or medicament](#)^c

Treatment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000007>

has super-classes

[Episode](#)^c

Treatment^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000015>

has super-classes

[Event](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Administration of medication](#)^c, [Radiotherapy](#)^c, [Surgical procedure](#)^c, [Therapeutic procedure](#)^c

is in domain of

[hasTreatmentIntent](#)^{op}

is in range of

[hasTreatment](#)^{op}

Treatment changed^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035796>

has super-classes

[Procedure with explicit context](#)^c

Treatment response value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001180>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Complete response](#)^c, [Partial response](#)^c, [Progressive disease](#)^c, [Stable disease](#)^c

is in range of

[hasTreatmentResponse](#)^{op}

Triglyceride [Mass/volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033594>

has super-classes

[Chemistry^c](#), [Triglycerides measurement^c](#), [Triglyceride|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c](#), [Triglyceride|Moment in time|Blood^c](#)

Triglycerides measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050596>

has super-classes

[Lipids measurement^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Triglyceride \[Mass/volume\] in Blood^c](#)

Triglyceride|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049936>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Triglyceride \[Mass/volume\] in Blood^c](#)

Triglyceride|Moment in time|Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050279>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Triglyceride \[Mass/volume\] in Blood^c](#)

Triple-negative breast cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046256>

is equivalent to

[HER2 negative^c](#) and [ER negative^c](#) and [PR negative^c](#)

has super-classes

[HER2 negative^c](#), [Hormone receptor negative neoplasm^c](#)

has sub-classes

[Basal-like 1^c](#), [Basal-like 2^c](#), [Immunomodulatory^c](#), [Luminal androgen receptor^c](#), [Mesenchymal stem-like^c](#), [Mesenchymal-like^c](#)

Trivial cigarette smoker (0-1 cigarettes per day)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059169>

has super-classes

[Cigarette smoker^c](#)

True^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000036>

has super-classes

[Boolean value^c](#)

Trunk excision^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1004787>

has super-classes

[Excision](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Abdomen excision](#)^c, [Excision of malignant lesion of trunk](#)^c, [Excision of mass of pelvic region](#)^c, [Excision of pelvis](#)^c, [Removal of entire genital organ](#)^c, [Thorax excision](#)^c

Trunk structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000002>

has super-classes

[Body part structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Structure of half of trunk lateral to midsagittal plane](#)^c, [Structure of subregion of trunk](#)^c

Tubular adenocarcinoma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1063555>

has super-classes

[Adenomas and adenocarcinomas](#)^c

Tubular adenocarcinoma of breast, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060887>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Tumor](#)^c

Tucatinib^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036045>

An orally bioavailable inhibitor of the human epidermal growth factor receptor tyrosine kinase ErbB-2 (also called HER2) with potential antineoplastic activity. Tucatinib selectively binds to and inhibits the phosphorylation of ErbB-2, which may prevent the activation of ErbB-2 signal transduction pathways, resulting in growth inhibition and death of ErbB-2-expressing tumor cells. ErbB-2 is overexpressed in a variety of cancers and plays an important role in cellular proliferation and differentiation. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c

Tumor antigen measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039710>

has super-classes

[Tumor marker measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cancer antigen 15-3 measurement](#)^c, [Cancer antigen 19-9 measurement](#)^c

Tumor border configuration^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050984>

has super-classes

[Tumor configuration](#)^c

Tumor budding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059061>

has super-classes

[Growth alteration](#)^c

Tumor calcification^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035380>

has super-classes

[Tumor finding](#)^c

Tumor configuration^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049733>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Tumor border configuration](#)^c

Tumor configuration^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049734>

has super-classes

[Tumor finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Cribriform tumor pattern](#)^c, [Diffuse tumor configuration](#)^c, [Hemorrhagic tumor](#)^c, [Necrotic tumor](#)^c

Tumor configuration (finding)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035406>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

Tumor configuration observable entity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049103>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

Tumor Examination^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1047421>

An assessment or evaluation of a neoplastic mass. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Medical Assessment](#)^c

Tumor extension finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049693>

has super-classes

[Tumor finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Extraprostatic Extension \(EPE\)](#)^c, [Extraprostatic extension of tumor present](#)^c

Tumor finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005480>

has super-classes

[Finding of lesion](#)^c, [Tumor Observation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Distant metastasis present](#)^c, [Gleason finding](#)^c, [Gleason grade finding for prostatic cancer](#)^c, [Recurrent tumor](#)^c, [Regional lymph node metastasis present](#)^c, [Tumor Progression](#)^c, [Tumor calcification](#)^c, [Tumor configuration](#)^c, [Tumor extension finding](#)^c, [Tumor invasion finding](#)^c, [Tumor stage finding](#)^c

Tumor focality^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034970>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Qualitative distribution of primary malignant neoplasm](#)^c

Tumor grade^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#TumorGrade>

has super-classes

[Staging and scales](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Grade 1 tumor](#)^c, [Grade 2 tumor](#)^c, [Grade 3 tumor](#)^c, [Grade 4 tumor](#)^c

is in range of

[hasGrade](#)^{op}

Tumor histopathological grade status values^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1046013>

has super-classes

[Generic tumor staging descriptor](#)^c

Tumor internal vascularity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016699>

[BI-RADS] US: Blood vessels present within the mass [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Tumor vascularity](#)^c

Tumor invasion finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015105>

has super-classes

[Finding of histologic grading differentiation AND/OR behavior](#)^c, [Tumor finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Invasion into the Seminal vesicle](#)^c, [Lymphatic \(small vessel\) tumor invasion finding](#)^c, [No vascular invasion by tumor](#)^c, [Perineural invasion finding](#)^c, [Seminal vesicle invasion by tumor present](#)^c, [Tumor invasion of perineural tissue absent \(prostate\)](#)^c, [Tumor invasion of perineural tissue present \(prostate\)](#)^c, [Vascular invasion by tumor present](#)^c, [Venous \(large vessel\) invasion by tumor present](#)^c

Tumor invasion of perineural tissue absent (prostate)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1027888>

has super-classes

[Tumor invasion finding](#)^c

Tumor invasion of perineural tissue present (prostate)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1028002>

has super-classes

[Tumor invasion finding](#)^c

Tumor Location^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016742>

has super-classes

[VASARI Criteria](#)^c

Tumor marker measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000224>

has super-classes

[Evidence Type](#)^c, [Measurement of substance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[ATRX \(ATRX chromatin remodeler\) gene variant measurement](#)^c, [BRCA1 gene mutations tested for in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c, [Cancer Ag 15-3](#)^c, [Carcinoembryonic antigen measurement](#)^c, [Cells.Ki-67 nuclear Ag/100 cells in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c, [Cells.estrogen receptor/100 cells in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c, [Cells.progesterone receptor/100 cells in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c, [Chromosome region 6q22 rearrangements in Tissue by FISH](#)^c, [ERBB2 gene duplication \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by FISH](#)^c, [Estrogen receptor Ag.\[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c, [HER2 Ag.\[Presence\] in Tissue by Immune stain](#)^c, [HER2 \[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c, [IDH1 \(isocitrate dehydrogenase \(NADP\(±\)\)1\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [IDH2 \(isocitrate dehydrogenase \(NADP\(±\)\)2\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [MGMT \(O-6-methylguanine-DNA methyltransferase\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [Progesterone receptor Ag.\[Presence\] in Breast cancer specimen by Immune stain](#)^c, [Prostate specific antigen measurement](#)^c, [TERT \(telomerase reverse transcriptase\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [TP53 \(tumor protein p53\).gene variant measurement](#)^c, [TP53 gene mutations found \[Identifier\] in Blood or Tissue by Molecular genetics method Nominal](#)^c, [Thyroglobulin \[Mass/volume\] in Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Tumor antigen measurement](#)^c

is in range of

[hasTumorMarkerTest](#)^{op}

Tumor measureable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050478>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Number of lymph nodes containing metastatic neoplasm in excised specimen](#)^c, [Number of tumor nodules](#)^c, [Tumor quantitation](#)^c, [Tumor volume](#)^c

Tumor Morphology^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049522>

A classification system grouping neoplasms according to their cellular characteristics. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Histology/Morphology](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm and/or hamartoma \(morphologic abnormality\)](#)^c

is in range of

[hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op}, [hasMorphology](#)^{op}

Tumor Observation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000026>

has super-classes

[Generic Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Density descriptor](#)^c, [Deposit](#)^c, [Enhancement pattern](#)^c, [Imaging Criteria](#)^c, [Imaging observation descriptor](#)^c, [Margin](#)^c, [Orientation descriptor](#)^c, [Tissue composition](#)^c, [Tumor finding](#)^c, [Tumor vascularity](#)^c

is in range of

[hasTumorObservation](#)^{op}, [hasTumorObservationValue](#)^{op}

Tumor of respiratory system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051154>

has super-classes

[Disorder of respiratory system](#) ^c, [Mass of respiratory structure](#) ^c, [Neoplasm by body site](#) ^c, [Neoplastic disease](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Malignant neoplasm of respiratory system](#) ^c, [Neoplasm of respiratory tract](#) ^c

Tumor Progression^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1028117>

has super-classes

[Tumor finding](#) ^c

Tumor quantitation^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050505>

has super-classes

[Neoplasm observable](#) ^c, [Tumor measureable](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Needle biopsy specimen tumor quantitation](#) ^c

Tumor Regression Grade^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049083>

A pathologic grading system used to evaluate the tumor response to preoperative chemotherapy and radiation. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Staging and scales](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Modified Ryan Scheme for Tumor Regression](#) ^c

Tumor Regression Grade 0|Complete response: No viable cancer cells|No residual tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002714>

has super-classes

[Disease Grade Qualifier](#) ^c

Tumor Regression Grade 1|Moderate response: Single cells or small groups of cancer cells^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002724>

has super-classes

[Disease Grade Qualifier](#) ^c

Tumor Regression Grade 2|Minimal response: Residual cancer outgrown by fibrosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002735>

has super-classes

[Disease Grade Qualifier](#) ^c

Tumor Regression Grade 3|Poor response: Minimal or no tumor kill; extensive residual cancer^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002747>

has super-classes

[Disease Grade Qualifier](#) ^c

Tumor Regression Score 0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001776>

A score on the Modified Ryan Scheme for Tumor Regression that indicates a complete response, defined as having no viable cancer cells. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[Tumor Regression Grade 0|Complete response: No viable cancer cells|No residual tumor](#)^c

has super-classes

[Disease Grade Qualifier](#)^c

Tumor Regression Score 1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001785>

A score on the Modified Ryan Scheme for Tumor Regression that indicates a near complete response, defined as the presence of single cells or rare small groups of cancer cells. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[Tumor Regression Grade 1|Moderate response: Single cells or small groups of cancer cells](#)^c

has super-classes

[Disease Grade Qualifier](#)^c

Tumor Regression Score 2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001795>

A score on the Modified Ryan Scheme for Tumor Regression that indicates a partial response, defined as the presence of residual cancer with evident tumor regression but more than single cells or rare small groups of cancer cells. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[Tumor Regression Grade 2|Minimal response: Residual cancer outgrown by fibrosis](#)^c

has super-classes

[Disease Grade Qualifier](#)^c

Tumor Regression Score 3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001806>

A score on the Modified Ryan Scheme for Tumor Regression that indicates poor or no response, defined as extensive residual cancer with no evident tumor regression. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[Tumor Regression Grade 3|Poor response: Minimal or no tumor kill; extensive residual cancer](#)^c

has super-classes

[Disease Grade Qualifier](#)^c

Tumor Size Method^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000028>

has super-classes

[Generic Module](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gross examination and sampling of tissue specimen](#)^c, [Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c, [Light microscopy](#)^c, [Physical examination](#)^c, [Radiographic imaging procedure](#)^c

is in range of

[hasTumorSizeMethod](#)^{op}

Tumor stage finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050821>

has super-classes

[Tumor finding](#)^c

Tumor staging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044182>

has super-classes

[Staging and scales](#)^c

has sub-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer, Cancer Staging Manual, 8th edition neoplasm staging system](#)^c, [American Urological Association staging system for prostate cancer](#)^c, [Cancer staging](#)^c, [FIGO staging system of gynecological malignancy](#)^c, [Intergroup Rhabdomyosarcoma Study Group Clinical Staging and Grouping System](#)^c, [Malignant tumor staging](#)^c

is in domain of

[CancerStagingMethodFor](#)^{op}

is in range of

[Has staging](#)^{op}, [hasStageMethod](#)^{op}

Tumor vascularity^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016696>

[BI-RADS] US: Must reference a contralateral normal area or unaffected site in the same breast as the basis for comparison [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Imaging Module](#)^c, [Tumor Observation](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Tumor internal vascularity](#)^c, [Tumor vascularity absent](#)^c, [Vessels in rim of tumor](#)^c

Tumor vascularity absent^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016698>

has super-classes

[Tumor vascularity](#)^c

Tumor volume^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1030900>

has super-classes

[Tumor measurable](#)^c

Tumour marker levels^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1055890>

has super-classes

[Substance observable](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Carcinoembryonic antigen level](#)^c

Two dimensional external beam radiation therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005275>

has super-classes

[External beam radiation therapy procedure](#)^c

TZ+CZ^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000423>

is equivalent to

[Transition zone of prostate](#)^c and [Central zone of prostate](#)^c

UIH^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000063>

has super-classes

[Manufacturer](#)^c

Ultra high dose rate radiotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005274>

has super-classes

[External beam radiation therapy procedure](#) ^c

Ultrasonic guidance procedure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005572>

has super-classes

[Imaging guidance](#) ^c, [Ultrasound](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[US-guided systematic biopsy](#) ^c, [Ultrasound guided biopsy](#) ^c

Ultrasonographic observable^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016253>

has super-classes

[Imaging observable](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Acoustic feature of mass](#) ^c

Ultrasonography of abdomen^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005518>

has super-classes

[Imaging of abdomen](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy of abdomen using ultrasound guidance](#) ^c, [US scan of prostate](#) ^c

Ultrasonography of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016137>

has super-classes

[Ultrasonography of thorax](#) ^c

Ultrasonography of thorax^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016135>

has super-classes

[Chest imaging](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Ultrasonography of breast](#) ^c

Ultrasound^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000035>

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#) ^c

Ultrasound^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1000040>

High frequency sound, generally with a frequency greater than 20,000 Hz. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Ultrasonic guidance procedure](#) ^c

Ultrasound guided biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005497>

has super-classes

[Imaging guided biopsy](#)^c, [Ultrasonic guidance procedure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Biopsy of abdomen using ultrasound guidance](#)^c

Ultrasound scan finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016290>

has super-classes

[Imaging finding](#)^c

Unable to determine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002024>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

Unapproved attribute^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002669>

has super-classes

[Attribute](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Nodes removed](#)^c

Undetermined^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001088>

has super-classes

[Condition stability status](#)^c, [Finding value](#)^c

Unifocal^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002429>

has super-classes

[Distributions](#)^c

Unilateral^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016695>

has super-classes

[Laterality](#)^c, [Relative sites](#)^c

Unit of measure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000147>

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Derived Unit of International System of Units](#)^c, [Unit of radiotherapy](#)^c, [Unit of time](#)^c, [centimeter](#)^c, [cubic centimeter](#)^c, [cubic millimeter](#)^c, [enzyme unit per liter](#)^c, [enzyme unit per milliliter](#)^c, [gram per deciliter](#)^c, [international unit per milliliter](#)^c, [mg/kg](#)^c, [mg/m2](#)^c, [milli-international unit per liter](#)^c, [milli-international unit per liter](#)^c, [milligram](#)^c, [milligram per 24 hours](#)^c, [milligram per deciliter](#)^c, [milliliter](#)^c, [millimeter](#)^c,

[millimole per liter](#)^c, [millisecond](#)^c, [milliunit per liter](#)^c, [nanogram per deciliter](#)^c, [nanogram per milliliter](#)^c, [nanomole per liter](#)^c, [per microliter](#)^c,
[per nanoliter](#)^c, [percent](#)^c, [picogram per milliliter](#)^c

is in range of

[hasUnitofMeasure](#)^{op}

Unit of radiation dose^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000143>

has super-classes

[Unit of radiotherapy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Gy](#)^c, [mGy](#)^c, [mSv](#)^c

is in range of

[hasRadiationDoseUnit](#)^{op}

Unit of radiotherapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000142>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Unit of radiation dose](#)^c

Unit of time^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000150>

has super-classes

[Unit of measure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[day](#)^c, [month](#)^c, [week](#)^c, [year](#)^c

is in range of

[hasUnitofTime](#)^{op}

Unknown^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001289>

has super-classes

[Finding context value](#)^c

Unknown or no information|Not documented in patient record^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001219>

has super-classes

[Neoadjuvant Therapy response value](#)^c

Unknown or no information|Not documented in patient record^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002760>

has super-classes

[Disease Grade Qualifier](#)^c

Unspecified^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001288>

has super-classes

[Finding context value](#)^c

Upper body part structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000097>

has super-classes

[Upper body structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Head and neck](#)^c, [Thoracic segment of trunk](#)^c

Upper body structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000289>

has super-classes

[Body part structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Upper body part structure](#)^c

Upper extremity part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000091>

has super-classes

[Arm](#)^c, [Extremity part](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Connective, Subcutaneous and other soft tissues of upper limb and shoulder](#)^c, [Structure of lymphatic system of upper limb](#)^c

Upper limb lymph node structure^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000048>

has super-classes

[Lymph node structure of limb](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Axillary lymph node structure](#)^c

Upper-inner quadrant of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000278>

has super-classes

[Breast](#)^c

Upper-outer quadrant of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000276>

has super-classes

[Breast](#)^c

Upright position^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016601>

has super-classes

[Patient Position](#)^c

Urate [Mass/volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033495>

has super-classes

[Blood urate measurement](#)^c, [Chemistry](#)^c, [Urate|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c

Urate|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050413>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Urate \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Urea [Mass/volume] in Blood^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1033470>

has super-classes

[Blood urea measurement](#)^c, [Chemistry](#)^c, [Urea|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma](#)^c, [Urea|Moment in time|Blood|60.056 g/mole](#)^c

Urea|Mass Concentration|Moment in time|Blood, Serum or Plasma^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049954>

has super-classes

[Flowsheet - laboratory](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Urea \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Urea|Moment in time|Blood|60.056 g/mole^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050311>

has super-classes

[Mass-Molar conversion](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Urea \[Mass/volume\] in Blood](#)^c

Uric acid measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050555>

has super-classes

[Measurement of substance](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Blood urate measurement](#)^c

Urinary incontinence^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1028233>

has super-classes

[Bladder control - finding](#)^c, [Bladder finding](#)^c, [Impaired urinary system function](#)^c, [Incontinence](#)^c

Urinary system finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015452>

has super-classes

[Urogenital finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Disorder of the urinary system](#)^c, [Finding of urinary tract proper](#)^c, [Impaired urinary system function](#)^c, [Kidney finding](#)^c

Urinary tract^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000044>

The parts of the urinary system that discharge urine. These include the renal pelvis, ureter, bladder, and urethra. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Structure of genitourinary system](#)^c

Urinary tract pain^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000354>

has super-classes

[Finding of urinary tract proper](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Dysuria](#)^c

Urine albumin measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050495>

has super-classes

[Fluid sample albumin measurement](#)^c, [Urine protein measurement](#)^c, [Urine protein test](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Albumin measurement, urine, quantitative](#)^c

Urine finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000351>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Blood in urine](#)^c

Urine protein measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050451>

has super-classes

[Protein measurement](#)^c, [Urine protein test](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Urine albumin measurement](#)^c

Urine protein test^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050456>

has super-classes

[Protein measurement](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Urine albumin measurement](#)^c, [Urine protein measurement](#)^c

Urine stream interrupted^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1000357>

has super-classes

[Flow of urine - finding](#)^c

Urine substance measurement^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050586>

has super-classes

[Evaluation of urine specimen](#)^c, [Measurement of substance in specimen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Creatinine measurement, urine](#)^c

Urogenital finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1015278>

has super-classes

[Finding of abdominopelvic segment of trunk](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Genital finding](#)^c, [Urinary system finding](#)^c

US male genital system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005605>

has super-classes

[US scan of genitourinary system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[US scan of prostate](#)^c

US scan and biopsy of pelvis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1001997>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of trunk](#)^c, [Pelvic echography](#)^c

has sub-classes

[US scan and biopsy of prostate](#)^c

US scan and biopsy of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1016628>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of prostate](#)^c, [US scan and biopsy of pelvis](#)^c, [US scan of prostate](#)^c

has sub-classes

[MRI-US fusion guided prostate biopsy](#)^c

US scan of genitourinary system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005588>

has super-classes

[Imaging of genitourinary system](#)^c

has sub-classes

[US male genital system](#)^c

US scan of prostate^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1005557>

has super-classes

[Pelvic echography](#)^c, [US male genital system](#)^c, [Ultrasonography of abdomen](#)^c

has sub-classes

[US scan and biopsy of prostate](#)^c

US-guided systematic biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1031038>

has super-classes

[Imaging guided biopsy](#)^c, [Ultrasonic guidance procedure](#)^c

Uses contraception^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1034434>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Uses hormonal contraception](#)^c

Uses hormonal contraception^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035208>

has super-classes

[Uses contraception](#)^c

Uterus^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000085>

A hollow, thick-walled, muscular organ located within the pelvic cavity of a woman. Within the uterus the fertilized egg implants and the fetus develops during pregnancy. [NCIT]

is equivalent to

[Uterus, NOS](#)^c

has super-classes

[Female genital tract structure](#)^c, [Structure of female genital system in pelvic cavity](#)^c, [Structure of female internal genital organ](#)^c, [Structure of organ within cavity of true pelvis](#)^c, [Structure of pelvic viscus](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Entire uterus](#)^c, [Uterus part](#)^c

Uterus and fallopian tubes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000221>

has super-classes

[Combined site](#)^c

Uterus part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000295>

has super-classes

[Uterus](#)^c

Uterus, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000291>

has super-classes

[ICDO3Topography](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Uterus, NOS](#)^c

Uterus, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000294>

has super-classes

[Uterus, NOS](#)^c

V - Hepatic vein marker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1044442>

has super-classes

[Markers for liver tumor staging](#)^c

Vacuum assisted biopsy of lesion of breast^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1060461>

has super-classes

[Biopsy of breast](#) ^c

Vagina^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000299>

has super-classes

[Female genital organ structure](#) ^c, [ICDO3Topography](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Vagina, NOS](#) ^c

Vagina, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000300>

has super-classes

[Vagina](#) ^c

Vaginal lesion^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1003149>

has super-classes

[Disorder of vagina](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of vagina](#) ^c

Vaginal mass^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1039386>

has super-classes

[Mass of female genital structure](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Neoplasm of vagina](#) ^c

Value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000006>

A numerical quantity measured or assigned or computed. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Common Module](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Data Value](#) ^c

VASARI Criteria^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016751>

Comprehensive list of 24 most common features used to describe primary cerebral neoplasia on standard contrast enhanced MR imaging

has super-classes

[Imaging Criteria](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Calvarial Remodeling](#) ^c, [Cortical Involvement](#) ^c, [Cysts](#) ^c, [Deep White Matter Invasion](#) ^c, [Diffusion Characteristics](#) ^c, [Eloquent Brain](#) ^c, [Enhancement Quality](#) ^c, [Enhancing margin](#) ^c, [Enhancing tumor Crosses Midline](#) ^c, [Ependymal Extension](#) ^c, [Hemorrhage volume](#) ^c, [Multifocal or Multicentric](#) ^c, [Non-enhancing margin](#) ^c, [Pial Invasion](#) ^c, [Proportion Enhancing](#) ^c, [Proportion Necrosis](#) ^c, [Proportion nCET](#) ^c, [Proportion of Edema](#) ^c, [Satellites](#) ^c, [Side of Lesion Center](#) ^c, [T1/FLAIR Ratio](#) ^c, [Thickness of enhancing margin](#) ^c, [Tumor Location](#) ^c, [nCET tumor Crosses Midline](#) ^c

VASARI Criteria value^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1016751>

has super-classes

[Answer or Value Set](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Calvarial Remodeling value](#)^c, [Cortical Involvement value](#)^c, [Cysts value](#)^c, [Diffusion Characteristics value](#)^c, [Enhancement Quality value](#)^c, [Enhancing margin value](#)^c, [Enhancing tumor Crosses Midline value](#)^c, [Ependymal Extension value](#)^c, [Hemorrhage volume value](#)^c, [Multifocal or Multicentric value](#)^c, [Non-enhancing margin value](#)^c, [Pial Invasion value](#)^c, [Proportion Enhancing value](#)^c, [Proportion Necrosis value](#)^c, [Proportion nCET value](#)^c, [Proportion of Edema value](#)^c, [Satellites value](#)^c, [T1/FLAIR Ratio value](#)^c, [Thickness of enhancing margin value](#)^c, [nCET tumor Crosses Midline value](#)^c

Vascular invasion by tumor present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1028350>

has super-classes

[Tumor invasion finding](#)^c

Venography^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016775>

has super-classes

[Angiography](#)^c

Venous (large vessel) extramural invasion by tumor present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050812>

has super-classes

[Venous \(large vessel\) invasion by tumor present](#)^c

Venous (large vessel) intramural invasion by tumor present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059424>

has super-classes

[Venous \(large vessel\) invasion by tumor present](#)^c

Venous (large vessel) invasion by tumor present^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050777>

has super-classes

[Pathology examination findings present](#)^c, [Tumor invasion finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Venous \(large vessel\) extramural invasion by tumor present](#)^c, [Venous \(large vessel\) intramural invasion by tumor present](#)^c

Ventricle, NOS^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000353>

has super-classes

[Brain](#)^c

Very heavy cigarette smoker (more or equal to 40 cigarettes per day)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1059168>

has super-classes

[Cigarette smoker](#)^c

Very heavy drinker^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1056341>

has super-classes

[Current drinker](#)^c

Very high^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002064>

has super-classes

[High](#)^c, [Risk assessment value](#)^c

Very low^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002173>

has super-classes

[Low](#)^c, [Risk assessment value](#)^c

Vessels in rim of tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016697>

[BI-RADS] US: Blood vessels may be marginal, occupying part or all of the rim of the mass. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Tumor vascularity](#)^c

Video imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016779>

has super-classes

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Colonoscopy Video Recording](#)^c

Video imaging - action^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004465>

has super-classes

[Imaging modality](#)^c

Vinorelbine^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1035913>

A semisynthetic vinca alkaloid. Vinorelbine binds to tubulin and prevents formation of the mitotic spindle, resulting in the arrest of tumor cell growth in metaphase. This agent may also interfere with amino acid, cyclic AMP, and glutathione metabolism; calmodulin-dependent Ca⁺⁺-transport ATPase activity; cellular respiration; and nucleic acid and lipid biosynthesis. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Antineoplastic agent](#)^c, [Immunologic agent](#)^c

Viscus structure finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051140>

has super-classes

[Clinical finding](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Lung finding](#)^c, [Neoplasm of intrathoracic organs](#)^c

Vital Signs^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GEN1000024>

has super-classes

[Observation Category](#)^c

Volumetric Imaging Criteria^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1003880>

has super-classes

[Imaging Criteria](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Edema Volume](#)^c, [Enhancing Tumor Volume](#)^c, [Haemorrhage Volume](#)^c, [Necrosis Volume](#)^c, [Non-Enhancing Tumor Volume](#)^c, [Total Tumor Volume](#)^c

Volumetric modulated arc therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005272>

has super-classes

[Intensity modulated radiation therapy](#)^c

Volumetric modulated arc therapy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1005284>

Radiation therapy delivered to the whole volume of target tissue by a single rotation of the linear accelerator gantry. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Intensity modulated radiation therapy](#)^c

Voxel^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000132>

The smallest distinguishable 'rectangular-parallel-piped-shaped' part of a three-dimensional space or image. [NCIT]

has super-classes

[Qualifier](#)^c

Vulva^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000400>

has super-classes

[Female genital tract structure](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Entire vulva](#)^c, [Vulval part](#)^c

Vulval part^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000401>

has super-classes

[Vulva](#)^c

Wedge-shaped^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1010774>

[LI-RADS] Triangular in shape. [PI-RADS]: Having the shape of a wedge, pie, or V-shaped. [RadLex]

has super-classes

[Morphologic descriptor](#)^c

week^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000155>

has super-classes
[Unit of time](#)^c

Weight change finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050791>

has super-classes
[Weight trend finding](#)^c
has sub-classes
[Weight loss](#)^c

Weight finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050782>

has super-classes
[Body measurement finding](#)^c
has sub-classes
[Weight trend finding](#)^c

Weight loss^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050804>

has super-classes
[Weight change finding](#)^c

Weight trend finding^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1050786>

has super-classes
[Weight finding](#)^c
has sub-classes
[Weight change finding](#)^c

Well defined^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002021>

has super-classes
[Degree findings](#)^c, [Enhancing margin value](#)^c, [Non-enhancing margin value](#)^c

Wernicke's area^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BP1000440>

has super-classes
[Eloquent Brain Areas](#)^c, [Region of temporal cortex](#)^c

White^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001311>

has super-classes
[Ethnicity](#)^c, [Race](#)^c
has sub-classes
[European](#)^c

White blood cell disorder^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1036514>

has super-classes

[Disorder of immune function](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Leukopenia](#)^c

WHO CNS tumor grading system^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1037293>

has super-classes

[Histological grading systems](#)^c

WHO grade for central nervous system tumor^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1049680>

has super-classes

[Histologic grade of neoplasm](#)^c

Whole body bone imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016752>

has super-classes

[Radioisotope study of musculoskeletal system](#)^c

Whole Slide Imaging^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1004459>

Procedure step protocol for imaging slide specimens using a whole slide scanner. [DCM]

has super-classes

[Digital Microscopy](#)^c

has sub-classes

[Digitized hematoxylin-eosin \(HE\) slides](#)^c

Wife^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001037>

has super-classes

[Spouse](#)^c

Worsened^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002079>

has super-classes

[Condition stability status](#)^c

X-ray guided biopsy^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IMG1016754>

has super-classes

[Imaging guided biopsy](#)^c, [Radiologic guidance procedure](#)^c

year^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1000151>

has super-classes

[Unit of time](#)^c

Yes^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001363>

has super-classes

[Cortical Involvement value](#)^c, [Enhancing tumor Crosses Midline value](#)^c, [Ependymal Extension value](#)^c, [Hemorrhage volume value](#)^c, [Pial Invasion value](#)^c, [Presence findings](#)^c, [nCET tumor Crosses Midline value](#)^c

ypN0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001080>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypN1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001082>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypN1a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001089>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypN1b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001094>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypN1c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001100>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypN1mi^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001085>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypN2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001107>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypN2a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001115>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypN2b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001124>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypN3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001134>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypN3a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001145>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypN3b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001157>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypN3c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001170>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypN category allowable value](#)^c

ypT0^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001607>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypT1^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001610>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypT1a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001614>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypT1b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001619>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypT1c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001625>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypT1mi^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001632>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypT2^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001640>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypT3^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001649>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypT4^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001659>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypT4a^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001670>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypT4b^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001682>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypT4c^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001695>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypT4d^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001709>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypTis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001724>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#)^c

ypTis(DCIS)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002253>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#) ^c

ypTis(Paget)^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1002256>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#) ^c

ypTx^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#COM1001740>

has super-classes

[American Joint Committee on Cancer ypT category allowable value](#) ^c

Zonal necrosis^c back to [ToC](#) or [Class ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CLIN1051019>

has super-classes

[Necrosis](#) ^c

has sub-classes

[Central zone necrosis](#) ^c

Object Properties

- [Answer of](#)
- [Associated morphology of](#)
- [Associated With](#)
- [CancerGradingMethodFor](#)
- [CancerStagingMethodFor](#)
- [causedBy](#)
- [collectionMethod](#)
- [ComorbidityAssociatedWith](#)
- [Composed Of](#)
- [diagnosedWith](#)
- [Finding site of](#)
- [GeneVariantMutationFor](#)
- [has assessment test value](#)
- [Has Associated](#)
- [Has Associated Dimension](#)
- [Has Associated Tumor Marker Test](#)
- [Has condition](#)
- [has date of last contact](#)
- [has deceased](#)
- [Has Diagnostic Value](#)
- [Has direct site](#)
- [Has direct substance](#)
- [Has finding context](#)
- [Has imaging interpretation result](#)
- [Has inherent location](#)
- [Has interpretation result](#)
- [Has interprets](#)
- [Has Location](#)
- [has maximum dimension value](#)
- [Has method](#)
- [Has normality value](#)
- [Has observational value](#)
- [has other dimension value](#)
- [Has pathologic interpretation result](#)
- [Has pathologic interpretation result](#)
- [Has relative degree](#)
- [Has specimen source topography](#)
- [Has staging](#)
- [Has subject relationship context](#)

- [Has Technique](#)
- [Has temporal context](#)
- [has unitof diameter](#)
- [has unitof volume](#)
- [has volume value](#)
- [hasAbsentComorbidity](#)
- [hasAcquisitionParameter](#)
- [hasAcquisitionParameterValue](#)
- [hasAdministeredMedication](#)
- [hasAdverseEvent](#)
- [hasAgeAtDiagnosis](#)
- [hasAgeAtScan](#)
- [hasAlgorithmType](#)
- [hasAnnotationLabel](#)
- [hasAnnotationStatus](#)
- [hasAnnotationType](#)
- [hasAnnotatorSpecialty](#)
- [hasAnswer](#)
- [hasAnswerAsFinding](#)
- [hasAssociatedFinding](#)
- [hasAssociatedMorphology](#)
- [hasAssociatedPatient](#)
- [HasAssociatedPrimaryCondition](#)
- [hasAssociatedProcedure](#)
- [hasBirthSex](#)
- [hasBodySite](#)
- [hasCancerConditionType](#)
- [hasCancerDiseaseStatus](#)
- [hasCancerStage](#)
- [hasCategory](#)
- [hasCauseOfDeath](#)
- [hasClinicalStatus](#)
- [hasComorbidity](#)
- [hasCondition](#)
- [hasCorrespondence](#)
- [hasDiagnosticCategory](#)
- [HasDirectProcedureSite](#)
- [hasDoseDeliveredToVolume](#)
- [hasEpisodeEventRelatedEntity](#)
- [hasEpisodeType](#)
- [hasEquipmentManufacturer](#)
- [hasEquivalentPathologicClassification](#)
- [hasEthnicity](#)
- [hasEvaluationFinding](#)
- [hasEvidenceType](#)
- [hasFindingSite](#)
- [hasFindingSite\(metastasized\)](#)
- [hasFocus](#)
- [hasGender](#)
- [hasGenericCategory](#)
- [hasGrade](#)
- [hasHealthStatusAssessment](#)
- [hasHistologicalGradingSystem](#)
- [hasHistologicGrade](#)
- [hasHistologicGradeType](#)
- [hasHistologicGradeValue](#)
- [hasHistology](#)
- [hasHistologyICDO](#)
- [hasHistologyMorphologyBehavior](#)
- [hasImageBodyPart](#)
- [hasImageCoordinateSystem](#)
- [hasImageModality](#)
- [hasImageProcedure](#)
- [hasImageVendor](#)
- [hasInterpretation](#)
- [hasInterpretationValue](#)
- [hasLabTestResult](#)
- [hasLaterality](#)
- [hasLocation](#)
- [hasMeasurementUnit](#)
- [hasMedicalAssessment](#)

- [hasMedicalHistory](#)
- [hasMedicalHistoryValue](#)
- [hasModalityDescriptor](#)
- [hasMorphology](#)
- [hasObservationCategory](#)
- [hasPart](#)
- [hasPathologyConfirmation](#)
- [hasPerformanceStatusAssessment](#)
- [hasPrimaryCancerCondition](#)
- [hasProcedure](#)
- [hasProcedureCategory](#)
- [hasProcedureSite](#)
- [hasRace](#)
- [hasRadiationDoseUnit](#)
- [hasRadiationModality](#)
- [hasRadiationTechnique](#)
- [hasRelatedCondition](#)
- [hasRelatedPrimaryCancerCondition](#)
- [hasRelatedProcedure](#)
- [hasRelatedTumor](#)
- [hasRelationship](#)
- [hasResponse](#)
- [hasResult](#)
- [hasResultingEffect](#)
- [hasResultValue](#)
- [hasRiskAssessment](#)
- [hasRiskAssessmentValue](#)
- [hasScore](#)
- [hasSecondaryCancerCondition](#)
- [hasSegmentationMethod](#)
- [hasSegmentLabel](#)
- [hasStageMethod](#)
- [hasStageValue](#)
- [hasSubject](#)
- [hasSurgicalProcedure](#)
- [hasTopography](#)
- [hasTopographyICDO](#)
- [hasTreatment](#)
- [hasTreatmentIntent](#)
- [hasTreatmentResponse](#)
- [hasTreatmentType](#)
- [hasTumorMarkerTest](#)
- [hasTumorObservation](#)
- [hasTumorObservationValue](#)
- [hasTumorSizeMethod](#)
- [hasUndergone](#)
- [hasUnitofMeasure](#)
- [hasUnitofTime](#)
- [ImagingAssessmentMethodFor](#)
- [Inheres In](#)
- [interoperabilityLevel](#)
- [Interpretation Of](#)
- [Interprets of](#)
- [involve_staining_method](#)
- [is clinical interpretation result of](#)
- [Is imaging interpretation result of](#)
- [Is interpretation result of](#)
- [Is pathologic interpretation result of](#)
- [Is Subject For](#)
- [Is Value For](#)
- [Lab test for](#)
- [Part Of](#)
- [Suffers from](#)
- [Surgically treats](#)
- [SymptomAssociatedWith](#)
- [Technique Of](#)
- [Treats](#)
- [TumorMarkerTestFor](#)
- [Unit for measuring](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#AnswerOf>

Associated morphology of^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Associated_morphology_of

is inverse of

[hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op}

Associated With^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Associated_With

is inverse of

[Has Associated](#)^{op}

CancerGradingMethodFor^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CancerGradingMethodFor>

has domain

[Histological grading systems](#)^c

has range

[Malignant neoplastic disease](#)^c

CancerStagingMethodFor^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#CancerStagingMethodFor>

has domain

[Tumor staging](#)^c

has range

[Malignant neoplastic disease](#)^c

causedBy^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#causedBy>

collectionMethod^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#collectionMethod>

has range

[Collection method](#)^c

ComorbidityAssociatedWith^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#ComorbidityAssociatedWith>

is inverse of

[hasComorbidity](#)^{op}

Composed Of^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Composed_Of

is inverse of

[Part Of](#)^{op}

diagnosedWith^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#diagnosedWith>

has equivalent properties

[Has condition](#)^{op}

has domain

[Cancer Patient](#)^c

has range

[Neoplastic disease](#)^c

Finding site of^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#FindingSiteOf>

GeneVariantMutationFor^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#GeneVariantMutationFor>

has assessment test value^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAssessmentTestValue>

has super-properties

[has value](#)^{OP}

Has Associated^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_Associated

is inverse of

[Associated With](#)^{OP}

Has Associated Dimension^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_Associated_Dimension

has range

[Lesion size](#)^c

[Primary tumor size](#)^c

Has Associated Tumor Marker Test^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_Associated_Tumor_Marker_Test

is inverse of

[TumorMarkerTestFor](#)^{OP}

Has condition^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_condition

has equivalent properties

[diagnosedWith](#)^{OP}

has range

[Disease](#)^c

has date of last contact^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasDateOfLastContact>

has domain

[Patient](#)^c

has range

[Date of Last Contact](#)^c

has deceased^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasDeceased>

has domain

[Patient](#)^c

has range

[Boolean value](#)^c

Has Diagnostic Value^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_Diagnostic_Value

Has direct site^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_direct_site

has range

[Body structure](#)^c

Has direct substance^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_direct_substance

Has finding context^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_finding_context

Has imaging interpretation result^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_imaging_interpretation_result

has super-properties

[Has interpretation result](#)^{OP}

is inverse of

[Is imaging interpretation result of](#)^{OP}

Has inherent location^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: [https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_inherent_location_\(SNOMED\)](https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_inherent_location_(SNOMED))

Has interpretation result^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_interpretation_result

has sub-properties

[Has imaging interpretation result](#)^{OP}, [Has pathologic interpretation result](#)^{OP}, [Has pathologic interpretation result](#)^{OP}

is inverse of

[Is interpretation result of](#)^{OP}

Has interprets^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_interprets

is inverse of

[Has interprets](#)^{OP}, [Has interprets](#)^{OP}

Has Location^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_Location

has maximum dimension value^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasMaximumDimensionValue>

has super-properties

[has value](#)^{OP}

has range

[Size.maximum dimension in Tumor](#)^c

Has method^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_method

Has normality value^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_normality_value

Has observational value^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_Observational_Value

has other dimension value^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasOtherDimensionValue>

has super-properties

[has value](#)^{OP}

has range

[Size additional dimension in Tumor](#)^c

Has pathologic interpretation result^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_clinical_interpretation_result

has super-properties

[Has interpretation result](#)^{OP}

is inverse of

[is clinical interpretation result of](#)^{OP}

Has pathologic interpretation result^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_pathologic_interpretation_result

has super-properties

[Has interpretation result](#)^{OP}

is inverse of

[Is pathologic interpretation result of](#)^{OP}

Has relative degree^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_relative_degree

Has specimen source topography^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: [https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_specimen_source_topography_\(SNOMED\)](https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_specimen_source_topography_(SNOMED))

Has staging^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_staging

has domain

[Malignant neoplastic disease](#)^c

has range

[Tumor staging](#)^c

Has subject relationship context^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_subject_relationship_context

Has Technique^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_Technique

is inverse of

[Technique Of](#)^{op}

Has temporal context^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_temporal_context

has unitof diameter^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasUnitofDiameter>

has super-properties

[hasUnitofMeasure](#)^{op}

has unitof volume^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasUnitofVolume>

has super-properties

[hasUnitofMeasure](#)^{op}

has volume value^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasVolumeValue>

has super-properties

[has_value](#)^{op}

hasAbsentComorbidity^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAbsentComorbidity>

hasAcquisitionParameter^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAcquisitionParameter>

has domain

[Imaging modality](#)^c

has range

[Imaging.procedure.property](#)^c

hasAcquisitionParameterValue^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAcquisitionParameterValue>

has domain

[Imaging modality](#)^c

has range

[Imaging.procedure.property](#)^c

hasAdministeredMedication^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAdministeredMedication>

hasAdverseEvent^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAdverseEvent>

hasAgeAtDiagnosis^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAgeAtDiagnosis>

has range

[Age at diagnosis](#)^c

hasAgeAtScan^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAgeAtScan>

has domain

[Patient](#)^c

has range

[Patient age](#)^c

hasAlgorithmType^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAlgorithmType>

has range

[Segmentation Method](#)^c

hasAnnotationLabel^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAnnotationLabel>

has range

[Body structure](#)^c

hasAnnotationStatus^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAnnotationStatus>

has range

[Annotation Status](#)^c

hasAnnotationType^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAnnotationType>

has range

[Annotation Type](#)^c

hasAnnotatorSpecialty^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAnnotatorSpecialty>

has range

[Annotator Specialty](#)^c

hasAnswer^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAnswer>

has range

[Finding value](#)^c

hasAnswerAsFinding^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAnswerAsFinding>

has range

[Performance Status Assessment Answer Finding](#)^c

hasAssociatedFinding^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAssociatedFinding>

hasAssociatedMorphology^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAssociatedMorphology>

has super-properties

[hasMorphology](#)^{op}

has range

[Tumor Morphology](#)^c

is inverse of

[Associated morphology of](#)^{op}

hasAssociatedPatient^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAssociatedPatient>

has range

[Cancer Patient](#)^c

HasAssociatedPrimaryCondition^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Has_Associated_Primary_Condition

hasAssociatedProcedure^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasAssociatedProcedure>

hasBirthSex^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasBirthSex>

has domain

[Patient](#)^c

has range

[Sex assigned at birth](#)^c

hasBodySite^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasBodySite>

has sub-properties

[hasFindingSite](#)^{op}, [hasFindingSite\(metastasized\)](#)^{op}, [hasTopography](#)^{op}

has range

[Body structure](#)^c

hasCancerConditionType^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasCancerConditionType>

has range

[Cancer Condition Type](#)^c

hasCancerDiseaseStatus^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasCancerDiseaseStatus>

has range

[Patient condition finding](#)^c

hasCancerStage^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasCancerStage>

has sub-properties

[hasStageMethod](#)^{op}, [hasStageValue](#)^{op}

hasCategory^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasCategory>

has sub-properties

[hasDiagnosticCategory](#)^{op}, [hasGenericCategory](#)^{op}, [hasObservationCategory](#)^{op}, [hasProcedureCategory](#)^{op}

hasCauseOfDeath^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasCauseOfDeath>

hasClinicalStatus^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasClinicalStatus>

has range

[Condition clinical status value](#)^c

hasComorbidity^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasComorbidity>

has range

[Disease](#)^c

is inverse of

[ComorbidityAssociatedWith](#)^{op}

hasCondition^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasCondition>

has sub-properties

[hasPrimaryCancerCondition](#)^{op}, [hasSecondaryCancerCondition](#)^{op}

has range

[Malignant neoplastic disease](#)^c

hasCorrespondence^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasCorrespondence>

hasDiagnosticCategory^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasDiagnosticCategory>

has super-properties

[hasCategory](#)^{op}

has domain

[Patient](#)^c

has range

[Population](#)^c

HasDirectProcedureSite^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasDirectProcedureSite>

has range

[Body structure](#)^c

hasDoseDeliveredToVolume^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasDoseDeliveredToVolume>

hasEpisodeEventRelatedEntity^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasEpisodeEventRelatedEntity>

has domain

[Episode](#)^c

has range

[Primary Cancer Condition](#) ^c
[Administration of medication](#) ^c

hasEpisodeType^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasEpisodeType>

hasEquipmentManufacturer^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasEquipmentManufacturer>

has range
[Manufacturer](#) ^c

hasEquivalentPathologicClassification^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasEquivalentPathologicalGrade>

hasEthnicity^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasEthnicity>

has domain
[Patient](#) ^c

has range
[Ethnicity](#) ^c

hasEvaluationFinding^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasEvaluationFinding>

hasEvidenceType^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasEvidenceType>

has domain
[Cancer disease progression](#) ^c

has range
[Evidence Type](#) ^c

hasFindingSite^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasFindingSite>

has super-properties
[hasBodySite](#) ^{OP}

hasFindingSite(metastasized)^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: [https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasFindingSite\(metastasized\)](https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasFindingSite(metastasized))

has super-properties
[hasBodySite](#) ^{OP}

hasFocus^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasFocus>

has range
[Primary Cancer Condition](#) ^c

hasGender^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasGender>

has range

[Gender](#)^c

hasGenericCategory^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasGenericCategory>

has super-properties

[hasCategory](#)^{OP}

has domain

[Generic Category](#)^c

hasGrade^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasGrade>

has range

[Tumor grade](#)^c

hasHealthStatusAssessment^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasHealthStatusAssessment>

has sub-properties

[hasMedicalAssessment](#)^{OP}, [hasPerformanceStatusAssessment](#)^{OP}

has range

[Health Status Assessment](#)^c

hasHistologicalGradingSystem^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasHistologicalGradingSystem>

has range

[Histological grading systems](#)^c

hasHistologicGrade^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasHistologicGrade>

has range

[Histologic grade of neoplasm](#)^c

hasHistologicGradeType^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasHistologicGradeType>

has range

[Histologic grade of neoplasm](#)^c

hasHistologicGradeValue^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasHistologicGradeValue>

has range

[Histological grades](#)^c

hasHistology^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasHistology>

hasHistologyICDO^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasHistologyICDO>

has super-properties

[hasHistologyMorphologyBehavior](#)^{op}

has range

[ICDO3Morphology](#)^c

hasHistologyMorphologyBehavior^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasHistologyMorphologyBehavior>

has sub-properties

[hasHistologyICDO](#)^{op}, [hasMorphology](#)^{op}

has range

[Histology/Morphology](#)^c

hasImageBodyPart^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasImageBodyPart>

has range

[Body structure](#)^c

hasImageCoordinateSystem^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasImageCoordinateSystem>

hasImageModality^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasImageModality>

has range

[Imaging modality](#)^c

hasImageProcedure^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasImageProcedure>

has range

[Imaging \(Procedure\)](#)^c

hasImageVendor^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasImageVendor>

has range

[Manufacturer](#)^c

hasInterpretation^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasInterpretation>

hasInterpretationValue^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasInterpretationValue>

has range

[Finding value](#)^c

hasLabTestResult^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasLabTestResult>

hasLaterality^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasLaterality>

has range

[Laterality](#)^c

hasLocation^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasLocation>

has range

[Body structure](#)^c

hasMeasurementUnit^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasMeasurementUnit>

has equivalent properties

[hasUnitofMeasure](#)^{op}

is inverse of

[Unit for measuring](#)^{op}

hasMedicalAssessment^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasMedicalAssessment>

has super-properties

[hasHealthStatusAssessment](#)^{op}

has range

[Medical Assessment](#)^c

hasMedicalHistory^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasMedicalHistory>

hasMedicalHistoryValue^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasMedicalHistoryValue>

has super-properties

[has value](#)^{op}

hasModalityDescriptor^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasModalityDescriptor>

has domain

[Imaging modality](#)^c

has range

[Modality descriptor](#)^c

hasMorphology^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasMorphology>

has super-properties

[hasHistologyMorphologyBehavior](#)^{op}

has sub-properties

[hasAssociatedMorphology](#)^{op}

has range

[Tumor Morphology](#)^c

hasObservationCategory^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasObservationCategory>

has super-properties

[hasCategory](#)^{op}

has range

[Observation Category](#) ^c

hasPart^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasPart>

hasPathologyConfirmation^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasPathologyConfirmation>

hasPerformanceStatusAssessment^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasPerformanceStatusAssessment>

has super-properties

[hasHealthStatusAssessment](#) ^{OP}

has range

[Performance Status Assessment](#) ^c

hasPrimaryCancerCondition^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasPrimaryCancerCondition>

has super-properties

[hasCondition](#) ^{OP}

has range

[Primary Cancer Condition](#) ^c

hasProcedure^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasProcedure>

has sub-properties

[hasRelatedProcedure](#) ^{OP}, [hasSurgicalProcedure](#) ^{OP}

has range

[Procedure](#) ^c

hasProcedureCategory^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasProcedureCategory>

has super-properties

[hasCategory](#) ^{OP}

has domain

[Procedure](#) ^c

has range

[Procedure Category](#) ^c

hasProcedureSite^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasProcedureSite>

hasRace^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasRace>

has range

[Race](#) ^c

hasRadiationDoseUnit^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasRadiationDoseUnit>

has range

[Unit of radiation dose](#) ^c

hasRadiationModality^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasRadiationModality>

has range

[Radiotherapy](#) ^c

hasRadiationTechnique^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasRadiationTechnique>

has range

[Radiotherapy](#) ^c

hasRelatedCondition^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasRelatedCondition>

has sub-properties

[hasRelatedPrimaryCancerCondition](#) ^{OP}

has range

[Malignant neoplastic disease](#) ^c

hasRelatedPrimaryCancerCondition^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasRelatedPrimaryCancerCondition>

has super-properties

[hasRelatedCondition](#) ^{OP}

has range

[Primary Cancer Condition](#) ^c

hasRelatedProcedure^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasRelatedProcedure>

has super-properties

[hasProcedure](#) ^{OP}

has range

[Procedure](#) ^c

hasRelatedTumor^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasRelatedTumor>

has range

[Lesion](#) ^c

hasRelationship^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasRelationship>

has range

[Person in the family](#) ^c

hasResponse^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasResponse>

has sub-properties

[hasTreatmentResponse](#) ^{OP}

hasResult^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasResult>

hasResultingEffect^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasResultingEffect>

has domain

[Disease](#)^c

hasResultValue^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasResultValue>

has super-properties

[has value](#)^{OP}

has range

[Finding value](#)^c

hasRiskAssessment^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasRiskAssessment>

hasRiskAssessmentValue^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasRiskAssessmentValue>

has range

[Risk assessment value](#)^c

hasScore^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasScore>

hasSecondaryCancerCondition^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasSecondaryCancerCondition>

has super-properties

[hasCondition](#)^{OP}

has range

[Secondary Cancer Condition](#)^c

hasSegmentationMethod^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasSegmentationMethod>

has range

[Segmentation Method](#)^c

hasSegmentLabel^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasSegmentLabel>

has range

[Body structure](#)^c

hasStageMethod^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasStageMethod>

has super-properties

[hasCancerStage](#)^{OP}

has range

[Tumor staging](#)^c

hasStageValue^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasStageValue>

has super-properties

[hasCancerStage](#) ^{OP}

has range

[American Joint Committee on Cancer allowable value](#) ^c

hasSubject^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasSubject>

has range

[Patient](#) ^c

is inverse of

[Is Subject For](#) ^{OP}

hasSurgicalProcedure^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasSurgicalProcedure>

has super-properties

[hasProcedure](#) ^{OP}

has range

[Surgical procedure](#) ^c

hasTopography^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasTopography>

has super-properties

[hasBodySite](#) ^{OP}

has sub-properties

[hasTopographyICDO](#) ^{OP}

hasTopographyICDO^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasTopographyICDO>

has super-properties

[hasTopography](#) ^{OP}

has range

[ICDO3Topography](#) ^c

hasTreatment^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasTreatment>

has sub-properties

[hasTreatmentType](#) ^{OP}

has domain

[Cancer Patient](#) ^c

has range

[Treatment](#) ^c

hasTreatmentIntent^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasTreatmentIntent>

has domain

[Treatment](#) ^c

has range

[Intents](#) ^c

hasTreatmentResponse^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasTreatmentResponse>

has super-properties

[hasResponse](#)^{OP}

has range

[RECIST finding](#)^C

[Treatment response value](#)^C

hasTreatmentType^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasTreatmentType>

has super-properties

[hasTreatment](#)^{OP}

hasTumorMarkerTest^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasTumorMarkerTest>

has range

[Tumor marker measurement](#)^C

hasTumorObservation^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasTumorObservation>

has range

[Tumor Observation](#)^C

hasTumorObservationValue^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasTumorObservationValue>

has super-properties

[has value](#)^{OP}

has range

[Tumor Observation](#)^C

hasTumorSizeMethod^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasTumorSizeMethod>

has range

[Tumor Size Method](#)^C

hasUndergone^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasUndergone>

has super-properties

[Is Subject For](#)^{OP}

hasUnitofMeasure^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasUnitofMeasure>

has equivalent properties

[hasMeasurementUnit](#)^{OP}

has sub-properties

[has unitof diameter](#)^{OP}, [has unitof volume](#)^{OP}, [hasUnitofTime](#)^{OP}

has range

[Unit of measure](#)^C

hasUnitofTime^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#hasUnitofTime>

has super-properties

[hasUnitofMeasure](#)^{OP}

has range

[Unit of time](#)^C

ImagingAssessmentMethodFor^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#ImagingAssessmentMethodFor>

has domain

[Assessment](#)^C

has range

[Primary Cancer Condition](#)^C

Inheres In^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#inheresIn>

interoperabilityLevel^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#interoperabilityLevel>

has range

[Interoperability level](#)^C

Interpretation Of^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Interpretation_Of

Interprets of^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: [https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Interprets_of_\(SNOMED\)](https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Interprets_of_(SNOMED))

involve_staining_method^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#involve_staining_method

is clinical interpretation result of^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#is_clinical_interpretation_result_of

has super-properties

[Is interpretation result of](#)^{OP}

is inverse of

[Has pathologic interpretation result](#)^{OP}

Is imaging interpretation result of^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Is_imaging_interpretation_result_of

has super-properties

[Is interpretation result of](#)^{OP}

is inverse of

[Has imaging interpretation result](#)^{OP}

Is interpretation result of^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Is_interpretation_result_of

has sub-properties

[Is imaging interpretation result of](#) ^{op}, [Is pathologic interpretation result of](#) ^{op}, [is clinical interpretation result of](#) ^{op}
is inverse of

[Has interpretation result](#) ^{op}

Is pathologic interpretation result of^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Is_pathologic_interpretation_result_of

has super-properties

[Is interpretation result of](#) ^{op}

is inverse of

[Has pathologic interpretation result](#) ^{op}

Is Subject For^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Is_Subject_For

has sub-properties

[hasUndergone](#) ^{op}

is inverse of

[hasSubject](#) ^{op}

Is Value For^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Is_Value_For

is inverse of

[has value](#) ^{op}

Lab test for^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#LabTestFor>

has sub-properties

[TumorMarkerTestFor](#) ^{op}

Part Of^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Part_Of

is inverse of

[Composed Of](#) ^{op}

Suffers from^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Suffers_from

has domain

[Cancer Patient](#) ^c

has range

[Disease](#) ^c

Surgically treats^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SurgicallyTreats>

has domain

[Surgical procedure](#) ^c

has range

[Malignant neoplastic disease](#) ^c

SymptomAssociatedWith^{op} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SymptomAssociatedWith>

has domain

[Clinical finding](#) ^c

has range

[Malignant neoplastic disease](#) ^c

Technique Of^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Technique_Of

is inverse of

[Has Technique](#) ^{op}

Treats^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Treats>

TumorMarkerTestFor^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#TumorMarkerTestFor>

has super-properties

[Lab test for](#) ^{op}

is inverse of

[Has Associated Tumor Marker Test](#) ^{op}

Unit for measuring^{OP} back to [ToC](#) or [Object Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#UnitFor>

is inverse of

[hasMeasurementUnit](#) ^{op}

Data Properties

- [AcquisitionDate](#)
- [AcquisitionParameterValueNumber](#)
- [AgeAtDiagnosis](#)
- [AnnotatorExperience](#)
- [AssertedDate](#)
- [AssessmentTestValue](#)
- [BirthDate](#)
- [BirthYear](#)
- [ConditionPresent](#)
- [Date](#)
- [DateOfLastContact](#)
- [Deceased](#)
- [EdemaVolumeValue](#)
- [EffectiveTimeInterval](#)
- [EndDate](#)
- [EnhancingTumorVolumeValue](#)
- [FractionsDelivered](#)
- [HaemorrhageVolumeValue](#)
- [Identifier](#)
- [image series u i d](#)
- [ImageAcquisitionDate](#)
- [ImageSeriesDescription](#)
- [ImageSeriesNumber](#)
- [ImageStudyUID](#)
- [IsIndex](#)
- [LabTestResultValue](#)
- [ManagingOrganizationIdentifier](#)
- [MaximumDimensionValue](#)
- [MedicalHistoryValue](#)
- [nbrOfAnnotators](#)
- [nbrOfSegmentations](#)
- [nbrOfStudies](#)
- [NecrosisVolumeValue](#)
- [Non-EnhancingTumorVolumeValue](#)

- [NumberOfInstances](#)
- [NumberOfSeries](#)
- [NumberOfSessions](#)
- [OffsetFromDiagnosis](#)
- [OnsetAge](#)
- [OtherDimensionValue](#)
- [PatientIdentifier](#)
- [PerformedDate](#)
- [PerformedDateTime](#)
- [Present](#)
- [PrimaryTumorSampleID](#)
- [RiskAssesmentValue](#)
- [SegmentAlgorithmName](#)
- [SegmentationToolName](#)
- [SegmentationToolVersion](#)
- [SegmentNumber](#)
- [SequenceNumber](#)
- [StartDate](#)
- [TotalDoseDelivered](#)
- [TotalTumorVolumeValue](#)
- [TumorIdentifier](#)
- [TumorMarkerTestValue](#)
- [TumorObservationValue](#)
- [TumorVolumeValue](#)
- [UID](#)
- [ValueAsNumber](#)

AcquisitionDate^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#AcquisitionDate>

has super-properties

[Date](#)^{dp}

has range

[date time](#)

AcquisitionParameterValueNumber^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#AcquisitionParameterValueNumber>

has super-properties

[ValueAsNumber](#)^{dp}

has range

[float](#)

AgeAtDiagnosis^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#AgeAtDiagnosis>

has range

[decimal](#)

AnnotatorExperience^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#AnnotatorExperience>

has range

[unsigned int](#)

AssertedDate^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#AssertedDate>

has super-properties

[Date](#)^{dp}

has range

[date time](#)

AssessmentTestValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#AssessmentTestValue>

has super-properties

[ValueAsNumber](#)^{dp}

has range

[int](#)

BirthDate^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BirthDate>

has super-properties

[Date](#)^{dp}

has domain

[Patient](#)^c

has range

[date time](#)

BirthYear^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#BirthYear>

has domain

[Patient](#)^c

ConditionPresent^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#ConditionPresent>

has super-properties

[Present](#)^{dp}

has range

[boolean](#)

Date^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Date>

has sub-properties

[AcquisitionDate](#)^{dp}, [AssertedDate](#)^{dp}, [BirthDate](#)^{dp}, [DateOfLastContact](#)^{dp}, [EndDate](#)^{dp}, [ImageAcquisitionDate](#)^{dp}, [PerformedDate](#)^{dp}, [PerformedDateTime](#)^{dp}, [StartDate](#)^{dp}

DateOfLastContact^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#DateOfLastContact>

has super-properties

[Date](#)^{dp}

has range

[date time](#)

Deceased^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Deceased>

has domain

[Patient](#)^c

has range

[boolean](#)

EdemaVolumeValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#EdemaVolumeValue>

has super-properties
[ValueAsNumber](#) ^{dp}
has domain
[Edema](#) ^c

EffectiveTimeInterval^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#EffectiveTimeInterval>
has range
[int](#)

EndDate^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#EndDate>
has super-properties
[Date](#) ^{dp}
has range
[date time](#)

EnhancingTumorVolumeValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#EnhancingTumorVolumeValue>
has super-properties
[ValueAsNumber](#) ^{dp}
has domain
[Enhancing tumor](#) ^c

FractionsDelivered^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#FractionsDelivered>
has domain
[Radiotherapy](#) ^c
has range
[unsigned int](#)

HaemorrhageVolumeValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#HaemorrhageVolumeValue>
has super-properties
[ValueAsNumber](#) ^{dp}
has domain
[Hemorrhage](#) ^c

Identifier^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Identifier>
has sub-properties
[ManagingOrganizationIdentifier](#) ^{dp}, [PatientIdentifier](#) ^{dp}, [PrimaryTumorSampleID](#) ^{dp}, [TumorIdentifier](#) ^{dp}
has range
[literal](#)
[string](#)

image series u i d^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#ImageSeriesUID>
has super-properties
[UID](#) ^{dp}
has domain
[Image Series](#) ^c

ImageAcquisitionDate^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#ImageAcquisitionDate>

has super-properties

[Date](#)^{dp}

has range

[date time](#)

ImageSeriesDescription^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#ImageSeriesDescription>

has domain

[Image Series](#)^c

has range

[string](#)

ImageSeriesNumber^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#ImageSeriesNumber>

has domain

[Image Series](#)^c

has range

[unsigned int](#)

ImageStudyUID^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#ImageStudyUID>

has super-properties

[UID](#)^{dp}

has domain

[Image Study](#)^c

IsIndex^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#IsIndex>

has range

[boolean](#)

LabTestResultValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#LabTestResultValue>

has super-properties

[ValueAsNumber](#)^{dp}

has range

[float](#)

ManagingOrganizationIdentifier^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#ManagingOrganizationIdentifier>

has super-properties

[Identifier](#)^{dp}

has range

[string](#)

MaximumDimensionValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#MaximumDimensionValue>

has super-properties

[ValueAsNumber](#)^{dp}

has range

[float](#)

MedicalHistoryValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#MedicalHistoryValue>

has super-properties

[ValueAsNumber](#)^{dp}

has range

[float](#)

nbrOfAnnotators^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#nbrOfAnnotators>

has range

[int](#)

nbrOfSegmentations^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#nbrOfSegmentations>

has range

[int](#)

nbrOfStudies^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#nbrOfStudies>

has range

[int](#)

NecrosisVolumeValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#NecrosisVolumeValue>

has super-properties

[ValueAsNumber](#)^{dp}

has domain

[Necrosis](#)^c

Non-EnhancingTumorVolumeValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Non-EnhancingTumorVolumeValue>

has super-properties

[ValueAsNumber](#)^{dp}

has domain

[Non-enhancing tumor](#)^c

NumberOfInstances^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#NumberOfInstances>

has range

[unsigned int](#)

NumberOfSeries^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#NumberOfSeries>

has range

[unsigned int](#)

NumberOfSessions^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#NumberOfSessions>

has domain

[Radiotherapy](#)^c

has range

[unsigned int](#)

OffsetFromDiagnosis^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#OffsetFromDiagnosis>

has range

[int](#)

OnsetAge^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#OnsetAge>

has range

[int](#)

OtherDimensionValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#OtherDimensionValue>

has super-properties

[ValueAsNumber](#)^{dp}

has range

[float](#)

PatientIdentifier^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#PatientIdentifier>

has super-properties

[Identifier](#)^{dp}

has domain

[Patient](#)^c

PerformedDate^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#PerformedDate>

has super-properties

[Date](#)^{dp}

has range

[date time](#)

PerformedDateTime^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#PerformedDateTime>

has super-properties

[Date](#)^{dp}

has range

[date time](#)

Present^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#Present>

has sub-properties

[ConditionPresent](#)^{dp}

has range

[boolean](#)

PrimaryTumorSampleID^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#PrimaryTumorSampleID>

has super-properties

[Identifier](#)^{dp}

RiskAssesmentValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#RiskAssesmentValue>

has super-properties

[ValueAsNumber](#)^{dp}

has range

[float](#)

SegmentAlgorithmName^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SegmentAlgorithmName>

has range

[string](#)

SegmentationToolName^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SegmentationToolName>

has range

[string](#)

SegmentationToolVersion^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SegmentationToolVersion>

has range

[string](#)

SegmentNumber^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SegmentNumber>

has range

[unsigned int](#)

SequenceNumber^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#SequenceNumber>

has domain

[Episode](#)^c

has range

[int](#)

StartDate^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#StartDate>

has super-properties

[Date](#)^{dp}

has range

[date time](#)

TotalDoseDelivered^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#TotalDoseDelivered>

has super-properties
[ValueAsNumber](#) ^{dp}

has range
[float](#)

TotalTumorVolumeValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#TotalTumorVolumeValue>

has super-properties
[ValueAsNumber](#) ^{dp}

TumorIdentifier^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#TumorIdentifier>

has super-properties
[Identifier](#) ^{dp}

has domain
[Lesion](#) ^c

TumorMarkerTestValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#TumorMarkerTestValue>

has super-properties
[ValueAsNumber](#) ^{dp}

has range
[float](#)

TumorObservationValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#TumorObservationValue>

has super-properties
[ValueAsNumber](#) ^{dp}

has range
[float](#)

TumorVolumeValue^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#TumorVolumeValue>

has super-properties
[ValueAsNumber](#) ^{dp}

has range
[float](#)

UID^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#UID>

has sub-properties
[ImageStudyUID](#) ^{dp}, [image series u i d](#) ^{dp}

has range
[string](#)

ValueAsNumber^{dp} back to [ToC](#) or [Data Property ToC](#)

IRI: <https://cancerimage.eu/ontology/EUCAIM#ValueAsNumber>

has sub-properties

[AcquisitionParameterValueNumber](#) ^{dp}, [AssessmentTestValue](#) ^{dp}, [EdemaVolumeValue](#) ^{dp}, [EnhancingTumorVolumeValue](#) ^{dp},
[HaemorrhageVolumeValue](#) ^{dp}, [LabTestResultValue](#) ^{dp}, [MaximumDimensionValue](#) ^{dp}, [MedicalHistoryValue](#) ^{dp}, [NecrosisVolumeValue](#) ^{dp}, [Non-EnhancingTumorVolumeValue](#) ^{dp},
[OtherDimensionValue](#) ^{dp}, [RiskAssesmentValue](#) ^{dp}, [TotalDoseDelivered](#) ^{dp}, [TotalTumorVolumeValue](#) ^{dp},
[TumorMarkerTestValue](#) ^{dp}, [TumorObservationValue](#) ^{dp}, [TumorVolumeValue](#) ^{dp}

Legend back to [ToC](#)

^c: Classes

^{op}: Object Properties

^{dp}: Data Properties

Acknowledgments back to [ToC](#)

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